

Social Dynamics on Networks

Ancient Roads, Public Goods, and Impartial Selection

vorgelegt von

M.Sc.

Maximilian Julius Stahlberg

ORCID: [0000-0002-0190-2693](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0190-2693)

an der Fakultät II – Mathematik und Naturwissenschaften
der Technischen Universität Berlin
zur Erlangung des akademischen Grades

Doktor der Naturwissenschaften

– Dr. rer. nat. –

genehmigte Dissertation

Promotionsausschuss:

Vorsitzende: Prof. Dr. Gabriele Steidl

Gutachter: Prof. Dr. Max Klimm

Gutachter: Dr. Felix Fischer

Tag der wissenschaftlichen Aussprache: 24. Juli 2024

Berlin 2024

Maximilian J. Stahlberg

Social Dynamics on Networks

Dissertation, Berlin 2024

Gutachter: Prof. Dr. Max Klimm, Dr. Felix Fischer

Technische Universität Berlin

Discrete Optimization

Institut für Mathematik

Straße des 17. Juni 136

10623 Berlin

Abstract

Social dynamics shape and are shaped by interaction networks: Footpaths may develop into roads, inviting people to settle and then seek new connections. Road networks facilitate the provision of goods and foster the division of labor, prompting individuals to form larger and more complex communities. Communities, in turn, self-organize through the pairwise propagation of norms, practices, and trust through a network of social ties. This work explores abstract models of such phenomena through a computational lens and within three application contexts.

We first study the growth of ancient road networks under the assumption that the timescale of their evolution and limited cartographic means lead to a myopic and essentially sequential development. In our path-dependent model of this process, a backbone forms rapidly and shapes the network for generations to come. We develop a toolchain to inform this model with sparse archaeological data, and show that its network predictions are in good agreement with expert reconstructions of the Roman roads that spanned Sardinia.

In the second chapter, we study equilibria in the binary public goods game, which models the production and provision of a resource that is freely shared along network links. We analyze the computational complexity of finding such stable states, first for agents who maintain production for as long as their demand is not met externally, then in a more general setting in which the agents' response is not monotone in the number of producing peers. We show the existence of equilibria in the former case by drawing a connection to congestion games, and prove computational hardness in the latter.

Last, we examine the self-organization of communities through internal nominations. When the voters in an election are also the candidates, they have an incentive to misreport an honest evaluation of their peers in order to increase their own chances of winning. An impartial mechanism aggregates votes in such a way that this is not possible. Such a mechanism cannot always select the highest-voted candidates but must compromise on the nomination weight of the winning set. We propose an impartial mechanism for multi-winner elections that is deterministic and can handle weighted votes, while providing an improved guarantee on the score of the subset selected relative to the score of the most popular candidates.

Zusammenfassung

Netzwerke prägen soziale Interaktion und werden durch diese geformt: Aus Trampelpfaden entwickeln sich mitunter Straßen, an denen sich Menschen ansiedeln und neue Pfade beschreiten. Das entstehende Netzwerk verteilt Güter über weite Strecken und fördert die Arbeitsteilung; komplexere Gemeinschaften entstehen und organisieren sich durch die Weitergabe von Normen, Werten, und Praktiken entlang einer sozialen Netzwerkstruktur. Wir untersuchen in diesem Werk abstrakte Modelle solcher dynamischer Phänomene durch eine algorithmische Linse und im Kontext dreier Anwendungen.

Zunächst erforschen wir die Entwicklung antiker Straßennetze unter der Annahme, dass der verhältnismäßig lange Zeitraum ihrer Entstehung und begrenzte kartografische Mittel zu einer kurzfristig orientierten und weitgehend sequentiellen Bauweise führten. Wir bilden diesen Prozess mit einem pfadabhängigen Modell nach: Darin entsteht sehr schnell ein Rückgrat, das die weitere Entwicklung des Straßennetzes über Generationen hinweg beeinflusst. Wir stellen zudem Werkzeuge bereit, mit denen sich das Modell mit spärlichen archäologischen Daten kalibrieren lässt. In einer Fallstudie der Römerstraßen auf Sardinien zeigt sich dadurch eine gute Übereinstimmung mit professionellen Rekonstruktionen des Netzwerks.

Im zweiten Kapitel beleuchten wir die Komplexität der Berechnung von Gleichgewichten in einem formalen Spiel, das die Produktion und den Vertrieb öffentlicher Güter modelliert, die entlang von Netzwerkverbindungen frei zugänglich sind. Zunächst betrachten wir die Strategie, nur dann zu produzieren, wenn der eigene Bedarf nicht durch die Produktion innerhalb der Nachbarschaft gedeckt ist. Anschließend untersuchen wir komplexere Interaktionsmuster, bei denen die Produktionsentscheidung nicht monoton in der Verfügbarkeit der Resource ist. Im ersten Fall stellen wir eine Verbindung zu Auslastungsspielen her und zeigen, dass Gleichgewichte immer existieren, aber mitunter schwierig zu berechnen sind. Im zweiten Fall ist schon die Entscheidung der Existenz ein schwieriges Problem.

Schließlich analysieren wir die Selbstorganisation von Gemeinschaften durch interne Nominierungen. Da hier Wahlbeteiligung und Kandidatur zusammenfallen, besteht für Teilnehmende ein Anreiz, strategisch und entgegen einer aufrichtigen Bewertung der Konkurrenz zu stimmen. Ein Auswahlverfahren, bei dem hierdurch niemals ein Vorteil entsteht, nennen wir unbefangen. Ein solches Verfahren kann nicht stets nur nach der Stimmzahl entscheiden; es muss diesbezüglich einen Kompromiss eingehen. Wir entwickeln ein unbefangenes Auswahlverfahren für die Wahl einer Teilgruppe, das deterministisch und mit gewichteten Stimmen kompatibel ist. Es weist ein verbessertes Mindestverhältnis zwischen der Stimmzahl der gewählten Gruppe und der mit den meisten Stimmen auf.

Acknowledgements

I am deeply thankful to all the people who made this journey possible. Foremost, I want to thank Max Klimm for guiding me through the last three years. Neither your office door nor your inbox seem to have any closing times, and despite conditions ranging from a pandemic to water damages difficult to keep count of, you remained remarkably collected and created an exceptionally positive work environment for the entire group! Besides Max, I thank Guillaume Sagnol for the opportunity to join the group in the first place, and for teaching me convex optimization and sharing responsibility for PICOS with me. Navigating the applied end of my research project would have been much harder without the archaeological expertise of Benjamin Ducke. I thank all three of you for supporting me in my “Roman era,” and MATH+ for financing this unique research proposal that taught me more Italian than school.

Another research project that really stood out for me was my joint work with Javier Cembrano and Svenja Griesbach. From the hike where we rediscovered the greatest mechanism that would never work, over a miraculous train ride, to editing sentences concurrently with three cursors was all great fun, and I am both proud of our result and thankful that I am allowed to present it here.

When it comes to compiling these results into the present form, I first have to thank Philipp Warode for letting me build upon his pretty template. This saved me so much time that I owe you a good part of the sleep that I could afford during the writing period. I am also greatly indebted to Javier Cembrano, Ekin Ergen, and Lea Strubberg for proofreading the main chapters, to Franziska Eberle and once more to Philipp for checking the introduction and the preliminaries on short notice, and to Bini for her critical feedback on the chapter introductions from an archaeological and socio-scientific point of view. I’m looking forward to returning these favors! An even larger body of text would find its way onto the tables of the doctoral committee. I thank Max Klimm and Felix Fischer for reviewing this work, and Gabriele Steidl for kindly agreeing to chair.

Throughout the last years, I am especially thankful for the openness and kindness that is common to all past and present members of the working groups jointly known as DISCOGA. I will miss a great deal of activities with all of you! More recently, when a friendly group of computer scientists adopted us, we amalgamated further to DISCOGAKT. Having done my Bachelor’s thesis with AKT, this felt much like coming home, and I want to thank you in the name of all the lost souls for welcoming us with shelter and electricity and a very clear schedule concerning lunch.

Finally, Toshi, I am infinitely grateful for having you at my side throughout this intense time, waking me with countless coffees, and telling me that it will all be fine.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Preliminaries	5
2.1	Basic notation	5
2.1.1	Sets and multisets	5
2.1.2	Sequences and permutations	7
2.1.3	Asymptotic notation	8
2.2	Graph theory	9
2.3	Computational complexity	11
2.3.1	Decision problems	13
2.3.2	Optimization problems	15
2.3.3	Search problems	17
3	Ancient roads	21
3.1	Related work	24
3.2	Preliminaries	26
3.3	Elements of network formation	28
3.3.1	Model definition	30
3.3.2	Local perspective	32
3.3.3	Global perspective	33
3.4	Computational complexity	43
3.4.1	Problem definitions	46
3.4.2	Finding efficient connection orders	47
3.4.3	Matching a body of evidence	52
3.5	Reconstructing Roman road networks	57
3.5.1	Constructing the terrain network	58
3.5.2	Searching connection orders	65
3.5.3	Results	77
3.6	Conclusion	83
3.6.1	Discussion	85
3.6.2	Reproducibility and software	86

4	Public goods	87
4.1	Related work	90
4.2	Preliminaries	93
4.2.1	Pattern notation	93
4.2.2	Game representations	94
4.2.3	Game isomorphisms	96
4.3	Decreasing patterns	97
4.3.1	Existence of equilibria in heterogeneous games	97
4.3.2	Computational hardness for weighted contributions	101
4.4	Picky patterns	105
4.4.1	Computational hardness	105
4.5	Conclusion	114
5	Impartial selection	115
5.1	Related work	118
5.2	Preliminaries	122
5.2.1	Weighted selection mechanisms	122
5.2.2	Hypergraphs	124
5.2.3	Graph colorings	124
5.3	Partition systems	125
5.4	Selection mechanism	130
5.4.1	Tightness of the analysis	136
5.4.2	Instructions for use	137
5.5	Assignment mechanism	138
5.5.1	Preliminaries	138
5.5.2	Construction	139
5.6	Conclusion	146
	Bibliography	147

1 Introduction

A thousand fibres connect you with your fellow-men, and along those fibres, as along sympathetic threads, run your actions as causes, and return to you as effects.

Henry Melvill, *The Golden Lectures* [92]

In this work, we investigate the effects of strategic behavior on the formation and configuration of networks, and the converse effects of network structures on the organization of communities: We will study the long-term effects of myopic planning on a road network's topology, the stability of economic arrangements emerging from complex interaction patterns, and the possibility for policymakers to align self-interested actions with a common good. Our mode of operation is model-based and computational, focusing on two key questions: How can one capture the intricate dynamics of a social system in rigorous mathematical terms, and to what extent can the resulting models be employed algorithmically to make predictions or support decisions? With these questions in tow, we embark on a journey through three application contexts that differ in the way that strategic interaction manifests over time, but which share a fundamental concern with how individual behaviors aggregate to shape collective outcomes.

Our journey first leads us along established roads—namely those constructed in antiquity. Few ancient societies have been studied as thoroughly as the Romans, yet the archaeological record of their widespread land transport networks remains quite fragmentary to date. Some roads have survived the millennia, either preserved in their original material or retraced and overlaid by modern pavement. Others, less fortunate, have withered beyond recognition and not rarely turned from a passage to a barrier, now delineating properties or hosting thick vegetation. While some of these abandoned pathways are referenced in textual sources, were rediscovered in construction work or excavation efforts, or could be spotted using non-invasive methods like airborne lidar scanning, others may be lost without a trace. To fill the gaps in our understanding of how past societies traveled the lands, with wide-ranging implications on the role and significance of ancient settlements, archaeologists have been keen on exploring predictive methods: from reconstructing a probable course of a single road between two given endpoints in great detail, to recovering the macroscopic topology of the road network as a whole.

Here, we are concerned with the second goal: reconstructing a probable structure of a past road network at large. To this end, we study a sequential model of network formation where roads are established one after the other, taking the pre-existing network into account. Our procedure iterates over pairs of key locations presumed to require a connection and computes a least-cost path through a network representation of the study region for each pair. If a network link along the chosen path represents an existing road segment, it is left unchanged. However,

if a link represents a movement corridor through untouched wilderness, then its inclusion is understood as the construction of a new road, represented through a decrease of that link's cost. This reduced cost favors existing roads when future connections are established, resulting in a path-dependent network formation process: past actions govern what is possible in the future. The conceptual novelty of our approach is to promote the sequence of events to an explicit model parameter, which frames network reconstruction as an inverse problem: Which construction histories can best explain the outcome that we observe in the form of archaeological evidence? Examining the model, we find that the first few connections by road rapidly define a backbone that determines the shape of the network as a whole. Conversely, later connections have an increasingly reduced chance to affect the course of roads at all. We can computationally exploit this temporal concentration of impact via an embedding that maps possible connection sequences to a metric search space. Nearby points in this space represent sequences that produce similar networks on average, which enables search procedures to navigate it effectively. In a case study of Roman Sardinia, this approach allows us to fit our model to a sparse body of spatial evidence, producing a network prediction that is in good agreement with expert reconstructions.

Once the construction of roads led to a sizeable transport network, it may be used to efficiently exchange goods. We study in the second chapter an idealized resource, which, once produced at a network node, can be freely accessed and consumed both by the producer and by all of its neighbors in the network. In ancient times, such a resource could be a physical place, say a marketplace or a public temple, or it may have been immaterial: Innovation and cultural offerings profit not only those who produce them but anyone who can engage with them. Access to either type of resource was tied to human mobility, rendering road networks a medium on which public goods were provided. Nowadays, immaterial public goods such as free and open-source software or academic preprints can flow along information networks seemingly unrestricted by physical distance. However, their availability remains restricted by the knowledge of skills and conventions that propagates along the links of a social or professional network.

We approach the theory of public goods through a game-theoretic model that describes the interplay between their production and their network-bound provision. The model considers a number of agents, say local communities, that concurrently configure their production level, trying to balance associated costs with benefits from satisfying a local demand. A classical result tells us that, for such a process, there always exist stable states in which some agents only consume while others specialize in production. This insight motivates the study of a binary variant of the game: agents choose to either produce or not, depending only on the number of neighbors who are producing at the time. Within this combinatorial variant of the model, we first study the economically well-motivated setting where agents opt to produce until a threshold number of producing neighbors is exceeded. Here, we draw a connection to congestion games to show that pure-strategy equilibria, a type of stable state, are guaranteed to exist but can be difficult to compute if network links are assigned a weight that modifies the gain from externally sourced resources. We further study a class of interaction patterns that is somewhat more nuanced: What happens if agents want to produce only alone or alongside a particular number of neighbors? For such a behavior, we show that already deciding the existence of equilibria is a difficult task. Our treatment at the interface of graph theory and social choice serves to shed some light on the

conditions under which all-or-nothing interactions can give rise to robust arrangements.

In the third chapter, we examine a setting in which strategic choices are made simultaneously: a multi-winner election among peers. We study specifically the case where the sets of candidates and voters coincide. This scenario creates a strong incentive for participants to vote strategically—potentially misreporting an honest evaluation of their peers—to maximize their own chances of winning. Such polls are not uncommon in practice and can be critical for the self-organization of communities. For instance, manuscripts submitted to a scientific conference are rated by researchers who may have submitted to the conference themselves, and often only a fraction of all manuscripts can be accepted, rendering the judges anything but detached. Likewise, when a group of peers nominates some of their own for an award, holds an election to fill a prestigious position, or, conversely, is looking to distribute duties and chores, agents might be equally inclined to factor their own chances in and vote accordingly.

A mechanism that aggregates the results of a poll in such a way that the votes cast by an agent never influence that agent's own chance of being selected is called *impartial*. Impartiality is a desirable but challenging axiom to uphold: A mechanism that always selects the top-ranked candidates is not impartial, which gives rise to the study of impartial mechanisms that do so approximately. The best known guarantees regarding the relative popularity of the selected subset are, however, far below the identified theoretical limits, and arguably too low to be practical. This issue is particularly pronounced with deterministic mechanisms, where one fixed choice for every possible result of the poll is mandated: Previously, no method providing a positive guarantee was known that would always select more than two agents in this setting, regardless of the number of winners permitted. We respond with a deterministic and impartial mechanism that is based on a structured system of bipartitions of the agents into voters and candidates, ensuring that each vote is processed exactly once and independently of the voter's selection. The procedure can be applied whenever the maximum allowed number of winners is at least proportional to the square root of the number of candidates. Then, it declares at least half as many winners as allowed, rounded down, and significantly improves upon the best known popularity guarantee for deterministic mechanisms. It is notably the first deterministic mechanism that, while allowing agents to nominate any number of peers, further allows their votes to carry an arbitrary weight. We finally examine an extension of the mechanism to a setting in which agents should be selected into at most one of multiple groups, based again on mutual nominations for each category. This makes it applicable, for instance, to the formation of working groups and committees.

While the applications studied differ in terms of the temporal framework in which strategic interaction is organized—sequentially, concurrently, or simultaneously—and, accordingly, in some of the analytical methods employed, our treatment is unified by a computational perspective: We seek algorithmic solutions or corresponding hardness results for the recovery of missing links, the discovery of stable states, and the optimal processing of a poll under constraints. To this end, we employ techniques from mathematical optimization, computational complexity, and graph theory. Fundamental concepts from these fields are introduced in the following section, while more application-specific definitions and methods are provided on a per-chapter basis.

2 Preliminaries

This seems to be the only chapter without a quote, but that's certainly intended.

Max Klimm, 2024

This chapter introduces mathematical concepts and notational conventions that are relevant throughout this work. Additional definitions are found in Sections 3.2, 4.2 and 5.2 on pages 26, 93 and 122, respectively.

2.1 Basic notation

We assume basic familiarity with foundational mathematical objects such as sets, low-order tensors (scalars, vectors, and matrices), and functions, and with standard operations and associated common notations concerning these objects. Additionally, the following shorthands and conventions are used throughout the document.

2.1.1 Sets and multisets

As this work is at the interface of computer science and math, which adhere to differing conventions regarding the smallest natural number, we state the range of integers explicitly.

Definition 2.1: Integers. We write $\mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ for the positive and $\mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ for the nonnegative integers.

We often deal with finite ranges of integers. For instance, we will number the n agents in a formal game from 1 to n . This warrants a compact notation for bounded sets of numbers.

Definition 2.2: Ranges. For $n \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$, we define the sets of integers

$$[n] := \{i \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1} \mid i \leq n\}$$

and

$$[n]_0 := \{i \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0} \mid i \leq n - 1\}.$$

For $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{R}$, it is

$$[\alpha, \beta] := \{\gamma \in \mathbb{R} \mid \alpha \leq \gamma \leq \beta\}$$

and

$$(\alpha, \beta) := \{\gamma \in \mathbb{R} \mid \alpha < \gamma < \beta\}.$$

The mixed forms $[\alpha, \beta)$ and $(\alpha, \beta]$ are defined analogously.

We use vertical bars to denote the cardinality of a set.

Definition 2.3: Cardinality. For a finite set A , we write $|A|$ for the number of elements of A .

For instance, it is $|[n]| = |[n]_0| = n$. The following notation describes nested sets.

Definition 2.4: Power set. If A is a set, then

$$\mathcal{P}(A) := \{X \subseteq A\}$$

denotes its power set and

$$\mathcal{P}_k(A) := \{X \subseteq A \mid |X| = k\}$$

the set of all its size k subsets, for $k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$.

In particular, $\mathcal{P}_2(A)$ denotes the set of unordered pairs over A . Sometimes, we partition a set into multiple non-overlapping subsets. The following notation lets us formalize this concisely.

Definition 2.5: Disjoint union. For two sets A and B , the disjoint union

$$A \dot{\cup} B$$

is equivalent to the union $A \cup B$, but asserts to the reader that $A \cap B = \emptyset$.

When we associate a quantity with the elements of a set, say a cost or a weight, then a natural task is to aggregate this quantity over all elements. We use the following notation for this.

Definition 2.6: Linear extension. If $f: D \rightarrow C$ with $C \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ is a function and $A \subseteq D$ is a countable set, we write

$$f(A) := \sum_{x \in A} f(x).$$

The following notation allows us to express common case distinctions concisely.

Definition 2.7: Indicator functions. For a set A , we write

$$\mathbf{1}_A(x) := \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \in A, \\ 0 & \text{if } x \notin A. \end{cases}$$

For a proposition ϕ , we further write

$$\mathbf{1}[\phi] := \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \phi \text{ is true,} \\ 0 & \text{if } \phi \text{ is false.} \end{cases}$$

Finally, we will make use of generalized sets that can contain multiple copies of an element.

Definition 2.8: Multiset. A multiset is a set X equipped with a *multiplicity function* $\mu_X: X \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$. For clarity, we avoid the notation $|X|$ but instead employ Definition 2.6 and write

$$\mu(X) = \sum_{e \in X} \mu_X(e)$$

for the cardinality of X . When a multiset Y is defined by a comprehension of the form $Y := \{e \in X \mid \phi(e)\}$ for some predicate ϕ , then this implies $\mu_Y(e) := \mu_X(e)$ for all $e \in X$ satisfying $\phi(e)$. Similarly, if a multiset Y is defined from a set A via a comprehension of the form $Y := \{f(x) \mid x \in A\}$ for some function f , then this implies $\mu_Y(e) := |\{x \in A \mid f(x) = e\}|$ for all $e \in Y$.

2.1.2 Sequences and permutations

Sometimes we want to assign one mathematical object to each integer in a range, say one set of possible strategies to each agent. For this purpose, we will put the objects in a sequence.

Definition 2.9: Sequences. We write $x = (x_i)_{i=1}^n$ short for the sequence (x_1, \dots, x_n) . The *length* of x is $|x| := n$. The *empty sequence* $()$ has length $|()| = 0$. A one-element sequence is noted as (x_1) .

We formally distinguish one-element sequences from the element that they contain. This is necessary, for example, to distinguish the cardinality $|A|$ of a set A from the length of a sequence of sets, which can amount to $|A| = 1$ in particular.

Sequences may be concatenated to yield longer sequences.

Definition 2.10: Concatenation. Let $x = (x_i)_{i=1}^m$ and $y = (y_i)_{i=1}^n$ be two sequences. We write

$$x \cdot y := (z_i)_{i=1}^{m+n}, \quad \text{where} \quad z_i := \begin{cases} x_i & \text{if } i \in [m], \\ y_{i-m} & \text{if } i \in [m+n] \setminus [m], \end{cases}$$

for the concatenation of x and y .

Sequences can further be obtained by combining sets.

Definition 2.11: Set products. Let A and B be sets. The *Cartesian product* of A and B is

$$A \times B := \{(a, b) \mid a \in A \wedge b \in B\}.$$

If A and B both contain only sequences, then their *concatenation product* is given by

$$A \bullet B := \{a \cdot b \mid a \in A \wedge b \in B\}.$$

For example, it is $\{(1, 2)\} \times \{(3, 4)\} = \{(1, 2), (3, 4)\}$ and $\{(1, 2)\} \bullet \{(3, 4)\} = \{(1, 2, 3, 4)\}$. The Cartesian product is generalized from two to any number of operands as follows.

Definition 2.12: Cartesian product. For a sequence of sets $(A_i)_{i=1}^n$ with $n \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$, we write

$$\prod_{i=1}^n A_i := \{(a_i)_{i=1}^n \mid \forall i \in [n]: a_i \in A_i\}$$

for the n -ary Cartesian product. If $n \geq 2$, we may also write it extensively as $A_1 \times \dots \times A_n$. Higher-arity Cartesian products in extensive notation take operator precedence over lower-arity ones. For a single set A and an integer $k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$, we further write

$$A^k := \prod_{i=1}^k A.$$

Operator precedence implies that $A \times A \times A \neq (A \times A) \times A$: the left-hand side contains triples while the right-hand side contains pairs. Note that the above definition does not interfere with established notation from linear algebra, for instance with the n -dimensional real vector space being denoted \mathbb{R}^n , as we may consider vectors an extension of sequences.

One kind of sequence that we are interested in is strings, which are sequences of varying length whose elements come from a common set.

Definition 2.13: Strings. For a finite set A , we write

$$A^* := \bigcup_{k=0}^{\infty} A^k$$

for the set of strings over A . For $n \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$, we further denote the length-bounded strings by

$$A^{\leq n} := \bigcup_{k=0}^n A^k.$$

In the context of strings, we will also refer to the set A as an *alphabet*. Another type of sequence that will play a role is an ordering of the elements of a finite set; we call these permutations.

Definition 2.14: Permutations. If A is a finite set, then we write

$$\mathcal{S}(A) := \left\{ (x_i)_{i=1}^{|A|} \mid \bigcup_{i=1}^{|A|} \{x_i\} = A \right\}$$

for the set of (one-line representations of) permutations over A . Given $\pi \in \mathcal{S}(A)$, we write $u <_{\pi} v$ if $\pi_i = u$ and $\pi_j = v$ for $i < j$. We write just $u < v$ when the permutation is clear from the context.

We remark that permutations are more commonly defined as bijections (one-to-one mappings) from a set to itself. Our sequence notation is justified by the following construction: For a given finite set A , assume an arbitrary but fixed base order $\pi^A \in \mathcal{S}(A)$. Then, any sequence $\pi \in \mathcal{S}(A)$ implicitly defines a bijection $f: A \rightarrow A$ wherein each element of the base order is mapped to the corresponding element of that sequence, formally $f(x) := \pi_i$, where $i \in [|A|]$ is the unique index with $\pi_i^A = x$. Related to this construction is the following definition.

Definition 2.15: Identity bijection. If A is a finite set, then we write

$$\text{id}_A: A \rightarrow A$$

for the identity bijection defined by $\text{id}_A(x) := x$ for all $x \in A$.

In particular, when $\pi^A \in \mathcal{S}(A)$ is taken to be the base order of A , then the permutation $\pi = \pi^A$ corresponds to the bijection id_A .

2.1.3 Asymptotic notation

We will make use of Bachmann–Landau notation, also known as “Big O ” notation, to capture the asymptotic behavior of scalar functions as their argument grows to infinity.

Definition 2.16: Bachmann–Landau notation. Let $f: D \rightarrow C$ with $\mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1} \subseteq D$ and $C \subseteq \mathbb{R}$. We write

$$O(f) := \{g: D \rightarrow C \mid \exists c \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}: \exists x_0 \in D: \forall x \geq x_0: 0 \leq g(x) \leq cf(x)\}$$

for the set of (eventually non-negative) functions that (asymptotically) grow at most as quickly as f , up to a positive constant factor. We further denote by

$$o(f) := \{g: D \rightarrow C \mid \forall c \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}: \exists x_0 \in D: \forall x \geq x_0: 0 \leq g(x) < cf(x)\}$$

the set of functions that grow strictly slower than f . Conversely, we write

$$\Omega(f) := \{g: D \rightarrow C \mid \exists c \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}: \exists x_0 \in D: \forall x \geq x_0: 0 \leq cf(x) \leq g(x)\}$$

for the functions that grow at least as quickly as f , up to a constant factor, and we denote by

$$\Theta(f) := O(f) \cap \Omega(f)$$

the set of functions that are eventually bounded from both sides by constant multiples of f . In all cases, the function f may be specified solely by its action on a variable; its domain D and codomain C are then inferred from the context.

As an example of the latter convention, we would write $g(n) \in O(n^2)$ to denote that a function g is asymptotically dominated by some polynomial of degree two, where the domain of g may be both discrete or continuous. We use the following arithmetic notation for convenience.

Definition 2.17: Asymptotic operations. Let $f, g: D \rightarrow C$ be two functions with D and C as in Definition 2.16. Let further $\star \in \{O, o, \Omega, \Theta\}$. We write

$$g(x) + \star(x) \quad \text{and} \quad g(x) - \star(x)$$

for a function $h: D \rightarrow C$ with $h(x) - g(x) \in \star(x)$ and $h(x) + g(x) \in \star(x)$, respectively.

For example, we would write $1 - o(1)$ for a function that converges from below to one as its argument approaches infinity. Additionally, we use the following shorthand.

Definition 2.18: Polynomial growth. We write

$$O(\text{poly}(n)) := \bigcup_{k=0}^{\infty} O(n^k)$$

to refer to the set of functions in n that are asymptotically dominated by some polynomial.

2.2 Graph theory

The formal object that we will use to represent a network is called a graph. It comprises a finite collection of vertices—nodes where links originate—and edges, the links' two endpoints. On its own, a graph does not contain information regarding the length, cost, or importance of links, their possible geographic course, or any such attribute associated with a connection. These additional data will be represented by functions on the edge set. On the other hand, vertices can be any fixed mathematical object. They may represent, for instance, the coordinates of an ancient site or the identifier of an agent in a formal game. To represent information that changes dynamically, such as an agent's evolving strategy choice, we will again use an external object that is in correspondence with the vertex set. Without these associated properties, a graph is a powerful discrete structure that encodes connectivity itself, allowing us to rigorously argue about a network's topology.

Definition 2.19: Graph. A (simple, undirected) graph is a pair $G = (V, E)$ where V is a finite set of *vertices* and $E \subseteq \mathcal{P}_2(V)$ is a set of *edges*. We refer to $|V|$ as the *order* and to $|E|$ as the *size* of G . We say that G is *empty*, if $E = \emptyset$, and *complete*, if $E = \mathcal{P}_2(V)$. We further call a vertex $v \in V$ and an edge $e \in E$ *incident* if $v \in e$.

If two vertices are incident to a common edge, typically representing an ability to interact directly along it, they are called neighbors.

Definition 2.20: Neighborhood. Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph. For a vertex $v \in V$, we denote by

$$N_G(v) := \{u \in V \mid \{u, v\} \in E\}$$

its *open neighborhood* and by

$$N_G[v] := N_G(v) \cup \{v\}$$

its *closed neighborhood*. We omit the subscript when the graph is clear from the context.

The number of neighbors is a key local measure of how central or well-connected a vertex is.

Definition 2.21: Degree. Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph. We write

$$\deg_G(v) := |N_G(v)|$$

for the *degree* of a vertex $v \in V$ and

$$\Delta(G) := \max_{v \in V} \deg_G(v)$$

for the maximum degree of G . We say that G is *d-regular* if $\deg_G(v) = d$ for all $v \in V$. Again, we omit the subscript and write just $\deg(v)$ when the graph is clear from the context.

Graphs are characterized into an abundance of classes based on their topological properties. One such class is bipartite graphs, where every edge has one endpoint in each of two partitions.

Definition 2.22: Bipartite graph. A graph $G = (V, E)$ is *bipartite* if there is a bipartition $V = V_1 \cup V_2$ such that $|e \cap V_1| = 1$ for all $e \in E$. It is *complete bipartite* if further $E = \{\{u, v\} \mid u \in V_1 \wedge v \in V_2\}$.

Another relevant class are the planar graphs, for which a conceptual definition will suffice.

Definition 2.23: Planar graph (informal). A graph is *planar* if it can be embedded into the real plane \mathbb{R}^2 —by mapping vertices to points and edges to continuous curves whose endpoints are the images of the two vertices that they contain—such that the images of two distinct edges do not intersect in any point other than common endpoints.

For example, a road network without tunnels or bridges can be represented by a planar graph. Graphs can be broken down into smaller structures, called subgraphs.

Definition 2.24: Subgraph. Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph, $V' \subseteq V$ a subset of vertices, and $E' \subseteq E$ a subset of edges. We call (V', E') a *subgraph* of G , and we further call

$$G[V'] := (V', E \cap \mathcal{P}_2(V')) \quad \text{and} \quad G[E'] := (\bigcup E', E')$$

a *vertex-induced* and an *edge-induced* subgraph of G , respectively.

A fundamental subgraph structure is a path, which connects two vertices directly or via a number of intermediate vertices, without visiting a vertex twice. We identify paths both with the edges and with the vertices that they visit.

Definition 2.25: Path. A path (of length ℓ) in a graph $G = (V, E)$ is a subset of edges $P \subseteq E$ with $|P| = \ell$ such that there is a permutation $\pi \in \mathcal{S}(P)$ with $|\pi_1 \cap \pi_\ell| = 2 \cdot \mathbf{1}[\ell = 1]$ and $|\pi_i \cap \pi_{i+1}| = 1$, for all $i \in [\ell - 1]$. We further call P an s - t -path if, for some $s, t \in V$, either $\ell = 1$ and $\{s, t\} = \pi_1$, or $\ell > 1$ and $s \in \pi_1 \setminus \pi_2$ and $t \in \pi_\ell \setminus \pi_{\ell-1}$ hold. We additionally adopt a vertex-based notation and represent P by the sequence $(v_i)_{i=1}^{\ell+1}$ where $v_1 := s$, $v_{\ell+1} := t$, and $v_i := \pi_{i-1} \cap \pi_i$ for all $i \in [\ell] \setminus \{1\}$. Finally, we say that G is *connected* if there is a u - v -path for all $u, v \in V$ with $u \neq v$.

Note that the permutation of edges π is never unique as it remains feasible when reversed. Thus, an s - t -path is also a t - s -path and has two vertex-based representations. This ambiguity justifies the formal definition of paths as edge sets, which are a unique description.

Paths may be decomposed further into subpaths.

Definition 2.26: Subpath. Let P be an s - t -path in a graph $G = (V, E)$. A u - v -subpath P' of P is a u - v -path in G with $P' \subseteq P$.

Another fundamental substructure are cycles.

Definition 2.27: Cycle. A cycle in a graph $G = (V, E)$ is a nonempty subset $C \subseteq E$ such that $G[C]$ is 2-regular and connected. A graph without cycles is called a *forest*; a connected forest is a *tree*.

While paths and cycles are defined in terms of a graph's edges, the following substructures are defined in terms of vertex sets.

Definition 2.28: Independent and dominating sets. Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph. We call a vertex subset $U \subseteq V$ *independent* (in G), if $\{u, v\} \notin E$ for all $u, v \in U$, and *dominating* (in G), if for every $v \in V \setminus U$ there is a $u \in U$ such that $\{u, v\} \in E$.

The edges of an undirected graph describe a symmetric relation between pairs of vertices: either vertex is connected to the other. While not pertinent to our results, we sometimes refer to related work on graphs in which edges are directed from one vertex to another.

Definition 2.29: Directed graph. A directed graph is a pair $D = (V, A)$ where V is a finite set of *vertices* and $A \subseteq V \times V$ is a set of *arcs*. It is *simple*, or *without loops*, if $(u, v) \in A$ implies $u \neq v$.

An extension of graphs employed more prominently are *hypergraphs*, wherein edges can occur with multiplicity and contain any number of vertices. We will introduce them in Section 5.2.

2.3 Computational complexity

A recurring question in this thesis is the computational feasibility of a task. In particular, we ask how much more difficult solving a problem gets as the description of the problem grows in size, with difficulty quantified in terms of the number of *elementary operations* needed to solve it. As an example, consider the task of sorting a list. A simple algorithm, well-suited for use with pen and paper, is to repeatedly scan the unsorted list from start to finish, keeping track of the smallest

element encountered in each sweep. Every time when the end of the unsorted list is reached, that element is appended to a second list on another sheet of paper, and is crossed out from the unsorted list to indicate that it should be skipped during subsequent passes. Once all entries on the unsorted list have been crossed out, the second sheet contains the sorted list. Clearly, this is a fine method for sorting a list of 10 entries, but how does it fare for 100 or 1000 records? As an elementary operation, assuming the entries are about equally long, it would be reasonable to count both the acts of reading and writing a line as one operation each. If the length of the original list is n , then in total we append to the sorted list n times, and, for each time we do, have to scan the original list of n entries for one that is not crossed out and minimal. This amounts to a total of $n(1+n) \in O(n^2)$ operations. The use of asymptotic notation is crucial here. Otherwise, our analysis might get lost in details: How much longer does it take to write a line than to observe it? How much quicker can we skim over a crossed-out line compared to one that still needs to be transferred? Or, when the task is undertaken by a computer: How much faster is one CPU architecture at a particular operation than another? Regardless of the answer, the *asymptotic runtime* of our algorithm remains quadratic, and we can estimate to spend about 100 times as long processing the list of 100 entries than the one with just 10. While this would be daunting for a human, sorting a list with thousands of entries like this is well in reach for a computer. In fact, it can be done much faster using more sophisticated algorithms that perform just $O(n \log n)$ steps.

Sorting a list is doable at scale, as are many other everyday tasks: Querying a vast database for specific content or planning an optimal route that traverses a continent are two more examples of computational problems that can be solved well within a second on large real-world data sets. But, not all problems seem to be this well-behaved. If, instead of the shortest path from one place to another, one looks for the shortest tour visiting a number of places given their pairwise distances, then no efficient algorithm—requiring at most $O(\text{poly}(n))$ operations to handle n places—is known to date. The dichotomy between combinatorial problems solvable by a number of operations that grows polynomially in the size of their input, often no faster than quadratic or cubic, and those where no such algorithm appears to be in reach, is captured by the complexity classes P and NP. We introduce them in the upcoming section on decision problems. First, though, we look to capture the concepts of a problem and an algorithm in general terms.

Definition 2.30: Computational problem. Let Σ be a finite alphabet with $|\Sigma| \geq 2$. Let further $R \subseteq \Sigma^* \times \Sigma^*$ be a binary relation such that for all $x \in \Sigma^*$, there is a $y \in \Sigma^*$ with $(x, y) \in R$. A *computational problem* is the task of processing an *instance* or *input* $x \in \Sigma^*$ and reporting an *output* $y \in \Sigma^*$ such that $(x, y) \in R$. Both x and y can represent a structured mathematical object; we implicitly assume that these can be *encoded* as a string over Σ . The *input size* is $|x|$.

For the rest of Section 2.3, we assume that $\Sigma = \{0, 1\}$. Definition 2.30 is a framework that will be specified in the subsequent sections. In particular, the output that must be reported depends on the type of problem considered and can be as simple as a “yes” or “no” answer, encoded as one bit.

All problem types have in common that the input size of an instance generally depends on the encoding that is used to translate rich inputs such as graphs or sets into a binary string.

Definition 2.31: Encoding. Let Ω be a ground set. We write $\mathcal{L}_\Omega: \Omega \rightarrow \Xi$ for an arbitrary but fixed bijection with $\Xi \subseteq \Sigma^*$, and refer to it as the *encoding* of Ω .

We won't go into formal detail as to how the encoding operates. Conceptually, we may think of it as an explicit, immediate, and application-agnostic representation of mathematical objects. We only remark that integers are encoded in binary notation, so that their contribution to the input size grows only logarithmically in their magnitude. We next formalize the concept of an algorithm.

Definition 2.32: Algorithm. An *algorithm* is a description of a procedure that solves a computational problem represented by a relation $R \subseteq \Sigma^* \times \Sigma^*$: The procedure receives an input $x \in \Sigma^*$ and processes it to report an output $y \in \Sigma^*$ with $(x, y) \in R$. The (worst-case, asymptotic) *runtime* of an algorithm is given by a function $\tau: \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ that maps an input size to the largest number of *elementary operations* that the algorithm can perform before reporting an output for any input of that size. We call an algorithm with runtime $\tau(n) \in O(\text{poly}(n))$ a *polynomial-time algorithm*.

As with the encoding, we won't go into significant detail about what an elementary operation encompasses. For our purposes, it will be sufficient to think of it as an operation that is indivisible and requires uniform time to perform, regardless of the operands and of the overall state of the procedure. In practice, it depends on the machine that executes the latter: An antique computer that uses a magnetic tape for processing information would need multiple physical operations to read the content of one memory cell, namely advancing the tape the required number of cells, while a modern computer using random-access memory (RAM) can, as the name suggests, access any memory cell directly. Surprisingly, for deciding whether an algorithm runs in polynomial time or not, even this drastic distinction makes no difference: if the execution of an algorithm takes time polynomial in the input size on a modern machine, then it can populate at most a polynomial amount of memory in the process. Offloading that memory onto a tape would incur a daunting—but at most polynomial—time overhead to every memory access. The overall runtime thus remains polynomial, as $O(p(n) \cdot q(n)) \subset O(\text{poly}(n))$ for any two polynomials p and q .

The next notation will be convenient in the following.

Definition 2.33: Polynomial-time computable. We say that a function $f: A \rightarrow B$ is *polynomial-time computable* if there is a polynomial-time algorithm that solves the computational problem represented by the relation

$$R_f := \{(\mathcal{L}_A(x), \mathcal{L}_B(f(x))) \mid x \in A\}.$$

2.3.1 Decision problems

The first class of computational problems that we shall describe in greater depth are decision problems. Here, an algorithm is tasked with distinguishing between two classes of inputs.

Definition 2.34: Decision problem. A *decision problem* A is formally described by a *language* $L_A \subseteq \Sigma^*$. The associated computational problem is, given an input $x \in \Sigma^*$, to report the output (1), if $x \in L_A$, and (0), if $x \in \Sigma^* \setminus L_A$. We call $x \in L_A$ a *yes-instance* of A .

Decision problems are normally defined by a question about a structured mathematical object, such as “is the given graph bipartite?” The language L_A is then the set of strings that encode objects for which the answer is “yes.” While decision problems classify strings, we next classify decision problems, starting with those that are considered efficiently solvable.

Definition 2.35: P. A decision problem A is in the complexity class P (formally $L_A \in P$) if there is a polynomial-time algorithm that solves the associated computational problem.

It will be convenient to lift this definition from formal languages to any structured set.

Definition 2.36: Polynomial-time decidable. Given a ground set Ω , we say that a subset $S \subseteq \Omega$ is *polynomial-time decidable* if $\mathcal{L}_\Omega(S) \in P$.

In particular, this notation allows us to concisely define the following superclass of P .

Definition 2.37: NP. A decision problem A is in the complexity class NP ($L_A \in NP$) if there is a polynomial-time decidable relation $R_A \subseteq \Sigma^* \times \Sigma^*$ and a function $p: \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ with $p \in O(\text{poly}(n))$ such that for all $x \in \Sigma^*$, it is $x \in L_A$ if and only if there is a $y \in \Sigma^*$ with $|y| \leq p(|x|)$ and $(x, y) \in R_A$.

The *certificate* or *witness* y serves to help the decision algorithm render its verdict concerning x . As an example, consider the problem of deciding whether an integer $n \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ is composite. This is the case if and only if there is another integer $m \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ with $1 < m < n$ that divides n . An algorithm that is given both n and a candidate for m can efficiently check whether the latter obeys its bound and divides n , thus certifying that n is composite. On the other hand, if n is prime or unit, then no such m exists. The problem of deciding whether a number is composite is thus contained in NP .

The bread and butter of complexity theory is the notion of a reduction from one problem to another. The following variant is especially useful when dealing with the classes P and NP .

Definition 2.38: Polynomial-time reduction. A *polynomial-time reduction* from a decision problem A to a decision problem B is given by a polynomial-time computable function $f: \Sigma^* \rightarrow \Sigma^*$ such that for all $x \in \Sigma^*$, it is $x \in L_A$ if and only if $f(x) \in L_B$. If such a function exists, we write $A \leq_p B$.

The latter notation emphasizes that B is at least as difficult to solve as A , up to a polynomial factor in the runtime: Given a polynomial-time algorithm for B , we obtain also a polynomial-time algorithm for A by applying the function f to any input x to A and reporting whether $f(x) \in L_B$.

If we go as far as to treat problems that are equally difficult up to polynomial factors as *equivalent*, then it is easy to see that the relation \leq_p is, in fact, a partial order on the set of decision problems. The following important subset of NP then describes an equivalence class of problems that are all equally difficult to solve.

Definition 2.39: NP-hardness. A decision problem A is *NP-hard* if $B \leq_p A$ for all decision problems B in NP . Problem A is further *NP-complete* if, additionally, A is in NP .

The transitivity of \leq_p implies that it is sufficient to show the condition $B \leq_p A$ for a single NP -complete problem B . It follows further that the existence of a polynomial-time algorithm for any NP -complete problem would immediately imply that $P = NP$, thereby resolving the most famous open problem in computer science. However, fueled by decades of failure to devise any such algorithm, it is widely conjectured that $P \neq NP$, and by extension that efficient algorithms for solving general instances of NP -complete problems do not exist. We will employ NP -completeness and related hardness results in Section 3.4 to justify the design of a heuristic method, and in Section 4.4 to answer an open question concerning stable states.

2.3.2 Optimization problems

Decision problems are a tremendously useful tool for the formal analysis of computational tasks, albeit with limited expressivity, seeing that not every question demands a “yes” or “no” answer. The following class is more complex in its definition but captures more clearly the kind of problems that people may rely on a computer to solve.

Definition 2.40: Optimization problem. An *optimization problem* A is a structured description of a computational problem, defined by the following objects. We write \mathcal{I}_A for the set of *instances* and $\mathcal{O}_A = \mathcal{O}'_A \cup \{\perp\}$ for the set of *well-formed outputs* of A , where \perp denotes “infeasible.” For $I \in \mathcal{I}_A$, we write $\text{fsb}_A(I) \subseteq \mathcal{O}'_A$ for the set of *feasible solutions* of I . For $x \in \text{fsb}_A(I)$ with $I \in \mathcal{I}_A$, we write $\text{val}_{A,I}(x)$ for the *objective value* of x . Finally, we write

$$\text{opt}_A(I) := \underset{x \in \text{fsb}_A(I)}{\text{ext}} \text{val}_{A,I}(x)$$

for the *optimum value* of I , where $\text{ext} = \min$, if A is a *minimization problem*, and $\text{ext} = \max$, if A is a *maximization problem*. The computational problem associated with A is, given a string $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{I}_A}(I)$ encoding an instance $I \in \mathcal{I}_A$, to report $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{O}_A}(x)$ for some $x \in \text{fsb}_A(I)$ with $\text{val}_{A,I}(x) = \text{opt}_A(I)$, if such an x exists, and $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{O}_A}(\perp)$, otherwise.

For characterizing the complexity of an optimization problem, though, it is still useful to phrase it as a decision problem. For instance, instead of arguing about the problem of finding the shortest tour visiting a number of locations exactly once in terms of its optimum solution, namely a cycle represented by an edge set, one could ask instead whether there exists a feasible cycle whose length is at most a given threshold. If this *decision variant* of the problem turns out to be NP-hard, then this implies that also the original problem must be at least as difficult: otherwise we could solve it to optimality and would know the correct decision for any threshold as a byproduct. This motivates the following extension of Definition 2.39.

Definition 2.41: NP-hardness (optimization). A minimization (respectively maximization) problem A is NP-hard if deciding the existence of a feasible solution $x \in \text{fsb}_A(I)$ with $\text{val}_{A,I}(x) \leq \tau$ ($\text{val}_{A,I}(x) \geq \tau$) for a given instance $I \in \mathcal{I}_A$ and threshold $\tau \in \mathbb{R}$ is NP-hard.

One approach to overcoming the difficulty of solving an NP-hard optimization problem involves relaxing the optimality condition, allowing for solutions that come short of the optimum value but may be less demanding to find.

Definition 2.42: Approximation algorithm. Let A be an optimization problem with $\text{val}_{A,I}(x) \geq 0$ for all $I \in \mathcal{I}_A$ and $x \in \text{fsb}_A(I)$. Let further $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$. An α -*approximation algorithm* ALG for A solves the following computational problem. Given a string $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{I}_A}(I)$ that encodes an instance $I \in \mathcal{I}_A$, report $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{O}_A}(\perp)$ if $\text{fsb}_A(I) = \emptyset$. Otherwise, report $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{O}_A}(x)$ for some $x \in \text{fsb}_A(I)$ with $\text{val}_{A,I}(x) \leq \alpha \text{opt}_A(I)$, if A is a minimization problem, and with $\text{val}_{A,I}(x) \geq \alpha \text{opt}_A(I)$, if A is a maximization problem. We refer to α as a *performance guarantee* of ALG.

Note that we have $\alpha \geq 1$ for minimization and $\alpha \leq 1$ for maximization problems; a value of $\alpha = 1$ marks an exact algorithm for problem A in both cases. By the above definition, an α -approximation algorithm is also a β -approximation algorithm for $\beta > \alpha$ in the minimization and for $0 \leq \beta < \alpha$

in the maximization case. This degree of freedom is overcome using the following term, which captures the best performance guarantee achievable across different scopes.

Definition 2.43: Approximation ratio. Let A be an optimization problem, $I \in \mathcal{I}_A$ an instance of A , and ALG an approximation algorithm for A . If ALG outputs $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{O}_A}(x)$ given input $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{I}_A}(I)$, then we call

$$\frac{\text{val}_{A,I}(x)}{\text{opt}_A(I)}$$

the *approximation ratio* (of ALG) for I . We further call

$$\text{argmin}_{\alpha \in A} |\alpha - 1| \quad \text{with} \quad A := \{\alpha \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \mid \text{ALG is an } \alpha\text{-approximation algorithm for } A\}$$

the (*tight*) *approximation ratio* of algorithm ALG . Moreover, we refer to

$$\text{argmin}_{\alpha \in A'} |\alpha - 1| \quad \text{with} \quad A' := \{\alpha \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \mid \exists \text{ polynomial-time } \alpha\text{-approximation algorithm for } A\}$$

as the (*polynomial-time*) *approximation ratio* of problem A , if the minimum exists.

One would employ, for instance, the approximation ratio of an instance to bound that of an algorithm, to in turn bound that of a problem. The minimum in the last case does not necessarily exist as there may be a sequence of polynomial-time approximation algorithms approaching some ratio, also known as a PTAS if that ratio is one, but not necessarily an algorithm that attains it. On the other hand, the approximation ratio of an algorithm always exists: both when there is a worst-case instance attaining it and when there exists only a sequence of instances approaching it.

Polynomial-time approximation algorithms with good guarantees aren't always available: some optimization problems remain NP-hard even when the requirement to produce an exactly optimum solution is relaxed by a constant factor, so that already the existence of a PTAS for such a problem would imply $P = NP$. For transferring the known computational hardness of these problems to new problems under scrutiny, we will make use of another type of reduction.

Definition 2.44: L-reduction [31, 105]. Let A and B be optimization problems. A pair of polynomial-time computable functions (f, g) is an *L-reduction* (from A to B) with parameters α and β if, for all $I \in \mathcal{I}_A$, it is

1. $f(I) \in \mathcal{I}_B$,
2. $\text{opt}_B(f(I)) \leq \alpha \text{opt}_A(I)$,

and, for all $y \in \text{fsb}_B(f(I))$, it holds that

3. $g(y) \in \text{fsb}_A(I)$,
4. $|\text{opt}_A(I) - \text{val}_{A,I}(g(y))| \leq \beta |\text{opt}_B(f(I)) - \text{val}_{B,f(I)}(y)|$.

Informally, the function f of an L-reduction transforms an instance of A to an instance of B with an α -bounded change in optimal values while the function g transforms back a feasible solution such that the solution's suboptimality does not increase by more than a factor of β . The following result is a consequence of this definition.

Proposition 2.45 (Papadimitriou and Yannakakis [105]). *Let A and B be two minimization problems. If there is an L-reduction from A to B with parameters α and β and there is further a polynomial-time $(1 + \delta)$ -approximation algorithm for B, then a polynomial-time $(1 + \alpha\beta\delta)$ -approximation algorithm for A exists.*

2.3.3 Search problems

Search problems, in a sense, are a less ambitious endeavour than optimization problems: Here, an algorithm is tasked to report *any* feasible solution, if one exists, and otherwise to correctly report that there is none. Reminiscent of how decision problems are formally represented by languages and their associated complexity classes as sets thereof, search problems are commonly represented as relations between binary strings, and their associated complexity classes contain these. Therefore, the formal distinction between a search problem and a computational problem is quite subtle: for both, a relation describes which outputs are permissible for any given input. However, for a search problem we don't require this relation to be total. As with infeasible optimization problems, the fact that no solution exists, corresponding to an input string that is not in relation with any solution string, is communicated via a special symbol. Consequently, to derive the computational problem associated with a search problem, it is only necessary to employ an encoding that can represent both a solution string and the special symbol signifying its absence.

Definition 2.46: Search problem. Let $\mathcal{O} := \Sigma^* \dot{\cup} \{\perp\}$. A search problem A is described by a binary relation $R_A \subseteq \Sigma^* \times \Sigma^*$. We say that A is (*polynomially*) *balanced* if, additionally,

$$R_A \subseteq \bigcup_{n=0}^{\infty} (\Sigma^n \times \Sigma^{\leq p(n)}),$$

where $p: \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ with $p \in O(\text{poly}(n))$. The computational problem associated with A is, given $x \in \Sigma^*$, to report $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{O}}(y)$ for some $y \in \Sigma^*$ with $(x, y) \in R_A$, if such a y exists, and $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{O}}(\perp)$, otherwise.

The search problem analog of the class P is the following.

Definition 2.47: Function P. A balanced search problem A is in the complexity class FP (formally $R_A \in \text{FP}$) if there is a polynomial-time algorithm that solves the associated computational problem.

There is also an analog to the class NP.

Definition 2.48: Function NP. A balanced search problem A is in the complexity class FNP (written $R_A \in \text{FNP}$) if R_A is polynomial-time decidable.

There is an intriguing subclass of problems in FNP for which a solution, though not necessarily easy to find, is guaranteed to exist for any instance. The classical definition for that class establishes this property by requiring that R_A is total: for every $x \in \Sigma^*$, there must be some $y \in \Sigma^*$ such that $(x, y) \in R_A$ [90]. However, this formalization is rather strict and requires every possible string to encode a valid problem instance. For many structured search problems, say problems where the input is assumed to be a graph, this is not the case unless the encoding itself is specifically designed to be total. We therefore give a slightly broader definition of the following class.

Definition 2.49: Total Function NP (nonstandard). A balanced search problem A in FNP is further in the class TFNP if $\{x \in \Sigma^* \mid \exists y: (x, y) \in R_A\}$ is polynomial-time decidable. We then call A a *total search problem*.

The rationale behind this definition is that a search algorithm receiving an input string x may efficiently verify whether x encodes a valid instance of the problem, and reject the malformed string otherwise (by reporting $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{O}}(\perp)$). The relation describing the search problem becomes total when limited to these efficiently decidable encodings of valid instances. Note that this definition immediately implies that $\text{FP} \subseteq \text{TFNP} \subseteq \text{FNP}$, which is commonly assumed.

We next introduce a subclass of total search problems that captures the task of finding a *local optimum* of an optimization problem, which is a feasible solution whose value does not strictly improve through any small modification. Such modifications can be represented by a neighborhood correspondence which maps feasible solutions to others that are considered similar or nearby. The *standard algorithm* for a local search problem starts with an arbitrary feasible solution and repeatedly transitions to a neighboring one with better value, for as long as one exists. When it cannot make a transition, then a local optimum is found, and the algorithm returns it. In order for the standard algorithm to be an efficient procedure, the following conditions are necessary: First, it must be able to process and report feasible solutions, so the size of their representation needs to be polynomially bounded in that of the input. Second, it must be able to identify an initial feasible solution in polynomial time. Third, for any feasible solution it might encounter, the standard algorithm must be able to test the neighborhood for a better one in polynomial time. The class of *polynomial* local search problems is defined with these basic requirements in mind. For consistency with the literature, we additionally require that the feasibility of a solution can be efficiently decided, and its cost efficiently computed [69]. This is not formally necessary for the standard algorithm to have efficient iterations, but is essentially implied by its ability to process the neighborhood. The following definition formalizes the resulting complexity class.

Definition 2.50: Polynomial Local Search [69]. Let A be an optimization problem whose set of instances \mathcal{I}_A is polynomial-time decidable, and let $I \in \mathcal{I}_A$ be an instance of A . Let further $i := \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{I}_A}(I) \in \Sigma^*$ be the encoded instance and denote by $\mathcal{L} := \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{O}_A}$ the encoding function used to represent the feasible solutions $\text{fsb}_A(I)$. Assume that

1. the encoding size of feasible solutions is polynomially bounded by that of the instance, formally $\{\mathcal{L}(x) \mid x \in \text{fsb}_A(I)\} \subseteq \Sigma^{\leq p(|i|)}$ for some $p: \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ with $p \in O(\text{poly}(n))$,
2. $\text{fsb}_A(I)$ is polynomial-time decidable, and that
3. some initial feasible solution $x \in \text{fsb}_A(I)$ can be found in polynomial time given I .

Recall that we denote by $\text{val}_{A,I}: \text{fsb}_A(I) \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ the value of a feasible solution, and let it be polynomial-time computable. Let additionally $\text{nbh}_{A,I}: \text{fsb}_A(I) \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(\text{fsb}_A(I))$ denote the *neighborhood* of a feasible solution. Further, denote by

$$\text{loc}_A(I) := \left\{ x \in \text{fsb}_A(I) \mid \text{val}_{A,I}(x) = \text{ext}_{y \in \text{nbh}_{A,I}(x) \cup \{x\}} \text{val}_{A,I}(y) \right\}$$

the set of *local optima* of I , where $\text{ext} := \min$, if A is a minimization problem, and $\text{ext} := \max$, if A is a maximization problem. Finally, let there be a polynomial-time algorithm that decides for some $x \in \text{fsb}_A(I)$ whether $x \in \text{loc}_A(I)$ and, if this is not the case, provides some $y \in \text{nbh}_{A,I}(x)$ with $\text{val}_{A,I}(y) < \text{val}_{A,I}(x)$, if $\text{ext} = \min$, and $\text{val}_{A,I}(y) > \text{val}_{A,I}(x)$, if $\text{ext} = \max$. Then,

$$R_B := \{(i, \mathcal{L}(s)) \mid I \in \mathcal{I}_A \wedge s \in \text{loc}_A(I)\}$$

describes a balanced search problem B . A balanced search problem belongs to the class PLS if and only if it has the above form.

An instance of a problem in PLS implicitly defines a directed acyclic graph (DAG) in which vertices correspond to feasible solutions and arcs point to neighbors with strictly better value. Since every DAG has a sink, which is a vertex without outgoing arcs, it follows that the set of local optima is nonempty: there is at least one $s \in \text{loc}_A(I)$ for every $I \in \mathcal{I}_A$. As \mathcal{I}_A is polynomial-time decidable, it follows that $\text{PLS} \subseteq \text{TFNP}$.

To show that one local search problem is at least as difficult as another, we need one more type of reduction.

Definition 2.51: PLS-reduction. A PLS-reduction from a problem A in PLS to a problem B in PLS is given by polynomial-time computable functions $f: \mathcal{I}_A \rightarrow \mathcal{I}_B$ and $g: \text{fsb}_B(f(I)) \rightarrow \text{fsb}_A(I)$ such that $y \in \text{loc}_B(f(I))$ implies $g(y) \in \text{loc}_A(I)$ for all $I \in \mathcal{I}_A$. If such functions exist, we write $A \leq_{\text{PLS}} B$.

Recall that PLS is defined in such a way that the standard algorithm for finding local optima has polynomial-time computable iterations. However, we made no effort to bound their number. Indeed, for the most difficult problems in PLS, the standard algorithm might trace solution sequences that are exponentially long in the input size. Moreover, unless $\text{FP} = \text{PLS}$, there exists no algorithm that always avoids such sequences. These problems are captured by our last definition.

Definition 2.52: PLS-completeness. A problem A in PLS is PLS-complete if $B \leq_{\text{PLS}} A$ for all problems B in PLS.

As for the polynomial-time reduction in Definition 2.38, the relation \leq_{PLS} is transitive, and so reducing from one PLS-complete problem is sufficient for proving completeness of another. We will make use of this fact and a suited problem in Section 4.3.2.

3 Ancient roads

So why were so few roads built after the Romans? . . . The answer may simply lie in the availability of the existing Roman network. For all its faults, it was there and worked after a fashion . . .

M. C. Bishop, *The Secret History of the Roman Roads of Britain* [12]

Formalized road networks are a fundamental signature of civilization and shape the spatial extents of human interaction. At the height of their power at the beginning of 2nd century, the Roman's vast network of major roads spanned Southern, Central, and Western Europe, reached deep into West Asia, and enclosed the Mediterranean Sea along the coastline of North Africa with an estimated total length of more than 400 000 km [60, p. 264]. In the light of this scale and of their engineers' rigor, it may come as no surprise that some Roman roads have far outlived the Empire: either genuinely, like segments of the *Via Appia* in Rome that can still be traveled on original paving, or abstractly, in the sense that many modern day roads follow closely the course of a Roman predecessor [35, 136]. It should come as no more of a surprise, however, that many ancient roads did not survive the millennia. Abandoned and overgrown, it may still be possible to spot the marks that they left from the air, find their remains through excavation, or deduce their prior existence from textual sources. However, it would be daring to claim that one has identified them all and is in complete possession of an accurate map of antiquity. Indeed, less than 200 000 km of the Roman road network are available in digitized form today [35], falling short of the estimate by a factor of two. For archaeologists and historians studying patterns of interaction—trade, warfare, migration, the diffusion of ideas, and the exercise of power—the fragmentary account of historical transportation networks can pose a major challenge, as an analysis based on only the known network links could lead to a biased interpretation.

In this chapter, we will attempt a model-driven reconstruction of historical road networks that is based on a small set of fundamental assumptions about ancient decision-making and that can be informed using sparse archaeological evidence. One use case of such a model is the prediction of missing links, which may then be evaluated using complementary methods to expand the archaeological record. Another application is the study of the assumptions as such: What were the driving forces in the formation of early road networks, and how did they influence the network's topology? We will discuss in particular the question of *how quickly* a network is shaped by early strategic decisions.

All land transportation networks have in common that their linear features—be it trails, roads or rails—form an artificial corridor of reduced movement costs through the surrounding terrain. Here *movement costs* can refer to both the energy that individuals, animals, or vehicles expend when traversing the segment, measured as appropriate in calories, kilowatt-hours, or the amount

of fuel consumed, or to the time required for the transfer. Typically, a transportation network serves to reduce both types of cost at the same time. This is most apparent where ambient features have been dried, flattened, tunneled, or bridged, but already the simplest form of a trail, whose bed has been compacted and kept clear of vegetation through continued use alone, will typically be much easier and faster to traverse than the wilderness adjacent to it.

While simple footpaths can form through the act of movement alone, *formalized* roads are created with intent. As both their initial construction and their continued maintenance require expenses in the form of labor and material resources, they are the outcome of a deliberate economic consideration: Are the future savings in movement costs worth the one-time effort of construction plus future upkeep? Clearly, the answer depends critically on the society asking the question and on the terrain in which interaction takes place. A dense network of rivers can be a cost-efficient alternative for travel and transportation while navigating through wooded areas may be particularly challenging outside established routes. For technologically advanced societies, the efficient use of vehicles requires wider and tougher roads, which offer increased benefits in terms of energy and time savings but are more difficult to build, although advanced tools and techniques can reduce the construction costs. It is important to note that our use of the term *economic* is not limited to the exchange of goods: The benefits of a road can also be social, cultural, political, or military in nature. However, the sum of material and immaterial values provided by a road must be weighed against the cost of its construction.

Naturally, the economic trade-off extends beyond the question of whether or not one should build roads *at all*. Once a first connection has been established, every subsequent decision to construct another road in the same general area will be made with the existing road in mind. A new road that is redundant—connecting directly two locations that are close to a common and cost-efficient segment of an existing road—still incurs full construction and maintenance costs but yields little added benefit. Instead, short road segments may be placed to connect further locations to the existing network and gaps may be filled such that travelers can make use of multiple pre-existing stretches of road along their path. Apart from extensions, it may also be worthwhile to improve existing roads that will see increased traffic from the new connection. In the following, we will describe and analyze such a sequential process of spatial network formation and its effect on the emerging topology.

Of course, the global structure of a transportation network could also be planned ahead of time. This would allow the planning agency to take all connectivity requirements and prospective costs into consideration to produce a network topology that optimizes the cost–benefit trade-off over all connections simultaneously. The result could be a network that is both cheaper to build and more efficiently connected than one in which connections are added myopically, that is, without future requirements in mind. But for ancient road networks in particular, a model that describes their “final” state as the result of one central optimization process is conceptually not well suited. The reason for this is twofold. First, the time span of ancient road network formation may have been much longer than the lifespan of human planners, who would not be able to foresee future generations’ mobility demands in all detail. Each generation of planners would thus find a pre-existing network which was designed myopically and whose complete replacement with a network that is optimal with respect to contemporary needs would not be economically

feasible. Their most reasonable course of action would be to adapt or extend the existing network into one that is in general less efficient than a network that was planned from scratch. The second reason is that the macroscopic planning capabilities of the time were modest compared to what is possible for modern networks. If one assumes that sufficiently accurate maps were available to the planning officials of antiquity, it would already be questionable to what extent they could have executed optimization procedures that go beyond the sequential placement of planned roads that we study here. But there is little evidence of the necessary geographic data being available in the first place. Concerning the Romans, it is known that they used maps for administrative and representative purposes [41], but it is not evident that these maps were accurate enough, at larger scales in particular, to allow for precise calculations of optimal ensembles of routes (cf. [34]). The *Tabula Peutingeriana*, a Medieval map of the Roman Empire and its major roads that is believed to be a copy of a Roman original [93], hosts a detailed record of places of interest but suffers from extreme spatial distortion. Apart from being disproportionately stretched along the east–west axis, possibly the result of a papyrus roll being its original medium [40], it is reminiscent of modern maps of regional train or subway networks, where the precise courses of connections have been abstracted away to obtain a graphical representation of fundamental connectivity. Surviving textual itineraries such as the *Itinerarium Antonini* [32] tell a similar story: they comprise tables of places that could be visited in succession alongside the intermediate distances. With the aid of milestones that were erected at regular intervals along the roadside, these documents would have allowed travelers to reach their destination without a precise knowledge of directions, let alone an understanding of the routes' geographic embedding.

Apart from a centrally planned one, one could think of network formation also as a *negotiated* process. Here the driving force is not a single agency but a number of agents with independent connectivity requirements, say settlements looking to play a central role in a trade network. Agents could cooperate locally to find solutions that benefit them jointly, but they would not be willing to sacrifice their own position in the network for the greater benefit of others. To the extent that agents coordinate their road construction efforts *ahead of time*, the same complications as in the central optimization model emerge: planning an ensemble of roads requires both geographic data and mathematical insight and the degrees of freedom are limited by pre-existing connections that may offer mediocre connectivity but dominate the economic trade-off due to a lack of construction costs. Beyond such initial coordination, agents have the option to gradually adapt the road segments that they maintain to a dynamically changing network. Dynamics of this kind are readily captured by a game-theoretic model in which the predicted network is given by an equilibrium state of the adaptation process. However, in practice stretches of road are embedded in their environment and cannot easily be moved to accommodate new requirements. They must be abandoned and rebuilt, at best reusing some materials but repeating the construction efforts. Therefore (strict) equilibria, like global optima, appear to be of limited use for explaining the topology of ancient road networks.

We will make use of neither global optimality nor equilibrium states as a solution concept in our model. Instead, we analyze networks formed by a sequence of local, non-coordinated, and irrevocable decisions: Roads are constructed sequentially to optimally connect their endpoints given the pre-existing network and the surrounding terrain. Once built, they remain fixed through-

out the evolution of the network. In this model, the emerging network is determined by three key factors:

1. the *economic* trade-off between the competing goals of high connectivity and low costs,
2. the *spatial* environment (terrain and endpoints) in which the process takes place, and
3. the *temporal* sequence in which connections are established.

Formally, we will describe the trade-off by a scalar parameter between zero and one, the environment by an edge-weighted graph, and the connections by a sequence of vertex pairs. The model will be derived from a slightly more general one in which existing roads can be improved to account for an increase in traffic. We will discuss further extensions of the basic model at the end of the chapter in Section 3.6.1.

Chapter outline

In Section 3.1, we discuss the state of the art in model-based reconstruction of ancient transport networks. To enable the subsequent analysis, Section 3.2 then introduces concepts and notation that are relevant to this chapter only. In Section 3.3, we first discuss assumptions underlying our network formation model, followed by an introduction of the model in Section 3.3.1 and a discussion of its basic properties in Sections 3.3.2 and 3.3.3. We turn to a complexity analysis of the task of parameterizing the model in Section 3.4: In Section 3.4.1, we introduce simplified optimization problems that are motivated by application scenarios of the model, and we subsequently show that these problems are difficult to solve in Sections 3.4.2 and 3.4.3. Section 3.5 describes an application of the model in a case study of the Roman major road network on Sardinia, which we aim to reproduce from sparse archaeological data. We first describe a method to produce a graph-based description of the study region in Section 3.5.1 and then, in Section 3.5.2, develop a strategy to overcome the computational difficulties that were highlighted in Section 3.4. We finally present our reconstruction of the ancient network in Section 3.5.3.

Bibliographic remark. The results presented in this chapter, unless attributed otherwise, are joint work with Guillaume Sagnol, Benjamin Duce, and Max Klimm and have previously been published in *PNAS Nexus* [119].

3.1 Related work

Pinpointing the first use of mathematical models of network formation to make predictions about ancient transport networks proves challenging. An early seed of this field, which gained traction only with the widespread availability of geographic information systems (GIS) since the early 1990s, is found in the work of Stewart [120] and Stewart and Warntz [121]. The authors transferred concepts from classical mechanics to the study of social interaction within a geographical framework, hypothesizing that there is a law akin to a gravitational force that governs the strength of interaction between population centers based on their size and distance. While these early

studies considered air distance as a proxy for reachability, human interaction was soon tied to physical movement through geographic space. Among others, the works of Gorenflo and Gale [59], MacEachren [82], and Tobler [128] investigate the deformation of space as experienced and perceived by human actors, culminating in the development of *hiking functions* that translate topographical data into an estimate of travel efforts [129]. Such functions make it possible to compute *least-cost paths* through the terrain, which serve as an estimate of how humans would navigate the land [19, 140]. Yet, it is the analysis of island systems that appears to have produced some of the earliest applications of network formation models in the context of anthropology and archaeology: Using no more than a compass and ruler, Terrell [125] connected each of the Solomon Islands, larger ones represented by multiple vertices, to their three nearest neighbors to derive a network of probable interaction and to identify central locations of possible prehistoric activity. A similar analysis has been conducted more recently for maritime interaction in the Aegean Sea during the Bronze Age, initiated by the work of Broodbank [20], who applied the same three-nearest-neighbor approach to the Cyclades, then extended to the gravity-based *ariadne* model by Knappett, Evans, and Rivers [73]. The latter derives the network from a local minimum of an energy function in which both the sizes of sites and the strengths of links appear as variables and are both associated with costs and benefits. In follow-up work, Rivers et al. [112] contrast this approach with Terrell's and with another simple model that limits links not by their number but based on a maximum length, representing the reach of maritime technology at the time. Ducke and Suchowska [43] extend the study region to the broader Mediterranean and include both maritime and land routes. Their *XTENT* model is based on a namesake model for the influence regions of political centers by Renfrew and Level [111]. Unlike the two previous studies, the authors derive the distances between sites from detailed least-cost paths through the terrain and along the safer coastlines.

In maritime networks, evaluating the feasibility of connections independently of one another may be a reasonable strategy. The situation is different for land transport networks, where it is possible, and in part necessary, for human travelers to transform the terrain and to establish clear pathways. This makes it necessary to adopt a structural perspective when modeling these networks, where the presence of certain routes renders other routes less likely. Still with the Aegean Sea in mind, Amati, Shafie, and Brandes [6] employ an *exponential random graph model* [137] to obtain control over connectivity patterns beyond bidirectional links. In particular, their method is designed to favor networks in which certain places act as *brokers* that maintain non-redundant connections to far away sites. Another school of thought considers optimal network designs from the perspective of different locations and aggregates them into one global network topology. For instance, White and Barber [139] distribute points in a regular pattern over the study region of Oaxaca, Mexico, and compute least-cost paths from each point to every other point. They overlay all routes, which tend to converge in natural movement corridors, and keep only those path segments that appear most frequently and are thus convenient from the perspective of multiple points. Independently, Verhagen, Brughmans, Nuninger, and Bertonecello [132] distribute points in a regular pattern over the exemplary region of Zuid-Limburg, Netherlands, but compute the least-cost paths from each point not to every other point but to a fixed number of radially distributed destinations at a distance. A similar but more nuanced approach is employed by Pablo-Martí,

Alañón-Pardo, and Sánchez [101] in a study of the Spanish road network between the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries: In an iterative process, cities vote for the possible road segments that would be the most beneficial for their own connectivity at the time, then the most desired road segment is constructed, which result in a cost reduction of that segment much like in the model that we are about to propose. The authors further explore variants of the model in which the strength of a city's vote depends on the population and in which the cities favor some connections over others according to a gravity criterion, and show that their method is robust with respect to these options. Another model involving optimal sequential decisions are the efficiency networks introduced by Fulminante, Prignano, Morer, and Lozano [50, 107]. Here, in each iteration a road is built to connect two places for which the current best connection via the existing road network is the least efficient, measured in terms of how much longer that route is compared to the air distance between the places.

Our model is similar to both sequential methods as it also considers the evolution of costs and benefits as the network grows. But, it does not assume that a coordinated decision is made at each point in time. Instead, we will stress the temporal path dependence inherent in a sequential process—early decisions can influence later decisions and the final outcome—and propose to choose actions in such a way that the outcome is most consistent with prior knowledge about the road network.

3.2 Preliminaries

In this chapter, graphs typically have associated nonnegative edge weights. This warrants a more compact notation.

Definition 3.1: Network. A *network* (V, E, c) comprises a graph (V, E) and an edge cost function $c: E \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$. When the graph is written as $G = (V, E)$, then we write also (G, c) short for (V, E, c) . Where graph theoretic terms are used in reference to a network, they should be understood as referring to its underlying graph.

For instance, we may say that a network is connected or argue about its paths.

Definition 3.2: Least-cost path. Let $N = (V, E, c)$ be a network. For two distinct vertices $u, v \in V$ that are in the same connected component of N , we write

$$\text{LCP}(N, u, v) := \underset{P \text{ } u\text{-}v\text{-path in } N}{\operatorname{argmin}} c(P)$$

for the least-cost path between u and v with respect to costs c , which we assume is unique. The cost of a least-cost path is written as

$$\text{dist}_c(u, v) := c(\text{LCP}(N, u, v)).$$

In practice, the uniqueness of least-cost paths can be achieved almost surely by perturbing the costs c with random noise of negligible magnitude.

Often, network nodes represent locations in two-dimensional space.

Definition 3.3: Spatial network. We call a network (V, E, c) with $V \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ a *spatial network*.

Then, we may be interested also in a straight-line drawing of the network.

Definition 3.4: Geometric path. Let (V, E, c) be a spatial network. We associate with each edge $e \in E$ the line segment $l(e) := \{\lambda u + (1 - \lambda)v \mid \lambda \in [0, 1]\}$. If $P \subseteq E$ is a path in (V, E) , then we write $l(P) := \bigcup_{e \in P} l(e)$ for the geometric path associated with P .

By construction, a geometric path is (the image of) a piecewise linear and simple curve. This motivates the following definition.

Definition 3.5: Path dissimilarity. Let $N = (V, E, c)$ and $N' = (V', E', c')$ be two spatial networks with common vertices $u, v \in V \cap V'$. Let $P \subseteq E$ be a u - v -path in N and let $P' \subseteq E'$ be a u - v -path in N' . Then, we write $\delta(P, P') := A(l(P), l(P'))$ for the *geometric dissimilarity* between P and P' , where A denotes the unsigned area between two simple curves which are given by their image.

In particular, we will be comparing networks based on how similar the paths between important vertices in common locations are.

Definition 3.6: Network dissimilarity. Let $N = (V, E, c)$ and $N' = (V', E', c')$ be two connected spatial networks with a common vertex subset $S \subseteq V \cap V'$. Then, we write

$$\delta_S(N, N') := \sum_{\{u, v\} \in \mathcal{P}_2(S)} \delta(\text{LCP}(N, u, v), \text{LCP}(N', u, v))$$

for the *(geometric) dissimilarity* between N and N' with respect to S .

Intuitively, the measure considers the networks to be compared from the perspective of agents traveling cost-efficient routes between vertices in S along the drawn edges of the graphs.

In this chapter we report a number of empirical results. To this end we use a couple of methods to assess similarities of measured or predicted vectors, depending on the context. When we are testing the goodness of a functional fit, in particular in a linear regression setting, then we report coefficients of determination:

Definition 3.7: Coefficient of determination. For a vector of measurements $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and associated predictions $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$, the *coefficient of determination* is defined as

$$r^2(x, y) := 1 - \left(\frac{\|x - y\|}{\left\|x - \frac{1}{n}Jx\right\|} \right)^2,$$

where J denotes the $n \times n$ all-ones matrix. Following conventions, we omit the arguments when they are clear from the context, and we write $r^2 = \rho$ instead of $r^2 \approx \rho$ where ρ is written as a decimal with two significant figures.

Note that despite the notation of r^2 , the coefficient of determination can be negative. When $r^2 \geq 0$, then a common interpretation is that it describes the fraction of variance in x that is explained by the model that predicts y .

When we suspect that $x \approx y$, but there is no clear measurement–prediction relationship between the vectors, then the asymmetric coefficient of determination is conceptually unsuited. We discuss instead relative errors.

Definition 3.8: Relative error. The (symmetric) relative error between two scalars $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{R}$ is

$$\frac{2|\alpha - \beta|}{|\alpha| + |\beta|}.$$

We will frequently swap the entries of sequences or vectors in this chapter. For the latter, we can do so using a linear operator.

Definition 3.9: Swap matrix. Let $n \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 2}$ be clear from the context and let $i, j \in [n]$. We write $Q^{i,j} \in \{0, 1\}^{n \times n}$ with

$$Q_{p,q}^{i,j} := \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } (i \neq p = q \neq j) \vee (p = i \wedge q = j) \vee (p = j \wedge q = i), \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

for the linear operator that swaps the i -th and j -th entry of a vector. If $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is a vector, then we further write $x^{i,j}$ short for $Q^{i,j}x$.

For sequences, we adopt an analogous notation.

Definition 3.10: Transposition. Let $x := (x_i)_{i=1}^n$ be a sequence. For $i, j \in [n]$, we write $x^{i,j}$ for the same sequence with the i -th and j -th entries exchanged, formally

$$x_\ell^{i,j} := \begin{cases} x_i & \text{if } \ell = j, \\ x_j & \text{if } \ell = i, \\ x_\ell & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

If $|i - j| = 1$, then we refer to this operation as an *adjacent transposition*.

3.3 Elements of network formation

Before presenting our model, we will first discuss the simplifying assumptions concerning the growth of ancient road networks that underlie it. The first assumption rules out both central planning and local negotiations as possible driving factors of network evolution.

Assumption 1. Ancient roads have been constructed sequentially and myopically.

Here, the term *road* refers to any number of physical path segments built to facilitate movement between two endpoints that are the regular origin or destination of travel, such as settlements, cultic sites, harbors, or military camps. In the following, we will call the end-to-end connectivity requirement that is satisfied by a road a *connection*.

Assumption 1 takes our argument concerning the limited ancient planning capabilities (see the introduction of Chapter 3) to its logical extreme and is almost certainly an inaccurate description of reality. First, there is no reason to believe that no two roads were ever constructed concurrently. Second, it is certainly possible that the course of some roads was planned with a future connection or with a concurrently built other road in mind. Note that a model obeying Assumption 1 may still produce output consistent with the first counterargument: Whenever the relative order of a number of subsequently built roads does not influence the course of either, they might as well

have been constructed concurrently, and this may well be a common scenario when roads are built within a large environment.

The second assumption puts a lower bound on the connectivity provided by a road network.

Assumption 2. A road network will grow to contain adequate paths between all pairs of significant places.

The assumption is motivated by the prohibitive difficulty of traversing untamed terrain and critically depends on how *adequate* will be defined. This is circumscribed by the two remaining assumptions.

Assumption 3. The course of roads optimizes a trade-off between road construction and prospective maintenance costs on the one hand, and mobility benefit on the other hand.

While Assumption 1 serves to discretize the time evolution of the model, Assumptions 2 and 3 together determine what should happen at each time step. The most surprising bit may be that we finally attribute optimization capabilities to ancient decision makers, albeit limited to the course of one road at a time. This is a standard assumption in the field of least-cost path analysis; we refer to Branting [19] for a critical discussion.

In principle, construction, maintenance, and travel costs for a segment of road may be defined independently. In the basic model discussed in this chapter, we will derive them as dimensionless quantities from properties of the terrain in a straightforward way:

Assumption 4. The cost of traversing a road segment is isotropic and proportional to that segment's construction and maintenance costs.

For example, if traversing a segment of road upwards a steep hill is considered twice as difficult as traveling on a level road of the same length, where difficulty may be measured interchangeably in terms of travel time or energy expenditure, then we assume that the same difficulty is experienced when traveling down the hill (isotropy) and further that constructing and maintaining the sloped road is considered also twice as costly as for the level one. Isotropy of travel costs may be an inaccurate assumption for single voyages but becomes quite reasonable when one considers the total cost experienced by all travelers over the lifetime of a road. Proportionality of construction and maintenance costs to travel costs may be more controversial. Clearly, building and repairing a bridge is significantly more expensive than merely laying and preserving a road bed. However, the effort required to traverse the resulting paths is quite similar. In these scenarios, our model might under-estimate the cost of construction or over-estimate the cost of movement for one road segment in relation to others. For application areas where this is a concern, it would be straightforward to lift the proportionality assumption and define the costs separately. For the analysis, however, it will be informative to control the costs using a single proportionality parameter. This parameter will weigh costs that depend on the frequency of use, in particular the presumed sum of travel costs over the lifetime of a road, against those that don't, which include construction and the largest part of maintenance costs.

Algorithm 1: Progressive Road Network (PRN)

Input:

- A connected network $N = (G, c)$ with $G = (V, E)$,
- a sequence $(\pi)_{i=1}^k$ over a set of connections $K \subseteq \mathcal{P}_2(V)$ with $\bigcup_{i=1}^k \{\pi_i\} = K$, and
- a cost-reduction function $r: \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \times \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$.

Output: A network whose graph is an edge-induced subgraph of G .

Notation: We write c_τ short for the reduced-cost function $e \mapsto r(c(e), \tau(e))$.

```

1  $F \leftarrow \emptyset$  // road segments
2  $\tau \leftarrow$  empty map from  $E$  to  $\mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$  // road tiers
3 for  $e \in E$  do
4   |  $\tau(e) \leftarrow 0$ 
5 for  $\{u, v\} \leftarrow \pi_1$  to  $\pi_k$  do // consider each connection in order
6   |  $P \leftarrow \text{LCP}((G, c_\tau), u, v)$  // plan a route for the connection
7   |  $F \leftarrow F \cup P$  // update the road network
8   | for  $e \in P$  do
9   | |  $\tau(e) \leftarrow \tau(e) + 1$  // adjust road tiers
10 return  $(G[F], c_\tau)$  // report the final road network
```

3.3.1 Model definition

We are now prepared to state a formal network formation model; see Algorithm 1 for a multi-tiered and Algorithm 2 for a derived binary variant. Both variants are discrete and graph based: The environment in which network formation takes place is itself represented by a *terrain network* comprising a graph $G = (V, E)$ and associated edge costs $c: E \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$; see Section 3.5.1 for its derivation from geographic information. The edges E of G represent feasible movement corridors along which a segment of road may be constructed; their costs represent the difficulty of constructing and traveling that segment (see Assumption 4). The vertices V represent either the origin or destination of a connection, we call such a vertex a *site*, or a possible junction point of the road network. In addition to the terrain graph, both variants of the model take as an input a sequence of unordered vertex pairs, π , which contains the connections to be *established* in lines 6 to 9. Formally, since the set of connections K can be derived from π , only π is an argument to Algorithms 1 and 2. The algorithms as stated can handle repeated connections, but we focus here on the case where $\pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)$ is a permutation over K , implying that every connection is established exactly once. We call π a *connection order* to stress this convention. Typically, we will also apply Assumption 2 and choose K as the set of all pairwise connections $K := \mathcal{P}_2(S)$ among a set of (archaeological) sites $S \subseteq V$. Like this, every pair of sites establishes a connection eventually.

The model variants differ in their third parameter. The more general Algorithm 1 takes as an input a cost-reduction function $r: \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \times \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$, which we may assume is nondecreasing in the first argument, representing a *base cost*, and nonincreasing in the second argument, representing a *road tier*. Intuitively, a road tier of zero signifies undisturbed wilderness, a tier of one represents the most basic type of road, and higher tiers correspond to improved roads that offer progressively

Algorithm 2: Sequential Road Network (SRN)**Input:** A network $N = (G, c)$ and a sequence π as in Algorithm 1. A scalar $\alpha \in [0, 1]$.**Output:** A network as in Algorithm 1.

```

1 function  $r_\alpha(c, \tau)$ 
2   if  $\tau = 0$  then
3     return  $c$ 
4   else
5     return  $\alpha c$ 
6 return  $\text{PRN}(N, \pi, r_\alpha)$ 

```

lower movement costs. At smaller scales, road tiers can model footpaths that are gradually coming into existence through continued use, which in turn can be modeled by repeating the connections in π . At larger scales, road tiers describe the idea that a road that appears in multiple connections draws more traffic and is a reasonable target to invest into.

For the remainder of this chapter we will focus our attention on the special case of Algorithm 2, where there is effectively only one nonzero tier. This is achieved through the cost-reduction function r_α , which only distinguishes between a road being present, $\tau > 0$, or not, $\tau = 0$. More precisely, an edge e of tier $\tau(e) = 0$ incurs the full base cost of $c(e)$ while an edge of a positive tier has a reduced cost of $\alpha c(e)$. This has a simple interpretation in the sense of Assumption 4: The lifetime travel costs experienced along a road built at edge e are assumed to amount to $\alpha c(e)$ per connection involving it while the initial construction and prospective maintenance costs sum to $(1 - \alpha)c(e)$.¹ To see that this interpretation makes sense, note that only the first connection established along a least-cost path that includes some edge $e \in E$ sees the full cost of $c(e)$ while all later connections see a reduced cost of $\alpha c(e)$ for that edge. Thus, if ℓ connections involve e throughout the network formation procedure, then the total cost contributed by e to least-cost paths is $\ell \alpha c(e) + (1 - \alpha)c(e)$. We will refer to the total cost of all least-cost paths computed throughout an execution of Algorithm 1 as the *historical cost* of the evolving road network; see Definition 3.15 below for details.

Notation

For the analysis it will be helpful to introduce some notation. Unless stated otherwise, all of the following refers to Algorithm 1. First, we will distinguish variable states throughout the execution of the algorithm.

Definition 3.11: Time steps. The expression *at time* i always refers to the program state between lines 6 and 7 in the i -th iteration of the loop in line 5. We write P_i for P at time i , F_i for F at time i , and τ_i short for τ at time i .

Note that P , F , and τ without a time reference are defined only locally in Algorithm 1. In

¹Maintenance costs may have a component that depends on the number of users. This can be modeled by distributing them among the $\alpha c(e)$ and $(1 - \alpha)c(e)$ parts through an increase of α .

particular, we will reuse P and τ without the index as identifiers for paths and road tiers in proofs. We are also interested in the evolution of the edge cost function in line 6.

Definition 3.12: Reduced cost. We call $c_i: E \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ with $c_i(e) \mapsto r(c(e), \tau_i(e))$ the *reduced cost (function at time i)*. For clarity, we refer to a least-cost path with respect to c_i for some $i \in [k]$ as a least-reduced-cost path.

In particular, P_i has minimum reduced cost $c_i(P_i) = \sum_{e \in P_i} c_i(e)$ by definition.

Definition 3.13: Establishing paths. We say that P_i *establishes* the connection π_i . We further overload Definition 3.11 by saying that π_i *is established at time i* . For $K' \subseteq K$, a set of paths Q *establishes K'* if every $P \in Q$ establishes one-to-one a connection $\pi_i \in K'$ at some time i . The paths establishing K are jointly referred to as the (π) -*establishing paths*.

The shorthand *established at time i* is to be understood as the connection being processed during the i -th iteration of the main loop, which updates the state of edges along the path P_i . As we focus our attention on *sequential road networks*—those produced as an output of Algorithm 2—we can argue about the evolution of road tiers succinctly.

Definition 3.14: Cheap and costly edges. We say that an edge $e \in E$ is *i -cheap* if $\tau_i(e) > 0$. Otherwise, we say that e is *i -costly*.

Finally, we will refer to the output network and a measure of its cost.

Definition 3.15: Sequential road network. Given an input (N, π, α) to Algorithm 2, we write $R_{N, \alpha}(\pi) := \text{SRN}(N, \pi, \alpha)$ for the *(sequential) road network* returned by the algorithm, and we denote by $C_{N, \alpha}(\pi) := \sum_{i=1}^k c_i(P_i)$ its *historical cost*. When N and α are clear from the context, we write just $R(\pi)$ and $C(\pi)$, respectively.

The historical cost includes both construction and travel costs of a road, weighed by α . However, as we will detail in Section 3.4, it captures only provisory travel costs for a connection, which may decrease further as the network evolves.

3.3.2 Local perspective

Let us examine the parameter α from the perspective of two sites $u, v \in V$ that aim to establish a connection. In the extreme case of $\alpha = 1$, edge costs remain constant throughout the execution of Algorithm 1. Thus, new road segments are constructed in line 7 along an initial least-cost path P_0 that connects u and v in G with respect to the terrain costs c . In this sense, the sites ignore the pre-existing road network in their planning. It may happen by coincidence that they choose a path that includes existing road segments, represented by the edges in F , but they might as well create a new road right next to an existing one. Through this behavior, the reduced cost of a future least-cost u - v -path is minimized. Indeed, $\alpha c(P_0)$ is a lower bound for the reduced cost of any u - v -path. A natural interpretation of the $\alpha = 1$ regime is therefore that decision makers completely disregard construction costs to ensure the highest possible connectivity.

In the opposite extreme case of $\alpha = 0$, existing roads are assigned a reduced cost of zero. The least-cost path computed in line 6 of Algorithm 1 thus minimizes only the terrain cost of new road segments and accepts to this end detours of any length along existing roads. The economic

interpretation is that decision makers in the $\alpha = 0$ regime disregard travel times in order to establish basic road connectivity at the lowest cost possible.

Intermediate values of α interpolate between the two extreme regimes and lead to a non-trivial cost–benefit trade-off. In particular, we can give a condition on the creation of *shortcuts*, represented by the subpath P' in the following statement.

Proposition 3.16. *Let (N, π, α) be an input to Algorithm 2. Let further $i \in [k]$ and $\{u, v\} := \pi_i$, and assume that there are distinct vertices $a, b \in V$ such that*

1. P_i has an a - b -subpath P' with $P' \cap F_i = \emptyset$, and
2. there exists an a - b -path $Q \subseteq F_i$.

Then, $c(P') \leq \alpha c(Q)$.

Proof. Since $P' \cap F_i = \emptyset$, edges in P' are i -costly so that P has a reduced cost of

$$c_i(P_i) = c(P') + c_i(P_i \setminus P').$$

Let now $X \subseteq (P_i \setminus P') \cup Q$ be another u - v -path. Such a path exists as Q is an a - b -path while $P_i \setminus P'$ is either the union of a u - a -path and a b - v -path or the union of a u - b -path and an a - v -path. At time i , X has a reduced cost of

$$c_i(X) \leq c_i(Q) + c_i(P_i \setminus P') = \alpha c(Q) + c_i(P_i \setminus P')$$

as all edges in $Q \subseteq F_i$ are i -cheap. Since P_i is a minimum u - v -path with respect to c_i , the claim that $c(P') \leq \alpha c(Q)$ follows. ■

Since travel costs are proportional to terrain costs, this shows that shortcuts can only be added to a road network if their travel cost is at most α times the travel cost of any detour along existing roads with the same endpoints. For instance for $\alpha = 1/2$, shortcuts must cut travel costs in half to be considered cost-efficient. A global consequence of this argument is the following:

Corollary 3.17. *Let $N = (V, E, c)$ be a network with strictly positive edge costs $c: E \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{>0}$, let $\alpha = 0$, and let π be an arbitrary sequence over $\mathcal{P}_2(V)$. Then, $R_{N, \alpha}(\pi)$ is a forest.*

Proof. At the start of Algorithm 1, F is initialized as the empty set, which contains no cycle. Assume towards a contradiction that a cycle is added to F in some iteration i of the main loop in line 5. Then, the establishing path P_i contains an a - b -subpath P' with $a \neq b$ and $P' \subseteq E \setminus F_i$ such that a and b are already connected in F_i . Thus, there exists an a - b -path $Q \subseteq F_i$. By Proposition 3.16, it is $c(P') \leq \alpha c(Q) = 0$. As P' is nonempty, this contradicts $c(P') > 0$. ■

3.3.3 Global perspective

Let us next look at the network formation process as a whole and discuss the impact of both α and π on the topology of the network returned by Algorithm 2.

Figure 3.1: Sequential road networks for different values of α . Panel **A**: The artificial terrain network (V, E, c) with sites S . The graph (V, E) is obtained from a Delaunay triangulation of $|V| = 900$ points that are uniformly distributed in the square. The sites $S \subseteq V$ with $|S| = 20$ are selected at random. Edge costs c are proportional to the Euclidean length of an edge in the drawing and represent flat terrain. Panels **B** to **E**: Road networks generated by Algorithm 2 given a fixed connection order $\pi \in \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{P}_2(S))$ and a varying trade-off parameter α . Sequential decisions in **B** only minimize construction costs, in **E** only maximize benefit (low travel cost).

Cost reduction

From an economic perspective, we may infer from the per-connection behavior that the parameter α reflects a society's inclination towards infrastructure investments. Indeed, empirical observations demonstrate that α controls the density of the road network: Low values tend to produce sparser networks that are cheap to construct but impose long travel distances along some of the established routes. High values, on the other hand, produce densely connected networks which are expensive to build but offer more direct site-to-site paths. Panels 3.1B to 3.1E show road networks produced from a fixed connection order and for varying values of α . A planar drawing of the terrain graph G is shown in Figure 3.1A. The associated costs c are chosen proportional to the edges' lengths in this drawing. In other words, the input network represents a flat terrain with homogeneous surface conditions, where construction and travel costs only depend on the length of a road segment and not on its location or orientation.

To gain a better understanding of how α regulates density, it will again be instructive to look at the extreme cases, starting with $\alpha = 1$. Let us also take the flat terrain analysis to its logical extreme, which is to lift the network formation procedure from (planar) graphs to the Euclidean plane. As

our focus remains the discrete setting, we will only sketch this extension. Consider a set $S \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$ of n points that are placed at equal angular distances on the unit circle and suppose that all pairs of these points should be connected, that is $K := \mathcal{P}_2(S)$. In the discrete setting, the path computed in line 6 of Algorithm 1 for $\alpha = 1$ is a least-cost path with respect to terrain costs c . In the continuous setting, this translates to a shortest path in the Euclidean metric, which is simply the line segment connecting the two endpoints of a connection. Fix one of the points on the circle. The (clockwise) central angle between this point and its k -th neighbor, counted (clockwise) around the circle from one, is $\theta_k := 2\pi \frac{k}{n}$. This results in a Euclidean distance between the two points of $2 \sin \frac{\theta_k}{2} = 2 \sin \frac{2\pi k}{2n}$. The total length of straight line segments from the fixed point to all other points is thus given by

$$\ell' := \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} 2 \sin \frac{2\pi k}{2n}.$$

Applying Euler's formula and the fact that $\sin 0 = 0$ gives

$$\ell' = \frac{2}{2i} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left(e^{i \frac{\pi k}{n}} - e^{-i \frac{\pi k}{n}} \right).$$

We can substitute twice the closed form of a geometric series to obtain

$$\ell' = -i \left(\frac{1 - e^{i\pi}}{1 - e^{i \frac{\pi}{n}}} - \frac{1 - e^{-i\pi}}{1 - e^{-i \frac{\pi}{n}}} \right).$$

From $e^{i\pi} = e^{-i\pi} = -1$, it further follows that

$$\ell' = 2i \frac{e^{-i \frac{\pi}{n}} - e^{i \frac{\pi}{n}}}{2 - \left(e^{i \frac{\pi}{n}} + e^{-i \frac{\pi}{n}} \right)}.$$

Applying again Euler's formula and the symmetry $\sin(-x) = -\sin x$ yields

$$\ell' = \frac{2 \sin \frac{\pi}{n}}{1 - \cos \frac{\pi}{n}}.$$

Finally, we invoke a half-angle inequality of the tangent to arrive at

$$\ell' = 2 \cot \frac{\pi}{2n} \in \Theta(n).$$

The asymptotic behavior can be derived from the series expansion $\cot \frac{1}{x} = x + O\left(\frac{1}{x}\right)$ and is illustrated by the fact that $\tan x \approx x$ for x near zero. If we sum the above quantity over all n points, then we count each shortest path exactly twice. The total length of unique establishing paths in the continuous setting is thus

$$\ell := \frac{n\ell'}{2} = n \cot \frac{\pi}{2n} \in \Theta(n^2).$$

Since no three points in S are colinear, establishing paths can only intersect in finitely many points. Hence, ℓ is also the total length of the continuous road network $F \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$.

The case of $\alpha = 0$ is more intricate. For $\alpha < 1$, the LCP subroutine in the continuous setting returns a finite union of straight line segments. The set $F \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$ thus remains a union of line segments, which can now be traversed at zero cost. Corollary 3.17 translates readily to this setting and guarantees that F remains cycle-free throughout the network formation procedure. We are again interested in the total length ℓ of F and by extension in the number κ of connected components of the set $F \cup S$. Initially, we have $\ell = 0$ and $\kappa = n$. Consider a path P establishing a connection $\{u, v\}$. If u and v are already connected in F , then $P \subseteq F$, so that both ℓ and κ remain constant. Otherwise, by minimality of P , the connected components of $P \setminus F$ are $p \geq 1$ straight line segments that connect $p + 1$ connected components of $F \cup S$ in a cycle-free sequence. When F is updated in line 7, these connected components merge into one, so that κ decreases by p . On the other hand, ℓ increases by at most 2, the diameter of the circle, as this is an upper bound on the reduced cost of P . As $\kappa \geq 1$ throughout the procedure, it follows that

$$\ell \leq 2(n - 1) \in O(n)$$

at all times.

The example demonstrates that in an idealized, *continuous* setting, there can be a linear separation between the densities of road networks constructed for $\alpha = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$. In the discrete setting where the terrain is represented by a graph, the effect is limited by the density of the input graph and by the presence of low-cost movement corridors. Such corridors, which may represent geographic features such as valleys and ridges, can attract many connections and reduce network density even in the high α regime. This will become apparent when we generate the terrain network in Section 3.5.1, which involves a process very similar to Algorithm 2 for $\alpha = 1$.

We can take away one more insight from the continuous setup, which concerns the *efficiency* of the networks produced. When $\alpha = 0$, we argued that the goal of decision makers is to establish individual connections at the lowest construction cost possible. But does this also lead to a network of minimum length? If we require pairwise connectivity, captured by the canonical choice of $K := \mathcal{P}_2(S)$, then it follows from Corollary 3.17 that the resulting road network is a Steiner tree connecting the terminals S via intermediate nodes in \mathbb{R}^2 at which line segments of F cross or join. If the Steiner tree had minimum length, then the interior angles at each node would amount to 120° [55]. In the continuous setting sketched above, however, it can be shown that zero-cost line segments always meet at a right angle at nodes that are not a terminal [95]. In this sense, sequential road networks are suboptimal network designs. We will discuss efficiency in terms of historical cost from an algorithmic perspective in Section 3.4.2.

Connection order

Let us now turn to the parameter π , which captures the historical path of network link formation. The earliest connections in π see few pre-existing road segments and tend to be established along low-cost paths in terms of the terrain costs c . For $\alpha < 1$, later connections are less likely to follow such “direct” paths but will instead make detours along existing roads, for which construction costs have already been paid. In this sense, the parameter α regulates not only the cost–benefit trade-off and its direct effect on network density, but it also controls the intensity of temporal

Figure 3.2: Relative magnitude of path dependence for varying α . The input N to Algorithm 2 and the set of sites S are the same as in Figure 3.1. For every value of α , 5 000 pairs of road networks produced from independently and uniformly chosen connection orders $\pi \in \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{P}_2(S))$ are compared; see Definition 3.6 for the comparison. A value of 1 represents the largest dissimilarity observed in the experiment; whiskers denote the first and 99th percentile. Inset: Exemplary network topology effect of resampling π for $\alpha = 0.4$.

path dependence. This can be quantified by measuring the geometric dissimilarity between road networks generated on the same terrain and for equal sites S but with the connection order π chosen uniformly at random over all permutations of $\mathcal{P}_2(S)$; see Figure 3.2 for empirical results and an example of two networks emerging from distinct histories but otherwise equal conditions. We observe that the road network remains invariant at $\alpha = 1$ but is influenced by the connection order for $\alpha < 1$. As α goes to zero, the mean dissimilarity between pairs of networks that are produced from independently sampled random orders increases. The experiment demonstrates that the order of connections impacts the topology of the road network, depending on the relative importance of low construction costs. However, it does not indicate which connections are the most influential. To this end, we next fix α and measure the effect of a local change at different positions in the connection order π . In this setting, we find that the network topology emerges quite rapidly in the early stages of network formation, leaving little room for later connections to influence each other's establishing paths.

The second experiment is conducted as follows. We first fix a terrain network $N = (V, E, c)$, a set of designated sites $S \subseteq V$, and a cost-reduction parameter α . We write $s := |S|$ for the number of sites and $k := |K|$ for the number of connections $K := \mathcal{P}_2(S)$. Next, we sample 20 000 *base connection orders* uniformly at random from $\mathcal{S}(K)$ and store them in a multiset Π . For each $\pi \in \Pi$, the resulting road network $R_{N,\alpha}(\pi)$ forms the basis for $k - 1$ comparisons: For every index $i \in [k - 1]$, we consider the perturbed connection order $\pi^{i,i+1}$, which differs from π only by an exchange of the i -th and $(i + 1)$ -th position, and we compare the associated road network $R_{N,\alpha}(\pi^{i,i+1})$ to $R_{N,\alpha}(\pi)$ in terms of their geometric dissimilarity with respect to S . We store the results in a vector $d^\pi \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^{k-1}$:

$$d_i^\pi := \delta_S(R_{N,\alpha}(\pi), R_{N,\alpha}(\pi^{i,i+1})).$$

Figure 3.3: Vanishing impact of local changes around later positions i in a connection order of length k for $\alpha = 0.5$ and for varying networks N and sites S (first panel, shown with example road networks). It is $s := |S|$. Impact is measured as the normalized mean dissimilarity d_i between a network generated from a random connection order and the network obtained from the same order with the i -th and $(i + 1)$ -th connection exchanged; $d_i = 1$ ($\log d_i = 0$) denotes the largest mean observed. Each point represents 20000 comparisons; means of zero are omitted. Solid lines show a linear fit in log scale for $i \leq s$ (middle panel) and in log-log scale for $i > s$ (right panel). The value r^2 denotes the coefficient of determination of the regression line.

Finally, we sum d^π over all base orders π and rescale the result such that its largest entry becomes 1. Formally, this yields the vector of measurements

$$d := \frac{\sum_{\pi \in \Pi} d^\pi}{\max_{i \in [k-1]} \sum_{\pi \in \Pi} d_i^\pi}.$$

Intuitively, d provides a relative estimate of how much a road network changes depending on when in the temporal sequence of network formation a small adjustment is made. Figure 3.3 shows the results of performing the experiment for $\alpha = 0.5$ and in four different *scenarios* that comprise the terrain network N and associated sites S :

- Scenario **A** uses the same terrain network as in Figure 3.1A. For technical reasons, the random assignment of the $s = 20$ designated sites differs.
- Scenario **B** uses the same terrain graph and number of designated sites as scenario **A**, but the sites are chosen uniformly at random from a subset of vertices that are close to the corners of the unit square. This results in a clustered arrangement of the sites.
- Scenario **C**, on the other hand, concerns $s = 16$ well-distributed sites. To this end we place the sites at regular positions on a 46×46 square grid of order $|V| = 2116$. Terrain costs are uniform up to a small random perturbation, which enforces uniqueness of least-cost paths with high probability.
- Scenario **D** considers a drawing of the complete graph on $|V| = s = 30$ vertices: Each pair of vertices shares an edge and every vertex is selected as a designated site. Edge costs are again set to the Euclidean distance between the connected vertices.

Each scenario corresponds to one row of Figure 3.3 and is depicted along with an example road network in the left panel.

In all four scenarios, we observe a rapid decay of d_i as the index i grows. A closer look leads us to suspect that this decrease can be approximately described by an initial phase of exponential decay for $i \lesssim s$ and by a power law for $i \gtrsim s$. To put this hypothesis to test, we perform linear regression separately in log scale for $1 \leq i \leq s$ and in log-log scale for $s < i < k$. The rationale behind these transformations is that for a function $f: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ it holds that

$$f(t) = \beta e^{\lambda t} \iff \log f(t) = \lambda t + \log \beta$$

and

$$f(t) = \eta t^\gamma \iff \log f(e^t) = \gamma t + \log \eta$$

where $t \mapsto \log f(e^t)$ can be written as $\log t \mapsto \log f(t)$. Note that it is possible for some $(i, i + 1)$ -exchange to induce no network change for any of the base orders, implying $d_i = 0$. In this case, we cannot compute $\log d_i$, and we ignore the corresponding position i when fitting. This can happen especially for changes around later positions, where the probability of affecting the resulting road network is very low. The regression lines are shown in the middle and right panels of Figure 3.3 along with their coefficients of determination r^2 .

Figure 3.4: Logarithmic plot of the impact of swapping positions i and j in a connection order of length k for $\alpha = 0.5$. The terrain network N and the sites S are shown in Figure 3.1A. Impact is measured as in Figure 3.3 with $i + 1$ replaced by j . A log-value of zero (black) denotes the largest average dissimilarity observed. Means of zero (no change observed) are shown in white. Panel A: The measured dissimilarity matrix D . Each entry represents the mean geometric dissimilarity of 1 000 comparisons. Panel B: A simple reconstruction of D from its first off-diagonal: The diagonal is set to zero and, for $i < j$, entries (i, j) and (j, i) are both set to $\sum_{\ell=i}^{j-1} f(\ell)$ where $f(\ell) = D_{\ell, \ell+1}$. Panel C: A “smooth” reconstruction of D defined as for panel B but where f is a monotone approximation of the first off-diagonal.

For all scenarios tested, we find that the linear log-scale fit for $1 \leq i \leq s$ is a good approximation for the transformed measurements $\log d_i$, explaining 98% or more of the variance of the transformed data ($r^2 \geq 0.98$). In scenarios A to C, a slight upward curvature of the transformed measurements is visible, suggesting that the decay is a bit slower than exponential in this range. However, this would be consistent with a transition to a second regime of slower decay, given that such a transition is smooth and starts before time s . Also in the range $s < i < k$, the linear fits in log-log scale provide an adequate description of the transformed measurements. Here, our confidence is reduced by the fact that the measurements disperse around the linear approximation for $i \geq 2s$, leaving up to 34% of the variance of the transformed data unexplained ($0.66 \leq r^2 \leq 0.74$). Except for scenario D, this variance is “well-behaved” in the sense that the regression line remains accurate for $i < 2s$ despite the least-squares method being very sensitive to outliers. These results suggest two distinguishable regimes of decay for the relative importance of connections over time in the intermediate- α regime, for which an exponential and a power function appear to be adequate approximations. These findings seem to be structurally robust as we test sites that are unordered, clustered, and well-distributed, as well as a non-planar terrain graph structure.

We now extend the analysis to include general transpositions, where any two entries in a connection order are swapped. Data generation for the extended experiment is performed as before, except that

- the terrain network and sites are as in Figure 3.1A,
- we sample only $|\Pi| = 1\,000$ base connection orders,
- instead of the vector d^π , we prepare the matrix $D^\pi \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^{k \times k}$ with

$$D_{i,j}^\pi := \delta_S(R_{N,\alpha}(\pi), R_{N,\alpha}(\pi^{i,j}))$$

for all $\pi \in \Pi$, and

- instead of the vector d , we define the matrix of measurements

$$D := \frac{\sum_{\pi \in \Pi} D^\pi}{\max_{i,j \in [k]} \sum_{\pi \in \Pi} D_{i,j}^\pi}.$$

It follows that D is symmetric and has zero diagonal. Moreover, its first off-diagonal equals the vector d from the previous experiment up to the choice of base orders Π .

The entry-wise logarithm of the measurement matrix D is shown in Figure 3.4A. White areas correspond to entries $D_{i,j} = 0$, where $\log D_{i,j}$ is not defined. Visually, it appears as if the plot shows a fabric of interwoven translucent stripes that begin near the diagonal and extend both horizontally and vertically towards the perimeter of the depicted matrix. This leads us to suspect that

$$D_{i,j} \approx D_{i,\ell} + D_{\ell,j} \quad (3.1)$$

may be an adequate approximation for all $i \leq \ell \leq j$. This is because, informally, (i, ℓ) and (ℓ, j) move vertically and horizontally between (i, j) and the main diagonal as ℓ varies. Checking approximation (3.1) for all triples in

$$X := \{(i, \ell, k) \mid i \leq \ell \leq j \wedge D_{i,j} + (D_{i,\ell} + D_{\ell,j}) \neq 0\},$$

we find that the median relative error

$$\text{median}_{(i,\ell,j) \in X} \frac{2|D_{i,j} - (D_{i,\ell} + D_{\ell,j})|}{D_{i,j} + (D_{i,\ell} + D_{\ell,j})} \approx 10\%$$

is moderate while the mean relative error is somewhat more significant at 19%. Given that the entries of D span many orders of magnitude (see the logarithmic scale in Figure 3.4), we conclude that approximation (3.1) appears to be relatively accurate.

Approximation (3.1) might allow us to predict D from its first off-diagonal alone, which would reduce the number of network samples required for an estimate of D significantly. To this end, we apply it recursively to obtain the approximation

$$D_{i,j} \approx \sum_{\ell=i}^{j-1} D_{\ell,\ell+1} \quad (3.2)$$

for $i \leq j$, which is shown in Figure 3.4B. As it stands, approximation (3.2) is much less accurate than approximation (3.1): the median and mean relative errors, computed analogously, increase to 65% and 83%, respectively. As we intend to use the right-hand side of approximation (3.2) as a prediction for the left-hand side, it might now make sense to consider also the associated coefficient of determination, which is $r^2 = 0.98$. However, the coefficient may be inflated due to the measurements $D_{i,j}$ being highly non-linear in i and j so that larger entries of D could dominate the average that enters the denominator in Definition 3.6. A more informative statistic may be to measure r^2 in terms of the transformed measurements $\log D_{i,j}$ and predictions $\log \sum_{\ell=i}^{j-1} D_{\ell,\ell+1}$ over all $i \leq j$ for which both quantities are defined. This gives a more modest value of $r^2 = 0.56$.

Figure 3.4C will be discussed next.

Smoothing the measurements

Despite the noticeable error, we will make use of approximation (3.2) in Section 3.5 as a sample-efficient method to gain insight into the temporal sensitivity of a given set of connections in an application context. Then, for technical reasons, a strictly monotone estimate $f: X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ of the discrete function $i \mapsto d_i$ will be necessary, where $X \supseteq [k-1]$ can be continuous. This requirement is, however, quite natural: The effect that one connection has on another is communicated through the expansion of the road network, and the opportunities for this can only decrease as the network grows over time. Based on previous observations (see Figure 3.3 and the accompanying analysis), we define f as a piecewise function that transitions from an exponential to a power function:

$$f(t; h, \beta, \lambda, \eta, \gamma) := \begin{cases} \beta e^{\lambda t} & \text{if } t \in [1, h + \frac{1}{2}), \\ \eta t^\gamma & \text{if } t \in [h + \frac{1}{2}, k - 1]. \end{cases}$$

The parameter $h \in [k-2]$ specifies the transition time. For a fixed value of h and for a given a vector of measurements $x \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^{k-1}$ and a small constant $\varepsilon > 0$, the remaining parameters are obtained from an optimum solution $(\lambda, \gamma, \beta', \eta')$ to the conic quadratic program

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{minimize} && \left\| M^{(x_1, \dots, x_h)} \left(\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ h & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \lambda \\ \beta' \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} \log x_1 \\ \vdots \\ \log x_h \end{pmatrix} \right) \right\| && (3.3a) \\ & \lambda, \gamma, \beta', \eta' \in \mathbb{R} \end{aligned}$$

$$+ \left\| M^{(x_{h+1}, \dots, x_{k-1})} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \log(h+1) & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \log(k-1) & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \gamma \\ \eta' \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} \log x_{h+1} \\ \vdots \\ \log x_{k-1} \end{pmatrix} \right) \right\|$$

$$\text{subject to} \quad \left(h + \frac{1}{2} \right) \lambda + \beta' = \log \left(h + \frac{1}{2} \right) \gamma + \eta', \quad (3.3b)$$

$$\lambda \leq -\varepsilon, \quad (3.3c)$$

$$\gamma \leq -\varepsilon. \quad (3.3d)$$

We use λ and γ as reported by the solver and derive $\beta := e^{\beta'}$ and $\eta := e^{\eta'}$ from β' and η' . The objective (3.3a) combines two linear regression objectives: one in log scale for $1 \leq i \leq h$ and one in log-log scale for $h+1 \leq i \leq k-1$. Like this, it balances the goodness of the fits shown in the second and third columns of Figure 3.3. For a vector $v \in \mathbb{R}^n$, the matrix $M^v \in \{0, 1\}^{n \times n}$ is defined by

$$M_{i,j}^v := \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i = j \wedge v_i > 0, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Its purpose is to exclude any zero entries of x from the computation, which are frequent in practice. We assume to this end the formal convention that $0 \log 0 = 0$. Constraint (3.3b) ensures that f will be a continuous function. Note that without this requirement, balancing the two summands of objective (3.3a) would be trivial. The constant ε in constraints (3.3c) and (3.3d) guarantees that f will be strictly decreasing. It may come into play when the measurements x are based on a poor

sample size and suggest otherwise. In normal operation, however, we expect constraints (3.3c) and (3.3d) to be inactive.

In this section, we compute f in terms of the first off-diagonal of D , formally $x_i := D_{i,i+1}$ for all $i \in [k-1]$. Here and in Section 3.5, the transition point h is chosen to minimize the sum of squared errors $\sum_{i=1}^{k-1} (f(i) - x_i)^2$. This is achieved simply by trying all $k-2$ possible values for h and computing the remaining parameters using program (3.3). It turns out that $h = 11$ is optimal for the current choice of x . We note that this is not entirely consistent with our suspicion that the regime shift occurs around $s = 20$. However, the above method to choose h is by intention sensitive to scale and should prioritize a good fit in the initial regime, which is best achieved by excluding positions that are already showing signs of slower decay. Given f , we define the matrix $D^f \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^{k \times k}$ with

$$D_{i,j}^f := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } i = j, \\ \sum_{\ell=i}^{j-1} f(\ell) & \text{if } i < j, \\ \sum_{\ell=j}^{i-1} f(\ell) & \text{if } i > j. \end{cases}$$

The logarithm of this matrix, where defined, is shown in Figure 3.4C. The coefficient of determination of D^f as a prediction for D is $r^2 = 1.00$ when limited to the first off-diagonal of the matrices and $r^2 = 0.87$ for the (vectorized) full matrices. When the coefficients are computed in terms of $\log D_{i,j}$ and $\log D_{i,j}^f$ for all $i \leq j$ with $D_{i,j} \neq 0$, which corresponds to the regions in Figure 3.4A that are not white, then they decrease to moderate values of $r^2 = 0.43$ for the off-diagonal and $r^2 = 0.53$ at large. The median and mean relative errors between permissible entries of D and D^f are 120% and 112%, respectively. These are severe inaccuracies, yet they still suggest that D^f captures the vast differences in scale of the matrix D adequately. In Section 3.5, this will turn out to be sufficient for practical purposes. The reconstruction can be improved by sampling the off-diagonal at a higher resolution, although not significantly: At a tenfold sample size of 10000 base connection orders, the coefficients of determination increase to $r^2 = 0.53$ for the off-diagonal and $r^2 = 0.60$ for all finite entries of the log-transformed matrix while the median and mean relative errors for the untransformed matrices lower to 106% and 101%, respectively.

3.4 Computational complexity

In the previous section, we empirically analyzed a sequential network formation procedure that is designed to describe the possible evolution of past road networks and to predict missing links in their archaeological record. The experiments conducted so far have utilized random historical paths and focused on the model's sensitivity to small changes in such artificial histories. We found that the network predictions generated by the model depend critically on the order in which connections are established, particularly during the earliest stages of network formation.

Evidently, choosing historical paths at random is not appropriate for an application of the model in archaeological studies. Instead, it will be necessary to identify plausible connection orders that are consistent with a body of evidence. For this purpose we are interested in methods to fit the model parameter π to a set of real-world data, for example by minimizing the distance of the generated road network to locations that we suppose it has passed. This poses the model's

Figure 3.5: A terrain network on which establishing paths can differ from future least-cost paths.

application as an optimization task, where π is the variable being optimized over. In this section, we will discuss that task from a computational perspective.

We should clarify that we have not forgotten about the other model parameter, α . In theory, it could be included as another variable in the optimization problem. In practice, though, it is problematic that larger values of α produce a denser network, which increases the likelihood of road segments coinciding with spatial evidence. To find α procedurally, it would be necessary to augment the optimization target to favor solutions that match the true density of the studied network. Unfortunately, it is in the nature of the application that this density is typically unknown. Therefore, we will assume in this section that α is provided as a constant reflecting a prior belief.

One may wonder if it is possible, in moderately sized instances at least, to find an optimal connection order π simply by testing all possibilities and selecting the one that produced the most accurate network. To see the difficulties with this approach, consider a set of designated sites S of size $s := |S|$ that should be pairwise connected: $K := \mathcal{P}_2(S)$. Then, the set of candidate orders $\mathcal{S}(K)$ has a cardinality of

$$\binom{s}{2}! \in \Omega\left(\left(\frac{s^2}{4e}\right)^{s^2/4}\right).$$

This number exceeds one trillion at $s = 6$ and surpasses the number of clock cycles that a 5 GHz processor can accumulate in 300 years at $s = 7$ sites. Therefore, exhaustive enumeration of possibilities is not feasible for most real-world data.

The astronomical growth of the number of possible connection orders does not rule out the existence of an efficient algorithm that can identify the best option by exploiting the optimization problem's structure in a clever way. However, we will provide in this section evidence that such an algorithm, in all generality, most likely does not exist. For this purpose, we first need to formalize the desired optimization objectives and resulting problems in more detail. We will consider two high-level goals: Finding a connection order whose associated road network coincides with evidence and computing one whose network is as efficient as possible. For the latter, we make use of the historical cost C from Definition 3.15 as a proxy for efficiency. Note that this cost is not strictly a property of the final road network but depends to some extent on the history of its formation. This stems from the fact that, for $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, the least-cost path along which a connection is established is not necessarily the least-cost path for the same connection in the final road network. To see this, consider the terrain network in Figure 3.5 and generate the road

network for $\alpha = 0.5$ and the connection order

$$\pi := (\{b, t\}, \{s, t\}, \{s, a\}, \{a, t\}, \{s, b\}, \{a, b\}).$$

Network formation is as follows:

1. $\pi_1 = \{b, t\}$ is established along the edge $\{b, t\}$, decreasing its reduced cost from 6 to 3,
2. $\pi_2 = \{s, t\}$ is established along (s, b, t) at a reduced cost of 7 as the alternative path (s, a, t) has a reduced cost of 8, thus $\{s, b\}$ becomes cheap,
3. $\pi_3 = \{s, a\}$ and $\pi_4 = \{a, t\}$ are established along the costly edges $\{s, a\}$ and $\{a, t\}$, and,
4. as all edges are now cheap, $\pi_5 = \{s, b\}$ and $\pi_6 = \{a, b\}$ are established along the edge $\{s, b\}$ and the path (a, s, b) , respectively.

Since all edges are cheap eventually, it is easy to confirm that the only connection $\{u, v\} \in K$ for which the edge $\{b, t\}$ appears in a least-cost u - v -path in the final road network $R(\pi)$ is $\{u, v\} = \{b, t\}$. In particular, the unique least-cost s - t -path in $R(\pi)$ is (s, a, t) , which differs from the path (s, b, t) along which $\{s, t\}$ was established. Moreover, the historical cost for π is $C(\pi) = 29$ whereas the historical cost for the alternative history

$$\pi' := (\{s, a\}, \{a, t\}, \{s, b\}, \{b, t\}, \{a, b\}, \{s, t\})$$

is $C(\pi') = 26 < C(\pi)$ despite $R(\pi) = R(\pi')$. Fortunately, the possibility that least-cost paths may change after connections are established does not conflict with the assumptions underlying our model: As per Assumption 1, agents are unaware of the network's future development and may well construct roads that they later abandon for better options. We will consider the historical cost in our analysis as this allows us to keep track of both construction and *predicted* travel costs as connections are established. Considering the evolution of travel costs as the network grows further would complicate the analysis, with arguably little gain in insight.

With respect to the second optimization goal—producing a network that explains a body of spatial evidence—we will use the following simplified objective function:

Definition 3.18: Mismatch. Given a terrain network $N = (V, E, c)$, a road network $R_{N, \alpha}(\pi) = (V', E, c')$ produced by Algorithm 2, and a target edge set $T \subseteq E$, we define the *mismatch* of π with respect to T as the cardinality $M_T^{N, \alpha}(\pi) := |(F \setminus T) \cup (T \setminus F)|$ of the symmetric difference of F and T . We write just M_T when N and α are clear from the context.

Intuitively, the set of target edges T contains known or assumed roads and the mismatch M_T counts both the number of these edges missed by the predicted road network and the number of non-target edges it includes. In the case study presented in Section 3.5, more complex measures will be used in the objective: the sum of squared Euclidean distances between the road network and a set of evidence points and the geometric dissimilarity with respect to a reference network, whose junction points and edges are not part of the terrain network. For the purpose of a complexity analysis, however, we consider these measures to be too intricate. Underlying the present analysis is the sentiment that, if approximating evidence proves to be challenging already for the simple mismatch function defined above, then this suggests that more complex objectives may pose computational difficulties as well.

3.4.1 Problem definitions

Equipped with the mismatch function, we next define a family of prototypical problems that concern the sequential road networks produced by Algorithm 2.

Sequential road network problems	
Input:	A network $N = (V, E, c)$, a set of connections $K \subseteq \mathcal{P}_2(V)$, and a cost-reduction parameter $\alpha \in [0, 1]$. Where applicable, additionally a threshold value $\gamma \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ and an edge set $T \subseteq E$.
Problem 1:	SRN
Question:	Is there a permutation $\pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)$ such that $C(\pi) \leq \gamma$?
Problem 2:	MIN-SRN
Output:	A permutation $\pi^* := \arg \min_{\pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)} C(\pi)$.
Problem 3:	SRN-FIT
Question:	Is there a permutation $\pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)$ such that $M_T(\pi) \leq \gamma$?

The following problems are already known to be difficult to solve, we will thus use them as the basis for our reductions.

Independent domination problems	
Input:	A graph $G = (V, E)$. Where applicable an integer $k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$.
Problem 4:	IDS
Question:	Is there a set $U \subseteq V$ with $ U \leq k$ that is independent and dominating in G ?
Problem 5:	MIN-IDS
Output:	A set $U \subseteq V$ of minimum cardinality that is independent and dominating in G .

We have two hardness results for these problems at our disposal. The first is stated in terms of the decision variant, Problem 4, but implies hardness also for the optimization variant.

Theorem 3.19 (Manlove [85]). *IDS is NP-complete even on planar graphs of degree three.*

The second result concerns only Problem 5, the optimization variant.

Theorem 3.20 (Chlebík and Chlebíková [29]). *MIN-IDS is NP-hard to approximate within a factor of $681/680$ even in graphs of degree at most three.*

In Section 3.4.3, we will make use of one more difficult problem.

Permutation constraint satisfaction	
Problem 6:	ARITY 2 PERMUTATION CSP
Input:	A set U , a set of constraints $C \subseteq U^2$, and an integer $k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$.
Question:	Is there a permutation $\pi \in \mathcal{S}(U)$ fulfilling at least k constraints, formally
$ \{(u, v) \in C \mid u <_{\pi} v\} \geq k?$	

The problem is related to the well-known FEEDBACK ARC SET problem in directed graphs. We will utilize the following result.

Theorem 3.21 (Karp [70] and Younger [143]). *ARITY 2 PERMUTATION CSP is NP-complete.*

Proof. Let $D = (V, A)$ be a directed graph without loops. A *feedback arc set* of D is an arc subset $F \subseteq A$ such that $(V, A \setminus F)$ is acyclic. Younger [143, Theorem 1] shows that the size of a minimum cardinality feedback arc set of D is

$$\min_{\pi \in \mathcal{S}(V)} |\{(u, v) \in A \mid u >_{\pi} v\}| = |A| - \max_{\pi \in \mathcal{S}(V)} |\{(u, v) \in A \mid u <_{\pi} v\}|.$$

Thus, there is a feedback arc set of size at most ℓ if and only if there is a solution to the ARITY 2 PERMUTATION CSP instance (V, A, k) with $k := |A| - \ell$. The problem of deciding whether such a feedback arc set exists was shown to be NP-complete by Karp [70]. ■

3.4.2 Finding efficient connection orders

We begin our analysis with a positive result providing a trivial upper bound on the approximation ratio of the MIN-SRN problem.

Proposition 3.22. *Any feasible solution $\pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)$ to MIN-SRN with $\alpha > 0$ has cost $C(\pi) \leq C(\pi^*)/\alpha$.*

Proof. Let $N = (V, E, c)$, $K \subseteq \mathcal{P}_2(V)$, and $\alpha > 0$ comprise an input to MIN-SRN. Let further $\pi^* := \operatorname{argmin}_{\pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)} C_{N,\alpha}(\pi)$ be an optimum solution with $R^* := R_{N,\alpha}(\pi^*)$ the associated road network and $C^* := C_{N,\alpha}(\pi^*)$ its historical cost. We show that then $C^{\alpha} := C_{N,\alpha}(\pi) \leq C^*/\alpha$ holds for every $\pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)$. To this end, let $\pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)$ and consider the network $R^1 := R_{N,1}(\pi)$ with historical cost $C^1 := C_{N,1}(\pi)$. Since $r_1(\beta, \tau) = \beta$ for every $\tau \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$, we know that the π -establishing paths in the formation of R^1 are least-cost paths in N . Specifically, the path establishing some $\{u, v\} \in K$ in the formation of R^1 has a reduced cost of $\operatorname{dist}_c(u, v)$. Since further $r_{\alpha}(\beta, \tau) \geq \alpha\beta$ for every $\tau \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$, it follows that the path establishing $\{u, v\}$ in the formation of R^* has reduced cost at least $\alpha \operatorname{dist}_c(u, v)$. It is thus $\alpha C^1 \leq C^*$, and it only remains to show that $C^{\alpha} \leq C^1$. Assume towards a contradiction that $C^{\alpha} > C^1$. Then, there is a connection $\{u, v\} \in K$ that is established in the formation of $R_{N,\alpha}(\pi)$ at a reduced cost of more than $\operatorname{dist}_c(u, v)$. This however contradicts the fact that a least-cost u - v -path P in N has at all times a reduced cost of at most

$$\sum_{e \in P} \max_{\tau \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}} r_{\alpha}(c(e), \tau) = \sum_{e \in P} c(e) = \operatorname{dist}_c(u, v). \quad \blacksquare$$

A A *yes*-instance of IDS for $|V| = 5$ and $k = 2$; a solution $U = \{2, 5\}$ is shown in gray.

B An instance of SRN; the establishing paths of a solution π starting with $\{s_2, t_2\}$ and $\{s_5, t_5\}$ are drawn as solid lines. Edge costs not shown.

Figure 3.6: Example of a polynomial time reduction from IDS to SRN. For $\{i, j\} \in E$, the path (s_i, a_j, b_j, t_i) is cheaper than (s_i, a_i, b_i, t_i) if and only if (s_j, a_j, b_j, t_j) was used before, encoding the selection of j into an independent dominating set.

Proposition 3.22 coincides with the empirical observation in Section 3.3.3 that the influence of the connection order decreases as α grows and vanishes at $\alpha = 1$ (see Figure 3.2). On the negative side, we have the following hardness result.

Theorem 3.23. *SRN is NP-complete for all $\alpha \in [0, 1)$, even for integral terrain costs c .*

Proof. Containment in NP follows from the fact that the procedure in Algorithm 2 can be executed in polynomial time and computes the summands of $C(\pi)$ for a given $\pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)$ as a byproduct of line 6 in Algorithm 1.

To show NP-hardness, we present a polynomial-time reduction from IDS. Let a graph $G = (V, E)$ with $V = [n]$ for some $n \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ and an integer $k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ compose an instance of IDS. We construct an instance of SRN given by a network $N = (V', E', c)$, a set of connections $K \subseteq \mathcal{P}_2(V')$, and any fixed $\alpha < 1$ as follows; see Figure 3.6 for an example. First, define the vertex set $V' := \bigcup_{i \in [n]} V_i$ where $V_i := \{s_i, a_i, b_i, t_i\}$ for all $i \in [n]$. Then, define the edge set $E' := B \cup D_1 \cup D_2 \cup E_1 \cup E_2$ comprising

$$\begin{aligned} B &:= \{\{a_i, b_i\} \mid i \in [n]\}, \\ D_1 &:= \{\{s_i, a_i\} \mid i \in [n]\}, \\ D_2 &:= \{\{b_i, t_i\} \mid i \in [n]\}, \\ E_1 &:= \{\{s_i, a_j\} \mid \{i, j\} \in E\}, \text{ and} \\ E_2 &:= \{\{b_i, t_j\} \mid \{i, j\} \in E\}. \end{aligned}$$

We refer to edges in B as *bridges* (since any s_i - t_i -path needs to contain such an edge) and we can think of the sets D_1 and D_2 as *direct* edges (remaining within V_i for some $i \in [n]$) and of the sets E_1 and E_2 as *external* edges. Next, let $\beta \in \mathbb{Z}$ be an arbitrary integer strictly larger than $2/(1 - \alpha)$, so that $\beta \geq 3$ and $3\beta - 2 > (\alpha + 2)\beta$, and use it to define the edge costs $c(e) := \beta$ for all $e \in B \cup E_1 \cup E_2$ and

$c(e) := \beta - 1$ for all $e \in D_1 \cup D_2$ (direct edges are initially cheaper than external ones). Lastly, define the set of connections $K := \{\{s_i, t_i\} \mid i \in [n]\}$ and set the target historical cost to

$$\gamma := k(3\beta - 2) + (n - k)(\alpha + 2)\beta.$$

Intuitively, we are looking to establish a one-to-one correspondence between $\{a_i, b_i\}$ -edges appearing in π -establishing paths and the corresponding vertex i being selected into the independent dominating set $U \subseteq V$. It is obvious that the reduction can be computed in polynomial time. Further, all assigned costs are positive integers as required.

Whenever we consider a connection order $\pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)$ in the following, we assume without loss of generality that the vertices in V are labeled according to this order, that is $\pi = (\{s_i, t_i\})_{i=1}^n$. This allows us to identify a time $i \in [n]$ with a vertex $i \in V$ whose corresponding connection $\{s_i, t_i\} \in K$ is established at that time. Recall that we write $c_i(e)$ for the reduced cost of an edge e at time i .

Denote by $B_i := \{j \in [n] \mid \{a_j, b_j\} \text{ is } i\text{-cheap}\}$ the indices of bridges lying on some establishing path prior to time i . Before we prove decision equivalence, we show by induction that at every time $i \in [n]$, the path establishing π_i is of the form (s_i, a_j, b_j, t_i) for some $j \in N(i) \cap B_i$, if this intersection is nonempty, and $j = i$, otherwise. At time $i = 1$, we have $N(1) \cap B_1 = \emptyset$ as all edges are tier zero and (s_1, a_1, b_1, t_1) is the unique least-reduced-cost s_i - t_i -path by construction.

At a time $i \in [n]$ with $i > 1$, first consider the case of $N(i) \cap B_i \neq \emptyset$ and let $j \in N(i) \cap B_i$. By induction assumption, the edges $\{s_i, a_j\}$ and $\{b_j, t_i\}$ are i -costly, so the path (s_i, a_j, b_j, t_i) has reduced cost $\beta + \alpha\beta + \beta = (\alpha + 2)\beta$. On the other hand, this value is a lower bound for the reduced cost of any path P not remaining in V_i , as leaving from V_i and returning to V_i both incur a cost of at least β , and the cost for crossing a bridge is at least $\alpha\beta$, hence $c_i(P) \geq (\alpha + 2)\beta$. The only path remaining in V_i is (s_i, a_i, b_i, t_i) with reduced cost $(\beta - 1) + \beta + (\beta - 1) = 3\beta - 2 > (\alpha + 2)\beta$, showing that (s_i, a_j, b_j, t_i) is a least-reduced-cost s_i - t_i -path at time i .

Consider next the case $N(i) \cap B_i = \emptyset$, that is, for all $j \in N(i)$ the bridge $\{a_j, b_j\}$ is i -costly. Let P be an arbitrary path *not using* the bridge $\{a_i, b_i\}$. If P uses a bridge $\{a_j, b_j\}$ for some $j \in N(i)$, then $c_i(P) \geq 3\beta > 3\beta - 2$. Otherwise, $P = (e_1, e_2, \dots, e_{|P|})$ contains at least 5 distinct edges. Since the first bridge of P is not indexed in $N[i]$, the first two edges e_1 and e_2 of P are both in $D_1 \cup E_1$, and at most one of them is in D_1 . Moreover, by induction assumption, these two edges must be i -costly, hence $c_i(e_1) + c_i(e_2) \geq \beta + (\beta - 1) = 2\beta - 1$. A symmetric reasoning over the last two edges of P shows $c_i(e_{|P|-1}) + c_i(e_{|P|}) \geq 2\beta - 1$ and thus $c_i(P) \geq 4\beta - 2 > 3\beta - 2$. This shows that the path (s_i, a_i, b_i, t_i) is the unique least-reduced-cost s_i - t_i -path at time i , which concludes the induction.

Now that we have circumscribed the possible π -establishing paths for any $\pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)$, we will establish their reduced costs. Let $\pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)$ be fixed and consider the path establishing π_i for some $i \in [n]$. If the path is (s_i, a_i, b_i, t_i) , then all its edges are i -costly and it has a reduced cost of

$$r(c(\{s_i, a_i\}), 0) + r(c(\{a_i, b_i\}), 0) + r(c(\{b_i, t_i\}), 0) = 3\beta - 2.$$

We call such a path an *independent path*. Otherwise, π_i is established by a path (s_i, a_j, b_j, t_i) , and $\{a_j, b_j\}$ is i -cheap. Thus, (s_i, a_j, b_j, t_i) has a reduced cost of

$$r(c(\{s_i, a_j\}), 0) + r(c(\{a_j, b_j\}), \tau) + r(c(\{b_j, t_i\}), 0) = (\alpha + 2)\beta$$

where $\tau := \tau_i(\{a_j, b_j\}) \geq 1$. We call such a path a *dominated path*. In total, the historical cost of π is

$$k'(3\beta - 2) + (n - k')(\alpha + 2)\beta$$

where $k' \in [n]$ is the number of independent paths establishing π .

We are now prepared to show decision equivalence. For the forward direction, let $U \subseteq V$ with $|U| \leq k$ be an independent dominating set. We construct a connection order π starting from an empty sequence as follows: First, for every $i \in U$ in any order, append $\{s_i, t_i\} \in K$ to π . Then, for every $j \in V \setminus U$ in any order, append $\{s_j, t_j\} \in K$ to π . We show that $C(\pi) \leq \gamma$. Again, we assume without loss of generality that vertices are labeled according to π . This implies that $U = [k]$ and $V \setminus U = [n] \setminus [k]$. Since U is an independent set, we have for every $i \in [k]$ and every $h \in [i - 1] \subseteq U$ that there is no edge $e \in E'$ connecting a vertex in V_h with one in V_i . Hence, π_i is established by an independent path for every $i \in [k]$. Since U is also a dominating set, we have for every $j \in [n]$ with $j > k$ that there is some $i \in [k]$ such that $\{i, j\} \in E$. Thus, π_j is established by a dominated path, and we have

$$C(\pi) = k(3\beta - 2) + (n - k)(\alpha + 2)\beta = \gamma.$$

For the reverse direction, let $\pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)$ such that $C(\pi) \leq \gamma$. We construct an independent dominating set $U \subseteq V$ as follows: For every $i \in [n]$, add i to U if and only if π_i is established by an independent path. We first show that $|U| \leq k$. Assume towards a contradiction that $|U| > k$. Then, at least $k + 1$ many π -establishing paths are independent, and thereby at most $n - k - 1$ many π -establishing paths are dominated. As independent paths have a larger reduced cost than dominated paths, this gives

$$C(\pi) \geq (k + 1)(3\beta - 2) + (n - k - 1)(\alpha + 2)\beta = \gamma + (3\beta - 2) - (\alpha + 2)\beta > \gamma,$$

where the last inequality follows from our definition of β , contradicting $C(\pi) \leq \gamma$. We next show that U is an independent set. Assume towards a contradiction that there are $i, j \in U$ with $\{i, j\} \in E$. Without loss of generality let $i < j$; the case of $j < i$ is analogous with i and j swapped. Then, π_j was established by a dominated path, contradicting $j \in U$. Last we show that U is also a dominating set. Assume towards a contradiction that there is some $i \in V \setminus U$ such that there is no $j \in U$ with $\{i, j\} \in E$. Since $i \notin U$, it follows that π_i must be established by a dominated path. Hence, there must be some $h \in [i]$ such that π_h was established by an independent path and $\{h, i\} \in E$. The case of $h \in V \setminus U$ contradicts the definition of U while the case of $h \in U$ contradicts the assumption that there is no $j \in U$ with $\{i, j\} \in E$. In summary, we have that U is an independent dominating set with $|U| \leq k$. This concludes the reduction. ■

We can strengthen the result a bit based on Theorem 3.19.

Corollary 3.24. *SRN with $\alpha < 1$ remains NP-complete on networks with vertex degree at most five and, if $1 - \alpha \geq \varepsilon$ where $\varepsilon > 0$ is a constant, on networks with unit edge costs.*

Proof. For the bound on the degree, note that IDS is already hard on graphs of degree three which are reduced to an instance of SRN in which vertices have a degree of either four or five by construction. For unit edge costs, replace each edge in the resulting network with a path

whose topological length is the integral cost of the edge being replaced. The reduction remains polynomial-time computable as β is bounded from above by a constant. ■

Additionally, we can make use of Theorem 3.20 to show that there is most likely no polynomial time approximation scheme (PTAS) for MIN-SRN, which would allow us to efficiently find solutions that are arbitrarily close to being optimal.

Corollary 3.25. *There exists no polynomial-time $(1 + (1 - \varepsilon)(1 - \alpha)/8160)$ -approximation algorithm for MIN-SRN with $\alpha < 1$ for any $\varepsilon > 0$, unless $P = NP$.*

Proof. Let $\alpha \in [0, 1)$ be fixed, define $\omega := 1 - \alpha > 0$ for brevity, and adapt the reduction in the proof of Theorem 3.23 as follows. From the given instance of IDS, strip the integer k and require the graph $G = (V, E)$ to have maximum degree $\Delta = 3$. Consider then $I := (G)$ an instance of MIN-IDS. From the reduction procedure, strike the definition of the target cost γ and denote the remainder formally by a function f that maps an instance of MIN-IDS to an instance (N, K, α) of MIN-SRN where N is a network and K a set of connections. Recall that the edge costs of N depend on a constant β and set it equal to $\lceil 2/\omega \rceil + \kappa$ for some integer $\kappa > (1/\varepsilon - 1)(2/\omega + 1)$, so that

$$(3\beta - 2) - (\alpha + 2)\beta = \omega\beta - 2 \in [\omega\kappa, \omega(\kappa + 1)).$$

For a given MIN-IDS instance $\bar{I} = (\bar{G})$ with $\bar{G} = (\bar{V}, \bar{E})$, let further g be a function that maps a feasible solution π of $f(\bar{I}) = (\bar{N}, \bar{K}, \alpha)$ back to a solution U of \bar{I} as follows: $U := g(\pi)$ is the set of vertices $i \in \bar{V}$ for which the path establishing the connection $\{s_i, t_i\} \in \bar{K}$ in the formation of $R_{\bar{N}, \alpha}(\pi)$ is the independent path (s_i, a_i, b_i, t_i) . It is clear that f and g can be computed in polynomial time.

We show that (f, g) is an L-reduction from MIN-IDS to MIN-SRN (see Definition 2.44 on page 16). To this end, let k^* denote the smallest cardinality of a set that is both independent and dominating in G , and let π^* be an optimum solution to $f(I)$. From the proof of Theorem 3.23, it can be seen that a feasible solution of size k to I implies a feasible solution of historical cost $\Gamma(k) := k(3\beta - 2) + (n - k)(\alpha + 2)\beta$ to $f(I)$ and, vice versa, a feasible solution π to $f(I)$ has a historical cost of $\Gamma(k)$ for some k and $g(\pi)$ is a feasible solution to I of size k . Thus, we have for the optimum values k^* of I and $C(\pi^*)$ of $f(I)$ that

$$\begin{aligned} C(\pi^*) &= k^*(3\beta - 2) + (n - k^*)(\alpha + 2)\beta \\ &= n(\alpha + 2)\beta + k^*(\omega\beta - 2) \\ &\leq (1 + \Delta)k^*(\alpha + 2)\beta + k^*(\omega\beta - 2) \end{aligned} \tag{3.4}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= (4(\alpha + 2)\beta + \omega\beta - 2)k^* \\ &= (12\beta - 3\omega\beta - 2)k^* \\ &< \left(\frac{24}{\omega} + 12(\kappa + 1) - 3\omega\beta - 2 \right) k^* \end{aligned} \tag{3.5}$$

$$< 12 \left(\frac{2}{\omega} + \kappa + 1 \right) k^* \tag{3.6}$$

where inequality (3.4) follows from $\lceil n/(1 + \Delta) \rceil \leq k^*$ [11], inequality (3.5) holds due to $\omega\beta - 2 < \omega(\kappa + 1)$, and inequality (3.6) follows from $3\omega\beta + 2 > 0$. Furthermore, we have for a feasible

solution π to $f(I)$ with $k := |g(\pi)|$ that

$$|C(\pi^*) - C(\pi)| = |n(\alpha + 2)\beta + k^*(\omega\beta - 2) - (n(\alpha + 2)\beta + k(\omega\beta - 2))| = (\omega\beta - 2) |k^* - k|.$$

Since $\omega\beta - 2 \geq \omega\kappa$, we can relate the suboptimality of π and $g(\pi)$ by

$$|k^* - k| \leq \frac{1}{\omega\kappa} |C(\pi^*) - C(\pi)|.$$

Therefore, (f, g) is an L-reduction from MIN-IDS to MIN-SRN with parameters $12(2/\omega + \kappa + 1)$ and $(\omega\kappa)^{-1}$. By Proposition 2.45, the existence of a $(1 + \rho)$ -approximation algorithm for MIN-SRN implies the existence of a ρ' -approximation algorithm for MIN-IDS where

$$\rho' := 1 + \frac{12}{\omega\kappa} \left(\frac{2}{\omega} + \kappa + 1 \right) \rho.$$

Now, assume that there exists a $(1 + (1 - \varepsilon)\omega/8160)$ -approximation algorithm for MIN-SRN. Then, the L-reduction implies the existence of an approximation algorithm for MIN-IDS with performance guarantee

$$\begin{aligned} 1 + \frac{12}{\omega\kappa} \left(\frac{2}{\omega} + \kappa + 1 \right) \frac{(1 - \varepsilon)\omega}{8160} &= 1 + \frac{1 - \varepsilon}{680} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\kappa} \left(\frac{2}{\omega} + 1 \right) \right) \\ &< 1 + \frac{1 - \varepsilon}{680} \left(1 + \frac{\varepsilon}{1 - \varepsilon} \right) \\ &= 1 + \frac{1}{680}, \end{aligned}$$

where the inequality follows from our choice of κ . By Theorem 3.20, this implies $P = NP$. ■

3.4.3 Matching a body of evidence

The next result suggests that no efficient algorithm for matching a prescribed edge set is likely to exist, at least for values of α for which we can control establishing paths in the following reduction.

Theorem 3.26. *SRN-FIT is NP-complete for all $\alpha \in [1/2, 1)$, even for integral terrain costs c .*

Proof. Containment in NP follows from the fact that the procedure in Algorithm 2, which returns a network with an edge set F , and the resulting mismatch $M_T(\pi) = |(T \setminus F) \cup (F \setminus T)|$ can be computed in polynomial time.

To show NP-hardness, we present a polynomial-time reduction from ARITY 2 PERMUTATION CSP. Let thus a ground set U , a set of constraints $C \subseteq U^2$, and an integer $k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ compose an instance of ARITY 2 PERMUTATION CSP. We assume without loss of generality that the ground set contains no unconstrained elements, formally $\forall u \in U: \exists v \in U: (u, v) \in C \vee (v, u) \in C$, and further that no pair of conflicting constraints is present, that is $\forall (u, v) \in C: (v, u) \notin C$. In the former case, unconstrained elements can be ordered arbitrarily without affecting the number of fulfilled constraints. In the latter case, one can remove both constraints and decrement k . We construct a decision-equivalent instance of SRN-FIT from an empty network $N = (V, E, c)$ as follows: First,

Figure 3.7: A network gadget representing a constraint of the ARITY 2 PERMUTATION CSP problem. We simplify notation by identifying $\{\bullet_{ij}^s, \bullet_{ij}^t\}$ with a connection whose establishing path contains both vertices. The set F refers to the edge set of the generated road network.

Figure 3.8: A network representing an instance of ARITY 2 PERMUTATION CSP with ground set $U = [4]$ and constraints $C = \{(1,2), (3,2), (3,4), (1,4)\}$. Gadgets G_{ij} with $i > j$ are flipped vertically compared to Figure 3.7. All edges shown belong to gadgets. Doubly labeled vertices are identified.

we define the integer costs $\beta := \lceil 1/(1-\alpha) \rceil + 1$, $\delta := 2\beta + 12$, and $\kappa := |U|\alpha^{-1}(2\delta + 4\beta)$. This choice gives $\alpha\beta \in (\beta - 3, \beta - 1)$ as

$$\begin{aligned}\alpha\beta &\geq \alpha \left(\frac{1}{1-\alpha} + 1 \right) > \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} = \frac{1}{1-\alpha} - 1 > \left\lceil \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \right\rceil - 2 = \beta - 3, \\ \beta &> \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \implies (1-\alpha)\beta > 1 \implies \beta - \alpha\beta > 1 \implies \alpha\beta < \beta - 1,\end{aligned}$$

and further $\alpha\delta > 2\beta$ due to the above and $\alpha \geq 1/2$. Then, for every constraint $(i, j) \in C$, we add a gadget $G_{ij} = (V_{ij}, E_{ij})$ as shown in Figure 3.7A to N , formally

$$\begin{aligned}V_{ij} &:= \{a_{ij}^s, a'_{ij}, a''_{ij}, a^t_{ij}\} \cup \{b_{ij}^s, b'_{ij}, b''_{ij}, b^t_{ij}\} \cup \{c_{ij}^s, c'_{ij}, c^t_{ij}\} \text{ and} \\ E_{ij} &:= A_{ij} \cup B_{ij} \cup K_{ij}\end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}A_{ij} &:= \{\{a_{ij}^s, a'_{ij}\}, \{a'_{ij}, a''_{ij}\}, \{a''_{ij}, a^t_{ij}\}\}, \\ B_{ij} &:= \{\{b_{ij}^s, b'_{ij}\}, \{b'_{ij}, b''_{ij}\}, \{b''_{ij}, b^t_{ij}\}\} \cup \{\{b'_{ij}, c'_{ij}\}, \{c'_{ij}, c_{ij}^s\}, \{c_{ij}^s, b''_{ij}\}\}, \text{ and} \\ K_{ij} &:= \{\{c_{ij}^s, c^t_{ij}\}, \{a'_{ij}, c'_{ij}\}, \{a''_{ij}, c^t_{ij}\}\},\end{aligned}$$

and we update the edge costs c of N with

$$\begin{aligned}c(\{a_{ij}^s, a'_{ij}\}), c(\{a''_{ij}, a^t_{ij}\}), c(\{b_{ij}^s, b'_{ij}\}), c(\{b''_{ij}, b^t_{ij}\}) &:= \delta, \\ c(\{a'_{ij}, c'_{ij}\}), c(\{a''_{ij}, c^t_{ij}\}) &:= \kappa + 1, \\ c(\{a'_{ij}, a''_{ij}\}), c(\{c_{ij}^s, c'_{ij}\}) &:= 2\beta, \\ c(\{c_{ij}^s, c^t_{ij}\}) &:= 2\kappa + 4\beta, \\ c(\{b'_{ij}, b''_{ij}\}) &:= 4\beta.\end{aligned}$$

Additionally, we add isolated vertices s_i and t_i for every $i \in U$. It may be helpful to note that K_{ij} contains precisely the edges with a cost of at least κ and that $G_{ij}[E_{ij} \setminus K_{ij}]$ has connected components $G_{ij}[A_{ij}]$ and $G_{ij}[B_{ij}]$.

We wire the gadgets as follows (see Figure 3.8 for an example): First, fix an arbitrary order on the constraints C . Then, for every $i \in U$, let $C_{i\bullet} := \{(i, j) \in C \mid j \in U\}$, $C_{\bullet i} := \{(j, i) \in C \mid j \in U\}$, and $C_i := C_{i\bullet} \cup C_{\bullet i}$ be sets of constraints involving i . For every $\ell \in [|C_i|]$ in order, we consider the ℓ -th constraint x^ℓ from $C_i \subseteq C$ according to our ordering of C , and we let both $s^\ell := a_{ij}^s$ and $t^\ell := a_{ij}^t$, if $x^\ell = (i, j) \in C_{i\bullet}$, or both $s^\ell := b_{ji}^s$ and $t^\ell := b_{ji}^t$, if $x^\ell = (j, i) \in C_{\bullet i}$. Further, we identify s^ℓ with s_i , if $\ell = 1$, s^ℓ with $t^{\ell-1}$, whenever $\ell > 1$, and t^ℓ with t_i , if $\ell = |C_i|$. Lastly, we define the set of connections

$$K := \{\{s_i, t_i\} \mid i \in U\} \cup \{\{c_{ij}^s, c^t_{ij}\} \mid (i, j) \in C\}$$

and set the target distance to $\gamma := 3(|C| - k)$ and the target edge set (shown in Figure 3.7B) to

$$T := \bigcup_{(i,j) \in C} (E_{ij} \setminus \{\{b'_{ij}, b''_{ij}\}, \{c_{ij}^s, c^t_{ij}\}\}).$$

It is obvious that the reduction can be computed in polynomial time. Further, all assigned costs are positive integers as required.

Informally, every element $i \in U$ is now associated with a connection $\{s_i, t_i\} \in K$ and by extension with a least-cost s_i - t_i -path with respect to c that traverses precisely the gadgets that correspond to constraints involving i . Indeed, we will later show that the establishing path for such a connection will not be too different from this initial least-cost path. The remaining connections, which are $\{c_{ij}^s, c_{ij}^t\}$ for all $(i, j) \in C$, allow the gadget G_{ij} to detect the relative order of $\{s_i, t_i\}$ and $\{s_j, t_j\}$. More precisely, fulfilling (i, j) corresponds to ordering the associated connections as $\{s_i, t_i\} < \{c_{ij}^s, c_{ij}^t\} < \{s_j, t_j\}$.

Let us now analyze the instance of SRN-FIT constructed above. First, we investigate what establishing paths can occur in principle. To this end we define the sets

$$E_i := \left(\bigcup_{(i,j) \in C_i} A_{ij} \right) \cup \left(\bigcup_{(j,i) \in C_i} B_{ji} \right) \quad \text{and} \quad V_i := \bigcup_{e \in E_i} e$$

for every $i \in U$ and claim two properties.

Claim 1. For every $i \in U$, the path establishing the connection $\{s_i, t_i\}$ is contained in $G[E_i]$.

Proof of Claim 1. By construction, any other s_i - t_i -path must use an edge e with a terrain cost of $c(e) = \kappa + 1$. However, it is $\alpha(\kappa + 1) > \alpha\kappa = |U|(2\delta + 4\beta)$ with the right-hand side posing an upper bound on the least reduced cost of an s_i - t_i -path at any time.

Claim 2. For every $(i, j) \in C$, the path P_{ij} establishing $\{c_{ij}^s, c_{ij}^t\}$ is contained in G_{ij} .

Proof of Claim 2. By induction on the time t . Let t_0 be the first time when a connection $\pi_{t_0} = \{c_{ij}^s, c_{ij}^t\}$ with $(i, j) \in C$ is established by a path P_{ij} . Then, any connection established at a time $t < t_0$ has the form $\{s_\ell, t_\ell\}$ with $\ell \in U$. By Claim 1, none of these earlier connections is established by a path using an edge with terrain cost at least κ , so any such edge has also a reduced cost of at least κ at time t_0 . Assume now towards a contradiction that P_{ij} leaves the gadget G_{ij} . By construction, P_{ij} must then contain at least one of the two edges incident to c_{ij}^t , both of which have a reduced cost of at least κ at time t_0 , and P_{ij} must further use at least two distinct vertices $u, v \in \{a_{ij}^s, a_{ij}^t, b_{ij}^s, b_{ij}^t\}$ on the ‘‘boundary’’ of G_{ij} . We distinguish two cases. If $\{u, v\} = \{a_{ij}^s, a_{ij}^t\}$ (respectively $\{u, v\} = \{b_{ij}^s, b_{ij}^t\}$), then P_{ij} contains an a_{ij}^s - a_{ij}^t -subpath (a b_{ij}^s - b_{ij}^t -subpath) P'_{ij} containing at least two edges from $E \setminus E_{ij}$. Note that P'_{ij} cannot be completely contained within the set E_i (respectively E_j) as its endpoints form a cut set that partitions $G[E_i]$ ($G[E_j]$) into three components, two distinct of which contain, respectively, the second and penultimate vertex of P'_{ij} . Thus, P'_{ij} must contain at least two distinct edges with precisely one endpoint in V_i and in $V \setminus V_i$ each, none of which can be incident to c_{ij}^t and both of which have a reduced cost of at least κ at time t_0 by construction. The path P_{ij} has thereby a reduced cost of at least $3\kappa > 2\kappa + 4\beta = r(c(\{c_{ij}^s, c_{ij}^t\}), 0)$ at time t_0 , contradicting its minimality. In the remaining case of $\{u, v\} \in \{\{a_{ij}^s, b_{ij}^s\}, \{a_{ij}^t, b_{ij}^t\}, \{a_{ij}^s, b_{ij}^t\}, \{a_{ij}^t, b_{ij}^s\}\}$, P_{ij} contains a vertex in V_i and a vertex in V_j . It must thus contain a subpath P'_{ij} with edges disjoint from E_{ij} that contains precisely one vertex in V_i and in V_j each. By construction, no edge outside E_{ij} has one endpoint in each of V_i and V_j (otherwise it must be the case that both $(i, j) \in C$ and $(j, i) \in C$). It follows that P'_{ij} must contain another subpath P''_{ij} contained in V_ℓ for some $\ell \in U \setminus \{i, j\}$. As in the first case, two edges with a

reduced cost of at least κ are necessary to enter and leave V_ℓ , again contradicting the minimality of P_{ij} . This concludes the induction basis. The argument for the induction step is analogous with two modifications: When a connection $\pi_t = \{c_{ij}^s, c_{ij}^t\}$ with $(i, j) \in C$ is established at some time $t > t_0$, then the induction assumption in combination with Claim 1 again ensures that all edges in E_{ij} with terrain cost at least κ also have a reduced cost of at least κ at time t . However, any edge $e \in E \setminus E_{ij}$ with terrain cost $c(e) \geq \kappa$ can, in principle, have a reduced cost of only $\alpha c(e)$ at time t . Thus, a path P_{ij} that establishes π_t and leaves G_{ij} has a reduced cost of at least $(\kappa + 1) + 2\alpha\kappa > 2\kappa$. Adding to this a lower bound for the reduced costs of cheaper edges not counted so far, namely $2\alpha\delta > 4\beta$ for two edges incident to distinct vertices in $\{a_{ij}^s, a_{ij}^t, b_{ij}^s, b_{ij}^t\}$, we arrive at a reduced cost larger than $2\kappa + 4\beta = r(c(\{c_{ij}^s, c_{ij}^t\}), 0)$, contradicting again the minimality of P_{ij} . This proves the second claim.

As all edges of N are contained in gadgets, we may write the total mismatch for the constructed instance as the sum

$$M_T(\pi) = \sum_{(i,j) \in C} |(T_{ij} \setminus F_{ij}) \cup (F_{ij} \setminus T_{ij})|$$

where $T_{ij} := T \cap E_{ij}$ are the target edges of G_{ij} and where F_{ij} are the edges of π -establishing paths within G_{ij} for a solution candidate $\pi \in S(K)$. Let us thus fix a constraint $(i, j) \in C$ and determine F_{ij} . From Claims 1 and 2 and from the definition of the sets E_i and E_j , it follows that precisely three connections have π -establishing paths that traverse G_{ij} , being $A := \{s_i, t_i\}$, $B := \{s_j, t_j\}$ and $Q := \{c_{ij}^s, c_{ij}^t\}$. Further, the path establishing A induces an a_{ij}^s, a_{ij}^t -subpath in G_{ij} and the path establishing B induces a b_{ij}^s, b_{ij}^t -subpath in G_{ij} . We distinguish three cases with respect to the relative order of $A, B, Q \in K$ within π . It might be helpful to recall that we chose edge costs such that $\beta - 3 < \alpha\beta < \beta - 1$ and $\alpha\kappa = |U|(2\delta + 4\beta)$.

Case 1: $A < Q < B$. The path establishing A at some time t_0 is the first path to traverse G_{ij} and does so via a subpath $(a_{ij}^s, a_{ij}^t, a_{ij}^s, a_{ij}^t)$ with reduced cost $2\delta + 2\beta < \kappa + 1$. When Q is established at a time $t_1 > t_0$, then the path $:= (c_{ij}^s, c_{ij}^t, a_{ij}^t, a_{ij}^s, c_{ij}^t)$ has a reduced cost of $2\beta + 2(\kappa + 1) + \alpha(2\beta) < 2\kappa + 4\beta$. By Claim 2 and the construction of G_{ij} , this path thus establishes Q . Finally, when B is established at a time $t_2 > t_1$, then due to $2(\beta + 1) + \alpha(2\beta) < 2(\beta + 1) + 2(\beta - 1) = 4\beta$ (and $\alpha(\kappa + 1) > \alpha(2\beta)$), the establishing path induces the subpath $(b_{ij}^s, b_{ij}^t, c_{ij}^t, c_{ij}^s, b_{ij}^t, b_{ij}^s)$ in G_{ij} . It follows that $F_{ij} = T_{ij}$, so in this case the mismatch contributed by G_{ij} is 0.

Case 2: $Q < A$. This includes three subcases: $B < Q < A$ and $Q < B < A$ and $Q < A < B$. First note that the path establishing A unconditionally induces the subpath $P_A := (a_{ij}^s, a_{ij}^t, a_{ij}^s, a_{ij}^t)$ in G_{ij} as $2\delta + 2\beta < \alpha(\kappa + 1)$. For the path establishing B , consider the critical edge set $X := \{b_{ij}^s, b_{ij}^t, c_{ij}^t, c_{ij}^s, c_{ij}^s, b_{ij}^t\}$: If all edges in X have a reduced cost equal to their terrain cost at the time when B is established, then clearly the path establishing B induces the subpath $(b_{ij}^s, b_{ij}^t, c_{ij}^t, b_{ij}^s)$ in G_{ij} . If $B < Q < A$, then this condition is trivially satisfied and further Q is established by the path (c_{ij}^s, c_{ij}^t) as $2\kappa + 4\beta < 2(\kappa + 1) + 2(2\beta)$ and $2\beta < 2(\beta + 1)$, ruling out both alternative paths that do not leave G_{ij} . If $Q < A, B$, then Q is again established by the path (c_{ij}^s, c_{ij}^t) disjoint from X . Further, the unconditional path P_A is disjoint from X . So in all subcases the intersection of π -establishing paths with E_{ij} is equivalent and includes the non-target edges $\{b_{ij}^s, b_{ij}^t\}$ and $\{c_{ij}^s, c_{ij}^t\}$ while excluding the target edges $\{a_{ij}^s, c_{ij}^t, a_{ij}^t, b_{ij}^s, c_{ij}^s, b_{ij}^t\}$, and $\{c_{ij}^s, b_{ij}^t\}$. Thus, G_{ij} contributes a mismatch of 6 in this case.

Case 3: $A, B < Q$. As for Case 2, A is unconditionally established by a path inducing in G_{ij} the subpath P_A disjoint from X (both as defined there) and therefore B is established with the same subpath as in Case 2. Further, Q is established as in Case 1. The intersection of π -establishing paths with E_{ij} thus includes the non-target edge $\{b'_{ij}, b''_{ij}\}$ and excludes the target edges $\{b'_{ij}, c'_{ij}\}$ and $\{c^s_{ij}, b''_{ij}\}$. Thus, G_{ij} contributes a mismatch of 3 in this case.

We can now prove decision equivalence. Let first the constructed instance of SRN-FIT be a *yes*-instance with solution $\pi \in S(K)$. We construct a solution π' to the associated instance of ARITY 2 PERMUTATION CSP as follows. Without loss of generality, we may assume that Case 2 does not occur for any gadget: Otherwise, for a constraint $(i, j) \in C$ and associated connections $A := \{s_i, t_i\}$, $B := \{s_j, t_j\}$ and $Q := \{c^s_{ij}, c^t_{ij}\}$ for which Case 2 occurs, we can make G_{ij} contribute less mismatch (either 3 or 0 instead of 6) by moving Q such that $A < Q$. Clearly this does not affect the subpaths induced by π -establishing paths within any other gadget so that the total mismatch decreases by this change. Thus, for every $(i, j) \in C$, the gadget G_{ij} contributes either no mismatch, if $\{s_i, t_i\} <_\pi \{s_j, t_j\}$, or a mismatch of 3, otherwise. It follows immediately that the solution $\pi' \in S(U)$ corresponding to the total order $\{(i, j) \in U^2 \mid \{s_i, t_i\} <_\pi \{s_j, t_j\}\}$ violates at most $\gamma/3$ constraints, thereby fulfilling at least $|C| - \gamma/3 = k$ constraints.

Let last the instance of ARITY 2 PERMUTATION CSP be a *yes*-instance with solution $\pi' \in S(U)$ and define the relation

$$Z := \{(\{s_i, t_i\}, \{c^s_{ij}, c^t_{ij}\}) \mid (i, j) \in C\} \cup \{(\{c^s_{ij}, c^t_{ij}\}, \{s_j, t_j\}) \mid (i, j) \in C \wedge i <_{\pi'} j\} \subseteq K^2.$$

As we assume that $\forall (i, j) \in C: (j, i) \notin C$ and since $<_{\pi'}$ is an order, we have that Z is antisymmetric and hence can be extended to a total order on K . Let thus $\pi \in S(K)$ such that $<_\pi \supseteq Z$. To show that π is a solution to the constructed instance of SRN-FIT, let $(i, j) \in C$ and consider first the case where $i <_{\pi'} j$ ((i, j) is fulfilled). Then, we have $\{s_i, t_i\} <_\pi \{c^s_{ij}, c^t_{ij}\} <_\pi \{s_j, t_j\}$ and so the gadget G_{ij} associated with (i, j) contributes no mismatch (Case 1). Consider next the case where $j <_{\pi'} i$ ((i, j) is violated). Then, it is $\{s_i, t_i\} <_\pi \{c^s_{ij}, c^t_{ij}\}$ and so G_{ij} contributes a mismatch of at most 3 (Case 1 or 3). As π' violates at most $|C| - k$ constraints, the mismatch of π is at most $3(|C| - k) = \gamma$. ■

3.5 Reconstructing Roman road networks

The previous section presented formal evidence that computing efficient or explanatory construction histories can be a difficult task. We obtained this evidence from an analysis of abstract representations of network prediction problems that one might want to solve in practice. Notwithstanding these challenges, we will explore in this section the application of the network formation model introduced at the start of the chapter for predicting the course of ancient roads from sparse archaeological data. The computational difficulties are addressed by a combination of preprocessing, informed by the results of Section 3.3.3, and heuristic search methods tailored to the geometry of the processed data.

The mode of analysis will be a case study of the major road network of Roman Sardinia, which remains to this day the subject of a lively archaeological debate [76, 87]. As tangible evidence is sparse, scholarly reconstructions of the network rely heavily on the Itinerarium Antonini (IA),

an ancient text that mentions four north–south routes along the island, each represented by a sequence of places visited and the distances between them in Roman miles. However, not all the places listed can be located with certainty, and it has proven hard to embed the routes on the surface of Sardinia such that all distances in the IA are obeyed, in particular in the northern part of the island [76]. It is also unlikely that the itinerary contains a complete record of all major roads at the time. In particular, the document mentions only a single east–west connection, a route *per compendium* (shortcut) from *Portus Tibulas* to *Olbia*. Despite these gaps and uncertainties, a number of experts have correlated the textual source with external evidence and derived possible topologies of the road network, which coincide in large parts but disagree in some [76, 87, 91, 122]. This prior work presents an appropriate setting for our model to be tested against an established state of the art, yet there remains a marginal potential for it to contribute to the archaeological discourse by suggesting previously overlooked but plausible connections.

From an operational perspective, two aspects are convenient about Sardinia as a study region. First, the fact that it is an island provides a natural geographical boundary that simplifies and canonicalizes the delineation of the study area, making it comparable across studies. Second, the mentioned scholarly reference networks describe connected graphs as opposed to scattered linear features, which allows us to evaluate our model’s predictions in terms of graph-based metrics such as the geometric dissimilarity (Definition 3.6).

3.5.1 Constructing the terrain network

To apply our model to Roman Sardinia, we will first need a discrete representation of the study region in the form of a terrain network N . Our approach to generate such a network is inspired by the work of White and Barber [139]. Therein, the authors distribute points in a regular grid pattern on a map of the study region of Oaxaca, Mexico. Then, they compute a least-cost path for each pair of points in terms of a *cost surface*. This is a two-dimensional, georeferenced raster image whose cells (pixels) encode a cost for traversing the terrain at the associated location and which can be interpreted as an edge-weighted graph. We will elaborate on the creation and use of cost surfaces later in this section. White and Barber next consider the least-cost paths jointly, each represented by the subset of the raster’s cells that the path visits. They count for each cell the number of paths that it appears in and select those cells whose path number falls above a fixed percentile. Together the selected cells describe an ensemble of path segments that are found at the convergence of multiple least-cost paths. These segments are then studied as potential movement corridors through the terrain. The authors find that they correlate with the known locations of pre-Columbian settlements and with the documented travel routes between them. Based on these results, they propose their “from everywhere to everywhere” analysis as a general framework for identifying probable movement corridors.

Our approach for terrain network generation differs from the analysis of White and Barber mainly in the choice of the initial points and in how we aggregate the resulting pairwise paths. Instead of placing the points at regular intervals, we use a subset of the locations of the spatial evidence that the network prediction shall be informed by. In particular, this includes the designated sites that we will consider to be the origins and destinations of connections by road. In the

Figure 3.9: Terrain network N describing potential road segments overlaid onto an elevation-based movement cost surface of Sardinia. The network is obtained from a union of least-cost paths between all pairs of places visited by the *Itinerarium Antonini* (IA), which are the *sites* and *stations* shown. Vertices are introduced at crossing points so that N is planar. Edge costs are derived from the cost surface. In addition to stations, retrieval locations of Roman milestones will be used as spatial evidence for the presence of a road.

aggregating step, we do not filter paths on a per-cell basis, but we simply consider the union of all edges in the graph-based interpretation of the paths. This is possible as the number of points being connected is much lower than in [139], and it is necessary as we do not want to disconnect any designated site from the terrain network. Figure 3.9 shows the resulting terrain network overlaid onto an elevation model of Sardinia; the contents of the figure will be discussed in more depth in the following. Note that despite the selection of initial points being biased towards locations that we assume were connected by road, the resulting network is far too densely connected to serve as a prediction of the road network itself. The sequential network formation model will thus be employed to select a plausible subset among these possible movement corridors.

Least-cost path analysis

We first detail the process of finding a least-cost path between two geographic locations in terms of a cost surface, commonly referred to as a *least-cost path analysis* (LCPA). A cost surface is the digital representation of a geographical area as a matrix, called a *raster map* in geographic information systems (GIS) terminology, where each entry or *cell* is assigned a value that quantifies the relative cost of moving through the associated space. Typically, each cell represents an approximately square section of the landscape with a side length of 25 to 100 m, depending on the requirements of the application and the data available. A higher resolution not only enhances the “smoothness” of the generated paths but also allows them to follow narrower corridors such as valleys and ridges that may otherwise be overlooked [19]. Depending on the size of the study region, distortion effects can play a role as a rectangular grid of cells is used to represent the curved surface of the earth. Then, a possible course of action is to re-project and re-sample the available data into a local coordinate system where the assumed correspondence of raster cells to square pieces of terrain is not violated by too much.

For land transport routes, the most commonly used type of data is a *digital elevation model* (DEM) from which the slope of the terrain can be derived. The underlying assumption is that it is significantly more costly, in terms of both energy and time expenditure, to move uphill or downhill than to travel on flat terrain. The DEM can be combined with additional data on terrain conditions, such as the type of vegetation covering the land or an estimate of how well one can overlook the landscape from a given point, which has implications for navigation and safety. The combination of data sources has the potential to lead to a more accurate model of ancient decision-making. However, it does not alter the presumption in LCPA that humans travel and build their roads along *optimal* paths, which is an idealized and not necessarily accurate description of reality. We refer to Verhagen, Nuninger, and Groenhuijzen [133] for an in-depth discussion of possible data sources and to Branting [19] for insights into the shortcomings of the least-cost path analysis.

Once a cost surface for the study area has been assembled and the source and destination points of the least-cost path are set, the analysis proceeds by computing a *cumulative cost surface* and an associated *movement direction map* centered on the start location. These new raster maps store for every location in the study region the minimum cost required for reaching it from the start as well as a neighboring cell from which the location would be reached along a least-cost path. Both maps are typically computed using Dijkstra’s shortest path algorithm [39],

which internally keeps track precisely of the required per-location data. For the algorithm to be applicable, a neighborhood relation and associated edge costs must be defined on the cells of the cost raster, effectively turning it into a network. In principle, a directed graph can be used to model anisotropic movement costs, but we assume here that the graph is undirected. A first attempt at a neighborhood relation could be to simply connect each cell by an edge to its four orthogonal neighbors, jointly known as the *von Neumann neighborhood*, which results in a rectangular grid graph that is (approximately) aligned with the cardinal directions. This approach, however, would significantly distort travel costs experienced in the ordinal directions: To travel $\sqrt{2}$ units on this grid in the north-west direction, say, one needs to go one unit north and one unit south, leading to a distance and derived cost that is inflated by a factor of $2/\sqrt{2} \approx 1.41$. The natural solution is to add edges also in the ordinal directions. Like this, each raster cell is connected to its eight surrounding cells, together known as the *Moore neighborhood*. This reduces distortion significantly but still “favors” movement along the eight compass directions. For this reason, eight additional neighbors may be considered that are at a distance of two cells in one of the ordinal directions and at a distance of one cell in another. This is referred to as the *Knight’s move* extension, inspired by the movement pattern of the namesake Chess piece. It is important to note that the addition of the Knight’s move results in a non-planar graph structure, which makes it somewhat more difficult to detect the spatial intersection of two paths. For the edge costs, a weighted average of the costs of the cells being “touched” by the edge is used, with the sum of the weights chosen proportional to the Euclidean distance between the connected cells. When Dijkstra’s algorithm terminates, the direction map for a start point can be used to recover a least-cost path to any other location by tracing the previous-neighbor pointers that it encodes. Using the above interpretation of the cost surface as a graph, we can represent the resulting path as an edge set and derive a terrain cost for each edge.

Raster data processing

In our case study, the cost surface is derived from elevation data that originates from the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) conducted jointly by the German, Italian, and United States space agencies and the U.S. Department of Defense in the year 2000 [47]. The data has been downloaded from the website of the Ancient World Mapping Center along with shape files describing the shoreline of Sardinia [7]. The elevation readings are re-projected from geographic coordinates with a WGS84 datum to planar coordinates with an ETRS89 datum and a uniform resolution of 50 m. From this model we derive a raster of the steepest inclination for each cell, which is approximated from the Moore neighborhood of each cell [66]. To prevent least-cost paths from venturing into the “flat” sea, we artificially represent open waters by an inclination of 30° . Finally, we apply Tobler’s hiking function [129, 140] to each cell of the resulting raster, which gives a crude estimate of how difficult it would be for a human to move upwards the specified slope, expressed in time required per distance traveled. More precisely, for an inclination of θ , we set the cost of a cell to

$$0.6e^{3.5|\tan\theta+0.05|}.$$

Additionally, we add a small term of random noise to the cost of each cell to make least-cost paths unique with high probability. This is necessary as locally disagreeing path segments with common end points would inflate the number of vertices and edges of the terrain network. Finally, we use the Knight's move extended neighborhood when computing cumulative cost surfaces.

We stress that the above method to generate a cost surface is the most basic approach one can find in the literature and does not represent the state of the art in least-cost path analysis. More accurate results may be possible when using a more intricate hiking function that is based on additional data sources beyond elevation, as discussed earlier. In particular, White and Barber [139] use detailed land cover data in addition to elevation in their analysis while we only distinguish land from open waters. For Sardinia specifically, another reasonable addition would be to increase movement costs through the region of *Barbaria* in the central east of the island, whose inhabitants have resisted Roman rule substantially [87, pp. 173–175]. The use of a basic data source and conversion function in this study is, however, intentional: This minimizes degrees of freedom when modeling costs and allows the analysis to remain focused on the topological predictions made by our model.

Combining least-cost paths

The terrain network N is ultimately obtained from a combination of the edges of all pairwise least-cost paths between a set of initial locations, whose selection we detail next. The combination is such that we first form the union of all paths and then introduce additional junction vertices where edges cross. As a result, the terrain network is planar even when the Knight's move pattern is used. To improve computational performance, the terrain network undergoes further post-processing. Whenever the precise geometric course of paths is not relevant, we use a simplified representation of it in which all non-site vertices of degree two are contracted, so that only edges between sites and junction points remain. The cost of these edges equals the total cost of the path that they replace. Conversely, when path geometry is relevant, for example when we compute the geometric dissimilarity of a subnetwork of the terrain network with some other network, then we simplify linear features using the Ramer–Douglas–Peucker algorithm [42, 109] with a tolerance of 500 m. This reduces the number of vertices and edges but maintains the essential shape of paths.

Site selection

It remains to discuss how we select the initial points whose pairwise connection on the cost surface generates the terrain network $N = (V, E, c)$ and which vertices of N we select as the designated sites $S \subseteq V$ to pairwise connect using Algorithm 2. The first question is easily answered: We use as initial points all places mentioned in the Sardinian section of the *Itinerarium Antonini*, listed in Table 3.1, as they are charted in the monograph of Mastino in a map attributed to Salvatore Ganga [87, Fig. 37]. This excludes the locations of *Ad Turrem*, *Erucium*, and northern *Viniolae* on the route from *Tibula* to southern *Sulci*, which are missing from the map, but includes the known or suspected location of 37 ancient sites.² Instead of the way station of *Ad Turrem*, Mastino's map includes the

²The IA lists two distinct places called *Sulci* and two distinct places with the name *Viniolae* [87, p. 335].

Name	Site	Note
Ad Herculem	yes	must be the endpoint of a road based on its location in [87, Fig. 37]
Ad Medias	no	probably a way station [87, p. 208, 102, p. 606]
Ad Turrem	—	not charted in [87, Fig. 37]
Aquis Neapolitanis	no	a way station at the bath Aquae Neapolitanae [87, pp. 208, 363]
Biora	yes	a way station [87, p. 169], military camp [p. 174], possible city [p. 206]
Bosa	yes	a city [102, p. 605]
Caput Tyrsi	no	a village or way station [102, p. 606]
Carales	yes	a city [102, p. 605] and an endpoint of the IA
Carbia	no	a village or way station [102, p. 606]
Coclearia	no	a village or way station [102, p. 606]
Cornus	yes	a city [102, p. 605]
Elephantaria	no	a village or way station [102, p. 606]
Erucium	—	not charted in [87, Fig. 37], unattested outside the IA [76]
Fanum Carisi	no	a religious village or sanctuary [87, p. 170], not clearly located [p. 346f]
Ferraria	no	a village or way station [102, p. 606]
Forum Traiani	yes	an “important center” that obtained the status of a <i>civitas</i> [87, p. 206]
Gemellae	no	a village or way station [102, p. 606], unattested outside the IA [76]
Hafa	no	a village or way station [102, p. 606]
Longones	yes	a possible a city [87, p. 206] in an isolated coastal location [87, Fig. 37]
Luguidonis C(astra)	yes	a major military camp [87, p. 371]
Metalla	no	a village or way station [102, p. 606] with mining activity [87, p. 169]
Molaria	no	a village or way station [102, p. 606]
Neapolis	yes	a city [102, p. 605]
Nura	yes	a city [102, p. 605]
Nure	no	a village or way station [102, p. 606]
Olbia	yes	a city [102, p. 605]
Othoca	yes	a city [102, p. 605]
Porticenses	no	only mentioned as a “stazione” (station) in [87, p. 350]
Portus Luguidonis	yes	protected harbor serving Luguidonis C(astra) [87, p. 151]
Portus Tibulas	yes	harbor serving Tibula [87, p. 374], an endpoint of the IA
Sarcapos	yes	a minor trade center [87, p. 47]
Sorabile	yes	a military camp [87, p. 174] and possible city [87, p. 206]
Sulci (east)	yes	a possible city [87, p. 206], also mentioned as an urban center [p. 290]
Sulci (south)	yes	a city [102, p. 605] and an endpoint of the IA
Tegula	no	a village or way station [102, p. 606]
Tharros	yes	a fortified military camp [87, p. 174], a city [102, p. 605]
Tibula	yes	a city [102, p. 605]
Turublum Minus	no	unattested outside the IA [76], uncertain location [87, p. 344]
Viniolae (east)	no	a village or way station [102, p. 606]
Viniolae (north)	—	not charted in [87, Fig. 37], location unclear [87, p. 375, 76]
Turris Libisonis	yes	a city [102, p. 605] not listed in the IA, replaces Ad Turrem in [87, Fig. 37]

Table 3.1: The places mentioned in the Sardinian section of the Itinerarium Antonini (IA). We select some of them as designated sites to connect via Algorithm 2 (as located by Mastino [87, Fig. 37]); the remainder will form a body of evidence when searching for the connection order.

city of *Turris Libisonis* (today Porto Torres); we follow the example and include it as well.³ These 38 places are represented by the markers labeled *site* or *station* in Figure 3.9. All these locations are fine indicators of a nearby road, given that the IA is widely believed to trace the Roman public road network [87, p. 335, 76]. But, not all places mentioned in the document are reasonable travel *destinations* suited for inclusion in the set of sites *S*. A good part of them are most likely *mansiones* (way stations) that were by definition built *at* and *in support of* an existing road, as opposed to a road being constructed specifically to reach or connect them. Unfortunately, the data context does not allow us to make such a distinction with certainty for every named place, so that the following separation into *sites*—places that may have motivated an extension of the road network—and into *stations*—minor places that could have appeared in response to a road—remains speculative.

From the 38 candidates, we select as 21 sites

- 11 places identified as “oppidum avente ‘rem publicam’” (public city) by Pais [102, p. 605],
- five places mentioned as possible cities or *civitas* by Mastino [87, p. 206],
- the harbors Portus Tibulas and *Portus Luguionis*,
- the associated *Luguionis C(astra)*, a major military camp [87, p. 371],
- *Sarcapos*, a minor trade center [87, p. 47], and,
- for geographic reasons, the station *Ad Herculem*.

These are the places labeled *site* in Figure 3.9 and Table 3.1. *Ad Herculem* receives mention as a way station [87, p. 170] but its location in the extreme north-west of the island (according to the more recent [76, 87], cf. [91, 122]) implies that a road must have been constructed with *Ad Herculem* or a nearby uncharted place as its destination. Similarly, we found little evidence that *Longones* was a place of importance besides Mastino’s speculation that it may have qualified as a city. But, as its presumed location at the northern end of Sardinia implies that any road reaching it must at least take a significant detour to do so, we still include it into the set of sites *S*.

For the largest part, we have good reason to believe that the sites we selected were important enough to warrant an explicit connection to the public road network. Our criteria for selection were primarily based on factors such as a sizable population, derived from the formal recognition of a place as a city, the presence of military establishments, and indications of local trade or maritime interaction. The more speculative additions to the list are

- *Ad Herculem* and *Longones*, whose promotion to sites is based on their presumed locations,
- *Biora* and *Sorabile*, two smaller settlements that we include due to their military role, and
- *Sarcapos*, a center whose height of importance seems to predate the Roman period but which retained commercial activity nevertheless [87, p. 47].

Concerning the remaining places, their identification as minor stops along the *Itinerarium Antonini* is mainly based on the absence of sources highlighting their significance. In fact, some of them are only attested in the *Itinerarium Antonini* so that even their placement on the map

³The relationship between the toponyms *Ad Turrem* and *Turris Libisonis* is discussed by Mastino [87, p. 208, 273].

remains uncertain [76]. In any case, it is very much possible that some of these “minor” places have shaped the public road network at least locally, possibly by attracting the course of a road between two other locations, or simply because they were more relevant than we assume here. The least certain we were in excluding

- *Metalla* and *Ferraria*, whose names suggest mining activity,
- *Aquae Neapolitanae*, which was known for its thermal springs [87, p. 356], and
- *Fanum Carisi*, a toponym that implies religious significance.

Fortunately, these secondary locations are not lost for our analysis. Although we won’t consider them as direct endpoints of a connection, we will still leverage their positions to inform the search for a connection order, as detailed in the following section.

3.5.2 Searching connection orders

We are now equipped with a terrain network $N = (V, E, c)$ and a set of major sites $S \subseteq V$. Next, we will develop a search heuristic to identify a possible connection order $\pi \in \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{P}_2(S))$ from a collection of spatial *evidence*. The evidence includes places that we believe were less likely to have motivated the construction of a road yet indicate proximity to one. Our case study incorporates the 17 places from the Itinerarium Antonini that we did not select as sites (see Table 3.1) and further 32 locations where Roman milestones were found [87, Fig. 37]. Such milestones were originally placed at regular intervals of one Roman mile (ca. 1478 m [87, p. 333]) along major roads to inform travelers about the direction of travel and the distance towards the road’s destination. It is important to note that they are not entirely reliable evidence, given that they were frequently relocated and repurposed following the decline of the Roman Empire. All evidence locations are shown in Figure 3.9 alongside the designated sites.

To align the connection order π with the evidence, we will look to minimize the sum of squared distances from each evidence point to the nearest point within the road network. For the distance calculation, we consider the edges of the road network as they are drawn in Figure 3.9. Through this objective, we declare that those construction histories are the most probable whose resulting road network coincides best with the provided evidence. Unfortunately, although not tailored specifically towards the above objective, the complexity analysis in Section 3.4.3 suggests that achieving a high degree of similarity between the generated road network and some form of reference could prove challenging, at least if provably optimal solutions are desired. We will therefore turn to heuristics, which are algorithms that provide no performance guarantee but might work well on instances that occur in practice.

The use of heuristic methods is rather well-established in the solution of combinatorial network design problems, most prominently to tackle variants of the TRAVELING SALESPERSON PROBLEM (TSP) [100, 110]. The objective of the TSP is to order the vertices of an edge-weighted complete graph cyclically such that the sum of weights between vertices that are adjacent in the cycle is minimized. Compared to our model, the outcome network is rather simple: A solution to the TSP is a (short) cycle that visits every vertex exactly once. Yet, it may be instructive to briefly compare our network reconstruction problem to the TSP in terms of their solution spaces, both comprising

permutations. For a start, our problem differs in that we order site-to-site connections explicitly instead of implicitly via an order over the vertices. This accelerates the combinatorial explosion of the solution space in terms of the number of places that shall be connected: Our meager 21 sites already lead to 10^{398} possible connection orders, corresponding to a mid-sized TSP instance with 211 vertices. However, our model also differs from the TSP in the sense that the effect of any one connection on the outcome network depends critically on all previous connections in the order π . This makes it so that the first few connections in π typically have a much larger influence on the topology of the outcome network than later ones. This is unlike the TSP, where all positions in the vertex order are a priori equally important. In the following, we will make use of this concentration of importance, discussed in more detail in Section 3.3.3, to transform and compress the enormous solution space to a more manageable size for conventional heuristics. Intuitively, besides facing a larger than astronomical number, it does not make sense to test *all* connection orders as typically not much will change after the first few connections are fixed.

Towards a search space

Recall that $N = (V, E, c)$ is a terrain network, $S \subseteq V$ is a set of sites with an associated set of connections $K := \mathcal{P}_2(S)$ of size $k := |K|$, and $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ is a parameter that we consider to be fixed. The goal of this section is to design a parameterized function $\Phi_w: \mathcal{S}(K) \rightarrow \mathbb{V}$ that takes as an input a permutation π and maps it to a point in a normed vector space \mathbb{V} . It shall operate in such a way that the distance between the image of π and that of a transposed order $\pi^{i,j}$ is a good approximation of how dissimilar the two road networks produced from these orders would turn out to be, formally

$$\|\Phi_w(\pi) - \Phi_w(\pi^{i,j})\| \approx \delta_S(R_{N,\alpha}(\pi), R_{N,\alpha}(\pi^{i,j})) \quad (3.7)$$

for all $i, j \in [k]$. The hope is that the same function Φ_w may yield a passable approximation also when $\pi^{i,j}$ in approximation (3.7) is replaced with any $\pi' \in \mathcal{S}(K)$, representing a larger change to the order π . Additionally, we will require a pseudo-inverse function $\Phi_w^+: \mathbb{V} \rightarrow \mathcal{S}(K)$ such that

$$\Phi_w^+(x) = \operatorname{argmin}_{\pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)} \|\Phi_w(\pi) - x\|$$

for all $x \in \mathbb{V}$. The rationale behind this setup is the following: Given a connection order π and an associated road network $R(\pi)$, we would like to be able to choose (at random) another order π' such that the resulting network $R(\pi')$ is either similar to $R(\pi)$, if the latter is already a good match to our spatial evidence, or dissimilar to $R(\pi)$, if it is not a good prediction yet. In other words, we want to be able to move through the *solution space* of connection orders in a way that is consistent with a desired movement through the *prediction space* of generated road networks. While we could employ the insights of Section 3.3.3 to describe the rules for such movement directly, leading to a specialized search algorithm to tackle our evidence-matching problem, we find it more flexible to instead transform the solution space $S(\pi)$ into the *search space* \mathbb{V} , where the canonical measure of distance agrees roughly with the notion of geometric dissimilarity in the prediction space. The advantage of this transformation is that it will allow us to use any established procedure to search within \mathbb{V} as long as it considers the distance between two inputs as a proxy for the dissimilarity of the outcomes—a standard assumption in derivative-free optimization.

Aitchison geometry

Before we arrive at a definition of the target transformation Φ_w , we will construct an intermediate transformation $\Psi_w: \mathcal{S}(K) \rightarrow \Delta^{k-1}$. Its codomain $\Delta^{k-1} \subset \mathbb{R}^k$ is known as the $(k-1)$ -dimensional *standard, unit, or probability simplex*, whose elements are the k -dimensional nonnegative real vectors whose entries sum to one. When they do not express probabilities, such vectors are often referred to as *compositions* in application contexts; one may think for instance of the composition of a parliament or of a chemical substance. Thus, Ψ_w takes as an input a connection order $\pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)$ and maps it to a composition with k components.

We establish in the following that Δ^{k-1} is a suitable search space. Consider to this end the operation $\mathcal{C}: \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^k \rightarrow \Delta^{k-1}$ with

$$\mathcal{C}(x) := \frac{x}{\sum_{i=1}^k x_i},$$

called the *closure* of Δ^{k-1} . We will make use of the fact that Δ^{k-1} forms an inner product space with the vector operations of *perturbation*,

$$x \oplus y := \mathcal{C}((x_1 y_1, \dots, x_k y_k)^\top),$$

and *powering*,

$$\rho \odot x := \mathcal{C}((x_1^\rho, \dots, x_k^\rho)^\top),$$

and with the inner product given by

$$\langle x, y \rangle_A := \frac{1}{2k} \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=1}^k \log \frac{x_i}{x_j} \log \frac{y_i}{y_j},$$

where $x, y \in \Delta^{k-1}$ and $\rho \in \mathbb{R}$. Together with the induced norm

$$\|x\|_A := \sqrt{\langle x, x \rangle_A}$$

and the derived distance

$$d_A(x, y) := \|x \ominus y\|_A,$$

where

$$x \ominus y := x \oplus ((-1) \odot y),$$

this metric vector space is known as the *Aitchison geometry* [3, 4, 45]. Two extensive expressions for the Aitchison distance are given by

$$d_A(x, y) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2k} \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=1}^k \left(\log \frac{x_i}{x_j} - \log \frac{y_i}{y_j} \right)^2} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^k \left(\log \frac{x_i}{g(x)} - \log \frac{y_i}{g(y)} \right)^2},$$

where

$$g(x) := \left(\prod_{i=1}^k x_i \right)^{\frac{1}{k}}$$

denotes the geometric mean of $x \in \mathbb{R}^k$ [2, 45].

We will require two properties of d_A . First, reordering two compositions by the same permutation leaves their distance invariant.

Lemma 3.27. *Let $x, y \in \Delta^{k-1}$ and let $P \in \{0, 1\}^{k \times k}$ be a permutation matrix. Then,*

$$d_A(Px, Py) = d_A(x, y).$$

Proof. Expanding the definitions of d_A and g gives

$$d_A(Px, Py) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^k \left(\log \frac{(Px)_i}{\left(\prod_{j=1}^k (Px)_j \right)^{\frac{1}{k}}} - \log \frac{(Py)_i}{\left(\prod_{j=1}^k (Py)_j \right)^{\frac{1}{k}}} \right)^2}.$$

The operation P merely rearranges the entries of its operand. Thus, by the commutativity of scalar multiplication, replacing $(Px)_j$ by x_j and $(Py)_j$ by y_j does not change the value of either product in the expression. By the commutativity of scalar addition, we may further replace $(Px)_i$ and $(Py)_i$ jointly by x_i and y_i , which amounts to adding the squared terms in a different order. ■

The second lemma quantifies the Aitchison distance induced by a local change.

Lemma 3.28. *Let $x \in \Delta^{k-1}$ and $i, j \in [k]$. Then,*

$$d_A(x, x^{i,j}) = \sqrt{2} \left| \log \frac{x_i}{x_j} \right|.$$

Proof. By definition,

$$d_A(x, x^{i,j}) = \sqrt{\sum_{\ell=1}^k \left(\log \frac{x_\ell}{g(x)} - \log \frac{x_\ell^{i,j}}{g(x^{i,j})} \right)^2}.$$

Due to $g(x^{i,j}) = g(x)$ by commutativity and as $x_\ell \neq x_\ell^{i,j}$ holds only for $\ell \in \{i, j\}$, this simplifies to

$$d_A(x, x^{i,j}) = \sqrt{2 \left(\log \frac{x_i}{g(x)} - \log \frac{x_j}{g(x)} \right)^2}.$$

Using the identities $\log \rho \sigma = \log \rho + \log \sigma$ and $\log(1/\rho) = -\log \rho$ yields the claim. ■

In other words, the Aitchison distance of two vectors that differ only in terms of two entries being exchanged is proportional to the log-ratio of these entries.

Compositional embedding of connection orders

The first of two ingredients for the definition of the transformation Ψ_w is a composition w , constructed as follows. First, we follow the instructions in Section 3.3.3 to compute a strictly decreasing function $f: [1, k-1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ such that, for every $i \in [k-1]$, the value $f(i)$ is an estimate of the expected dissimilarity between a network produced from a uniform connection order and one produced from the same order but with the i -th and $(i+1)$ -th connection exchanged, formally

$$f(i) \approx \frac{1}{k!} \sum_{\pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)} \delta_S(R(\pi), R(\pi^{i,i+1})). \quad (3.8)$$

We use f to define w recursively. Let $w' \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}^k$ with

$$w'_i := \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i = 1, \\ w'_{i-1} e^{\frac{f(i-1)}{\sqrt{2}}} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Then, define $w := \mathcal{C}(w')$, so that $w \in \Delta^{k-1}$. Note that despite f being positive, it is quite possible that later entries of w end up numerically equal when they are represented with finite precision. However, the associated information loss will translate to an inability to distinguish connection orders that differ only in their later positions, which is very much acceptable. One may think of the outcome as a “lossy compression” of the solution space.

To motivate this particular definition of w , recall the definition of the matrix $D^f \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^{k \times k}$ with

$$D_{i,j}^f := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } i = j, \\ \sum_{\ell=i}^{j-1} f(\ell) & \text{if } i < j, \\ \sum_{\ell=j}^{i-1} f(\ell) & \text{if } i > j, \end{cases}$$

from Section 3.3.3. There, we showed empirically that, given approximation (3.8) is accurate, also

$$D_{i,j}^f \approx \frac{1}{k!} \sum_{\pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)} \delta_S(R(\pi), R(\pi^{i,j}))$$

is a passable approximation. For $i \leq j$, it is $w_j \geq w_i$ (as $e^\lambda \geq 1$ for $\lambda \geq 0$), so that $\log(w_j/w_i) \geq 0$ and thus

$$d_A(w, w^{i,j}) = \sqrt{2} \log \frac{w_j}{w_i} \quad (3.9)$$

by Lemma 3.28. By a telescopic sum argument, we can expand the log-ratio to obtain

$$d_A(w, w^{i,j}) = \sqrt{2} \sum_{\ell=i}^{j-1} \log \frac{w_{\ell+1}}{w_\ell}.$$

Next, we plug in the definition of $w_{\ell+1}$ to cancel out both w_ℓ and $\sqrt{2}$ and arrive at

$$d_A(w, w^{i,j}) = \sum_{\ell=i}^{j-1} f(\ell) = D_{i,j}^f. \quad (3.10)$$

This shows that we have defined w in such a way that the Aitchison distance between w and $w^{i,j}$ agrees with the estimated geometric dissimilarity between two sequential road networks whose connection orders differ only by a transposition of their i -th and j -th entry.

The second ingredient to Ψ_w is an arbitrary *ground connection order* $\psi \in \mathcal{S}(K)$. This allows us to define for every $\pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)$ a permutation matrix $P_{\psi \rightarrow \pi}$, given by

$$(P_{\psi \rightarrow \pi})_{i,j} := \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \pi_i = \psi_j, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Intuitively, if ψ and π were column vectors over some field instead of sequences of sets, then it would be the case that $P_{\psi \rightarrow \pi} \psi = \pi$. Finally, we may define

$$\Psi_w(\pi) := P_{\psi \rightarrow \pi}^{-1} w.$$

Observe that for all $\pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)$ and $i, j \in [k]$, we have $P_{\psi \rightarrow \pi^{i,j}} = Q^{i,j} P_{\psi \rightarrow \pi}$ where $Q^{i,j}$ is the involutory swap matrix from Definition 3.9, so that

$$\Psi_w(\pi^{i,j}) = P_{\psi \rightarrow \pi^{i,j}}^{-1} w = (Q^{i,j} P_{\psi \rightarrow \pi})^{-1} w = P_{\psi \rightarrow \pi}^{-1} Q^{i,j} w = P_{\psi \rightarrow \pi}^{-1} w^{i,j} = \Psi_w^{i,j}(\pi). \quad (3.11)$$

We conclude that Ψ_w is an appropriate mapping from the solution space $S(K)$ to the search space Δ^{k-1} , equipped with the Aitchison geometry, since

$$d_A(\Psi_w(\pi), \Psi_w(\pi^{i,j})) = d_A(P_{\psi \rightarrow \pi}^{-1} w, P_{\psi \rightarrow \pi}^{-1} w^{i,j}) = d_A(w, w^{i,j}) = D_{i,j}^f$$

holds for all $\pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)$ and $i, j \in [k]$ by Lemma 3.27 and equations (3.10) and (3.11).

It remains to show that we can “reverse” Ψ_w and associate with every point in the unit simplex the connection order that gets mapped closest to this point. We are thus looking for a function $\Psi_w^+ : \Delta^{k-1} \rightarrow \mathcal{S}(K)$ with

$$\Psi_w^+(x) = \operatorname{argmin}_{\pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)} \|\Psi_w(\pi) \ominus x\|_A.$$

By definition of $P_{\psi \rightarrow \pi}$, the feasible set is

$$\{\Psi_w(\pi) \mid \pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)\} = \{P_{\psi \rightarrow \pi}^{-1} w \mid \pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)\} = \{Pw \mid P \in \Pi\},$$

where Π is the set of all $k \times k$ permutation matrices. Thus, as a first step let us obtain

$$P_* := \operatorname{argmin}_{P \in \Pi} \|Pw \ominus x\|_A$$

for $x \in \Delta^{k-1}$ fixed. We show next that P_*^{-1} must sort x , that is $(P_*^{-1}x)_i \leq (P_*^{-1}x)_j$ for all $i \leq j$. Assume towards a contradiction the opposite. Then, as w is strictly sorted by definition, that is $w_i < w_j$ for all $i \leq j$, there are indices $p, q \in [k]$ with $p < q$ such that

$$w_p < w_q \quad \text{but} \quad (P_*^{-1}x)_p > (P_*^{-1}x)_q.$$

It follows for the unique $i, j \in [k]$ with $(P_*)_{i,p} = (P_*)_{j,q} = 1$ that

$$(P_*w)_i < (P_*w)_j \quad \text{but} \quad x_i = (P_*P_*^{-1}x)_i > (P_*P_*^{-1}x)_j = x_j.$$

Consider now $P_*^{i,j} := Q^{i,j} P_*$ as an alternative to P_* . Since P_* is optimal, we have

$$d_A(P_*^{i,j} w, x) \geq d_A(P_* w, x).$$

Expanding the definition of d_A yields

$$\sqrt{\frac{1}{2k} \sum_{p=1}^k \sum_{q=1}^k \left(\log \frac{(P_*^{i,j} w)_p}{(P_*^{i,j} w)_q} - \log \frac{x_p}{x_q} \right)^2} \geq \sqrt{\frac{1}{2k} \sum_{p=1}^k \sum_{q=1}^k \left(\log \frac{(P_* w)_p}{(P_* w)_q} - \log \frac{x_p}{x_q} \right)^2}.$$

Squaring both (nonnegative) sides and multiplying with $2k$ gives the equivalent inequality

$$\sum_{p=1}^k \sum_{q=1}^k \left(\log \frac{(P_*^{i,j} w)_p}{(P_*^{i,j} w)_q} - \log \frac{x_p}{x_q} \right)^2 \geq \sum_{p=1}^k \sum_{q=1}^k \left(\log \frac{(P_* w)_p}{(P_* w)_q} - \log \frac{x_p}{x_q} \right)^2.$$

We can subtract from both sides all common summands where $\{p, q\} \cap \{i, j\} = \emptyset$ and the zero summands where $p = q$. We may further apply the identities

$$(P_*^{i,j} w)_i = (P_* w)_j \quad \text{and} \quad (P_*^{i,j} w)_j = (P_* w)_i$$

to arrive at

$$\left(\log \frac{(P_* w)_j}{(P_* w)_i} - \log \frac{x_i}{x_j} \right)^2 + \left(\log \frac{(P_* w)_i}{(P_* w)_j} - \log \frac{x_j}{x_i} \right)^2 \geq \left(\log \frac{(P_* w)_i}{(P_* w)_j} - \log \frac{x_i}{x_j} \right)^2 + \left(\log \frac{(P_* w)_j}{(P_* w)_i} - \log \frac{x_j}{x_i} \right)^2.$$

After expanding the squares, we can cancel out all terms that involve a \log^2 and divide both sides by -2 while changing the direction of the inequality. This yields the equivalent statement

$$\underbrace{\log \frac{(P_* w)_j}{(P_* w)_i} \log \frac{x_i}{x_j}}_{>0} + \underbrace{\log \frac{(P_* w)_i}{(P_* w)_j} \log \frac{x_j}{x_i}}_{>0} \leq \underbrace{\log \frac{(P_* w)_i}{(P_* w)_j} \log \frac{x_i}{x_j}}_{<0} + \underbrace{\log \frac{(P_* w)_j}{(P_* w)_i} \log \frac{x_j}{x_i}}_{<0}.$$

This statement is false, contradicting the optimality of P_* . So, P_*^{-1} must indeed sort x . Let finally S and T be two distinct permutation matrices sorting x . Then, both S^{-1} and T^{-1} are optimal as

$$\|S^{-1} w \ominus x\|_A = \|w \ominus Sx\|_A = \|w \ominus Tx\|_A = \|T^{-1} w \ominus x\|_A$$

by Lemma 3.27.

Now, we only need to recover $\Psi_w^+(x) = \pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)$ such that $P_{\psi \rightarrow \pi}^{-1} = S^{-1}$, where S is any permutation matrix sorting x , that is $(Sx)_i \leq (Sx)_j$ for all $i, j \in [k]$ with $i \leq j$. It follows that $P_{\psi \rightarrow \pi} = S$ and so π can be obtained by rearranging ψ according to S . Formally, we let

$$\Psi_w^+(x)_i := \psi_{j(i)}$$

for all $i \in [k]$, where $j(i)$ denotes the unique index j with $S_{ji} = 1$. Thus, to compute $\Psi_w^+(x)$ in practice, one may use any sorting algorithm on the compositional vector x and apply the same rearrangements to the base connection order ψ . Note that $\Psi_w^+(x)$ is, in fact, independent of w : We only made use of the fact that the entries of w are increasing, which is achieved by any positive function f .

Spherical embedding of connection orders

While we have technically achieved the goal of transforming the discrete solution space $\mathcal{S}(K)$ to the “well-behaved” search space Δ^{k-1} with the metric d_A , the discerning reader might object that this space is somewhat esoteric and hardly admits an array of established search algorithms to choose from. The Aitchison geometry is, however, isometric to regular Euclidean space as witnessed by the *isometric log-ratio transformation* $\text{ilr}: \Delta^{k-1} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{k-1}$ with

$$\text{ilr}(x)_\ell := \sqrt{\frac{\ell}{\ell+1}} \log \frac{g(x_1, \dots, x_\ell)}{x_{\ell+1}},$$

which is both an isomorphism,

$$\text{ilr}(x \oplus y) = \text{ilr}(x) + \text{ilr}(y) \quad \text{and} \quad \text{ilr}(\rho \odot x) = \rho \text{ilr}(x),$$

and an isometric transformation,

$$\|x \ominus y\|_A = \|\text{ilr}(x) - \text{ilr}(y)\|,$$

where $x, y \in \Delta^{k-1}$ and $\rho \in \mathbb{R}$ and where the norm on the right-hand side is the Euclidean norm [45].⁴ This transformation allows us to finally define

$$\Phi_w := \text{ilr} \circ \Psi_w \quad \text{and} \quad \Phi_w^+ := \Psi_w^+ \circ \text{ilr}^{-1}.$$

Using Φ_w , we arrive in regular Euclidean space, equipped with the familiar Euclidean norm. Since the domain of Φ_w is finite, it would be natural to ask how the image of Φ_w is scattered around \mathbb{R}^{k-1} . Could it be that it lives in a proper subspace of \mathbb{R}^{k-1} ? To answer this question, let $\pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)$ and consider the norm

$$\|\Phi_w(\pi)\| = \|\Psi_w(\pi)\|_A = \|P_{\psi \rightarrow \pi} w\|_A = \|w\|_A.$$

The last equality follows from the permutation-invariance of the Aitchison inner product, which is due to the fact that the sum in its definition is commutative and goes over all ordered pairs of indices. We find that $\|\Phi_w(\pi)\|$ does not depend on the choice of π . Therefore, the image of Φ_w lives in a hypersphere of radius

$$\|\Phi_w(\pi)\| = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2k} \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=1}^k \left(\log \frac{w_i}{w_j} \right)^2} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{k} \sum_{i < j} \left(\log \frac{w_j}{w_i} \right)^2} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2k} \sum_{i < j} \left(\sqrt{2} \log \frac{w_j}{w_i} \right)^2}.$$

Using equations (3.9) and (3.10), this simplifies to

$$\|\Phi_w(\pi)\| = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2k} \sum_{i < j} \left(D_{i,j}^f \right)^2} = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{k}} \sqrt{2 \sum_{i < j} \left(D_{i,j}^f \right)^2} = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{k}} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=1}^k \left(D_{i,j}^f \right)^2} = \frac{\|D^f\|_F}{2\sqrt{k}},$$

Figure 3.10: Embedding of all orderings of the first four entries of a connection order (represented by the letters A–D) on the surface of a sphere. Edges represent adjacent transposition at varying positions; their length is by construction proportional to the mean dissimilarity reported in Figure 3.3A (smoothed via program (3.3)). The transformation Φ_w extends this embedding to a $(k-2)$ -sphere; the first 15 out of $k-1 = 189$ lengths are shown on the right. We expect close orders to produce similar networks on average.

where $\|\cdot\|_F$ denotes the Frobenius norm of a matrix, which equals the Euclidean norm of its vectorization.

We conclude that the scaled transformation

$$\|w\|_A^{-1}\Phi_w: \mathcal{S}(K) \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^{k-2}$$

associates with every $\pi \in \mathcal{S}(K)$ a unique point on the unit $(k-2)$ -sphere $\mathbb{S}^{k-2} \subset \mathbb{R}^{k-1}$. For an appropriately chosen compositional vector w , this happens in such a way that the Euclidean distance between the points associated with two connection orders π and $\pi^{i,j}$ is approximately proportional to how similar the two road networks generated from π and $\pi^{i,j}$ might be. In Figure 3.10, the image of this embedding is visualized for the low-dimensional case of $k = 4$ connections, resulting in a spherical arrangement.

Spherical estimation of distribution

By a search heuristic, also commonly referred to as a derivative-free or “black-box” optimization algorithm, we mean any procedure that tries to find a global minimum or maximum of a function to which it only has access through a finite number of function evaluations. If the function has a finite domain, then the number of evaluations is typically much smaller than the size of that

⁴More generally, an isometric log-ratio transformation is induced by an orthonormal basis with respect to the Aitchison inner product; this particular definition corresponds to the basis given in [45, Proposition 2].

domain. Nearly all search heuristics implicitly assume that the function being optimized exhibits local similarity: they expect that small changes in the input will result in correspondingly small changes in the function's value. This allows them to balance exploration, which involves the sampling of function values that are either distant from or independent of previous samples to gain knowledge about the search space, and exploitation, where learned information is used to select sample points in the vicinity of promising samples identified earlier.

Through the spherical embedding described in the last section, it is now possible to adapt established search heuristics designed for functions whose domain is the Euclidean space to search in the space of connection orders. For the adaptation, it must be possible to nudge a point that the heuristic wants to sample towards a nearby feasible one. Then, we can proceed as follows. Whenever the heuristic proposes to sample a point $x \in \mathbb{R}^{k-1}$:

1. Project x onto \mathbb{S}^{k-2} , that is, compute the normalized $y := x / \|x\|$.
2. Obtain the composition $z := \text{ilr}^{-1}(y)$.
3. Sort the entries of z in ascending order. Apply the same rearrangement to the entries of a fixed base connection order ψ to obtain π .
4. Compute the road network $R(\pi)$ and its objective value $c(R(\pi))$.
5. Inform the heuristic that $\Phi_w(\pi)$ was sampled instead of x and report $c(R(\pi))$ as the value.

In particular, algorithms that maintain a random distribution to generate sample points are easily adapted: just pretend that the distribution has produced z instead of x . It would also be possible to move the sampling point to $\lambda x + (1 - \lambda)z$ for some $\lambda \in [0, 1)$. For $\lambda > 0$, this is more consistent with the original description of the heuristic yet “pulls” it towards those points in the search space for which the Euclidean neighborhood contains points that are likely to produce similar networks. When no nudging is performed, corresponding to $\lambda = 1$, then the procedure above would still search the space of connection orders, but it would not profit at all from the statistical findings that are compiled into the composition w , which then plays no role.

In the following, we give a brief presentation of the custom search heuristic used in our case study. The procedure is designed to operate on a feasible subset X of a hyperspherical search space \mathbb{S}^d , $d \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$, and aims to minimize a function $f: X \subseteq \mathbb{S}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. We will employ it for $d = k - 2$ and for $f := m_B \circ R_{N,\alpha} \circ \Phi_w^+$, where m_B quantifies the mismatch of a road network with respect to a fixed body of evidence B . This implies that X is the image of Φ_w . The procedure belongs to the broader class of *estimation of distribution algorithms* (EDAs) [78] and is described in detail by Algorithm 3. The distribution $\text{vMF}(\mu, \kappa)$ and the four subroutines used are discussed after an informal description of the algorithm.

On a high level, the algorithm operates as follows. First, a random initial *population* (sequence) of $p \gg d$ *individuals* (vectors) is drawn uniformly at random from the d -sphere. All individuals are projected onto X and evaluated via f . The best $s < p$ individuals are selected as *survivors* and partitioned into ℓ clusters, initially $\ell = 1$, using spherical k -means [37]. Then, a mixture of von Mises–Fisher distributions [49, 138] is produced by estimating one data-generating distribution for each cluster [10]. If the concentration parameter κ of a distribution exceeds a convergence threshold κ_{\max} , in particular if a cluster contains only one individual so that the concentration

Algorithm 3: Estimation of von Mises–Fisher Mixture Algorithm (EvMFMA)**Parameters:**

- A number of generations $g \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$,
- a population size $p \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ and a survivor count $s \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ with $p > s \gg d$,
- a maximum concentration $\kappa_{\max} \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$.

Input: A function $f: X \subseteq \mathbb{S}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$.

Output: A point $x \in X$.

Notation: The point $v \in \mathbb{S}^d$ is arbitrary.

```

1  $P \leftarrow (x_{(i)} \sim \text{vMF}(v, 0))_{i=1}^p$  // uniform initial population
2  $(\mathcal{C}, C) \leftarrow ((P), (v))$  // clusters and cluster centers
3  $(D^\mu, D^\kappa) \leftarrow ((v), (0))$  // distribution parameters for each cluster
4  $(x_{\min}, v_{\min}) \leftarrow (v, \infty)$  // the best individual seen and its value
5  $v_{\text{avg}} \leftarrow \infty$  // last average value
6 for  $\ell \leftarrow 1$  to  $g$  do
7    $(P, V) \leftarrow \text{project\_and\_evaluate}_f(P)$  // project population and score it
8    $i \leftarrow \arg \min_{i=1}^p V_i$  // identify current best individual
9   if  $V_i < v_{\min}$  then
10      $(x_{\min}, v_{\min}) \leftarrow (P_i, V_i)$ 
11      $\bar{v} \leftarrow \sum_{i=1}^p V_i / p$  // get average value
12     if  $\bar{v} \geq v_{\text{avg}}$  then // detect lack of progress
13        $i \leftarrow \arg \min_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{C}|} D_i^\kappa$  // select least concentrated cluster
14        $\mu_{(1)}, \mu_{(2)} \sim \text{vMF}(D_i^\mu, D_i^\kappa)$  // sample twice from its distribution
15        $C \leftarrow (C_j)_{j=1}^{i-1} \cdot (\mu_{(1)}, \mu_{(2)}) \cdot (C_j)_{j=i+1}^{|\mathcal{C}|}$  // update centers to split it
16      $v_{\text{avg}} \leftarrow \bar{v}$ 
17      $P \leftarrow \text{sorted}(P, V)$  // rank population
18      $P \leftarrow (P_i)_{i=1}^s$  // select survivors
19      $(\mathcal{C}, C) \leftarrow \text{skmeans}(P, C)$  // update clusters
20      $(D^\mu, D^\kappa, \mathcal{C}^{\text{ok}}, C^{\text{ok}}) \leftarrow (( ), ( ), ( ), ( ))$  // clear distribution parameters
21     for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to  $|\mathcal{C}|$  do // fit a distribution to each cluster
22        $(\mu, \kappa) \leftarrow \text{estimate\_parameters}(\mathcal{C}_i)$ 
23       if  $\kappa < \kappa_{\max}$  then
24          $(D^\mu, D^\kappa) \leftarrow (D^\mu \cdot (\mu), D^\kappa \cdot (\kappa))$ 
25          $(\mathcal{C}^{\text{ok}}, C^{\text{ok}}) \leftarrow (\mathcal{C}^{\text{ok}} \cdot (\mathcal{C}_i), C^{\text{ok}} \cdot (C_i))$ 
26      $(\mathcal{C}, C) \leftarrow (\mathcal{C}^{\text{ok}}, C^{\text{ok}})$  // remove converged clusters
27     if  $|\mathcal{C}| = 0$  then // detect early convergence
28       return  $x_{\min}$ 
29      $M \leftarrow \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{C}|} |\mathcal{C}_i|$  // count clustered points
30      $P \leftarrow (x_{(i)} \sim \sum_{j=1}^{|\mathcal{C}|} (|\mathcal{C}_j| / M) \text{vMF}(D_j^\mu, D_j^\kappa))_{i=1}^p$  // sample next population
31 return  $x_{\min}$  // return best individual seen

```

would be infinite, then that distribution and the corresponding cluster is removed, resulting in a decrease of ℓ . The weight of the remaining distributions in the mixture is set proportional to the cardinality of their associated cluster. The next population is sampled from this mixture and the current cluster centroids are used to initialize the next round of k -means. If the average solution value of the new population does not represent an improvement over the last, then ℓ is incremented and two instead of one starting centroids are obtained from the cluster with the lowest concentration by sampling from its associated distribution. The above is repeated until a specified number of g generations have been evaluated or until there are no clusters left due to convergence. Finally, the best individual seen so far is returned.

The rationale behind the adaptive clustering is the following. If we estimated only one von Mises–Fisher distribution as a possible generator of the surviving individuals, then it could be the case that this distribution is concentrated around two or more basins of attraction of the function f . During the next generation it is possible, for a large number s of survivors in particular, that the survivors are selected around the same basins and with a similar relative frequency as before, resulting in a similar distributional estimate. When this happens, the algorithm may be unable to converge into either basin. We assume that this is the case whenever the average population does not represent an improvement over the last. Then, we split the least-concentrated cluster to allow the algorithm to “zoom in” on two promising regions separately.

In more detail, the distribution and the functions referred to in Algorithm 3 are as follows. First, $\text{vMF}(\mu, \kappa)$ denotes the von Mises–Fisher distribution with mean direction μ and concentration κ . Its density at $x \in \mathbb{S}^d$ is given by

$$C_n(\kappa) e^{\kappa \mu^\top x} \quad \text{with} \quad C_n(\kappa) := \frac{\kappa^{\frac{d}{2}-1}}{(2\pi)^{\frac{d}{2}} J_{\frac{d}{2}-1}(\kappa)}$$

a normalization term and where J_ρ denotes the modified Bessel function of the first kind of order ρ [10, 86].

The function `estimate_parameters(S)` estimates the distribution parameters μ and κ from a collection of samples $S = (x_{(i)} \in \mathbb{S}^d)_{i=1}^n$. For the mean direction, the maximum likelihood estimator is simply

$$\hat{\mu} = \frac{r}{\|r\|} \quad \text{where} \quad r := \sum_{i=1}^n x_{(i)}.$$

Unfortunately, no closed form for the maximum likelihood estimator for κ is known; we use here the approximation of Banerjee, Dhillon, Ghosh, and Sra [10],

$$\hat{\kappa} := \|r\| \frac{d - \|r\|^2}{1 - \|r\|^2},$$

which is suited for large d .

The function `skmeans(P, C)` performs spherical k -means clustering as proposed by Dhillon and Modha [37]. Here, P denotes the population to be partitioned and C serves as an initial guess for the cluster centers. Providing as C the cluster centers from the last generation speeds up the clustering process significantly and gives us some control over which old cluster we would like to see split into two.

Finally, the function $\text{sorted}(P, V)$ returns a copy of the sequence P sorted in ascending order according to the associated values V and the subroutine $\text{project_and_evaluate}_f(P)$ returns the pair of sequences

$$\left((P'_i)_{i=1}^{|P|}, (f(P'_i))_{i=1}^{|P|} \right)$$

where P'_i denotes the projection of P_i onto the domain X of f .

In the case study of Roman Sardinia, we set $p := 50(k - 1) = 10450$ and $s := 0.3 \cdot p = 3135$ and generate up to $g := 50$ generations for a total of 522500 evaluated connection orders per search.

3.5.3 Results

Let us recapitulate the experimental setup so far. We aim to attempt a reconstruction of the major public road network that spanned Sardinia during the Roman era. To this end, we have placed 38 places mentioned in an itinerary that is believed to be of ancient origin on a travel cost surface of Sardinia, as these places were located by an expert source. The cost surface was derived from a modern day digital elevation model of Sardinia using a basic transformation. We connected all pairs of places via least-cost paths in an undirected graph induced by the cost surface, which lead to the paths converging in natural movement corridors. We then merged all paths into one terrain network, whose edge costs are derived from the cost surface. As a next step, we selected 21 of the 38 places to form the pivotal sites of the road network, based on an estimate of their size and importance. The remaining 17 places and the retrieval locations of 32 Roman milestones form a body of spatial evidence. Our goal is to use the sequential network formation model described in Algorithm 2 to generate a subnetwork of the terrain network that connects the 21 selected sites and that agrees well with the provided evidence. To achieve this, we want to order the connections between all pairs of sites such that the resulting road network has a low sum of squared distances to all evidence points. We provided tangential evidence that, most likely, no efficient and optimal algorithm for this purpose exists and have turned instead to the design of a search heuristic. Therefore, we made use of the observation that the first few connections in the order are by far the most important. This allowed us to prepare the search space in such a way that connection orders that can be expected to produce similar networks are highly concentrated. As this “compressed” search space associates connection orders with points on a hypersphere, we designed an estimation of distribution algorithm that navigates this surface directly.

In this section, it remains to pick a suited value for the cost-reduction parameter α and to discuss the results. Concerning the parameter, we are not aware of an automated way to choose it. Fundamentally, this is due to the fact that the true density of the historical road network that one aims to reconstruct is naturally not known. Here, as the declared goal is to minimize the distance to a set of evidence points, we also face the issue that a higher value of α leads to a denser network that tends to perform better. Indeed, for $\alpha = 1$, we obtain by construction the entire terrain network as the road network prediction, which is optimal with respect to the declared objective yet not a plausible outcome. Thus, in practice, the choice of a suited value of α must be based to some extent on prior assumptions about the target network. To still pick α somewhat systematically, we repeat the experiment for nine values ranging from 0.3 to 0.7 with a step size of 0.05 and select the lowest parameter for which the improvement in the objective value appears

Figure 3.11: Sum of squared distances attained between the reconstructed road network and the points of evidence to which it is fitted, for varying α . The sharp decrease in the range $0.3 \leq \alpha \leq 0.4$ indicates that the road network is too sparse to explain all evidence (underfitting). As α increases beyond 0.4, the network prediction extrapolates from the evidence more liberally. We will report results for $\alpha = 0.4$.

to have stagnated. According to the results shown in Figure 3.11, the best candidate appears to be $\alpha = 0.4$. For this choice, we assume that the network density is sufficiently high so that most evidence points could be explained by the network prediction, yet low enough that only a few routes are extrapolated beyond the evidence.

The reconstructed network is shown in Figure 3.12 alongside a reference network that we digitized from the monograph of Mastino [87, Fig. 37]. The reference network, attributed to Salvatore Ganga, was not provided as evidence; we use it only to compare our model-based prediction against one made by a field expert. Since we digitized the evidence locations and the reference network from the same map, it is no coincidence that they form a near-perfect match: Ganga's network barely misses two milestones between Carales and Ferraria but connects all other sites, stations, and milestones without error. As far as we can tell, apart from the evidence locations themselves, at least the routes listed in the *Itinerarium Antonini* were used to inform the reference. This explains in particular the inclusion of a shortcut between Portus Tibulas and Olbia, which is mentioned in the IA but is not supported by the evidence discussed so far.

Comparing our prediction to the reference network, we find that it is a reasonably good match on the macroscopic scale, with some notable errors. Looking at the four north–south routes of the IA separately, we observe the following similarities and differences. First, along the western coastal route from Tibula to southern Sulci and further to *Carales*, we avoid a detour via the station of *Nure*, and we do not have a short direct connection between *Cornus* and *Tharros*. Otherwise, we match the northern section of this route quite well. One of the larger errors that our prediction makes, however, is to omit *Metalla* in the southern section of the route. While our terrain network does include four corridors to *Metalla*, these pass through a mountainous area and are initially only cost-efficient for connections that involve *Metalla* as a destination directly. As we never establish such a connection, and possibly due to these corridors' isolated locations, it appears that the inland route remains the least-cost path between *Neapolis* and southern Sulci at all times. Further down south, we miss *Tegula* for similar reasons, although the error is not as grave. On the western inland route from Tibula to *Carales*, both our prediction and that of Ganga include Portus

Figure 3.12: Model-based reconstruction of the Roman major road network on Sardinia. The network labeled *prediction* was produced by Algorithm 2 given the shown *terrain* network, the parameter $\alpha = 0.4$, and an order over the connections between all pairs of *sites* chosen such that the resulting network has a low distance to a body of sparse spatial evidence: *stations* and *milestones*. The *reference* network is an expert prediction [87, Fig. 37] that was not used in the prediction process.

Tibulas as an additional first stop. From there the route in both networks passes by *Gemellae*, *Luguidonis C(astra)*, *Hafa*, *Molaria*, and *Ad Medias* to reach *Othoca* via *Forum Traiani*. Only here do the networks differ, with our prediction including *Neapolis* as an additional stop before *Aquae Neapolitanae* while the reference passes by that settlement to remain consistent with the IA. On the remaining path towards *Carales*, we include a significant detour to use part of the existing route coming from southern *Sulci*. Next is the eastern inland route which only has four stops: *Olbia*, *Caput Tyrsi*, *Sorabile*, *Biora*, and *Carales*. We connect the latter three fine but, as a second major prediction error, miss the stop of *Caput Tyrsi* completely. Instead, our reconstructed network includes a road from *Sorabile* to *Portus Luguidonis* which then leads to *Olbia*. Finally, our prediction is rather accurate on the eastern coastal route from *Portus Tibulas* via *Longones* to *Carales*, which can be followed along the same stops as in the reference network.

Given that the reconstructed network is not too far off the expert prediction, it may be reasonable to discuss also those road segments that go beyond the routes found in the *Itinerarium Antonini*. First, our model proposes a shortcut connecting *Bosa* to the road from *Olbia* to *Tharros* just north of *Molaria*. Surprisingly, such a segment is also found in the reconstruction of *Meloni* [91], therein passing by the ancient place of *Gurulis Vetus* (not shown). Second, our prediction suggests *Sorabile* as a hub between the western inland sprawl and the eastern coast. A connection between *Forum Traiani* and *Sorabile* can also be found in the reconstructions proposed by *Meloni* [91] and *Talbert* [122], while *Mastino* [87, p. 349] discusses a possible road between *Sorabile* and the coast around eastern *Sulci*. Lastly, our model predicts a straight road connecting *Cornus* and *Biora*. This connection, however, has caused quite some trouble: its presence has likely prevented a more direct route both between *Cornus* and *Tharros* and between *Forum Traiani* and *Aquae Neapolitanae*. It is conceivable that this connection was scheduled early by our search heuristic in order to secure one of the milestones to the south of *Forum Traiani*. The area is ripe with designated sites but very low on spatial evidence, so we suspect that this route is best described as an overfitting artifact.

Model comparison

In addition to the qualitative comparison with a reference network, we conduct a quantitative comparison with seven baseline models, five of which were previously discussed in the context of Roman road network reconstruction by *Groenhuijzen* and *Verhagen* [61]. We stress that this comparison is inherently unequal: None of the baseline models is designed to incorporate spatial evidence beyond the sites being connected, so that our model has a clear information advantage. To probe the magnitude of this advantage, we include results for two additional application scenarios of our model: one where it is applied using a random connection order and one where it is fitted to the reference network directly, using geometric dissimilarity as the objective function. In the former scenario, no spatial evidence beyond the 21 designated sites is available. This negates our core assumption that the historical road construction order is important but removes the information advantage. The latter scenario probes what would be achievable by our model in the best case where the evidence situation was much better. The results are shown in [Figure 3.13](#). In detail, the baseline models tested are the following.

Figure 3.13: Quantitative comparison of our sequential road network model (Algorithm 2) with a number of baseline network formation models. Only our model receives spatial evidence beyond the sites being connected, except in the *random order* scenario. We measure the geometric dissimilarity (Definition 3.6) of a model’s predicted network with the scholarly reference network show in Figure 3.12; lower is better. Half of the models tested admit a parameter that influences network density. For them, we plot results for a range of parameter values according to the outcome network’s relative density. This is measured as the total Euclidean length of the proposed network divided by that of the reference. The gray stripe marks a density within 10% of the reference network’s; we suggest comparing the scores within this range.

- The *k-nearest neighbors* model, also known as a *proximal point analysis* [125], connects each site independently along a least-cost path to its k nearest neighbors.
- In the *path cost limit* or *maximum distance* model, each site is connected to all other sites whose topological distance does not exceed a terrain cost threshold c .
- The *efficiency network* family of models was introduced by Fulminante et al. [50] and Prignano et al. [107] specifically to model historical transport networks; we implement the variant reproduced by Groenhuijzen and Verhagen [61]. This recent model is, like ours, sequential but establishes connections in order of increasing *efficiency* of existing paths, defined as the Euclidean distance between two sites divided by the current cost of a least-cost path. The procedure stops when a target density is reached, here specified relative to the non-parametric MST model, discussed next.
- A *minimum spanning tree* (MST) is a connected network of minimum cost. Like a sequential road network for $\alpha = 0$, it contains no cycle and is typically too sparse to serve as a plausible

road network prediction.

- The *graph Delaunay triangulation* (DT) computes for the designated sites the Voronoi cells with respect to the least-cost path metric, which amounts to a partition of the vertices based on which site is the closest [46]. Then, all sites whose cells share an edge are connected.
- In Euclidean space, the *relative neighborhood graph* (RNG) is an intermediate model between a minimum spanning tree and a Delaunay triangulation in terms of the subgraph relation [130]. Its definition is easily adapted to a graph-based metric: Two sites are connected if their distance is at most the larger distance to both of them of any third point.
- Also in Euclidean space, the *Gabriel graph* (GG) is a subgraph of the Delaunay triangulation where only those edges are kept whose enclosing circles do not contain a third point [52]. Here, we use a simplified adaptation to the terrain cost metric and keep those connections proposed by the DT model whose least-cost path does not visit a third Voronoi cell (cf. [61]).

Given that the minimum spanning tree can be seen as a special case of an efficiency network, Groenhuijzen and Verhagen [61] discuss all models except for the relative neighborhood graph. The latter is considered alongside the Gabriel graph in an archaeological context for instance by Jiménez-Badillo [68]. The k -nearest neighbors and path cost limit models are discussed as baseline archaeological models also by Ducke and Suchowska [43] and Rivers et al. [112]. We include for both only a range of parameters for which the resulting network is connected, which is necessary for obtaining a finite dissimilarity. All models are executed on the terrain graph of Figure 3.9, using least-cost paths to determine site distances where appropriate. For our sequential road network model, we test the following three scenarios.

- The *fit to evidence* scenario is the experiment described earlier in this section. Each data point represents a single network, and the case of $\alpha = 0.4$ corresponds to Figure 3.12.
- In the *fit to reference* scenario, the full reference network is made available to the search procedure instead of the evidence points. Each data point describes the dissimilarity with respect to that same reference network, averaged over five predictions.
- In the *random order* scenario, we average for each parameter value the outcome of 1000 networks produced from a connection order that is sampled uniformly at random from $\mathcal{S}(K)$.

The results suggest that Gabriel-inspired graphs, Delaunay triangulations, and efficiency networks are all an excellent choice for reconstructing ancient road networks in the absence of archaeological evidence beyond the locations of sites that should be connected. When our model is applied in this evidence-free setting by picking the connection order uniformly at random, then the average dissimilarity with the reference network exceeds at all densities that of an efficiency network, wherein the roads are built in a deterministic order that favors the most beneficial connection at each point in time. On the other hand, the results suggest that this greedy order may not be the best possible, as a connection order tailored to account for supplementary evidence lets our model outperform the efficiency networks at most densities. Unsurprisingly, when a prior estimate of a road network is available, then fitting the connection order directly to this estimate results in an even more accurate “reconstruction.” We include this scenario to give an estimate

on what could be achieved through a manipulation of the connection order in principle. The significant difference in outcomes between this test and the random order experiment indeed suggests that the historical sequence of connections is a potent and possibly underexplored parameter in network formation models.

3.6 Conclusion

We proposed and studied in this chapter a mathematical model for the evolution of ancient road networks. At the heart of this model is the simplifying assumption that past connections by road were formed one at a time and without foresight for the network's eventual structure. Each new connection could thus be adapted to make use of existing roads, but we assume that there was not the possibility to optimize or coordinate the overall topology of the road network in advance. As a consequence, the network proposed by our model is shaped substantially by the historical path of its gradual formation. We describe this temporal path formally by an ordering π over pairs of important sites S that should, eventually, be adequately connected by road. What counts as an adequate connection is controlled by a second model parameter, α . This parameter enters as a factor by which a road modifies the friction imposed by its underlying terrain on human movement. Within the broader context of the network formation procedure, α controls an economic trade-off between construction costs and mobility benefits: Higher values favor shorter, more direct routes between the sites while lower values allow for increasingly long detours that make parsimonious use of existing infrastructure.

Empirically, we found that for intermediate values of α , specifically $\alpha = 0.5$, the first few connections in the order π exercise by far the most influence on the topology of the resulting network. More precisely, it appears that small modifications during the earlier stages of network evolution have a potential to alter the shape of the final network that diminishes exponentially over time. For later connections, the decrease of this potential is slower and can be approximately described by a power law. This observation enabled us to compress the astronomically large space of all possible connection orders into a well-behaved metric search space in which close points typically represent networks that are very similar.

The design of a search space and of a heuristic algorithm to navigate it was motivated by a formal complexity analysis of the task of identifying connection orders with certain properties. We showed that for $\alpha < 1$, it is NP-hard to decide whether a connection order exists in which the overall cost that is accumulated by least-cost paths over the course of network formation is small. We also proved that the minimum of this historical cost, as a function of the chosen connection order, cannot be approximated within arbitrary precision by a polynomial-time algorithm, unless $P = NP$. As we are particularly interested in connection orders that produce a network which closely resembles prior knowledge, we formalized the search for such orders as an abstract decision problem and showed NP-hardness within the range of $0.5 \leq \alpha < 1$. We conjecture that this result can be extended to hold for $\alpha < 0.5$.

In more detail, the mentioned search space is an embedding of all possible connection orders that could be used as an input to our model, formally the set $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{P}_2(S))$, as points into Euclidean space. The embedding is constructed in such a way that the Euclidean distance between two

resulting points is approximately proportional to a measure of how dissimilar the two associated road networks can be expected to be. As a first step, we represented the connection orders as vectors in the Aitchison geometry, which is an inner product space defined on the unit simplex. We found that the Aitchison distances between the embedded points agree with empirical observations on how the potential influence of certain larger changes to a connection order can be derived from that of smaller modifications. The potential influence of smaller changes, in turn, can be efficiently measured and matched by the Aitchison distance through a parameter vector that controls the embedding. Finally, we employed an isometric isomorphism to arrive in the Euclidean space. In total, construction orders are now mapped onto points on a hypersphere, between which the Euclidean distance serves as an estimate of network dissimilarity. In particular, connection orders that agree in their leading connections will be mapped to points that are extremely close; possibly to the same point if finite precision arithmetic is used.

After we reduced the search for suited connection orders to a search among points on a high-dimensional sphere, we discussed briefly a novel estimation of distribution algorithm that can be used to navigate this space systematically. While at first the algorithm samples uniformly from the hypersphere, it is gradually pulled towards areas in which points associated with well-performing networks were previously found. Apart from operating on a spherical space, a key feature of this search heuristic is that it detects when the current estimate of the promising region is recurrent. It reacts by redistributing the search effort around that region, which allows it to make further progress in practice.

Equipped with an empirical understanding of the sensitivity of connection orders and with a computational method derived from it, we turned to a test of our model in a case study of Roman Sardinia. There has been a lively archaeological debate around the major road network in this region and time as the primary textual source, an itinerary dated to antiquity, has evaded a conclusive interpretation. To apply our model, we first derived a graph-based representation of the study region from a contemporary elevation model of the island. The terrain's inclination was used to derive a base cost for travel and construction efforts along potential movement corridors, which were defined by an ensemble of least-cost paths on a more fine-grained, grid-like graph. From the places mentioned in the itinerary, as located by a field expert, we selected those that we believed were important ancient centers as designated sites. The remaining places and the retrieval locations of a number of milestones formed a body of secondary evidence. We then utilized the Euclidean embedding and our estimation of distribution algorithm to identify a connection order over all pairs of important sites whose resulting network agrees well with the evidence points. We did so for a range of possible parameters α and selected $\alpha = 0.4$ as the best candidate, based on the observation that lower values produced networks that were too sparse to collect most of the evidence. Finally, we compared the resulting network prediction with a reference network published by the same field expert. While not a perfect match, we found that a good number of road segments predicted by our model matched the topology of the scholarly reconstruction. Among the roads that our model extrapolated beyond both the provided evidence and the reference network, two were included or discussed in the broader literature while one appears to be an artifact of locally sparse evidence.

We concluded the case study with a quantitative comparison of our sequential road network

model both with alternative use scenarios of itself and with a number of baseline models that were discussed in an archaeological context before. Among these models, two simple proximity-based approaches turned out to be rather inaccurate while efficiency networks and predictions based on the graph Voronoi diagram fared better than sequential road networks when the connection order π was chosen at random in the latter. While this is not the intended way to apply our model, it results in a fair comparison where each model is only provided the graph-based description of the terrain and the sites to connect. When additional evidence points were used to inform the connection order as described above, our model reproduced the reference network more closely.

3.6.1 Discussion

We consider two aspects of this work to be our main contributions to the study and application of spatial network formation models. First, we explored the impact of temporal path dependence on the evolving network structure explicitly, which was previously recognized as an important factor but seldom modeled [141]. Second, we developed computational tools with which the vast solution space of possible connection orders can be navigated to identify one that is approximately consistent with the archaeological record. It should be noted that we do not claim that an order identified like this will be an accurate description of the true construction history of a network. We anticipate that at best, the order produced will reflect a tendency of which connection is more likely to have come before another for a limited subset of all pairs of connections. Exploring this intuition within the archaeological context remains a challenge: In our case study, we did not offer an analysis of temporal predictions as we are not in possession of comprehensive ground truth data concerning the actual construction, extension, or improvement times of the known or suspected Roman roads. More generally, the inverse problem of recovering the history of a path dependent process from the topology of its final (network) state certainly merits further research. The toolchain developed here may be a starting point for future empirical studies in this direction.

Extending the model

The basic network formation model introduced in this chapter offers several avenues for expansion. In particular, while we presumed a monotonic growth into a final network state, it would be possible to also consider *disconnection* events within the sequence π and to degrade or remove road segments that no longer appear in the least-cost path of any active connection. Roads that disappear eventually may still shape the network while they last, bringing it into a form that cannot necessarily be explained solely by the sites that remain connected during the later stages of network evolution. While such an extension may seem appropriate for diachronic studies that involve time frames of network decay, its application would hinge on the availability of data to parameterize and validate the added layers of complexity. In the context of ancient road networks, where temporal data is especially sparse, this requirement would pose a major obstacle.

A notable simplification in our model is the merging of construction, maintenance, and travel costs to refer to a single elevation-based cost surface. The cost-reduction function could be enhanced to differentiate between these costs and, in the case of maintenance costs, to distribute them: The first connection involving some edge might account for road construction costs as well

as the prospective costs of maintaining that road alone, while future connections could include a fair share of maintenance costs in their calculation.

Another natural extension of the basic model is already accounted for in Algorithm 1: One might assume that roads were not built “from scratch” but started out as simple paths that were gradually improved to account for an increase in use. To this end, one would only need to replace the cost-reduction function r_α with one that decreases strictly in the tier of a road segment, which counts the number of connections established along it. One possible avenue of research would be to set, for instance, $r(c, \tau) := c\beta^\tau$ for $1 \approx \beta < 1$ and to let connections correspond to individual agents traveling the road network as opposed to pairs of settlements, implying that the same connection can be established multiple times. Instead of following a fixed sequence π , each new connection could further be drawn from a probability distribution over possible source and destination pairs. Such a model may be particularly suited to study the evolution of routes before the prominence of formalized road networks and under the assumption that every traveler contributed to the improvement of a path.

3.6.2 Reproducibility and software

The source code used to produce the experimental results and associated figures of this chapter is available online at <https://gitlab.com/EF5-6> and has been archived at Zenodo [116, 117, 118]. An interactive demonstration of sequential road networks can be found at <https://wsgi.math.tu-berlin.de/roadnets>.

The research was conducted using free and open-source software. We used QGIS [108] to digitize and explore vector data, which was then processed in GRASS GIS [99] along with raster data to generate and export the terrain network. The remaining computations were done in Python using the third-party libraries

- NumPy [63], SciPy [134], and Pandas [89] for data processing and numerical computations,
- NetworkX [62] and rustworkx [131] for graph algorithms,
- PICOS [114] and CVXOPT [8] to model and solve program (3.3),
- Shapely [58] and similaritymeasures [67] for the computation of the geometric dissimilarity,
- composition_stats [126] for computations involving the Aitchison geometry,
- geomstats [94] for the spherical clustering, and
- Plotly [106] for figure generation.

4 Public goods

Sharing the code just seems like the right thing to do. It costs us rather little, but it benefits a lot of people in sometimes very significant ways.

John Carmack, 2009 [30]

In the previous chapter, we studied the emergence of spatial interaction networks from a sequence of strategic decisions. Next, we will explore how agents within such a network can coordinate their economic activity. We will study the exchange of a particular class of goods that may be freely accessed and simultaneously used by many individuals, albeit within availability constraints defined by the network. More precisely, a *public good* is any resource that is

- *non-excludable*, meaning it is difficult or impossible to limit access to it, and
- *non-rivalrous*, implying that any number of users can simultaneously access the resource without getting into conflict over it.

An example verging on this idealized definition—which meets a social reality in which access to any resource is restricted by complex mechanisms of discrimination and exclusion—are precisely the Roman public roads discussed in the last chapter: Constructed in the name of one administrative agency, they were henceforth freely accessible to all citizens of the Empire for travel, trade, and the exchange of information. This time, though, we are especially interested in resources provided at and by the *vertices* of a network. In antiquity, one example of such a good would be a lighthouse, but also ceremonial grounds, public squares, or city walls may qualify to some extent: While the lighthouse that broadcasts its signal onto the sea clearly fulfills both conditions, walls are built with the very intent to keep some people out. Yet, city walls qualify as a public good in the sense that they cannot selectively protect only some inhabitants, for example based on their social status or depending on whether they contributed to the structure's upkeep. A public good does not have to be a material structure, though: The results of experimentation with a novel crop, the discovery of a new medicine, and many more forms of innovation can spread by word of mouth or writing and profit any number of people who were not involved in the making. Whether material or not, ancient public goods needed to be reached or transported through space, so that a road network would have acted as a medium along which access to a public good was granted.

Much later, in the information age, immaterial public goods became ubiquitous, and their availability seemingly detached from spatial constraints. As data can be copied and exchanged around the globe at virtually no cost, information that was previously confined within the limits of oral transmission or to the semi-public space of a library became globally available, truly non-rivalrous, and largely non-excludable. Free and open-source software and preprints of academic

papers are fine examples of such digital public goods. Still, networks control who can benefit from them: The audience of an academic paper, as available as the document may be, is restricted by the technical language used and the prior knowledge assumed, both of which propagate through a network of academic communities. Likewise, free software may require domain knowledge or prior experience to be of any use and, more often than not, is advertised by word of mouth and supported by community structures.

In foundational work, Bramoullé and Kranton [17] study the network-bound provision of public goods from an economic perspective. They model their production and consumption as a game played on a graph: Each vertex corresponds to an agent whose strategy option is to pick a nonnegative real number that represents the production amount of (or effort contributed towards) a fixed public good. The production incurs a cost for the producing agent, but having access to the outcome yields a benefit both for the producer and for each of its neighbors in the graph. The authors consider in their model specifically the scenario where the marginal cost of production is constant while the benefit of each agent is given by a common function that is increasing but concave in the amount of the good available to it. This captures the concept of diminishing returns and allows production to saturate. Agents in this model are assumed to be rational and look to maximize the *utility* that they experience, defined as the benefit minus the cost.

In modelling the provision of public goods as a formal game, Bramoullé and Kranton intend to study the dynamics that underlie the configuration of production. They consider the pure Nash equilibrium (PNE) as a solution concept, which describes a state in which no agent has an incentive to unilaterally deviate from their currently chosen strategy. In terms of the public goods game, this means that no agent would experience greater utility from either increasing or decreasing their production level, given that all other agents maintain theirs. A central finding of the seminal work is that PNEs are not only guaranteed to exist, but, moreover, that there always exists a pure Nash equilibrium in which every agent belongs to one of two groups: Agents either produce nothing, being referred to as *free riders*, or they produce a fixed amount of the good that depends only on the cost of production and on the benefit function; such agents are called *specialists*. This type of equilibrium is thus referred to as a *specialized equilibrium*.

The existence of specialized equilibria, in which production efforts are distributed rather unevenly, inspired further studies to directly consider a discrete model of production. Therein, agents only face the decision whether to be *active*, which amounts to producing one unit of the public good, or *inactive*, thus consuming only what is produced by their neighbors. As the strategy space of the agents is restricted from a continuum of options to just two, the resulting model as stated so far would have a reduced expressivity. This is counteracted by the fact that a more general benefit function is considered, which is still assumed to be nondecreasing but not necessarily increasing or concave. For this first discrete variant of the public goods game, it was shown that a pure Nash equilibrium does not necessarily exist, and that deciding whether one does exist for a given instance is a difficult computational problem [142, 144]. As noted by Gilboa and Nisan [57], this hardness result hinges on the fact that agents may be indifferent with respect to their preferred strategy. Later studies eliminated such corner cases by specifying directly and unambiguously, given the number of active neighbors, whether an agent wants to pick up production itself or not [57, 84, 104]. In this stricter setting, which we will study also here, it is possible to abstract

away the costs and benefits associated with the good. Instead, the game may be defined through a *best-response pattern*: Every agent counts the number of active neighbors, looks up that number in a table, and responds by choosing whatever “best” strategy is listed there.

In this chapter, we consider two questions about the computational complexity of the (discrete and best-response based) public goods game that were raised in the work of Gilboa and Nisan: First, the authors conjectured that for any *decreasing* best-response pattern, where agents prefer to produce the good as long as at most $k \geq 1$ of their neighbors are also active, a pure Nash equilibrium might always exist. This pattern is quite natural as it models agents who are only willing to participate in production if they would not have access to a sufficient amount of the public good otherwise. It turns out that this conjecture, prior to being stated, had already been proven in the work of Levit, Komarovskiy, Grinshpoun, and Meisels [80]. We only became aware of this after answering the question a second time in [72]. Our result is, however, slightly more general: We confirm the conjecture even for heterogeneous games, where each agent has its own threshold k_i , and we provide a tighter bound on the length of any better-response sequence. We further show that when, in addition to agents’ thresholds, also the strength of network links that govern the availability of the good varies—such that an active neighbor behind an edge of weight $\ell \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ counts as ℓ active neighbors—then the existence of a pure Nash equilibrium is still guaranteed, but finding one becomes a PLS-complete problem. The second question raised by Gilboa and Nisan concerns the arguably simplest *non-monotone* pattern: Are equilibria guaranteed to exist when agents want to produce only alone or alongside exactly two producing neighbors? The topological structure of such equilibria is not too complicated: In graph theory terms, active agents in an equilibrium are either isolated or form cycles that are not adjacent to any other producer. Yet, we give examples of small graphs that do not have such stable states, and we show that deciding the existence of equilibria for this and for closely related patterns is an NP-complete problem. These findings contribute to a characterization of the public goods game in terms of its computational complexity and serve to establish a more nuanced understanding of the conditions under which social interaction patterns can lead to a stable arrangement.

Chapter outline

We first give a brief history of the networked public goods game and its variants in Section 4.1. Section 4.2 again introduces chapter-specific concepts and notation to set the stage for the analysis. In Section 4.3, we discuss decreasing best-response patterns: We confirm the existence of equilibria in heterogeneous games in Section 4.3.1 but prove the problem of finding an equilibrium in the presence of edge weights to be PLS-complete in Section 4.3.2. In Section 4.4, we prove that it is NP-hard to decide the existence of equilibria for a family of best-response patterns that contains the simple non-monotone pattern that was mentioned in the introduction.

Bibliographic remark. The results presented in this chapter, unless attributed otherwise, are joint work with Max Klimm and have previously been published in the *Proceedings of the 24th ACM Conference on Economics and Computation* [72].

4.1 Related work

Continuous model. Let $G = (V, E)$ with $V = [n]$ be an undirected graph of order n . In the model of Bramoullé and Kranton [17], each vertex $i \in V$ is an agent whose strategy is to pick a production effort $s_i \in S_i = \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$. For the resulting strategy profile $s \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n$, the utility of agent i is given by $u_i(s) := b(\sum_{j \in N(i)} s_j) - c s_i$, where $b: \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ is a benefit function with $b(0) = 0$, $b' > 0$, and $b'' < 0$, and where $c > 0$ denotes the marginal cost of production. The authors show the existence of a particular kind of pure Nash equilibrium, s with $s_i \in \{0, (b')^{-1}(c)\}$ for all $i \in V$, that they call a specialized equilibrium. Such equilibria correspond to maximal independent sets of G and can thus be computed efficiently by a greedy method. They further show that only equilibria of this type can be robust to small perturbations: An equilibrium is *stable* if all feasible strategy profiles within a sufficiently small ball around it will converge to it under simultaneous best-response dynamics, which is the case if and only if the equilibrium is specialized and every free rider ($s_i = 0$) is adjacent to at least two specialists ($s_i > 0$). Bramoullé and Kranton also discuss strategy profiles that provide maximum social welfare, defined as the sum of agents' utilities. They find that adding links can both increase and decrease the social welfare of an equilibrium that maximizes welfare, which is not necessarily specialized. Finally, the authors extend the existence guarantee of specialized equilibria to the case of *heterogeneous* agents with distinct costs c_i and benefit functions b_i , and they provide a greedy algorithm to compute one.

In follow-up work, Bramoullé, Kranton, and D'Amours [18] extend the theory to games in which the benefit of external public goods is modified, formally $u_i(s) := b(s_i + \delta \sum_{j \in N(i)} s_j) - c_i s_i$ for $\delta > 0$. They characterize the Nash equilibria as δ varies and show that there is a unique and stable equilibrium when $|\lambda_{\min}(G)| < 1/\delta$, where $\lambda_{\min}(G)$ denotes the smallest eigenvalue of the adjacency matrix of G . Pandit and Kulkarni [103] discuss the efficiency of specialized equilibria and give conditions under which they attain the maximum social welfare, maximum production effort, and minimum cost achieved by any equilibrium.

Utility-based binary games. Yu, Zhou, Brantingham, and Vorobeychik [144] study a binary variant of the game with strategy spaces $S_i := \{0, 1\}$, where they allow for arbitrary nondecreasing and agent-specific benefit functions b_i and agent-specific marginal costs c_i . They aim to show that in this setting, deciding the existence of a pure Nash equilibrium is an NP-complete problem. Yang and Wang [142] point out a flaw in the proof and provide a corrected version. They further extend this result to *homogeneous* games where again $b_i = b$ and $c_i = c$ are common for all agents $i \in V$. Kempe, Yu, and Vorobeychik [71] take a regulatory perspective and explore the computational feasibility of inducing preferred equilibria through small modifications of the graph.

Binary best-response games. The hardness result of Yang and Wang hinges on the fact that some agents are indifferent with respect to their binary decisions, formally $b(k+1) - b(k) = c$ for some $k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$. Maiti and Dey [84] exclude this possibility by studying *best-response patterns*. These are binary sequences $(T_\ell^i \in \{0, 1\})_{\ell=1}^n$ that explicitly state the response $T_{\deg_s(i)}^i$ of an agent $i \in V$ based on the number of its active neighbors $\deg_s(i) := \sum_{j \in N(i)} s_j$. The authors consider per-agent best-response patterns and provide a parameterized complexity perspective. They show that deciding the existence of equilibria remains NP-hard even on graphs of diameter at most two

(at most four for homogeneous games with a common pattern) or maximum degree at most three (homogeneous: at most nine). They further show that the problem is $W[1]$ -hard when parameterized by the graph's tree-depth and $W[2]$ -hard when parameterized by the maximum number of agents allowed to be active or inactive in an equilibrium.¹

Further work focuses on the homogeneous case of $T_i = T$ for a common pattern T of all agents $i \in V$. Predating the work of Maiti and Dey and phrased as a generalization of the best-shot game (see below), Levit et al. [80] study decreasing patterns $T = (\mathbf{1}_{[k]}(\ell))_{\ell=1}^n$ for $k \geq 1$ and show that the associated game is a potential game. This implies that equilibria always exist, and that one is reached by any better-response sequence. The authors show that the length of such a sequence is bounded by $O(kn^2)$, implying a polynomial-time algorithm to find a pure Nash equilibrium. Gilboa and Nisan [57] rediscover the existence of equilibria in the special case of $k = 2$ and settle the complexity for a number of non-monotone patterns. For patterns that start with zero, the profile in which no agent produces is always an equilibrium, so the authors consider here *non-trivial* equilibria in which at least one agent is active. They further show that hard patterns that start with $T_1 = 1$ remain hard when they are prefixed with $(1, 0)$. In independent and concurrent work, Gilboa [56] shows hardness for all patterns that begin with $(1, 0)$, include another one, and are zero eventually. Their Theorem 3.2 corresponds to our Theorem 4.35 for $k = 1$.

The best-shot game. Inspired by the correspondence of specialized equilibria to maximal independent sets of a graph, numerous works have studied the *best-shot* pattern $T = (1, 0, 0, 0, \dots)$ in more detail, in particular concerning the efficiency of equilibria. This pattern models precisely the situation where agents prefer to produce the good if and only if none of their neighbors does. The term *best shot* dates back to Hirshleifer [64], who ponders a precision shooting contest in which only the best single shot of each contender is scored (among other, less peaceful examples that involve shooting). It is first used in reference to the networked public goods game in an example given by Galeotti, Goyal, Jackson, Vega-Redondo, and Yariv [53]. Here, it translates to a benefit function that aggregates production by taking the maximum over the closed neighborhood; the pattern thus emerges for binary production and a marginal cost $c \in (0, 1)$. Galeotti et al. study Bayesian equilibria in a setting where agents have incomplete information and in a broader class of games. Dall'Asta, Pin, and Ramezani [33] take a regulatory perspective similar to that of Kempe et al. but where the network links are unknown to the intervening agency. The intervention studied is that a free rider is selected uniformly at random and turned into a producer, which induces the remaining agents to best-respond until another equilibrium is reached. This new strategy profile is accepted with some probability according to a time-varying Metropolis criterion, otherwise the prior state is restored. The authors show that these dynamics converge to the maximum social welfare (minimum production) equilibrium² for a sufficiently slow rate of decay of the probability of accepting worse outcomes. Boncinelli and Pin [14] consider equilibria that are stable with respect to perturbations. They, too, study scenarios in which random forced strategy changes affect active and inactive agents differently, but without the option to restore

¹ $W[\cdot]$ -hardness implies that the problem is unlikely to be efficiently solvable even for small values of the parameter.

²Such a state is precisely a solution to the NP-hard problem of finding a minimum cardinality independent and dominating (equivalently: maximal independent) set; see Problems 4 and 5 and Theorems 3.19 and 3.20 in Chapter 3.

a prior state. The authors show that if only producing agents are affected, then the only stable equilibria are those that minimize welfare.³ Komarovsky, Levit, Grinshpoun, and Meisels [74] study both social welfare and Pareto optimality as efficiency measures. They show that any pure Nash equilibrium is also Pareto optimal, meaning that there is no other profile in which one agent experiences higher utility while no other agent is worse off. They further prove that the best-shot game is a potential game and show that a profile of optimum potential has minimum social welfare among all equilibria. This is in line with the findings of Boncinelli and Pin, as potential optima are particularly stable. Finally, the authors discuss means to achieve favorable equilibria via side payments between the agents and to find them algorithmically. Besides extending the potential argument to all decreasing patterns, Levit et al. [80], in a much extended journal version of their earlier paper [74], give bounds on the prices of anarchy and stability, which compare the welfare of the worst and the best equilibrium to a maximum welfare (non-equilibrium) state, and they provide another, distributed algorithm for computing efficient states that are stabilized through side payments. Another work concerned with the best-shot pattern is that of López-Pintado [81], who initiates the study of public goods games on directed graphs.

Games on directed graphs. All variants of the public goods game naturally extend to a setting with directed edges. Here, an agent provides its own production to itself and to its out-neighbors, while it can only substitute local production with that of its in-neighbors. As noted by López-Pintado, pure Nash equilibria are not guaranteed to exist in directed graphs even under the best-shot pattern: An odd-length directed cycle does not have one, as it must contain an agent and its unique in-neighbor that are both in the same state. With this example, the author argues that the maximal independent set condition remains necessary but is not sufficient for an equilibrium in the directed best-shot game. They resort to studying a dynamic model in which, in every iteration, each agent chooses new out-neighbors uniformly at random along with playing their best response. This setting allows López-Pintado to characterize the stationary distribution of total production based on the fixed out-degree sequence of the varying graph. Papadimitriou and Peng [104] study the binary best-response game on a static directed graph. They give a complete pattern-wise categorization of the complexity of deciding the existence of equilibria.⁴ They show that, unless $P = NP$, exactly three pattern types induce polynomial-time decidable games: The all-ones pattern, any pattern starting with $T_1 = 0$, and, remarkably, the alternating pattern $T = (1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, \dots)$. These positive results translate directly to the undirected case studied here, which can be modeled as a special case of the directed setting. The authors further prove that finding an approximate mixed Nash equilibrium for the best-shot pattern, where the strategy of each agent is to produce the good with a certain probability, is a PPAD-hard problem.⁵ Finally, they show that a polynomial-time algorithm to approximate a mixed Nash equilibrium within arbitrary precision does exist when the treewidth of the underlying undirected graph is constant.

³This corresponds to a maximum cardinality independent set, which is also NP-hard to compute [54].

⁴The pattern notation itself was later introduced by Maiti and Dey [84] and is used here for consistency.

⁵The existence even of exact mixed Nash equilibria is guaranteed by a classic result [97, 98]. Approximate equilibria are discussed here as exact equilibria may involve irrational numbers that cannot be represented in finite precision. The hardness result suggests that it may take time exponential in the size of the instance to find such an equilibrium.

4.2 Preliminaries

We will need some notation and basic results to describe and relate formal games.

4.2.1 Pattern notation

We use a reduced variant of regular expressions over the binary alphabet to describe classes of best-response patterns. We first define their syntax.

Definition 4.1: Sub-regular expressions. The set \mathbb{X} of (*reduced*) regular expressions over the binary alphabet $\Sigma := \{0, 1\}$ is defined recursively as follows. The dot $\cdot \in \mathbb{X}$ and the character $c \in \mathbb{X}$ for all $c \in \Sigma$ are regular expressions. If $e, f \in \mathbb{X}$ are regular expressions, then so are

1. the concatenation $ef \in \mathbb{X}$,
2. the k -fold concatenation of e with itself, $(e)^k \in \mathbb{X}$ for all $k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$,
3. the one-or-more operation $(e)^+ \in \mathbb{X}$, and
4. the zero-or-more operation $(e)^* \in \mathbb{X}$.

Parentheses may be omitted; superscripts then take precedence over concatenation.

An example of the precedence rules is that $10^* = 1(0)^* \neq (10)^*$. We omit symbols for the empty set, the empty string, and for alternation, as we require only a subset of the regular languages. Expressions comprising only ones and zeros will not appear in this document, so that no confusion with numbers should arise.

Regular expressions are normally used to describe languages, which are sets of finite sequences.

Definition 4.2: Sub-regular languages. The language $L: \mathbb{X} \rightarrow \bigcup_{n=0}^{\infty} \prod_{i=0}^n \Sigma$ is defined recursively as follows. We have $L(\cdot) := \{(\cdot) \mid \cdot \in \Sigma\}$ and $L(c) := \{(c)\}$ for each character $c \in \Sigma$. For regular expressions $e, f \in \mathbb{X}$, it is

1. $L(ef) := L(e) \bullet L(f)$,
2. $L((e)^k) := L(e)^k$,
3. $L((e)^+) := \bigcup_{k=1}^{\infty} L(e)^k$, and
4. $L((e)^*) := L(e^+) \cup \{()\}$.

Here, we will use regular expressions specifically to describe infinite binary sequences.

Definition 4.3: Binary patterns. For a regular expression $e \in \mathbb{X}$, the set of *binary patterns* $P(e)$ is defined as follows. It is $x = (x_i \in \{0, 1\})_{i=1}^{\infty} \in P(e)$ if and only if there is a threshold $N \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ such that $(x_i)_{i=1}^n \in L(e)$ for all $n \geq N$. There are no other elements in $P(e)$.

For example, $P(1^*0^+) = P(1^*00^*)$ contains all infinite sequences that start with a nonnegative, finite number of ones and are zero thereafter, while $P(1^*0^*)$ contains in addition the infinite sequence of ones. This machinery allows us to write best-response patterns succinctly.

Definition 4.4: Best-response patterns. We write $T \in e$ short for $T \in P(e)$. We further write $T = e$ instead of $T \in e$ to signify that $|P(e)| = 1$.

4.2.2 Game representations

We draw in this chapter a formal connection between the strict variant of the binary public goods game that is defined by the agents' best-response behaviors [56, 57, 80, 84, 104] and the classical (continuous or binary) formulations where agents experience utility and, possibly, indifference [17, 18, 71, 103, 142, 144]. We first introduce a formal framework for each type of game.

Definition 4.5: Best-response game. A *best-response game* (BRG) is described by a triple

$$(n, (S_i)_{i=1}^n, (\beta_i)_{i=1}^n)$$

where n is the number of agents, S_i is the strategy set of agent $i \in [n]$, and

$$\beta_i: \prod_{j=1}^{i-1} S_j \cdot \prod_{j=i+1}^n S_j \rightarrow S_i$$

is a function such that $\beta_i(s_{-i})$ denotes the best response of agent i given that the other agents play s_{-i} . For a strategy profile $s \in \prod_{j=1}^n S_j$ and an agent $i \in [n]$, we write

$$s_{-i} := (s_j)_{j=1}^{i-1} \cdot (s_j)_{j=i+1}^n$$

for the strategy of the remaining agents, and we call s a *pure Nash equilibrium* (PNE) if $\beta_i(s_{-i}) = s_i$ for all $i \in [n]$.

It is straightforward to formalize the focal game of this chapter as a best-response game.

Definition 4.6: Binary public goods game. For an undirected simple graph $G = (V, E)$ with vertex set $V = [n]$ and for best-response patterns $T^i = (T_\ell^i)_{\ell=0}^\infty$ for all $i \in V$, we call the best-response game $(n, (\{0, 1\})_{i=1}^n, (\beta_i)_{i=1}^n)$ with $\beta_i(s_{-i}) := T_{\deg_s(i)}^i$ and $\deg_s(i) := \sum_{j \in N_G(i)} s_j$ a (*strict binary*) *public goods game* (PGG). We also refer to just G and the patterns T^i as a PGG. If $T^i = T$ for all $i \in V$ and for some pattern T , then we refer to the associated PGG as a *homogeneous PGG with pattern* T .

We'll introduce some notation specifically for this game.

Definition 4.7: Activity. Let $G = (V, E)$ and patterns $(T^i)_{i=1}^n$ comprise a PGG that is clear from the context. Let further $s \in \{0, 1\}^n$ be a strategy profile and $i \in V$ be an agent in G . Then, we call i *active* (in s), if $s_i = 1$, and *inactive*, if $s_i = 0$. We further call $\deg_s(i)$ the *active degree* of agent i , and we say that i is *best-responding* (in s) if $s_i = T_{\deg_s(i)}^i$.

While in a best-response game an agent's response is defined uniquely, in strategic games agents choose a strategy among all that maximize a utility function.

Definition 4.8: Strategic game. A strategic game is a triple

$$(n, (S_i)_{i=1}^n, (u_i)_{i=1}^n)$$

where n is the number of agents, S_i is the strategy set of agent $i \in [n]$, and $u_i: \prod_{j=1}^n S_j \rightarrow \mathbb{Q}$ is a function such that $u_i(s)$ denotes the utility experienced by agent $i \in [n]$ when the strategy profile

$s \in \prod_{j=1}^n S_j$ is played. For a strategy profile $s \in \prod_{j=1}^n S_j$, $i \in [n]$, and $a \in S_i$, we adopt a somewhat ambiguous but common notation and define the alternative-action profile

$$(s_{-i}, a) := (s_j)_{j=1}^{i-1} \cdot (a) \cdot (s_j)_{j=i+1}^n$$

We call a strategy profile $s \in \prod_{j=1}^n S_j$ with $u_i(s) \geq u_i(s_{-i}, a)$ for all $i \in [n]$ and all $a \in S_i$ a *pure Nash equilibrium* (PNE) of the strategic game.

An example of strategic games is the class of congestion games, which model a situation in which shared resources become increasingly costly the more agents use them.

Definition 4.9: Congestion game [113]. Let R be a set of *resources* equipped with a *delay function* $d_r: \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1} \rightarrow \mathbb{Q}$ for every $r \in R$. Then, we call a strategic game $(n, (S_i)_{i=1}^n, (u_i)_{i=1}^n)$ with $S_i \subseteq \mathcal{P}(R)$ and $u_i(s) = -\sum_{r \in S_i} d_r(x_s(r))$ for all $i \in [n]$, where $x_s(r) := \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{1}_{S_i}(r)$ denotes the number of users of $r \in R$ in s , a *congestion game*.

The prototypical example of a congestion game is played on a road network, where road segments are the resources. Each agent's strategy options are all the paths leading from that agent's start location to some destination, and each agent would like to choose a route that minimizes travel time. Of course, concurrently used road segments can become congested, leading to an increased time needed to traverse them.

With a suited utility function, we can represent any best-response game as a strategic game with equivalent best-response dynamics (cf. [84]).

Definition 4.10: Consistent representation. Let $A = (n, (S_i)_{i=1}^n, (\beta_i)_{i=1}^n)$ be a BRG. We call a strategic game $B = (n, (S_i)_{i=1}^n, (u_i)_{i=1}^n)$ a *consistent representation* of A if for all $s \in \prod_{j=1}^n S_j$ and all $i \in [n]$, it is $u_i(s_{-i}, a) > u_i(s_{-i}, a')$ for all $a' \in S_i \setminus \{a\}$ where $a := \beta_i(s_{-i})$ is the best response of i in A .

Consistent representations are closely related to the notion of a *weak isomorphism* between strategic games [51]. In particular, they also preserve the structure of pure Nash equilibria.

Lemma 4.11. *Let $A = (n, (S_i)_{i=1}^n, (\beta_i)_{i=1}^n)$ be a BRG and $B = (n, (S_i)_{i=1}^n, (u_i)_{i=1}^n)$ a consistent representation of A . Then, $s \in \prod_{i=1}^n S_i$ is a PNE of A if and only if s is a PNE of B .*

Proof. Let first s be a PNE of A and consider an agent $i \in [n]$ of A and their best response $a := \beta_i(s_{-i})$. Since A is a PNE, it is $s_i = a$. As further B is a consistent representation,

$$u_i(s) = u_i(s_{-i}, s_i) = u_i(s_{-i}, a) > u_i(s_{-i}, a')$$

for all $a' \in S_i \setminus \{a\}$. Thus, $u_i(s) \geq u_i(s_{-i}, a'')$ for all $a'' \in S_i$, so s is a PNE of B .

Let next s be a PNE of B and consider an agent $i \in [n]$ of B playing $a := s_i$. Assume towards a contradiction that $s_i \neq \beta_i(s_{-i}) =: b$. Since B is a PNE, $u_i(s_{-i}, a) = u_i(s) \geq u_i(s_{-i}, a')$ for all $a' \in S_i$. From $b \in S_i$, it follows in particular that $u_i(s_{-i}, a) \geq u_i(s_{-i}, b)$. As B is a consistent representation of A and $a \neq b$, we have $u_i(s_{-i}, b) > u_i(s_{-i}, a)$, a contradiction. Hence, $s_i = \beta_i(s_{-i})$, so s is a PNE of A . ■

We are further interested in the dynamics that may lead to an equilibrium.

Definition 4.12: Better-response sequence. For a best-response game $(n, (S_i)_{i=1}^n, (\beta_i)_{i=1}^n)$, a better-response sequence is a sequence of strategy profiles $(s^t)_{t=1}^N$ such that for all $t \in [N-1]$, it is $s^{t+1} = (s_{-i}^t, a)$ for some $i \in [n]$ and $a \in S_i$ with $a = \beta_i(s_{-i}^t)$ and $a \neq s_i^t$.

For a strategic game $(n, (S_i)_{i=1}^n, (u_i)_{i=1}^n)$, a better-response sequence is a sequence of strategy profiles $(s^t)_{t=1}^N$ such that for all $t \in [N-1]$, it is $s^{t+1} = (s_{-i}^t, a)$ for some $i \in [n]$ and $a \in S_i$ with $u_i(s_{-i}^t, a) > u_i(s^t)$.

By definition, consistent representations preserve better-response sequences.

Lemma 4.13. *If A is a BRG and B a consistent representation of A , then any better-response sequence in A is also a better-response sequence in B .*

Proof. Immediate from Definition 4.10. ■

The converse does not hold: While the better response of an agent in a best-response game is unique, there may be multiple unilateral strategy changes that improve the utility of the deviating agent in a strategic game.

4.2.3 Game isomorphisms

We will make use of the following notion of equivalence of strategic games.

Definition 4.14: Strong isomorphism [51]. Two strategic games $A = (n, (S_i)_{i=1}^n, (u_i)_{i=1}^n)$ and $B = (n, (S'_i)_{i=1}^n, (u'_i)_{i=1}^n)$ are called (*strongly*) *isomorphic* when there are bijections $\pi: [n] \rightarrow [n]$ and $\phi_i: S_i \rightarrow S'_{\pi(i)}$ for all $i \in [n]$ such that for all agents $i \in [n]$ (of A) and strategy profiles $s \in \prod_{j=1}^n S_j$, it is $u_i(s) = u'_{\pi(i)}(\phi(s))$ where

$$\phi(s) := \left(\phi_{\pi^{-1}(j)}(s_{\pi^{-1}(j)}) \right)_{j=1}^n.$$

Note that for $\pi = \text{id}_{[n]}$, it is simply $\phi(s) = (\phi_j(s_j))_{j=1}^n$. Informally, an isomorphism describes a one-to-one mapping between the agents and strategy profiles of two games that preserves the agents' utility and, by extension, the agents' strategy preferences and the PNE structure of both games. In particular:

Lemma 4.15. *If two games A and B are isomorphic and A admits a PNE, then so does B .*

Proof. If $A = (n, (S_i)_{i=1}^n, (u_i)_{i=1}^n)$ has a PNE $s \in \prod_{i=1}^n S_i$, then $u_i(s_{-i}, a) \leq u_i(s)$ for all $i \in [n]$ and $a \in S_i$. As A and $B = (n, (S'_i)_{i=1}^n, (u'_i)_{i=1}^n)$ are isomorphic, there exist bijections π and ϕ such that

$$u'_{\pi(i)}(\phi(s_{-i}, a)) = u_i(s_{-i}, a) \leq u_i(s) = u'_{\pi(i)}(\phi(s))$$

for all i and a as above. Letting $j := \pi(i)$ and $b := \Phi_i(a)$, this simplifies to

$$u'_j(\phi(s)_{-j}, b) \leq u'_j(\phi(s))$$

where now $j \in [n]$ is an arbitrary agent of B (as π is surjective) and $b \in S'_j$ is an arbitrary strategy of agent j (as Φ_i is surjective). It follows that $\phi(s)$ is a PNE of B . ■

4.3 Decreasing patterns

Decreasing best-response patterns begin with a positive but finite number of ones and are zero thereafter, formally $T^i \in 1^+0^+$ for all agents $i \in V$. Such patterns have a natural economic interpretation: They describe agents who will cease production as soon as a sufficient amount of the public good is available in their neighborhood, but who will substitute with one unit of local production as long as their demand is not met. The limitation of producing either one unit or nothing is the main distinction from the continuous model of Bramoullé and Kranton [17], where the above scenario without this restriction is considered by assuming a linear cost of production and an increasing but concave benefit associated with any amount of the good. The specialized equilibria studied by Bramoullé and Kranton in the homogeneous setting, however, are precisely captured by the “best-shot” special case of $T^i = 10^*$ for all $i \in V$. This is a consequence of the fact that active agents in a specialized equilibrium all produce the same amount of the good, which is sufficient for every agent in the closed neighborhood.

4.3.1 Existence of equilibria in heterogeneous games

In the homogeneous setting where every agent exhibits the same behavior, the existence of pure Nash equilibria was established by Bramoullé and Kranton [17] for the best-shot pattern via the one-to-one correspondence of specialized equilibria with maximal independent sets, and later extended to general decreasing patterns by Levit et al. [80]. In their proof, Levit et al. show that this game is an *ordinal potential game*: Such a strategic game $(n, (S_i)_{i=1}^n, (u_i)_{i=1}^n)$ admits an *ordinal potential function* $\Phi: \prod_{i=1}^n S_i \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with the property that for all agents $i \in [n]$, actions $a \in S_i$, and states $s \in \prod_{j=1}^n S_j$, it is

$$u_i(s_{-i}, a) > u_i(s) \iff \Phi(s_{-i}, a) > \Phi(s).$$

Every ordinal potential game with finite strategy space has a pure Nash equilibrium [96]: Otherwise, there must be an infinite sequence of better responses, each of which strictly increases the deviating player’s utility and in turn the state’s potential. But, since the state space is finite, every increase obeys a constant lower bound while the potential function has a global maximum, so such a sequence cannot exist. This argument not only establishes the existence of equilibria but also provides a method to compute one: Any better-response sequence will reach a PNE eventually. The folklore greedy algorithm to compute a maximal independent set, proposed by Bramoullé and Kranton for finding specialized equilibria, is, in fact, nothing but a better-response sequence in the best-shot game that starts from the zero state.

The following result proves that also the heterogeneous public goods game with agent-specific, decreasing best-response patterns is an (exact) potential game and enjoys the same convergence property of better-response sequences. We do so by phrasing the PGG as a congestion game; a class known to be equivalent to exact potential games [96, 113]. For an intuition on how the public goods game relates to the concept of congestion, the reader may enjoy the following re-interpretation of its dynamics: Imagine that you are contemplating adopting a recent fashion trend of, say, wearing a waist bag diagonally over your shoulder. By embracing this style early, you would signal to your friends that you are well-informed about the current state of the vogue, potentially

framing you as a trendsetter. However, if your friends adopt this trend before you do, you risk being seen as a follower with no keen eye on recent developments. Therefore, within your circle of fashion-conscious peers, there is a critical number of prevalent waist bags above which you would pass on the opportunity. The perception of this threshold may well be modeled by agent-specific and decreasing best-response patterns.⁶ The motivation of agents in this “hipster game” is dual to that of the public goods game: In the latter, production is only picked up if necessary and sourcing the good externally is preferred. Here, agents would like to take an action but having too many active peers discourages them from doing so. Yet, both phenomena are equally consistent with a decreasing pattern. We next formalize this idea.

Proposition 4.16. *The binary public goods game on undirected graphs with best-response patterns $T^i \in 1^+0^+$ for all $i \in V$ has a consistent representation that is isomorphic to a congestion game.*

In the proof, we construct a congestion game as follows. Every edge and every vertex of the public goods game $G = (V, E)$ is represented by a resource in the congestion game C . An agent $i \in V$ remaining inactive in G is represented by the associated agent $i \in [n]$ choosing the singleton strategy $\{i\}$ in C , which has a constant cost just below the number of ones in the agent’s pattern, k_i . The alternative strategy of i in C corresponds to i being active in G and amounts to selecting the set of all edges incident to i in G . The cost of this strategy in C is the number of edges that are used by both agents who have the edge in their strategy. The idea is that agents will strictly prefer the “edge” strategy as long as less than k_i of its neighbors do so, and the “vertex” strategy otherwise.

Proof of Proposition 4.16. Let $G = (V, E)$ be an instance of the PGG with patterns $T^i = 1^{k_i}0^*$, $k_i \geq 1$, for all $i \in V = [n]$. Define the strategic game $G_{\text{sg}} := (n, (S_i)_{i=1}^n, (u_i)_{i=1}^n)$ with $S_i := \{0, 1\}$ and

$$u_i(s) := \begin{cases} -(k_i - \frac{1}{2}) & \text{if } s_i = 0, \\ -\deg_s(i) & \text{if } s_i = 1, \end{cases} \quad (4.1)$$

for all $i \in V$.

We first show that G_{sg} is a consistent representation of G . Let $i \in V$ be an agent and $s \in \{0, 1\}^n$ a strategy profile of G . Let further

$$a := \beta_i(s_{-i}) = T_{\deg_s(i)}^i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \deg_s(i) \leq k_i - 1, \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg_s(i) \geq k_i, \end{cases}$$

be the best response of i and $a' := 1 - a$ its unique alternative. We show that then $u_i(s_{-i}, a) > u_i(s_{-i}, a')$. If $a = 1$, then $\deg_s(i) \leq k_i - 1$ and

$$u_i(s_{-i}, a) = -\deg_s(i) \geq -(k_i - 1) > -\left(k_i - \frac{1}{2}\right) = u_i(s_{-i}, a').$$

On the other hand, if $a = 0$, then $\deg_s(i) \geq k_i$, thus

$$u_i(s_{-i}, a) = -\left(k_i - \frac{1}{2}\right) > -k_i \geq -\deg_s(i) = u_i(s_{-i}, a').$$

⁶In the author’s working group, we found $T^i = 1^{k_i}0^*$ with $k_i \approx 3$.

Consider next the congestion game $C = (n, (S'_i)_{i=1}^n, (u'_i)_{i=1}^n)$ defined by the set of resources $R := V \cup E$ with delays

$$d_r(x) := \begin{cases} k_r - \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } r \in V, \\ x - 1 & \text{if } r \in E, \end{cases} \quad (4.2)$$

and by the strategies

$$S'_i := \{\{i\}, \{e \in E \mid i \in e\}\}$$

for all $i \in V$. Recall from Definition 4.9 that the utility of agent $i \in V$ in C takes the form

$$u'_i(z) = - \sum_{r \in z_i} d_r(x_z(r)), \quad \text{where} \quad x_z(r) = \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{1}_{z_i}(r)$$

is the number of agents using the resource $r \in R$ in the profile z of C . The strategy $z_i = \{i\}$ corresponds to i remaining inactive, which has no effect on adjacent agents, while $z_i = \{e \in E \mid i \in e\}$ corresponds to i being active, which makes being active more expensive for i 's neighbors by "congesting" incident edges.

We show that C is isomorphic to G_{sg} as witnessed by the bijections $\pi := \text{id}_{[n]}$ and $\phi_i: S_i \rightarrow S'_i$ given by

$$\phi_i(a) := \begin{cases} \{e \in E \mid i \in e\} & \text{if } a = 1, \\ \{i\} & \text{if } a = 0, \end{cases}$$

for all $i \in V$. To this end, let $i \in V$ be an agent and $s \in \prod_{j=1}^n S_j$ a strategy profile of G_{sg} . By Definition 4.14, we need to establish that $u_i(s) = u'_i(\phi(s))$ where, due to $\pi = \text{id}_{[n]}$, the function ϕ has the property $\phi(s)_j = \phi_j(s_j)$ for all $j \in V$. If $s_i = 0$, then $\phi(s)_i = \phi_i(s_i) = \{i\}$, and, as required,

$$u_i(s) = - \left(k_i - \frac{1}{2} \right) = - \underbrace{d_i(x_{\phi(s)}(i))}_1 = - \sum_{r \in \phi(s)_i} d_r(x_{\phi(s)}(r)) = u'_i(\phi(s)).$$

If $s_i = 1$, then we first note that

$$u_i(s) = - \deg_s(i) = - \sum_{j \in N(i)} s_j.$$

We can relate the active degree of i with its vertex degree in G to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} u_i(s) &= - \sum_{j \in N(i)} \left| \{h \in [n] \setminus \{i\} \mid s_h = 1 \wedge \underbrace{\{i, j\} \in \{e \in E \mid h \in e\}}_{h=j \text{ as } h \neq i} \} \right| \\ &= - \sum_{j \in N(i)} \left| \{h \in [n] \mid \underbrace{s_h = 1 \wedge \{i, j\} \in \{e \in E \mid h \in e\}}_{\{i, j\} \in \phi_h(s_h) = \phi(s)_h} \} \right| \\ &\quad + \sum_{j \in N(i)} \left| \{h \in \{i\} \mid \underbrace{s_h = 1 \wedge \{i, j\} \in \{e \in E \mid h \in e\}}_{\text{true as } h=i \text{ and } j \in N(i)} \} \right| \\ &= - \sum_{j \in N(i)} \left| \{h \in [n] \mid \{i, j\} \in \phi(s)_h \} \right| + \deg_G(i). \end{aligned}$$

Further rearrangement yields

$$u_i(s) = - \sum_{j \in N(i)} \left(\sum_{h=1}^n \mathbf{1}_{\phi(s)_h}(\{i, j\}) - 1 \right).$$

From the definitions of x_z and d_r for $r \in E$, it follows that

$$u_i(s) = - \sum_{j \in N(i)} d_{\{i, j\}}(x_{\phi(s)}(\{i, j\})).$$

Since $s_i = 1$, substituting $\phi(s)_i = \phi_i(s_i) = \{e \in E \mid i \in e\}$ yields again

$$u_i(s) = - \sum_{r \in \phi(s)_i} d_r(x_{\phi(s)}(r)) = u'_i(\phi(s)). \quad \blacksquare$$

The above observation leads to the following result.

Theorem 4.17. *The binary public goods game on undirected graphs with best-response patterns $T^i \in 1^+0^+$ for all $i \in V$ always admits a pure Nash equilibrium.*

Proof. As every congestion game has a PNE [113], the claim follows from Lemmas 4.11 and 4.15, which establish that both consistent representations and isomorphisms preserve PNEs, and from Proposition 4.16, which represents the PGG as a congestion game in terms of these relations. \blacksquare

Additionally, the representation as a congestion game brings with it convergence guarantees, which improve upon those given by Levit et al. [80] for the special case of homogeneous patterns.

Corollary 4.18. *In the game of Theorem 4.17, better-response dynamics converge to a pure Nash equilibrium after at most $O(n^2)$ improving steps.*

Proof. Let $k_{\max} := \max_{i \in V} k_i$. Any vertex can have at most $\Delta(G)$ active neighbors, so the game for $k_{\max} > \Delta(G) + 1$ is equivalent to the one for $k_{\max} = \Delta(G) + 1$. Let thus $k_{\max} \leq \Delta(G) + 1 \leq n$, without loss of generality.

The congestion game C in the proof of Proposition 4.16 is an exact potential game [96] with potential function

$$\Phi(s) = \sum_{r \in V \cup E} \sum_{\ell=1}^{x_s(r)} d_r(\ell) = \sum_{\{i, j\} \in E} s_i s_j + \sum_{i \in V} \left(k_i - \frac{1}{2} \right) (1 - s_i) < |E| + k_{\max} |V|.$$

From $d_r(\ell) \geq 0$ for all $\ell \geq 1$ and all $r \in V \cup E$, it follows that $\Phi(s) \geq 0$ for all $s \in \prod_{i \in [n]} S'_i$. On the other hand, it is $\Phi(s) < |E| + k_{\max} |V| < 2n^2$. As 2Φ is integral by construction, these bounds imply that any decreasing sequence $(\Phi(s^t) \mid s^t \in \prod_{i \in [n]} S'_i)_{t=1}^{N+1}$ has at most $N < 4n^2$ transitions. The claim follows as any better-response sequence in G corresponds to a better-response sequence in C , which has decreasing potential. \blacksquare

4.3.2 Computational hardness for weighted contributions

We next investigate a natural extension of the public goods game in which ties can have varying strength. Compared with Definition 4.6, the only novelty in the following definition is that integral edge weights influence the active degree of an agent; we write \deg_s^* instead of \deg_s to stress this.

Definition 4.19: Weighted binary public goods game. For an undirected simple graph $G = (V, E)$ with vertex set $V = [n]$, edge weights $w_e \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ for all $e \in E$, and for best-response patterns $T^i = (T_\ell^i)_{\ell=0}^\infty$ for all $i \in V$, we call the best-response game $(n, (\{0, 1\})_{i=1}^n, (\beta_i)_{i=1}^n)$ with $\beta_i(s_{-i}) := T_{\deg_s^*(i)}^i$ and $\deg_s^*(i) := \sum_{j \in N_G(i)} w_{\{i,j\}} s_j$ a *weighted binary public goods game*.

To see the relevance of this variant, consider a scenario in which agents represent communities of varying size, which is assumed to scale both the production capacity and the demand of the public good. One may model the behavior of a community $i \in V$ of size $k_i \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ with the decreasing pattern $T^i := 1^{k_i} 0^*$, indicating a demand of k_i units, and give two connected communities $i, j \in V$ an edge weight corresponding to the size of the smaller one, $w_{\{i,j\}} := \min\{k_i, k_j\}$. Like this, larger communities can support their neighborhood effectively, but would require multiple smaller producing neighbors to substitute local production, as each could contribute only up to its own size. This particular configuration of patterns and edge weights is reminiscent of the “heterogeneous agents” extension studied by Bramoullé and Kranton [17] in the continuous setting. The authors extend the existence guarantee of specialized equilibria to this case, with the modification that every agent produces either nothing or an amount that depends only on that agent’s perception of costs and benefits. Agents that associate a larger benefit and a lower cost with the good correspond to larger communities in the above setting.

The model of Definition 4.19 extends beyond the given example, even if only decreasing patterns are considered, as it also allows for more general edge weights. In particular, the weights do not have to be a function of the involved agents’ patterns. An adaption of the proof of Proposition 4.16 shows that games with decreasing patterns and arbitrary edge weights can still be represented as a congestion game.

Proposition 4.20. *The weighted binary public goods game on undirected graphs with best-response patterns $T^i \in 1^+ 0^+$, $i \in V$, has a consistent representation that is isomorphic to a congestion game.*

Proof. Consider the same construction as in the proof of Proposition 4.16, except that

1. the utilities in the definition of G_{sg} in equation (4.1) are given by

$$u_i(s) := -\deg_s^*(i)$$

in the case where $s_i = 1$, and

2. the delay functions in the definition of C in equation (4.2) are defined as

$$d_r(x) := w_r(x - 1)$$

in the case where $r \in E$.

In the argument that G_{sg} is a consistent representation of G , replace all occurrences of $\deg_s(i)$ with the weighted active degree $\deg_s^*(i)$.

In the argument that C is isomorphic to G , nothing changes for the case of $s_i = 0$ as $\phi(s)_i = \{i\}$ and $i \notin E$. For the case of $s_i = 1$, we show again that $u_i(s) = u'_i(\phi(s))$. Now, it is

$$\begin{aligned} u_i(s) &= -\deg_s^*(i) = -\sum_{j \in N(i)} w_{\{i,j\}} s_j \\ &= -\sum_{j \in N(i)} w_{\{i,j\}} |\{h \in [n] \mid \{i,j\} \in \phi(s)_h\}| + \sum_{j \in N(i)} w_{\{i,j\}} \\ &= -\sum_{j \in N(i)} w_{\{i,j\}} (x_{\phi(s)}(\{i,j\}) - 1). \end{aligned}$$

As $\{i,j\} \in E$, we can substitute $d_{\{i,j\}}(x) = w_{\{i,j\}}(x-1)$ to arrive at

$$u_i(s) = -\sum_{j \in N(i)} d_{\{i,j\}}(x_{\phi(s)}(\{i,j\})) = u'_i(\phi(s)). \quad \blacksquare$$

In Corollary 4.18, we established that better-response dynamics converge in polynomial time to a pure Nash equilibrium for unweighted binary public goods games. In contrast, we show that for weighted games, the computation of a PNE is a PLS-complete problem. For the proof, we give a straightforward reduction from the problem of computing a pure Nash equilibrium in a *threshold game*, a particular kind of congestion game where each agent has two strategies only.

Definition 4.21: Threshold game [1]. Let $n \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$, $\theta \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^n$, and $d_r^{\text{in}}: \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ nondecreasing for all $r \in \mathcal{P}_2([n])$. We call an n -agent congestion game with resources $R := R_{\text{in}} \cup R_{\text{out}}$, where $R_{\text{in}} := \mathcal{P}_2([n])$ and $R_{\text{out}} := [n]$, with delays d_r

$$d_r(x) := \begin{cases} d_r^{\text{in}}(x) & \text{if } r \in R_{\text{in}}, \\ \theta_r & \text{if } r \in R_{\text{out}}, \end{cases}$$

and with strategies $S_i = \{\{i\}, \{e \in \mathcal{P}_2([n]) \mid i \in e\}\}$ for all agents $i \in [n]$ a *threshold game*.

This should not be confused with another ‘‘threshold game’’ introduced in the related work of Papadimitriou and Peng [104], where agents pick their strategy from the unit interval. We will make use of the following result.

Theorem 4.22 (Ackermann, Röglin, and Vöcking [1]). *Computing a pure Nash equilibrium of a threshold game is PLS-complete.*

We need to refine the statement slightly.

Corollary 4.23. *Computing a pure Nash equilibrium of a threshold game is PLS-complete even when $\theta_i \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ for all $i \in [n]$, and $d_{\{i,j\}}^{\text{in}} = a_{\{i,j\}}(x-1)$ where $a_{\{i,j\}} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ for all $\{i,j\} \in \mathcal{P}_2([n])$.*

Proof. As explained by Ackermann et al. [1, Remark 4.2], the proof of Theorem 4.22 [1, Theorem 4.1] only uses delay functions where $d_{\{i,j\}}^{\text{in}} = a_{\{i,j\}}(x-1)$ with $a_{\{i,j\}} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ for all $\{i,j\} \in \mathcal{P}_2([n])$. We find that the chosen factors $a_{\{i,j\}}$ are the edge weights of the LOCAL MAXCUT instance being reduced. This problem is PLS-complete for nonnegative integer edge weights [115] and trivially remains so

if we multiply all edge costs in a LOCAL MAXCUT instance by two. Thus, we can assume without loss of generality that $a_{\{i,j\}}/2 \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ for all $\{i,j\} \in \mathcal{P}_2([n])$.

With respect to the thresholds θ_i , we find that they are defined as

$$\theta_i := \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j \in [n] \setminus \{i\}} a_{\{i,j\}} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$$

for all $i \in [n]$. If $\theta_i = 0$ for some agent $i \in [n]$, then this implies also $a_{\{i,j\}} = 0$ for all $j \in [n] \setminus \{i\}$. This means that agent i will always be indifferent, and its strategy choice will never affect the utility of any other agent in any state. Therefore, we can decide its strategy arbitrarily and remove it from the game alongside all resources that contain this agent in a preprocessing step. ■

We are ready to state our result. The only non-trivial part in the following reduction is the fact that in a threshold game, an agent may be indifferent between its two strategies, while in a weighted binary public goods game this cannot occur.

Theorem 4.24. *Computing a pure Nash equilibrium of a weighted binary public goods game on an undirected graph with patterns $T^i \in 1^+0^+$ for all $i \in V$ is PLS-complete.*

Proof. We first argue membership in PLS. An instance of the computational problem comprises an undirected graph $G = (V, E)$ with $V = [n]$, and edge weights $w_e \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ for all $e \in E$. Feasible solutions of such an instance are strategy profiles, which can be encoded as binary vectors of length n . Using standard encodings for graphs and vectors, recognition of valid instances and feasible solutions in polynomial time (in the size of the instance) is straightforward. To obtain an initial feasible solution, one may pick the all-zero vector. The integral value of a feasible solution can be taken to be twice that profile's potential value in the congestion game that is isomorphic to the game's consistent representation; see Proposition 4.20. Both this representation and the potential can be computed in polynomial time. The neighborhood of a feasible solution is given by all single-agent deviations to that agent's unique alternative strategy; it corresponds to the flip-neighborhood of binary vectors. Since the neighborhood has cardinality n , one can compute the value of every neighbor of a feasible solution in polynomial time to determine whether there is a neighbor with strictly lower value. Local optima of an instance are thus local potential minima, which are in one-to-one correspondence with the pure Nash equilibria of the PGG.

We next give a PLS-reduction from the threshold game. Consider an instance of the threshold game as in Corollary 4.23, that is, with thresholds $\theta_i \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ for all agents $i \in [n]$ and with delays

$$d_r(x) := \begin{cases} a_{\{i,j\}}(x-1) & \text{if } r \in R_{\text{in}}, \\ \theta_r & \text{if } r \in R_{\text{out}}, \end{cases}$$

where $a_{\{i,j\}} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ for all $\{i,j\} \in \mathcal{P}_2([n])$. We construct an instance of the weighted binary public goods game as follows. Let $G := (V, E)$ be a graph with $V := [n]$ and $E := \{\{i,j\} \in \mathcal{P}_2(V) \mid a_{\{i,j\}} \neq 0\}$. Let further $w_e := a_e$ for all $e \in E$. By definition of E , we have $w_e \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ for all $e \in E$ as required. Finally, define the decreasing patterns $T^i := 1^{\theta_i}0^*$ for all $i \in V$. Note that this construction can be computed in time polynomial in the size of the threshold game instance.

Let now $s \in \{0, 1\}^n$ be a pure Nash equilibrium of the constructed instance. We define a feasible solution s' of the underlying threshold game as follows. For all $i \in [n]$, consider the strategy options $s_i^{\text{in}} := \{e \in \mathcal{P}_2([n]) \mid i \in e\}$ and $s_i^{\text{out}} := \{i\}$, and let

$$s'_i := \begin{cases} s_i^{\text{in}} & \text{if } s_i = 1, \\ s_i^{\text{out}} & \text{if } s_i = 0. \end{cases}$$

It remains to show that s' is a pure Nash equilibrium. To this end, let $i \in [n]$ be an agent in the threshold game. Since s is a PNE of the public goods game and $T^i = 1^{\theta_i} 0^*$, we have

$$s'_i = s_i^{\text{in}} \iff \text{deg}_s^*(i) \leq \theta_i - 1 \quad (4.3)$$

and

$$s'_i = s_i^{\text{out}} \iff \text{deg}_s^*(i) \geq \theta_i. \quad (4.4)$$

If $s'_i = s_i^{\text{in}} = \{e \in \mathcal{P}_2([n]) \mid i \in e\}$, then agent i experiences a utility of

$$\begin{aligned} u_i(s') &= - \sum_{r \in s'_i} d_r(x_{s'}(r)) \\ &= - \sum_{e \in \mathcal{P}_2([n]): i \in e} a_e(x_{s'}(e) - 1). \end{aligned}$$

From the definitions of E and w_e for all $e \in E$, it follows that

$$u_i(s') = - \sum_{e \in E: i \in e} w_e(x_{s'}(e) - 1).$$

Consider an edge $e \in E$ with $i \in e$ as it occurs in the sum. It takes the form $e = \{i, j\}$ for some $j \in V$. Since $e \in s'_i$, it is $x_{s'}(e) = 1 + \mathbf{1}_{s'_j}(e)$. By construction, $e \in s'_j$ if and only if $s_j = 1$. Thus, agent i has no incentive to switch strategies as

$$u_i(s') = - \sum_{j \in N_G(i)} w_{i,j} s_j = - \text{deg}_s^*(i) \stackrel{(4.3)}{\geq} -(\theta_i - 1) > -\theta_i = u_i(s'_{-i}, s_i^{\text{out}}).$$

On the other hand, if $s'_i = s_i^{\text{out}} = \{i\}$, then agent i experiences a utility of

$$u_i(s') = -\theta_i \stackrel{(4.4)}{\geq} -\text{deg}_s^*(i) = u_i(s'_{-i}, s_i^{\text{in}}),$$

and is satisfied as well. ■

Theorem 4.24 establishes that, unless $\text{FP} = \text{PLS}$, there must be a family of instances of the weighted public goods game and a corresponding family of better-response sequences whose length grows superpolynomially in the size of the associated instance.⁷ However, our reduction is not tight [115], and could, in principle, shorten the distance between some initial strategy profile and the nearest reachable equilibrium state. The reason for this is that indifferent agents in the threshold game are given a strict preference in the public goods game, which creates additional better-response transitions—possible shortcuts—in the state space. Therefore, we leave open whether there are also families of instances and corresponding initial strategy profiles from which *any* better-response sequence has exponential length, as is known for the threshold game [1].

⁷Otherwise, any deterministic algorithm that simulates better-response dynamics of the weighted public goods game could be used to solve any problem in PLS in worst-case polynomial time.

Figure 4.1: Two instances of the binary public goods game with pattern $T = 1010^*$. Unlike for decreasing patterns (Section 4.3), pure Nash equilibria (PNEs) are not guaranteed to exist. The graph in panel B has the minimum number of both vertices and edges among graphs that do not admit an equilibrium.

Figure 4.2: A family of small graphs on which the binary public goods game with pattern $T = 10^k 10^*$ for $k \geq 2$ admits no pure Nash equilibrium. Complete enumeration confirms that for $k \leq 4$ ($k \leq 6$), every graph with fewer vertices (edges) does have a PNE.

4.4 Picky patterns

In the last section, we studied a configuration of the public goods game that offers a straightforward economic interpretation: Agents pick up production only in case of a shortage. We next investigate a slightly more nuanced response: Under a *picky pattern*, defined as $T = 10^k 10^*$ for $k \geq 1$, agents want to perform the action if either none or a particular number, at least two, of neighbors also do so. The first member of this family is $T = 1010^*$, whereby agents prefer to produce alongside zero or two producing neighbors only. Given a pure Nash equilibrium for this pattern, the set of vertices corresponding to active agents forms a dominating set that induces a disjoint union of cycles and independent vertices; see Figure 4.1A for an example. However, it is not the case that any such vertex set in the underlying graph forms a PNE in the public goods game: Additionally, it is necessary that no dominated vertex is dominated by exactly two neighbors. As a consequence, the existence of a PNE is not guaranteed. Figure 4.1B shows a small graph that does not admit one. A similar argument can be made for $k \geq 2$: Active agents in a PNE induce a disjoint union of isolated vertices and $(k + 1)$ -regular graphs and further form a dominating set such that no other vertex is incident to exactly $k + 1$ vertices from that set. Figure 4.2 shows a family of small graphs that do not admit a PNE under these best-response rules (see Lemma 4.27 below for a proof).

4.4.1 Computational hardness

We show that deciding the existence of equilibria under a picky pattern is an NP-complete problem, even in the homogeneous setting where each agent has the same pattern, via a reduction from the following satisfiability problem.

One-in-three satisfiability with positive literals and falsity

Problem 7: POSITIVE 1-IN-3-SAT

Input: A collection of ℓ clauses $I := \{l_1^i, l_2^i, l_3^i \mid i \in [\ell]\}$ with $l_j^i \in X \cup \{\perp\}$ for all $(i, j) \in [\ell] \times [3]$, where $X = \{\xi_1, \dots, \xi_m\}$ is a set of boolean variables and where \perp denotes unconditional falsity.

Question: Is there a truth assignment to the variables in X satisfying

$$\Phi(X) := \bigwedge_{i \in [\ell]} ((l_1^i \vee l_2^i \vee l_3^i) \wedge \neg(l_1^i \wedge l_2^i) \wedge \neg(l_2^i \wedge l_3^i) \wedge \neg(l_3^i \wedge l_1^i))?$$

The hardness of this problem is a classical result.

Theorem 4.25 (Garey and Johnson [54]). POSITIVE 1-IN-3-SAT is NP-complete.

In contrast to the preceding section, whose results are independent of the topology of the graph on which the public goods game is played, graph structure will play a central role in the following. We therefore write just (*in-*)*active vertex* to refer to a producing (respectively free-riding) agent that is represented by a vertex of a given graph.

In the reduction, the literals of a POSITIVE 1-IN-3-SAT instance (either non-negated variables or falsity) are represented by *literal vertices* and truth assignments to the underlying boolean variables are encoded by these vertices' strategies. The gadgets represent logical operators and connect the literal vertices in such a way that the resulting graph admits a pure Nash equilibrium of the binary public goods game if and only if the POSITIVE 1-IN-3-SAT formula is satisfiable. To this end, every gadget has a set of *operand vertices* that are identified with a subset of the literal vertices; no other gadget vertex has an edge leaving the gadget. We refer to gadget vertices that are adjacent to the operator vertices as *membrane vertices*. Three out of four gadgets are constructed in such a way that membrane vertices are inactive in any PNE on a graph containing the gadget. We call this property *safety* as it rules out potential side effects when the gadget is added to a graph. In particular, this ensures that adding a gadget to a graph that admits no PNE will not allow a PNE to exist in the resulting graph.

Lemma 4.26. Let $G_\circ = (V_\circ, E_\circ)$ be a graph gadget with operand vertices $X \subseteq V_\circ$ and membrane vertices $M := N_{G_\circ}(X)$ such that for all graphs $G' = (V', E')$ with $V' \cap V_\circ = X$, for all PNE s on $(V' \cup V_\circ, E' \cup E_\circ)$, and for all $m \in M$, it is $s_m = 0$. Let further $G = (V, E)$ be a fixed graph with $V \cap V_\circ = X$ that admits no PNE. Then, also $H = (V \cup V_\circ, E \cup E_\circ)$ admits no PNE.

Proof. Let G_\circ, X, M, G , and H as in the lemma and assume towards a contradiction that H admits a PNE s . Consider the strategy profile t obtained by limiting s to vertices in G . If $\deg_t(v) = \deg_s(v)$ for all $v \in V$, then s is a PNE on G , so there is a $v \in V$ with $\deg_t(v) \neq \deg_s(v)$. If $N_H(v) \subseteq V$, then $\deg_t(v) = \deg_s(v)$ by construction of t , so there is further a $u \in N_H(v) \setminus V$ with $s_u = 1$. Since $u \notin V$, $\{u, v\} \notin E$, so $\{u, v\} \in E_\circ$, implying $u, v \in V_\circ$. From $v \in V$ it follows that $v \in X$ and from $u \in N_H(v)$ it follows that $u \in N_{G_\circ}(v)$ and thus $u \in N_{G_\circ}(X) = M$, contradicting $s_u = 1$. ■

Figure 4.3: NEAR-OR gadget: In any PNE s on a graph that contains this gadget as a subgraph in such a way that non-black vertices are connected only to other gadget vertices, it is $\sum_{i=1}^{\ell} s_{x_i} \notin \{0, k+1\}$. We refer to black vertices as *operand vertices*, to gray vertices as *membrane vertices*, and to white vertices as *internal vertices*.

The NEAR-OR gadget

The NEAR-OR gadget (Figure 4.3) is used to ensure (under the assumption that a PNE exists) that at least one literal in each clause of a POSITIVE 1-IN-3-SAT instance evaluates to true. The “near” in its name stems from the fact that, when used to represent an ℓ -ary logical operator with $\ell > k$, the gadget cannot distinguish between a total of 0 or $k+1$ operands evaluating to true; in both cases the gadget will prevent a PNE. The gadget further appears as a building block in other gadgets, where we make use of this property. We call the NEAR-OR gadget for $\ell = 1$ the TRUE gadget as it forces its single operand vertex to be active in any PNE.

The following lemma implies that the NEAR-OR gadget forbids a PNE in which none of its operand vertices are active.

Lemma 4.27. *The NEAR-OR gadget with operand vertices removed admits no PNE.*

Proof for $k = 1$. Let G be the graph of Figure 4.3A without the vertices in X and assume towards a contradiction that G admits a PNE s . Assume further that $\deg_s(v) \geq 4$ for some $v \in V$. Then, v is a vertex with $\deg(v) = 4$ and v is inactive in s . Consider $\{u, v\} \in E$ with $\deg(u) = 2$. Then, u is active with $\deg_s(u) = 1$ as $N(u) = \{v, v'\} \in E$, contradicting that s is a PNE. We have thus $\deg_s(v) \leq 3$ for all $v \in V$. In particular, $v \in V$ is active if and only if $\deg_s(v)$ is even. Let next $A \subseteq V$ active and $I = V \setminus A$ inactive. Since $\sum_{a \in A} \deg_s(a) + \sum_{i \in I} \deg_s(i) = \sum_{a \in A} \deg(a)$ is even, also $|I|$ and, by extension, $|A| = 6 - |I|$ are even. The cases of $|A| \in \{0, 6\}$ are easily ruled out, so either $|A| = 2$ or $|I| = 2$. If $A = \{a_1, a_2\} \in E$, $\deg_s(a_1) = 1$ contradicts a_1 active. If $A = \{a_1, a_2\} \notin E$, $\text{diam}(G) = 2$ implies an $i \in I$ with $A \subseteq N(i)$ so that $\deg_s(i) = 2$ contradicts i inactive. If $I = \{i_1, i_2\} \in E$, then $G[A]$ is either the paw graph or the union of a P_3 and a singleton. Both have a vertex of degree one, implying $a \in A$ with $\deg_s(a) = 1$, which contradicts a being active. Finally, if $I = \{i_1, i_2\} \notin E$, then $\deg_s(i_1) = \deg(i_1) \in \{2, 4\}$. As we ruled out $\deg_s(i_1) = 4$ earlier, this contradicts i_1 inactive. ■

Proof for $k \geq 2$. Let G be the graph of Figure 4.3B without the vertices in X and assume towards a contradiction that G admits a PNE s . If both y and z are inactive, then w and all vertices

in Y and in Z have no active neighbors and are active. This contradicts y being inactive, as $\deg_s(y) = |Y| + 1 = k + 1$. If both y and z are active, then $\deg_s(v) \in \{1, 2\}$ for all $v \in \{w\} \cup Y \cup Z$, so all vertices other than y and z are inactive. Thus, $\deg_s(y) = 1$, which contradicts y being active. If exactly one of y and z is active, say y , then all vertices in Y are inactive and all in Z are active. If further w is inactive, then $\deg_s(z) = k + 1$ contradicts z being inactive. If however w is active, then $\deg_s(y) = 1$ contradicts y being active. ■

The next lemma states that the NEAR-OR gadget also forbids a PNE in which exactly $k + 1$ of its operand vertices are active.

Lemma 4.28. *Let $G_\vee = (V_\vee, E_\vee)$ an instance of the NEAR-OR gadget, $G = (V, E)$ a graph with $V \cap V_\vee = \{x_i \mid i \in [\ell]\}$, and $H := (V \cup V_\vee, E \cup E_\vee)$. Then, H admits no PNE s with $\sum_{i=1}^\ell s_{x_i} = k + 1$.*

Proof for $k = 1$. Assume towards a contradiction that s is a PNE of H with $\sum_{i=1}^\ell s_{x_i} = k + 1$. If w is active, then both y and z are inactive as otherwise $\deg_s(w) > k + 1$. If further q is inactive, then both y' and z' are active as $\deg_s(y') = \deg_s(z') = 0$. This contradicts q inactive, as $\deg_s(q) = 2$, so q is active. If y' is inactive, then $\deg_s(y) = 2$ contradicts y inactive. So y' must be active, contradicting $\deg_s(y') = 1$. If w is inactive, then $\deg_s(w) > k + 1$, so y or z or both are active. If both y and z are active, then exactly one of y' and q must be active, otherwise $\deg_s(y) \in \{1, 3\}$. If q is active, $\deg_s(y') = 2$ contradicts y' inactive. If y' is active, this contradicts $\deg_s(y') = 1$. Thus, exactly one of y and z is active, say y . Since $\deg_s(y) \in \{0, 2\}$ with z and w both inactive, it follows that y' and q are either both active or both inactive. If both are active, this contradicts z inactive as then $\deg_s(z) = 2$. If both are inactive, it is $\deg_s(z') = 0$, so z' is active. This again implies $\deg_s(z) = 2$, contradicting z inactive. ■

Proof for $k \geq 2$. Assume towards a contradiction that s is a PNE of H with $\sum_{i=1}^\ell s_{x_i} = k + 1$. Analogous to the proof for $k = 1$, we have that either w is active and both y and z are inactive, or that w is inactive and at least one of y and z is active. In the former case, all vertices in Y have no active neighbors and are active, contradicting y inactive as $\deg_s(y) = |Y| + 1 = k + 1$. In the latter case, if both y and z are active, then all vertices in Y are inactive, contradicting y active as $\deg_s(y) = 1$. If only z is active, then all vertices in Y are active, contradicting y inactive as again $\deg_s(y) = |Y| + 1$. A symmetric argument rules out that only y is active. ■

Next, we show that the NEAR-OR gadget permits a PNE in every other case.

Lemma 4.29. *Let $G_\vee = (V_\vee, E_\vee)$ an instance of the NEAR-OR gadget, $G = (V, E)$ a graph with $V \cap V_\vee = X$, and $H := (V \cup V_\vee, E \cup E_\vee)$. Then, if G admits a PNE s with $\sum_{i=1}^\ell s_{x_i} \notin \{0, k + 1\}$, then also H admits a PNE t with $t_v = s_v$ for all $v \in V$.*

Proof for $k = 1$. We claim that t with

$$t_v := \begin{cases} s_v & \text{if } v \in V, \\ 1 & \text{if } v \in \{q\}, \\ 0 & \text{if } v \in V_\vee \setminus (X \cup \{q\}), \end{cases}$$

is a PNE on H . Since $t_v = s_v$ and, due to $t_w = 0$, also $\deg_t(v) = \deg_s(v)$ holds for all $v \in V$ by construction, it remains to show that vertices in $(V \cup V_v) \setminus V = V_v \setminus X$ are best-responding. This is the case as $\deg_t(q) = 0$ and q is active, $\deg_t(w) = m \notin \{0, k+1\}$ and w is inactive, and for all $v \in \{y, z, y', z'\}$, $\deg_t(v) = 1$ and v is inactive. ■

Proof for $k \geq 2$. Let $Q := Y \cup Z$. We claim that t with

$$t_v := \begin{cases} s_v & \text{if } v \in V, \\ 1 & \text{if } v \in Q, \\ 0 & \text{if } v \in V_v \setminus (X \cup Q), \end{cases}$$

is a PNE on H . Again, we only need to show that vertices in $V_v \setminus X$ are best-responding. This is the case as for all $q \in Q$, $\deg_t(q) = 0$ and q is active, $\deg_t(w) = m \notin \{0, k+1\}$ and w is inactive, and $\deg_t(y) = \deg_t(z) = k$ and y and z are both inactive. ■

Additionally, we argue that the NEAR-OR gadget is safe.

Lemma 4.30. *Let $G_v = (V_v, E_v)$ an instance of the NEAR-OR gadget, $G = (V, E)$ a graph with $V \cap V_v = X$, and $H := (V \cup V_v, E \cup E_v)$. Then, H admits no PNE in which w , the unique vertex in $N_{G_v}(X)$, is active.*

Proof for $k = 1$. Let t be a PNE of H and assume towards a contradiction that $t_w = 1$. By Lemmas 4.27 and 4.28, $\sum_{i=1}^{\ell} t_{x_i} = m \notin \{0, k+1\}$. Since w is active and $\deg_t(w) \geq m > 0$, it is $\deg_t(w) = k+1 = 2$. Therefore, at least one of y and z must be active, as otherwise $\deg_t(w) = m$. If both y and z are active, then neither y' nor q can be active as otherwise $\deg_s(y) > 2$. An analogous argument rules out that z' is active. This implies $\deg_t(q) = 2$, contradicting q inactive. Thus, exactly one of y and z is active, say y . If further q is active, also y' is active as $\deg_s(y') = 2$, but this contradicts y active as then $\deg_s(y) = 3$. So q is inactive, implying that z' is active due to $\deg_s(z') = 0$. If further y' is inactive, then $\deg_s(q) = 2$ contradicts q inactive, so also y' is active, contradicting $\deg_s(y') = 1$. ■

Proof for $k \geq 2$. Let t be a PNE of H and assume towards a contradiction that $t_w = 1$. By analogy with the proof for $k = 1$, we have $\deg_t(w) = k+1 > m$ so that at least one of y and z must be active. If y is active, then $\deg_t(y') = 1$ for all $y' \in Y$, so all vertices in Y are inactive and $\deg_t(y) \in \{1, 2\}$. Since $2 < k+1$, this contradicts y active. An analogous argument rules out that z is active. ■

Finally, we summarize the behavior of the NEAR-OR gadget.

Corollary 4.31. *Let $G_v = (V_v, E_v)$ an instance of the NEAR-OR gadget, $G = (V, E)$ a graph with $V \cap V_v = X$, and $H := (V \cup V_v, E \cup E_v)$. Then:*

1. *NEAR-OR is permissive: If G admits a PNE s with $\sum_{x \in X} s_x \notin \{0, k+1\}$, then also H admits a PNE t with $t_v = s_v$ for all $v \in V$.*
2. *NEAR-OR is restrictive: If H admits a PNE t , then $\sum_{x \in X} t_x \notin \{0, k+1\}$.*
3. *NEAR-OR is safe: In any PNE t on H and for all $m \in N_{G_v}(x)$, $t_m = 0$.*

A FALSE gadget: In any PNE s on a graph defined as for Figure 4.3, $s_x = 0$.

B EQUIV gadget: In any PNE s on a graph defined as for Figure 4.3, $s_{x_1} = s_{x_2}$.

Figure 4.4: FALSE and EQUIV gadgets. Only the name and operand vertices of auxiliary gadgets are shown.

Proof. Permissiveness was shown in Lemma 4.29, restrictiveness is the sum of Lemmas 4.27 and 4.28, and safety follows from Lemma 4.30. ■

The FALSE gadget

In a POSITIVE 1-IN-3-SAT instance, literals are either non-negated boolean variables or falsity (\perp). To represent the latter, we introduce a gadget that forces a vertex to be inactive in any PNE (Figure 4.4A).

Lemma 4.32. Let $G_{\perp} = (V_{\perp}, E_{\perp})$ an instance of the FALSE gadget, $G = (V, E)$ a graph with $V \cap V_{\perp} = \{x\}$, and $H := (V \cup V_{\perp}, E \cup E_{\perp})$. Then:

1. FALSE is permissive: If G admits a PNE s with $s_x = 0$, then also H admits a PNE t with $t_v = s_v$ for all $v \in V$.
2. FALSE is restrictive: If H admits a PNE t , then $t_x = 0$.
3. FALSE is safe: In any PNE t on H and for all $m \in N_{G_{\perp}}(x)$, $t_m = 0$.

Proof. *Permissiveness.* Let G admit a PNE s with $s_x = 0$. Then, the partial strategy profile p with $p_v = s_v$, for all $v \in V$, and $p_{y_i} = 1$, for all $i \in [k]$, can be extended to a PNE for H by the permissiveness of the NEAR-OR gadget.

Restrictiveness. Assume towards a contradiction that H admits a PNE t with $t_x = 1$. Since TRUE is restrictive, $t_{y_i} = 1$ for all $i \in [k]$. This contradicts NEAR-OR being restrictive, as $t_x + \sum_{i=1}^k t_{y_i} = k + 1$.

Safety. Follows from the safety of the NEAR-OR gadget as x is identified with an operand vertex of the $(k + 1)$ -ary NEAR-OR gadget in G_{\perp} . ■

The EQUIV gadget

Next, we introduce a gadget to identify equal variables in distinct clauses (Figure 4.4B).

Lemma 4.33. Let $G_{\leftrightarrow} = (V_{\leftrightarrow}, E_{\leftrightarrow})$ an instance of the EQUIV gadget, $G = (V, E)$ a graph with $V \cap V_{\leftrightarrow} = \{x_1, x_2\}$, and $H := (V \cup V_{\leftrightarrow}, E \cup E_{\leftrightarrow})$. Then:

1. EQUIV is permissive: If G admits a PNE s with $s_{x_1} = s_{x_2}$, then also H admits a PNE t with $t_v = s_v$ for all $v \in V$.

Figure 4.5: CLAUSE gadget: Admits three symmetric PNE with $s_{t_1} + s_{t_2} + s_{t_3} = 1$.

2. *EQUIV is restrictive*: If H admits a PNE t , then $t_{x_1} = t_{x_2}$.
3. *EQUIV is safe*: In any PNE t on H and for all $m \in N_{G_\perp}(\{x_1, x_2\})$, $t_m = 0$.

Proof. Permissiveness. Let G admit a PNE s with $s_{x_1} = s_{x_2}$. We first show that the strategy profile p with

$$p_v := \begin{cases} s_v & \text{if } v \in V, \\ 0 & \text{if } v = y, \\ 1 & \text{if } v \in \{z_i \mid i \in [k]\}, \end{cases}$$

is a PNE in the graph G' that is obtained by removing all vertices in $V_\leftarrow \setminus (\{x_1, x_2, y\} \cup \{z_i \mid i \in [k]\})$ from H . Since $p_y = 0$, all $v \in V$ are best-responding in p , so it remains to show that also y and z_i for $i \in [k]$ are best-responding. This is the case as for all $i \in [k]$, $\deg_p(z_i) = 0$ and z_i is active, while $\deg_p(y) \in \{k, k+2\}$ with $k \geq 1$ and y is inactive. Since p is a PNE on G' , it follows from the permissiveness of the TRUE and FALSE gadgets that also H admits a PNE t with $t_v = p_v = s_v$ for all $v \in V$.

Restrictiveness. Assume towards a contradiction that H admits a PNE t with $t_{x_1} \neq t_{x_2}$. Without loss of generality let $t_{x_1} = 1$ and $t_{x_2} = 0$. By the restrictiveness of the TRUE and FALSE gadgets, $t_y = 0$ and $t_{z_i} = 1$ for all $i \in [k]$. Thus, $\deg_t(y) = k + 1$, contradicting y inactive.

Safety. It is $N_{G_\perp}(\{x_1, x_2\}) = \{y\}$ and, in any PNE t on H , $t_y = 0$ as FALSE is restrictive. ■

The CLAUSE gadget

Finally, we represent each clause of a POSITIVE 1-IN-3-SAT instance by a CLAUSE gadget (Figure 4.5). Here, we do not require the familiar trio of properties. Instead, the gadget is designed to admit three symmetric PNE, each of which has one distinct vertex from $\{t_1, t_2, t_3\}$ in active state. We prove a slightly weaker claim, which is sufficient for the reduction.

Lemma 4.34. *Let G be an instance of the CLAUSE gadget. Then,*

- for every $t \in \{t_1, t_2, t_3\}$, G admits a PNE s with $s_t = 1$, and
- in any PNE s on G , $s_{t_1} + s_{t_2} + s_{t_3} = 1$.

Proof. The case of $k \geq 2$ is trivial: Exactly the profiles in which exactly one of the three vertices is active are PNE. Let thus $k = 1$ in the following.

We show the first claim only for $t = t_2$ as the other cases are analogous. We claim that the partial strategy profile s with

$$s_v := \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } v \in \{t_2, z_1, z_2, z_3\}, \\ 0 & \text{if } v \in \{t_1, t_3, x_1, x_2, x_3, y_1, y_2, y_3\}, \end{cases}$$

can be extended to a PNE on G . We first argue that s is a PNE on the graph obtained by removing all non-operand vertices of the NEAR-OR gadget from G . On this graph it is $\deg_s(t_2) = 0$ and t_2 is active while $\deg_s(t_1) = \deg_s(t_3) = 3$ and both t_1 and t_3 are inactive. Further, $\deg_s(z) = 0$ and z is active for every $z \in \{z_1, z_2, z_3\}$ while $\deg_s(v) = 1$ and v is inactive for all $v \in \{x_1, x_2, x_3, y_1, y_2, y_3\}$. Since $t_1 + t_2 + t_3 = 1 \notin \{0, k+1\}$, it follows from Lemma 4.29 that s can be extended to a PNE on G .

Next, let s be any PNE on G and assume towards a contradiction that $\ell := s_{t_1} + s_{t_2} + s_{t_3} \neq 1$. The cases of $\ell = 0$ and $\ell = 3$ are ruled out by the restrictiveness of the NEAR-OR gadget, so it remains to rule out $\ell = 2$. Without loss of generality let $s_{t_1} = s_{t_2} = 1$ and $s_{t_3} = 0$; the other cases are analogous. Then, $\deg_s(x_i) = 2$ and x_i is active for all $i \in [3]$. Thus, $\deg_s(t_1) \geq 3$, contradicting t_1 active. ■

Reduction

With our assortment of gadgets, we can prove the main result of this section.

Theorem 4.35. *The homogeneous binary public goods game equilibrium decision problem on undirected graphs with best-response pattern $T \in 10^+ 10^*$ is NP-complete.*

Proof. Containment in NP is obvious. For NP-hardness, we describe a polynomial-time reduction from POSITIVE 1-IN-3-SAT. In the following, we consider the best-response pattern $T = 10^k 10^*$ for a fixed $k \geq 1$. To ease notation, we write $s(v)$ instead of s_v to denote the strategy of a vertex v in a strategy profile s .

Let $I := \{\{l_1^i, l_2^i, l_3^i\} \mid i \in [\ell]\}$ with $l_j^i \in X \cup \{\perp\}$ for all $(i, j) \in [\ell] \times [3]$, $\ell \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$, and $X = \{\xi_1, \dots, \xi_m\}$ a set of boolean variables, be an instance of POSITIVE 1-IN-3-SAT. Recall that I is a *yes*-instance if and only if the formula

$$\Phi(X) := \bigwedge_{i \in [\ell]} ((l_1^i \vee l_2^i \vee l_3^i) \wedge \neg(l_1^i \wedge l_2^i) \wedge \neg(l_2^i \wedge l_3^i) \wedge \neg(l_3^i \wedge l_1^i))$$

is satisfiable. We construct an instance $G = (V, E)$ of the binary public goods game that has a PNE if and only if this is the case. Starting from the empty graph, we introduce a disjoint CLAUSE gadget $C^i = (V^i, E^i)$ for every $\{l_1^i, l_2^i, l_3^i\} \in I$, whose vertices we relabel with a superscript i . We call the resulting graph G' . Note that for some $i \neq i' \in [\ell]$ and $j, j' \in [3]$, it may be the case that $l_j^i = l_{j'}^{i'} \in X$ while $t_j^i \neq t_{j'}^{i'}$ are disjoint vertices. For every such quadruple (i, j, i', j') , we add an EQUIV gadget on fresh non-operand vertices whose operand vertices are identified with t_j^i and $t_{j'}^{i'}$. We call the graph at this point G'' . Next, for every $(i, j) \in [\ell] \times [3]$ with $l_j^i = \perp$, we add a FALSE gadget on fresh non-operand vertices whose operand vertex we identify with t_j^i . This yields the graph G . Clearly, the number of vertices added is polynomial in the number of clauses ℓ , so that this construction can be accomplished in time polynomial in the size of I . In the following we show decision equivalence.

Let first I be a *yes*-instance. Then, there is a truth assignment $\sigma: X \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ satisfying Φ . We claim that the partial strategy assignment s^0 with

$$s^0(t_j^i) := \begin{cases} \sigma(\xi) & \text{if } l_j^i = \xi \in X, \\ 0 & \text{if } l_j^i = \perp, \end{cases}$$

for all $(i, j) \in [\ell] \times [3]$ can be extended to a PNE on G . To this end consider first the **CLAUSE** gadgets and the associated subgraph G' of G . Since Φ is satisfied, we have $s^0(t_1^i) + s^0(t_2^i) + s^0(t_3^i) = 1$ for every $i \in [\ell]$. By Lemma 4.34, it follows that G' admits a PNE s' with $s'(t_j^i) = s^0(t_j^i)$ for all $(i, j) \in [\ell] \times [3]$. Consider next the **EQUIV** gadgets and the associated subgraph G'' of G . Let t_j^i and $t_{j'}^{i'}$ be the operand vertices of an **EQUIV** gadget. Then, $l_j^i = l_{j'}^{i'} \in X$ by construction so that $s'(t_j^i) = s^0(t_j^i) = s^0(t_{j'}^{i'}) = s'(t_{j'}^{i'})$ by definition of s' and s^0 . From the permissiveness of the **EQUIV** gadgets (applied iteratively), it follows that G'' admits a PNE s'' with $s''(t_j^i) = s'(t_j^i) = s^0(t_j^i)$ for all $(i, j) \in [\ell] \times [3]$. Consider next the **FALSE** gadgets in G . Let t_j^i be the operand vertex of such a gadget. Then, by construction, $l_j^i = \perp$ and thus $s''(t_j^i) = s^0(t_j^i) = 0$. By the permissiveness of the **FALSE** gadgets (applied iteratively), we have that G admits a PNE as required.

Let next G admit a PNE s . We show that the truth assignment $\sigma: X \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ given by $\sigma(l_j^i) := s(t_j^i)$ for all $(i, j) \in [\ell] \times [3]$ with $l_j^i \in X$ satisfies Φ . First, we show that σ is well-defined. To this end assume towards a contradiction that there are $(i, j) \neq (i', j') \in [\ell] \times [3]$ such that $l_j^i = l_{j'}^{i'}$ but $s(t_j^i) \neq s(t_{j'}^{i'})$. By construction, there is an **EQUIV** gadget in G with operand vertices t_j^i and $t_{j'}^{i'}$, whose restrictiveness contradicts s being a PNE. Next, we show that Φ is satisfied. Let $i \in [\ell]$ index a clause $\{l_1^i, l_2^i, l_3^i\} \in I$ and consider the associated **CLAUSE** gadget C^i with operand vertices $V^i = \{t_1^i, t_2^i, t_3^i\}$. Since **EQUIV** and **FALSE** are safe gadgets, implying $s(v) = 0$ for all $v \in N_G(V^i)$, it follows that s limited to V^i is a PNE on G . By Lemma 4.34, this implies $s(t_1^i) + s(t_2^i) + s(t_3^i) = 1$. Without loss of generality, assume that $s(t_1^i) = 1$ and $s(t_2^i) = s(t_3^i) = 0$. We establish that $l_1^i \in X$. To this end assume towards a contradiction that $l_1^i = \perp$. Then, by construction, there is a **FALSE** gadget in G whose operand vertex is t_1^i . Since **FALSE** is restrictive, $s(t_1^i) = 1$ contradicts s being a PNE. Since $l_1^i \in X$, we have $\sigma(l_1^i) = s(t_1^i) = 1$, so $(l_1^i \vee l_2^i \vee l_3^i)$ is satisfied by σ . It remains to show that both l_2^i and l_3^i are *false* under σ . We do so for l_2^i ; the argument for l_3^i is analogous. The case of $l_2^i = \perp$ is clear, so let $l_2^i \in X$. Then, $\sigma(l_2^i) = s(t_2^i) = 0$. It follows that also $\neg(l_1^i \wedge l_2^i) \wedge \neg(l_2^i \wedge l_3^i) \wedge \neg(l_3^i \wedge l_1^i)$ and, by extension, Φ is satisfied by σ . ■

Gilboa and Nisan [57] proved that any NP-hard pattern starting with a 1 remains NP-hard when it is prefixed with the sequence 10. This lets us identify another natural family of patterns that is NP-hard to decide, that of all *truncated alternating* sequences:

Corollary 4.36. *The homogeneous binary public goods game equilibrium decision problem on undirected graphs with best-response pattern $T \in (10)^+ 10^*$ is NP-complete.*

What makes this family interesting is that its “limit case”, the alternating sequence $T = (10)^*$, is polynomial-time decidable already for the more general case of directed graphs, as shown by Papadimitriou and Peng [104].

4.5 Conclusion

In this chapter, we turned our attention from the formation of spatial networks to the study of interaction patterns within a fixed network structure. To this end, we analyzed the rich combinatorial structure of a formal game that models the provision of *public goods*, which are idealized non-excludable and non-rivalrous resources that can be produced at the vertices and accessed along the edges of a graph. While the basic model considers strategic agents that can produce any amount of such a resource to satisfy local consumption, a classical result suggests that the most stable arrangements feature agents that specialize on production and others that do not produce at all. We studied a binary model of these reduced dynamics and its generalization to complex decision patterns beyond the original economic framework.

We first remained within the economic framework, though, and rediscovered that the decreasing best-response patterns, formally $T \in 1^+0^*$, induce a potential game and therefore always admit a pure Nash equilibrium. Our construction is slightly more general than the result of Levit et al. [80] and proves the existence of equilibria even in the case where each agent has a private threshold that determines when their own demand is satisfied, and further in the case where network links scale the provision by an integer factor. In the latter scenario, however, we showed that *finding* such an equilibrium amounts to a PLS-complete search problem.

We then studied a basic family of non-monotone best-response patterns under which agents are “picky” about the number of neighbors that they would like to produce along. Such dynamics are formalized by a pattern $T \in 10^+10^*$. We showed that the existence of equilibria is NP-hard to decide for all $k \geq 1$, thereby answering a question raised by Gilboa and Nisan [57].

In concert with concurrent work by Gilboa [56] and analog results for directed graphs by Papadimitriou and Peng [104], these findings establish an extensive understanding of the pattern-wise complexity of the strict binary public goods game on general graphs. Future research concerning this model might pursue a more fine-grained analysis of the influence of graph parameters on the difficulty of the equilibrium problem: Given a non-monotone pattern, for what network topologies are equilibria guaranteed to exist and for which is their existence already difficult to decide? Or, taking the perspective of a policymaker: How can a network be modified to facilitate a stable arrangement under complex interactions patterns?

5 Impartial selection

A judge, replied the Empress, is easy to be had; but to get an impartial judge, is a thing so difficult, that I doubt we shall hardly find one. . . I'll try what may be done.

Margaret Cavendish, *The Blazing World* [23]

In the last chapter, the subset of agents that end up investing in the production of a public good has been the stable outcome of a dynamical process driven by decentralized, pairwise interactions. In the following, we maintain both the pairwise interaction patterns and the task of finding an agreeable partition of agents into two groups, but we shift the focus from a decentralized and dynamic to a centrally coordinated and simultaneous model of self-organization. More precisely, we introduce a central authority that coordinates the selection of a subset of agents based on the same agents' pairwise votes. In this setting, instead of responding to the status quo autonomously with a change in behavior, agents propose their preferred configuration independently, see it aggregated in a predefined manner, and adhere to the outcome. In Section 4.3.1, we highlighted the duality of distributing chores that have to be done on the one hand, namely the contribution to a public good, and assigning desired but limited positions on the other hand. In this chapter, it will again be more natural to consider the latter perspective: Being selected is desirable, but not everyone can be. We thus turn to the study of *multi-winner elections*.

A straightforward mechanism for selecting multiple candidates based on popular preferences is *approval voting*: Voters can signal endorsement for any number of the candidates, and a fixed-size group that receives the highest number of votes is elected, if necessary after ties are resolved by an auxiliary mechanism. This system is easily implemented and communicated to the voters, yet it has at least one drawback in situations where votes are cast as part of the self-organization of communities: When there is a large overlap between voters and candidates, agents in the intersection may be inclined to vote strategically, and orthogonal to an honest evaluation of their peers. To visualize the issue, imagine two highly regarded candidates in a poll that allows for only one winner. Both candidates may hold the honest opinion that their respective contender would be well-suited for the position. So, suppose that they indeed vote for each other. After the ballots are counted, it may turn out that both candidates received the top number of votes. As the tie is resolved, be it by means of a fair coin toss or by a repetition of the poll with just the two candidates remaining, both of them have to fear losing the election by a hair's breadth. Now, suppose that one of the two anticipated this possible outcome, and abstained from voting for their likely contender. Then, the situation is quite different: The candidate who misrepresented their true valuation is rewarded and wins the election by one vote.

In this chapter, we study strategy-proof mechanisms for aggregating votes in the extreme case where the sets of voters and candidates are equal. Under such a mechanism, no participant may be able to influence their own chance of being selected through a modification of the votes that they cast. This axiomatic notion of strategy-proofness is known as *impartiality* in the literature. Unfortunately, impartiality is incompatible with the concept of optimality that underlies approval voting: A mechanism that simply selects (at random from) a subset of agents that receives the highest number of votes is not impartial, as illustrated by the example above. On the other hand, any mechanism that disregards the votes entirely and selects winners at random or according to a predefined order over the candidates is trivially impartial, but anything but optimal, and most likely not in the voters' best interest. A natural question is whether there can be a trade-off between these two extremes: a mechanism that is impartial yet selects—either in expectation or in the worst case—a set of agents that receives a nontrivial fraction α of the highest voted subset of the allowed size. We call such a mechanism α -optimal and refer to α as a *performance guarantee*.

It is sensible to distinguish two variants of α -optimal impartial mechanisms. On the one hand, the mechanism may be allowed to incorporate randomness in its decision: If k out of n agents are to be selected, the latter represented by the integers $[n]$, then the mechanism outputs (or is allowed to sample from) a probability distribution $p: \mathcal{P}_k([n]) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ over the candidate subsets of size k . This distribution induces a vector $x \in [0, 1]^n$ with

$$x_i := \sum_{S \in \mathcal{P}_k([n]): i \in S} p(S)$$

for all $i \in [n]$ such that $\sum_{i=1}^n x_i = k$ and such that the probability of agent $i \in [n]$ being selected into the winning set is x_i .¹ Impartiality is then understood with respect to the vector x : For all $i \in [n]$, x_i must be independent of the vote of agent i . On the other hand, one may require the voting mechanism to be deterministic. Then, it outputs just one winning set $S \subseteq [n]$ as a function of the votes or, equivalently, a binary vector x where $x_i = 1$ implies that agent i is selected.

Determinism is a natural axiom in its own right: Candidates may be reluctant to accept a loss if it could have been due to bad luck, or even caused by a manipulation of the odds that may be difficult to detect from the random outcome alone. But, it comes at a steep price: Determinism is incompatible with α -optimality for any $\alpha > 0$ when we continue to require that $|S| = k$, which impedes in particular the case of $k = 1$. To see the latter, consider the example of just two agents voting for each other, first described by Alon, Fischer, Procaccia, and Tennenholtz [5]: A deterministic mechanism tasked to select one agent has to break symmetry by selecting one of the agents with probability one, say the first agent. Now, impartiality demands that the first agent must remain selected if the second agent retracts its vote, as otherwise the second agent could profit from such a change in strategy. But then, the mechanism selects an agent receiving no votes, while another agent receiving a nonzero number of votes exists. Thus, the mechanism is at most 0-optimal. Clearly, the situation does not improve if the mechanism is allowed to select *at most*

¹Vice versa, any vector $x \in [0, 1]^n$ with $\sum_{i=1}^n x_i = k$ can be mapped to a permissible distribution over $\mathcal{P}_k([n])$ that induces this vector [13, Lemma 2.1]. While this mapping is not necessarily unique, a natural choice would be to report the unique distribution with maximum entropy, which is closest to the uniform distribution among all distributions consistent with x (according to the Kullback–Leibler distance) and can be computed by a convex program [16, p. 362].

Figure 5.1: Performance guarantee of the deterministic impartial mechanism proposed in this chapter for selecting $k \geq 2\sqrt{n} + (k \bmod 2)$ out of n agents. The guarantee is better for even k ; this equalizes in the limit.

one agent, as it still needs to select one of two agents voting for each other, or else is 0-optimal immediately. It follows that nothing can be done, by a deterministic mechanism and in the worst case, when the task is to select up to one agent.²

Remarkably, even when $k \geq 2$ agents must be selected, Alon et al. [5] prove that no α -optimal deterministic mechanism with $\alpha > 0$ exists. But, no less surprising, the authors show that a positive performance guarantee is indeed achievable for $k \geq 2$ when the mechanism is allowed to select k or fewer agents in each instance, which we refer to as the *inexact selection* setting. Their simple mechanism only ensures that one or two agents receiving a vote are selected whenever any vote is cast, and is just $\Theta(1/(nk))$ -optimal as a result. Bjelde, Fischer, and Klimm [13] respond with a $1/k$ -optimal deterministic impartial mechanism for this relaxed setting, which remained the best known approximation ratio so far. Both the proof of concept by Alon et al. and the refined mechanism by Bjelde et al. order the agents in an arbitrary but fixed way and select one agent in a forward and another agent in a backward pass, each time considering a different set of votes. Both mechanisms can select the same agent twice, and the upper bound by Alon et al. implies that this event cannot be averted while maintaining both impartiality and approximate optimality.

Declaring just one or two winners in an election held to populate a parliament or to invite speakers to a conference might not live up to expected standards. One may thus wonder whether the inexact selection setting is more powerful than the strict one at scale, or whether $k = 2$ remains

²A randomized mechanism for $n = 2$ and $k = 1$ can achieve 1/2-optimality: The best one can do is to ignore the votes and select the winner uniformly at random in all instances.

the only tractable case for deterministic mechanisms. A look at the best known upper bound is inconclusive in this regard: Sitting at $(k-1)/k$ [13], it is tight for $k=2$, but the gap could hardly be larger as the selection budget k grows. In this chapter, we will narrow this gap substantially when k is large compared to n : We propose a deterministic impartial mechanism that is α -optimal for

$$\alpha = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\lceil \frac{2n}{k} \rceil} & \text{if } k \geq 2\sqrt{n} \text{ is even,} \\ \frac{k-1}{k \lceil \frac{2n}{k-1} \rceil} & \text{if } k \geq 2\sqrt{n} + 1 \text{ is odd.} \end{cases}$$

In particular, the mechanism approaches a performance guarantee of $\alpha = 1/4$ when selecting at most half and $\alpha = 1/3$ when selecting at most two thirds of the agents in the limit of $n \rightarrow \infty$. It is best behaved when $2n/k \leq k/2$ are both integral: Then, the mechanism achieves a ratio of $\alpha = k/(2n)$, which we show is attained for a worst-case instance, and selects to this end at least $k/2$ distinct agents. The applicable range of the mechanism and the corresponding performance guarantee are visualized in Figure 5.1.

Among the deterministic mechanisms that provide a nonzero performance guarantee and allow multiple nominations per voter, our mechanism is notably the first that is able to handle votes carrying an arbitrary nonnegative weight. It does so without a loss in the performance guarantee, which is defined in terms of the maximum weight received by any k -subset of the agents. This allows agents to assign a rating to one another as opposed to merely signaling approval, which can be relevant, for instance, in a peer review setting where submissions are scored on a discrete scale ranging from a clear rejection to a judgement of excellence. The mechanism can further be adapted to the *impartial assignment* setting, where the goal is to select agents into a number of disjoint teams. Here, we lose a factor of two in the approximation guarantee, which is measured in terms of the optimal sum of weights over all feasible assignments.

Chapter outline

We first discuss prior and related work in Section 5.1. Mathematical preliminaries pertinent to this chapter only are then introduced in Section 5.2. In Section 5.3, we lay the foundation for the proposed mechanism by showing the existence of a certain set system that we will use to redundantly partition the agents. Section 5.4 then makes use of this construction to state the mechanism and prove lower and upper bounds on its performance. In Section 5.5, we discuss its extension to the impartial assignment setting.

Bibliographic remark. The results presented in this chapter, unless attributed otherwise, are joint work with Javier Cembrano and Svenja M. Griesbach and have previously been published in the *Proceedings of the 19th Conference on Web and Internet Economics* [27]. An extended version appeared in the *ACM Transactions on Economics and Computation* [28].

5.1 Related work

Deterministic selection. The study of deterministic and impartial mechanisms for selecting (at most) k out of n agents in an approximately optimal way—as discussed in the introduction and

summarized in the following—has been initiated by Alon, Fischer, Procaccia, and Tennenholtz [5]. Agents in this setting can signal approval for any subset of the other agents. The authors consider the parameterized axiom of α -optimality, which poses a lower bound of α on the worst case ratio between the number of votes received by the selected subset and the maximum number received by any subset of size k . They provide a strong impossibility result for the *exact selection* setting, namely that every mechanism selecting exactly k agents in every instance is at most 0-optimal. On the other hand, they initiate the study of *inexact* mechanisms by showing that nonzero guarantees are possible when fewer than k agents may be selected on a per-instance basis. Bjelde, Fischer, and Klimm [13] capitalize on this fact and give a refined mechanism coined *bidirectional permutation* that, while still selecting at most two agents regardless of $k \geq 2$, is $1/k$ -optimal. The authors additionally show that no mechanism can be more than $(k-1)/k$ -optimal, providing a first upper bound for the inexact setting and proving their own mechanism optimal for $k = 2$.

Randomized selection. In addition to their work on deterministic mechanisms, Alon et al. [5] provide initial bounds for the randomized setting, where α refers to the worst-case *expected* performance ratio over all possible polls. On the positive side, they introduce the *m-partition mechanism* that first assigns agents uniformly at random to one of m partitions, and then selects k/m top agents from each partition (up to random rounding) while counting only votes coming from agents in a different partition. For a suitable choice of m , this mechanism has a performance guarantee of $1/4$ when $k = 1$ agent should be selected, and $1 - O(1/\sqrt[3]{k})$ in general. On the negative side, the authors give respective upper bounds of $1/2$ and $1 - \Omega(1/k^2)$.

Fischer and Klimm [48] match the upper bound of $1/2$ for the single-selection setting. Their *permutation mechanism* iterates over the agents in a random order, passing the metaphorical crown to the first agent that matches or surpasses the current contender's score. This score is based on all votes that the new agent receives from agents considered previously, excluding the current contender. The authors further consider a restricted setting in which no agent may abstain from casting a vote. Here, they show that the permutation mechanism is at least $67/108 \approx 0.62$ and at most $2/3$ -optimal, and that no impartial mechanism can beat a guarantee of $\alpha = 3/4$, for $n = 3$ agents, or $\alpha = (3n-1)/4n$, for $n \geq 4$. Bousquet et al. [15] study the permutation mechanism in the limit where the incoming nominations of the top-voted agent tend to infinity, and show that it is $(3/4 - o(1))$ -optimal in this setting. They then close the gap by proposing an asymptotically $(1 - o(1))$ -optimal mechanism for single-selection, thus illustrating that the difficult instances for multiplicative performance guarantees are those in which the leading number of votes is small.

Bjelde et al. [13], besides their work on deterministic mechanisms, provide an array of improved bounds also for the randomized setting. Somewhat surprisingly, also here selecting fewer than the allowed number of agents is beneficial: For selecting (up to) $k = 2$ out of $n = 3$ agents, they show that no exact mechanism achieves a guarantee better than $\alpha = 2/3$, while a $3/4$ -optimal inexact mechanism exists. For $k = 2$ and n arbitrary, the authors prove that a randomized version of their (inexact) bidirectional permutation mechanism is at least $2/3$ -optimal, and they give a $7/12$ -optimal exact mechanism that utilizes both partitions and permutations. Bjelde et al. then extend this concept to general k via the *k-partition with permutation* mechanism, which is exact and has a performance guarantee that approaches $\alpha = 1 - 1/e \approx 0.63$ as k grows. Finally, they

provide an upper bound of $(k + 1)/(k + 2)$, which holds already for the inexact setting.

Cembrano, Fischer, and Klimm [26] analyze the single-nomination and single-selection setting: every agent casts exactly one vote to determine a single winner. This special case was first studied in the work of Holzman and Moulin [65] discussed below. Here, Cembrano et al. show that the permutation mechanism is in fact $2/3$ -optimal, matching its upper bound in the more general no-abstentions setting. However, they show further that the permutation mechanism is not best possible by interpolating between three mechanisms to achieve a lower bound of $2105/3147 \approx 0.669$. This result is accompanied by a new upper bound of $76/105 \approx 0.72$ for the setting studied, improving upon a side result of $35/48 \approx 0.73$ in Fischer and Klimm’s earlier paper [48].

Additive guarantees. Motivated by the observation that instances providing upper bounds on the multiplicative approximation ratio feature top-voted agents that receive few votes, Caragiannis, Christodoulou, and Protopapas [21] initiate the study of additive guarantees: A mechanism is α -additive if the number of votes of the selected subset plus α is at least the number of votes of the optimal k -subset. The authors also consider the single-selection setting, and study both the single-nomination and the unlimited votes variant. In the former case, they give a randomized mechanism that achieves an additive performance guarantee of $\Theta(\sqrt{n})$. For multiple nominations, they propose another mechanism that is $\Theta(n^{2/3} \log^{1/3} n)$ -additive. Both mechanisms work by sampling a multiset of designated voters and then selecting the winner among all remaining agents that receive at least one vote from a voter. The mechanisms differ in how the winner is selected from this candidate set: For the single-nomination mechanism, all votes from non-candidates are counted while in the multiple-nomination setting, only those of the designated voters count but with multiplicity. Caragiannis et al. further provide lower bounds on achievable additive guarantees both for a class of such sampling mechanisms, namely $n - 2$ for deterministic and $\Omega(\sqrt{n})$ for randomized mechanisms, and of $\alpha \geq 3$ for deterministic mechanisms in general. In subsequent work [22], the authors incorporate prior information and study a deterministic mechanism that breaks ties in favor of a default agent that is expected to perform well.

Cembrano, Fischer, Hannon, and Klimm [24] interpolate between the single and multiple-nomination settings by considering an upper bound of $O(n^\kappa)$ on the number of votes cast by each of the n agents, where $\kappa \in [0, 1]$. Notably, they introduce a deterministic mechanism whose impartiality is non-obvious, and they show that it is $O(n^{(1+\kappa)/2})$ -additive. This matches the performance guarantee of $O(\sqrt{n})$ provided by Caragiannis et al. in the single-nomination setting, which is a special case of $\kappa = 0$, but gives the trivial upper bound of $O(n)$ for $\kappa = 1$. However, the authors also strengthen the corresponding lower bound of Caragiannis et al. and show that no deterministic mechanism can, in fact, achieve an additive performance guarantee that is better than $n - 1$ in the case of unbounded nominations, which in turn is achieved already by the mechanism that selects a winner independently of the votes. Additionally, Cembrano et al. provide a lower bound of $\alpha \geq 3$ for the single-nomination setting.

Peer review. A natural extension of the multiple-nomination setting allows for votes to be weighted. The primary motivation for this adaptation is a peer review process, where researchers assess and rate each other’s submissions on a point scale. Inspired by a peer review pilot for project proposals of the U.S. National Science Foundation, Kurokawa, Lev, Morgenstern, and

Procaccia [77] study a setup where each agent making a submission has to review and rank m competing submissions (in such a way that each submission receives m reviews), which translates to a score of $m - 1$ points for the first and zero points for the last rank. The authors propose an inexact and randomized impartial mechanism that provides a multiplicative performance guarantee of $k/(k + m)$ with respect to an abstract model of the pilot mechanism, where k is the number of funded projects. Aziz, Lev, Mattei, Rosenschein, and Walsh [9] study a partition-based mechanism for the same setting that uses normalization and randomized rounding to aggregate the evaluations, which they compare to existing methods in a simulation. Mattei, Turrini, and Zhydkov [88] propose a monotonic and impartial mechanism for the same setting that selects roughly k agents in expectation, and also evaluate it experimentally. The authors together with Lev [79] extend this work to a setting with unreliable reviewers, whose impact is reduced by a weighting of their scores. Dhull, Jecmen, Kothari, and Shah [38] study partition-based impartial mechanisms that maximize the reviewers' expertise with respect to the assigned submissions. On the negative side, the authors identify fundamental limitations on the achievable assignment quality, and they prove computational hardness of finding optimal assignments for each instance. On the positive side, they propose two polynomial-time mechanisms that deal optimally with worst-case instances.

Compatibility with other axioms. Impartiality was first introduced as a desirable axiom in the context of a fair division problem by De Clippel, Moulin, and Tideman [36]. The authors consider the task of distributing a divisible resource among agents who maintain an opinion about the relative amount that everyone else should receive, but who may misreport it in order to receive a larger share themselves. They seek a mechanism that is impartial, here implying that the share that any agent receives is independent of that agent's reported valuations, and *consensual*, implying that exactly consistent valuations are propagated through the mechanism. Despite the leniency of the consensuality axiom, De Clippel et al. show that the unique impartial and consensual mechanism for three agents distributes strictly less than the available amount of the resource whenever the agents' reports are inconsistent. For four or more agents, they give a family of mechanisms that satisfy both axioms while always distributing the entire amount of the resource, and in a way that treats the agents symmetrically with respect to their index.³ Tideman and Plassmann [127] provide intuition for these rules in a follow-up paper.

Holzman and Moulin [65] study a single-winner election setting where each agent casts exactly one vote for one of its peers, motivated by the scenario of an award nomination. They show that for $n \geq 7$ agents, impartiality is compatible jointly with *monotonicity*, the property that the selected agent remains selected when it receives additional votes, and *full influence*, implying that any agent can influence whether any other agent is declared the winner for some suited configuration of the remaining votes. Full influence can further be strengthened to the *full pivot* axiom, meaning that every agent influences the race between each pair of other agents in some instance, for $n \geq 13$. On the flip side, Holzman and Moulin prove that impartiality is not compatible with both positive and negative unanimity at the same time, which respectively imply that an agent receiving the vote of every other agent is always selected while an agent receiving no vote is never selected.

³If the agents' identifiers are permuted, the output changes accordingly; also known as *name independence* [83].

Tamura and Ohseto [124] relax the setting of Holzman and Moulin: They maintain that each agent casts exactly one vote but allow for the adaptive selection of multiple winners. The authors introduce the *plurality with runners-up* mechanism, which selects all top-voted agents and, if there is just one top-voted agent, additionally all agents who received one less vote than this agent and voted for it. They show that for $n \geq 4$, this index-symmetric mechanism satisfies both positive and negative unanimity, contrasting with the impossibility result in the single-selection setting. In follow-up work, Tamura [123] shows that it also satisfies monotonicity and another symmetry axiom called *anonymity*, which implies that the source of a (non-self) nomination is not relevant, and that fulfilling these axioms in combination with impartiality and index-symmetry renders the mechanism unique up to mechanisms that select a superset of the winners. Tamura and Ohseto further propose an asymmetric variant of plurality with runners-up that utilizes a fixed order of the agents to ensure that at most two winners are selected. Cembrano, Fischer, and Klimm [25] extend this second variant and allow for up to d votes instead of exactly one. Their mechanism selects at most $d + 1$ winners who are again either top-voted agents or receive one vote less. For the extreme case of $d = n - 1$, they strengthen this bound and show that it is possible to avoid selecting all n agents. On the negative side, the authors prove that no impartial mechanism exists that only selects top-voted agents.

Mackenzie [83], like Tamura, characterizes impartial mechanism in terms of symmetry axioms satisfied by them, though again in the single-selection setting introduced by Holzman and Moulin. The author shows that any two of the three studied symmetries together imply the third under impartiality, and that an impartial mechanism satisfying all three is a convex combination of two simple rules that pick some agent at random and consider only that agent's nomination. The first such rule, called *uniform random dictatorship*, is further characterized by being the unique impartial mechanism satisfying both anonymity and negative unanimity. Finally, Edelman and Por [44] give another characterization of uniform random dictatorship in which anonymity is replaced with a combination of three other axioms.

5.2 Preliminaries

We shall first make the concept of an impartial mechanism formal and introduce discrete structures that we will use to construct ours.

5.2.1 Weighted selection mechanisms

A weighted poll can be represented by a nonnegatively edge-weighted directed graph without loops or, equivalently, by a nonnegative square matrix with zero diagonal.

Definition 5.1: Poll matrices. We write

$$\mathcal{A}_n := \left\{ A \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^{n \times n} \mid \sum_{i=1}^n A_{i,i} = 0 \right\}$$

for the set of n -agent polls.

In a poll $A \in \mathcal{A}_n$, agent $i \in [n]$ assigns a score of $A_{i,j}$ to agent $j \in [n]$. In principle, it would be possible to allow agents to cast a vote for themselves, thus permitting positive diagonal entries in A . However, under an impartial mechanism, these votes could only influence the selection of *other* agents, rendering them redundant with respect to external nominations.

Aggregating the incoming votes yields the score of an agent.

Definition 5.2: Score. Let $A \in \mathcal{A}_n$ and $R, S \subseteq [n]$. We write

$$\sigma_R(S; A) := \sum_{(i,j) \in R \times S} A_{i,j}$$

for the *score* of the agents in S coming from agents in R , and $\sigma(S; A)$ short for $\sigma_{[n]}(S; A)$. We omit the weight matrix A whenever it is clear from the context, and we write j short for $S = \{j\}$ in the above definitions. In particular, $\sigma(j)$ is the total score of agent j .

In particular, we are interested in highest-scoring subsets of agents.

Definition 5.3: Optimal set. Let $n, k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ with $k < n$. For $A \in \mathcal{A}_n$, we let

$$\text{OPT}_k(A) := \operatorname{argmax}_{S \subseteq [n]: |S|=k} \sigma(S; A)$$

denote an arbitrary set with the largest score among all k -subsets of agents.

The following notion is useful to argue about impartiality.

Definition 5.4: Remaining votes. Let $A \in \mathcal{A}_n$ be a poll. For an agent $i \in [n]$, we write A_{-i} for the rectangular matrix obtained from removing the i -th row of A .

We are now ready to formalize the object of study.

Definition 5.5: Selection mechanism. A (deterministic and inexact) (n, k) -*selection mechanism* is a function $f: \mathcal{A}_n \rightarrow \mathcal{P}([n])$ such that $|f(A)| \leq k$ for all $A \in \mathcal{A}_n$. It is *impartial* if, for every pair of polls $A, A' \in \mathcal{A}_n$ and for all agents $i \in [n]$, it obeys

$$A_{-i} = A'_{-i} \implies f(A) \cap \{i\} = f(A') \cap \{i\}.$$

We further call the mechanism α -*optimal* for $\alpha \in [0, 1]$, if, for all $A \in \mathcal{A}_n$, it satisfies

$$\frac{\sigma(f(A))}{\sigma(\text{OPT}_k(A))} \geq \alpha.$$

In the analysis, we will make use of lexicographic comparisons to express tie-breaking rules.

Definition 5.6: Lexicographic comparison. For scalars $a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2 \in \mathbb{R}$, it is $(a_1, a_2) < (b_1, b_2)$ if and only if either $a_1 < b_1$ holds or $a_1 = b_1$ and $a_2 < b_2$ both hold.

In particular, we will take the argmax over pairs where the first entry denotes a score while the second entry breaks ties when the scores are equal.

5.2.2 Hypergraphs

Although our mechanism will eventually be stated in terms of simple graphs, basic hypergraph theory will be useful in its derivation.

Definition 5.7: Hypergraph. A hypergraph is a pair $H = (V, E)$ where V is a finite set of *vertices* and where $E \subseteq \mathcal{P}(V)$ is a multiset of (*hyper-*)*edges*.

The property of regularity is defined analogously to that of graphs. Recall that we write $\mu(X)$ for the cardinality of a multiset X and $\mu_X(e)$ for the multiplicity of an element $e \in X$.

Definition 5.8: Regularity. A hypergraph $H = (V, E)$ is *d-regular* if each vertex is contained in exactly d edges, formally $\mu(\{e \in E \mid v \in e\}) = d$ for all $v \in V$

Uniformity is an analogous property pertinent to edges.

Definition 5.9: Uniformity. A hypergraph $H = (V, E)$ is *b-uniform* if each edge contains exactly b vertices, that is $|e| = b$ for all $e \in E$.

Note that a 2-uniform hypergraph without repeated edges is just a (simple) graph. We need one more structural property.

Definition 5.10: Linearity. A hypergraph $H = (V, E)$ is *linear* if two distinct edges intersect in at most one vertex, $|e_1 \cap e_2| \leq 1$ for all $e_1, e_2 \in E$ with $\mu_E(e_1) > 1$ or $e_1 \neq e_2$.

Finally, hypergraphs feature a natural notion of duality, which should not be confused with the dual of a planar graph.

Definition 5.11: Dual graph. The *dual* of a hypergraph $H = (V, E)$ is given by $H^* := (E, X)$ where $X := \{\{e \in E \mid v \in e\} \mid v \in V\}$ is a multiset of sets.

One may think of the dual graph in terms of the vertex–edge incidence matrix, which is transposed when taking the dual. Note that the dual graph may have repeated edges and loops even if the original graph does not have either.

5.2.3 Graph colorings

A fundamental concept in graph theory is assigning colors to vertices such that no adjacent vertices share the same color.

Definition 5.12: Vertex coloring. A vertex b -coloring of a graph $G = (V, E)$ is a function $\pi: V \rightarrow [b]$. It is *feasible*, if $\pi(u) \neq \pi(v)$ for all $u, v \in V$ such that $u, v \in e$ for some $e \in E$.

Likewise, one can color the edges of a graph.

Definition 5.13: Edge coloring. An edge b -coloring of a graph $G = (V, E)$ is a function $\pi: E \rightarrow [b]$. It is *feasible*, if $\pi(e_1) \neq \pi(e_2)$ for all $e_1, e_2 \in E$ with $e_1 \cap e_2 \neq \emptyset$.

We will make use of the following classical result.

Theorem 5.14 (König [75]). *If G is a bipartite graph with maximum vertex degree Δ , then there exists an edge Δ -coloring of G .*

The statement is true for any, not necessarily bipartite graph if Δ is replaced by $\Delta + 1$ by Vizing's theorem [135], and for no graph if Δ is replaced by $\Delta - 1$. While we later construct a bipartite graph, any Δ -edge-colorable graph with maximum degree Δ , known as a *class 1* graph, could be used.

5.3 Partition systems

Partitions have been a fundamental building block for *randomized* impartial mechanisms, as the fact that the resulting procedure is strategy-proof is typically obvious. In the deterministic setting, however, the technique has not been rewarding so far. Let us briefly recapitulate the partition mechanism of Alon et al. [5] in the single-selection setting of $k = 1$ and for uniformly weighted votes, and see why this approach fails in the deterministic realm. First, the mechanism assigns each of the n agents uniformly and independently at random to one of two partitions, $S_1 \dot{\cup} S_2 = [n]$. If one of the partitions is empty, the winner is selected uniformly at random. Otherwise, we may refer to S_1 as the *voter* and to S_2 as the *candidate* partition, and the mechanism selects the agent $\arg \max_{i \in S_2} (\sigma_{S_1}(i), i)$. As anticipated, impartiality is clear: Apart from agents' indices, which are used for tie-breaking, only the votes of agents in S_1 influence the outcome, but no agent in S_1 can be selected. It is also not difficult to develop an intuition that this mechanism is at least 1/4-optimal [5]: In expectation, half of the votes are invisible to the mechanism as they are cast among agents within a partition, while half of the remaining votes are not seen as they are cast from a candidate to a voter. The mechanism selects an agent receiving a maximum number of visible votes, which is not less than the number of visible votes for an agent that receives the most votes overall. In expectation, the latter agent's overall score is four times its visible score.

In the deterministic setting, the above argument is of little use. Indeed, an adversary may ensure that all agents receiving any votes are placed together in the voter partition, so that the mechanism is forced to select an agent receiving none. The situation does not improve in the multi-selection setting, either. Here, the mechanism of Alon et al. selects an equal number of agents from all partitions, up to random rounding. An adversarial instance now features only votes among agents appearing in the same partition, so that the mechanism still sees none of them, and it orders agents such that those picked by the tie-breaking rule receive no vote.

The (n, k) -selection mechanism developed in the following is based on a system of bipartitions of the agents, each of which is responsible for the selection of one agent. The key ingredient that makes it applicable to the deterministic setting is redundancy: Every agent is a candidate exactly twice, and competes against a disjoint set of contenders each time. Like this, we ensure that the mechanism is able to see every vote at least once: If a nomination is hidden for the first candidacy of an agent, then only because it is coming from a contender, who is bound to be a voter when the first agent re-appears as a candidate. Of course, repeated candidacy runs the risk of selecting agents multiple times, at the expense of their second-best contenders. But, we know from the fundamental impossibility result of Alon et al. that sometimes selecting fewer agents than the budget permits is unavoidable if a nonzero performance guarantee is desired, and this is precisely what a duplicate selection leads to. On the other hand, we can (and need to) limit the extent of the problem simply by removing duplicate votes cast between agents that do not appear as candidates together, which does not diminish impartiality.

In this section, we establish the existence of a system of k bipartitions with the above discussed property that each of the n agents competes exactly twice and with disjoint competitors. For now, we make further the simplifying assumption that n and k are such that all candidate sets have equal size $b = 2n/k$. As we will show in Section 5.4, this restriction not too harmful as we may fill smaller partitions with dummy agents who cast and receive no votes and whose selection is ignored. We call a collection of partitions meeting these requirements a *balanced partition system*.

A partition of the agents into voters and candidates is fully described by either set. A balanced partition system may thus be written as a family E of candidate subsets of the set of agents $V := [n]$. In other words, we may represent it by a hypergraph $H = (V, E)$ without repeated edges, where each $e \in E$ is the candidate set of a single partition. To fulfill the requirements of a balanced partition system, H has to be 2-regular, so that every agent appears in exactly two candidate sets, and b -uniform, so that all candidate sets $e \in E$ have the same size $|e| = b$. The remaining requirement that no two agents compete twice against each other, formally $|e_1 \cap e_2| \leq 1$ for all $e_1, e_2 \in E$ with $e_1 \neq e_2$, translates to H being linear. The following observation implies that we can represent a balanced partition system also by a simple graph.

Lemma 5.15. *A hypergraph is 2-regular and linear if and only if its dual is a simple graph.*

Proof. Let $H = (V, E)$ be a 2-regular and linear hypergraph. Its dual graph is $H^* = (E, X)$ where $X = \{\{e \in E \mid v \in e\} \mid v \in V\}$ is a multiset of sets. We show that H^* is a graph, meaning that H^* is 2-uniform and has no repeated edges. Let $x \in X$. Then, $x = \{e \in E \mid v \in e\}$ for some $v \in V$. Since H is 2-regular, we have $|x| = 2$ for all $x \in X$, so H^* is 2-uniform. It remains to show that H^* has no repeated edges. Assume towards a contradiction that there is an $x \in X$ with multiplicity at least two. Then, there are $v_1 \neq v_2 \in V$ with $x = \{e \in E \mid v_1 \in e\} = \{e \in E \mid v_2 \in e\}$. Since H is 2-regular, again $|x| = 2$ holds. Let thus $e_1 \neq e_2 \in E$ with $v_1, v_2 \in e_1$ and $v_1, v_2 \in e_2$. Then, $\{v_1, v_2\} \subseteq e_1 \cap e_2$, hence $|e_1 \cap e_2| \geq 2$ contradicts that H is linear.

Let next $G = (V, E)$ be a graph. Its dual graph is a hypergraph $G^* = (E, X)$ with X defined as before. We show that G^* is 2-regular and linear. To this end, let $e \in E$ be a vertex of G^* . Since G is 2-uniform, it is $e = \{v_1, v_2\}$ with $v_1 \neq v_2$ and thus

$$\begin{aligned} \deg_{G^*}(e) &= \mu(\{x \in X \mid e \in x\}) \\ &= \mu(\{x \in \{\{f \in E \mid v \in f\} \mid v \in V\} \mid e \in x\}) \\ &= \mu(\{\{f \in E \mid v \in f\} \mid v \in V \wedge e \in \{f \in E \mid v \in f\}\}) \\ &= \mu(\{\{f \in E \mid v \in f\} \mid v \in V \wedge v \in e\}) \\ &= \mu(\{\{f \in E \mid v_1 \in f\}, \{f \in E \mid v_2 \in f\}\}) = 2, \end{aligned}$$

so G^* is 2-regular. Finally, assume towards a contradiction that G^* is not linear. Then, there are $v_1 \neq v_2 \in V$ such that $x_1 := \{e \in E \mid v_1 \in e\} \in X$ and $x_2 := \{e \in E \mid v_2 \in e\} \in X$, possibly $x_1 = x_2$ as X is a multiset, and $|x_1 \cap x_2| \geq 2$. Since G is simple, E is a set, so there are $e_1 \neq e_2 \in E$ with $v_1, v_2 \in e_1$ and $v_1, v_2 \in e_2$. Since G is 2-uniform, $e_1 = \{v_1, v_2\} = e_2$, a contradiction to G being simple. ■

By Lemma 5.15 and the fact that order and size as well as degree and rank are dual for hypergraphs, there is a one-to-one correspondence between balanced partition systems where n agents

Figure 5.2: The construction of Lemma 5.16 for $k = 12$ vertices and degree $b \in [6]$. Every edge represents an agent and every vertex corresponds to a partition. A vertex and an edge are incident if the corresponding agent is in the corresponding candidate set. In graph theory terms, one obtains the disjoint edges $(k/2)P_2$ for $b = 1$, the cycle C_k for $b = 2$, the prism $Y_{k/2}$ for $b = 3$, and the complete bipartite graph $K_{b,b}$ for $b = k/2$.

are distributed among k candidate sets of size b on the one hand, and b -regular simple graphs of order k and size n on the other hand. In the simple graph representation, edges correspond to agents while incident vertices correspond to candidate sets that the agents appear in.

In the proof of approximate optimality presented in Section 5.4, we will bound the weight of the agents $S \subseteq [n]$ selected by our mechanism for some poll $A \in \mathcal{A}_n$ from below by the weight $\sigma(U)$ of a suited subset $U \subseteq \text{OPT}_k(A)$. More precisely, we will partition the set of top-rated agents $\text{OPT}_k(A)$ into b many subsets with the property that no two agents within the same subset compete, and U will be a subset of maximum weight. From this definition, one obtains $\sigma(U) \geq \sigma(\text{OPT}_k(A))/b$ rather easily. On the other hand, the fact that $\sigma(S) \geq \sigma(U)$ —leading to a performance guarantee of $1/b = k/(2n)$ —will be derived from the following observation: Whenever the mechanism does not select an agent $i \in U$, then only because it recovers the “missed” score $\sigma(i)$ from the votes that lead to the selection of the two agents that it selects instead of i . We already established that these two agents are distinct when a balanced partition system is used, which we will make use of in the analysis. But, we still need to ensure that a partition of the top-rated agents into b many non-competing subsets always exists. We call a partition system that guarantees this *robust*. In terms of the hypergraph representation H , where vertices correspond to agents and hyperedges to candidate sets, a sufficient condition for robustness is that any subgraph of H induced by k vertices can be partitioned into b many internally independent sets. In terms of the b -regular dual graph $G := H^*$, this condition is equivalent to the existence of an edge coloring with b colors for every subgraph induced by k edges: the edges of any one color do not share a vertex, which corresponds to vertices not sharing a hyperedge in H . A sufficient condition for this property of G is that G itself admits an edge b -coloring, which can be “inherited” to any induced subgraph. In other words, it is sufficient for our purposes that the graph G defining the balanced partition system is a class 1 graph. A sufficient condition for this, in turn, is that G is bipartite [75].

Bipartite and b -regular graphs of even order k and size n exist for all $b = 2n/k$ with $b \leq k/2$. A simple construction is shown in Figure 5.2. Informally, the graph is obtained as follows: Align the k vertices in two columns, resulting in $k/2$ rows. Then, for every row $i \in [k/2]_0$ and for all $\ell \in [b]_0$, both indexed from zero, connect the left-hand side vertex in row i with the right-hand side vertex in row $(i + \ell) \bmod (k/2)$. The following lemma formalizes this.

Lemma 5.16. *Let $b, k, n \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ with $k' := k/2 \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ and $b = 2n/k \leq k'$. Then, $G = (V, E)$ with $V := [k]_0$ and*

$$E := \{\{i, k' + ((i + \ell) \bmod k')\} \mid i \in [k']_0 \wedge \ell \in [b]_0\}$$

is a b -regular bipartite graph of order k and size n .

Proof. The order of G is $|V| = |[k]_0| = k$ as claimed. To see that G is bipartite, let $\{u, v\} \in E$. Then, $\{u, v\} = \{i, j\}$ with $j := k' + ((i + \ell) \bmod k')$ for some $i \in [k']_0$ and $\ell \in [b]_0$. It follows from

$$i < k' \leq k' + ((i + \ell) \bmod k') = j \quad (5.1)$$

that $u < k'$ if and only if $v \geq k'$. Hence, a bipartition of the vertices is given by $V = V_1 \dot{\cup} V_2$ with $V_1 := [k']_0$ and $V_2 := [k]_0 \setminus [k']_0$.

To prove that the size of G is indeed n , we first show that $f: [k']_0 \times [b]_0 \rightarrow V \times V$ with

$$f(i, \ell) := (i, k' + ((i + \ell) \bmod k'))$$

is injective. To this end, let $f(i, \ell) = f(i', \ell')$ for some $(i, \ell), (i', \ell') \in [k']_0 \times [b]_0$. Clearly, it is $i = i'$, so it remains to show that $\ell = \ell'$. This is the case as

$$\begin{aligned} & k' + ((i + \ell) \bmod k') = k' + ((i + \ell') \bmod k') & (5.2) \\ \iff & i + \ell = i + \ell' \pmod{k'} \\ \iff & \ell = \ell' \pmod{k'}, \end{aligned}$$

which implies $\ell = \ell'$ as $0 \leq \ell, \ell' < b \leq k'$. From inequality (5.1), it follows that $f': [k']_0 \times [b]_0 \rightarrow E$ with $f'(i, \ell) := \{f(i, \ell)_1, f(i, \ell)_2\}$ is also injective, so $|E| = k'b = kb/2 = n$ as required.

For the degree, we consider each partition V_1 and V_2 separately. For $i \in V_1$, let $f_i: [b]_0 \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ with $f_i(\ell) := f(i, \ell)_2$ enumerate the neighbors of vertex i and assume that $f_i(\ell) = f_i(\ell')$ for some $\ell, \ell' \in [b]_0$. As this implies equation (5.2), we have again that $\ell = \ell'$, so also f_i is injective and $\deg(i) = b$. For $j \in V_2$, the degree of vertex j is

$$\deg(j) = |\{(i, \ell) \in [k']_0 \times [b]_0 \mid f_i(\ell) = j\}|.$$

We have that

$$\begin{aligned} & f_i(\ell) = j \\ \iff & (i + \ell) \bmod k' = j - k' \\ \iff & i = j - k' - \ell \pmod{k'} \end{aligned} \quad (5.3)$$

where the last equivalence follows from $0 \leq j - k' < k'$. Equation (5.3) has a unique solution $i \in [k']_0$ for any fixed $\ell \in [b]_0$, so also $\deg(j) = b$ and G is b -regular. ■

We condense the findings of this section in the following lemma.

Lemma 5.17. *Let $n, k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ with $k < n$ be such that $b := 2n/k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ and $b \leq k/2 \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$. Let further V be a set of agents with $|V| = n$. Then, one may form k partitions $S_1^p \dot{\cup} S_2^p = V$, $p \in [k]$, such that*

k	Number of agents n																			
	9	12	15	16	18	20	21	24	25	28	30	32	35	36	40	42	48	49	56	64
6	3
8	.	3	.	4
10	.	.	3	.	.	4	.	.	5
12	3	.	.	4	.	.	5	.	.	6
14	3	.	.	4	.	.	5	.	.	6	.	7	.	.
16	3	.	.	.	4	.	.	5	.	6	.	7	8

Table 5.1: Block size $b = 2n/k$ of a robust partition system for selecting k out of n agents, if it exists by Lemma 5.17, for small n and k . Theorem 5.18 in the next section states that there exists a deterministic impartial mechanism providing a performance guarantee of $\alpha = 1/b$ for these well-behaved pairs.

- (i) $|S_2^p| = b$ for all $p \in [k]$,
- (ii) $|S_2^p \cap S_2^q| \leq 1$ for all $p, q \in [k]$ with $p \neq q$,
- (iii) $|\{p \in [k] \mid v \in S_2^p\}| = 2$ for all $v \in V$, and
- (iv) for every $U \subseteq V$, there is a partition $\bigcup_{t \in [b]} U_t = U$ with $u \in S_2^p \Rightarrow v \notin S_2^p$ for all $t \in [b]$, $u, v \in U_t$ with $u \neq v$, and $p \in [k]$.

Proof. For n , k , and b as in the statement, Lemma 5.16 guarantees the existence of a b -regular bipartite graph $G = (X, V)$ of order $|X| = k$ and size $|V| = n$. Let $H := G^* = (V, E)$ be its dual graph. Note that H is b -uniform and has order n and size k . By Lemma 5.15, H is further 2-regular and linear. As $b \geq 2$ by definition, it follows from linearity that H has no repeated edges, thus E is a set.

We use H to form a system of partitions of V . First, enumerate E by an arbitrary but fixed bijection $\phi: [k] \rightarrow E$. Then, for every $p \in [k]$, define a candidate set $S_2^p := \phi(p)$ and the associated voter set $S_1^p := V \setminus \phi(p)$. As H is b -uniform, we have (i) by construction. As it is linear, (ii) follows. Since H is 2-regular, also (iii) holds.

It remains to show property (iv). By König's line coloring theorem [75], there exists a feasible edge b -coloring $\pi: V \rightarrow [b]$ of G . Let G' be the subgraph of G induced by an edge set $U \subseteq E$. Clearly, π restricted to U remains a feasible edge b -coloring. The dual $H' := (G')^*$ is the subgraph of H induced by the vertex set U . In terms of H' , π assigns colors to vertices. Since π restricted to U is feasible for G' , it follows from vertex–edge duality that vertices in H' are colored differently if they appear in a hyperedge together, thus π is a feasible vertex coloring for H . Define thus $U_t := \{v \in U \mid \pi(v) = t\}$ for each color $t \in [b]$. Then, the sets U_t are disjoint by definition and $\bigcup_{t \in [b]} U_t = U$ as $\pi(U) \subseteq \pi(V) \subseteq [b]$. Let finally $t \in [b]$ and $u, v \in U_t$ with $u \neq v$ and assume towards a contradiction that $u, v \in S_2^p$ for some $p \in [k]$. Then, $u, v \in \phi(p) \in E$ and $\pi(u) = t = \pi(v)$ by construction of S_2^p and U_t , contradicting that π is a feasible vertex coloring for $H = (V, E)$. ■

Table 5.1 lists small n and k fulfilling the conditions of Lemma 5.17, together with the resulting “block size” b of the candidate sets. In the following, we write $\mathcal{S}(n, k)$ for an arbitrary but fixed sequence $((S_1^p, S_2^p))_{p \in [k]}$ that satisfies the properties of Lemma 5.17.

5.4 Selection mechanism

We are prepared to propose the first partition-based deterministic impartial mechanism. The main result of this chapter is the following.

Theorem 5.18. *Let $n, k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ with $k < n$ and $k - (k \bmod 2) \geq 2\sqrt{n}$. Then, there exists an (n, k) -selection mechanism that is impartial and α -optimal for*

$$\alpha = \frac{k - (k \bmod 2)}{k \left\lceil \frac{2n}{k - (k \bmod 2)} \right\rceil}.$$

The performance guarantee of Theorem 5.18 for small n and k is depicted in Figure 5.1 on page 117. As already discussed there, our mechanism is best behaved when k is even and $b := 2n/k$ with $b \leq k/2$ is integral: Then, we can utilize a robust partition system without preprocessing the instance, wherein b is the size of the candidate partitions, and obtain a performance guarantee of $1/b = k/(2n)$. See Table 5.1 on page 129 for small n and k with this property.

The mechanism operates as follows. First, if n and k fulfill the conditions of Theorem 5.18 but not of Lemma 5.17, then we decrement k if it is odd, and we add dummy agents to increase n to the next larger value such that the conditions of Lemma 5.17 are satisfied, implying that a robust partition system exists. Then, using the adjusted values of n and k , we construct such a system comprising k pairs of voter and candidate sets, the latter of equal size $2n/k$. Recall that a robust partition system entails that each agent appears as a candidate exactly twice, but does not compete against any other agent more than once. For the second candidacy of an agent, we remove votes that are already present in its first candidacy to avoid double-counting. Finally, the mechanism selects the top scoring candidate from each partition, breaking ties in favor of agents with the larger index.⁴ The mechanism for n and k already satisfying the conditions of Lemma 5.17 is formalized by Algorithm 4. Figure 5.3 illustrates its execution for $n = 9$ and $k = 6$. We will detail the preprocessing step for adjusting n and k to permissible values later.

For the remainder of this section, whenever $n, k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ and $A \in \mathcal{A}_n$ are fixed, we write

- (S_1^p, S_2^p) for the p -th bipartition into voters S_1^p and candidates S_2^p ,
- $\triangleleft(i)$ and $\triangleright(i)$ for the indices of the first and second partition in which agent i is a candidate,
- $v_p(i)$ for the *modified score* of agent i in partition $p \in \{\triangleleft(i), \triangleright(i)\}$,
- w_p for the agent selected in the p -th partition, and
- $\text{SELECT}_k(A) = X$ for the set of all selected agents,

all as defined when Algorithm 4 returns and for all agents $i \in [n]$ and partitions $p \in [k]$. We further write $v_p(i; A)$ when A is ambiguous in the context. In the proof of the following statement, it will be particularly useful to recall that the modified score of an agent i that appears as a candidate in the p -th partition, formally $i \in S_2^p$, is simply the weight of all votes that it receives from that partition's voters, if $p = \triangleleft(i)$ marks i 's first candidacy, and the weight of all *new* votes, if $p = \triangleright(i)$ is its second candidacy.

⁴This is just a convention; any deterministic tie-breaker could be used instead.

Algorithm 4: $\text{SELECT}_k(A)$

Parameter: An even integer $k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$.
Input: A matrix $A \in \mathcal{A}_n$ with $2n/k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ and $2\sqrt{n} \leq k < n$.
Output: A set $X \subseteq [n]$ with $|X| \leq k$.

```

1  $((S_1^p, S_2^p))_{p=1}^k \leftarrow \mathcal{S}(n, k)$  // a robust partition system
2 for  $i \in [n]$  do
3    $\triangleleft(i) \leftarrow \min\{p \in [k] \mid i \in S_2^p\}$  // first partition agent  $i$  is candidate in
4    $\triangleright(i) \leftarrow \max\{p \in [k] \mid i \in S_1^p\}$  // second partition agent  $i$  is candidate in
5    $v_{\triangleleft(i)}(i) \leftarrow \sigma_{S_1^{\triangleleft(i)}}(i)$  // consider full score in first partition
6    $v_{\triangleright(i)}(i) \leftarrow \sigma_{S_1^{\triangleright(i)} \setminus S_1^{\triangleleft(i)}}(i)$  // omit duplicate votes in second partition
7  $X \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
8 for  $p \in [k]$  do // pick one winner in each partition
9    $w_p \leftarrow \arg\max_{i \in S_2^p} (v_p(i), i)$  // break ties in favor of larger index
10   $X \leftarrow X \cup \{w_p\}$ 
11 return  $X$ 

```

Proposition 5.19. *Let $n, k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ with $k < n$ be such that $b := 2n/k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ and $b \leq k/2 \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$. Then, Algorithm 4 is an impartial and $1/b$ -optimal (n, k) -selection mechanism.*

Proof. We first note that the input conditions of SELECT_k are equivalent to the conditions on n and k in the statement, as squaring both sides of $2\sqrt{n} \leq k$ and dividing by $2k$ yields $2n/k \leq k/2$. Let thus n , k , and b as in the statement.

We next argue that the mechanism is well-defined. As the conditions on n and k match those of Lemma 5.17, the robust partition system $\mathcal{S}(n, k)$ indeed exists, so line 1 is good. By property (iii) of Lemma 5.17, we have $|\{p \in [k] \mid i \in S_2^p\}| = 2$ for each agent $i \in [n]$, so further the minimum and maximum in lines 3 and 4 are well-defined, the assignments in lines 5 and 6 are well-defined and non-overlapping by $\triangleleft(i) \neq \triangleright(i)$. Further, line 9 is well-defined as $i \in S_2^p$ implies $p \in \{\triangleleft(i), \triangleright(i)\}$ and since the use of the agent's index for tie-breaking ensures that the $\arg\max$ is unique.

To see that SELECT_k is impartial, consider two polls $A, B \in \mathcal{A}_n$ and an agent $i \in [n]$ such that $A_{-i} = B_{-i}$. Assume further that $i \in \text{SELECT}_k(A)$. Then, there is a partition $p \in [k]$ such that

$$i = \arg\max_{i \in S_2^p} (v_p(i; A), i).$$

As $i \in S_2^p$ implies $i \notin S_1^p$, and $A_{-i} = B_{-i}$ by assumption, we have that $v_p(j; A) = v_p(j; B)$ for all $j \in S_2^p$. Thus, we also have that

$$i = \arg\max_{i \in S_2^p} (v_p(i; B), i),$$

and so $i \in \text{SELECT}_k(B)$. By symmetry, we conclude that $\text{SELECT}_k(A) \cap \{i\} = \text{SELECT}_k(B) \cap \{i\}$.

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 3 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 3 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 3 & 2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 2 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

A Matrix representation of A . The entry in the i -th row and j -th column is the weight of the vote cast by i for j .

B Graph representation of A . The weight of a vote is represented by the number of arrow heads.

C The $k = 6$ bipartitions. Voters are drawn in gray, losers in white, and the winner is marked by a black dot. Votes drawn thin and gray are duplicates that are ignored by the mechanism.

Figure 5.3: Example execution of $\text{SELECT}_6(A)$ for a weighted poll $A \in \mathcal{A}_9$. The selected agents have a score of $\sigma(\text{SELECT}_6(A)) = 17$ while the best subset of size $k = 6$ attains $\sigma(\text{OPT}_6(A)) = 27$, implying a $17/27 \approx 0.63$ approximation ratio for this instance. The a priori guarantee provided by Proposition 5.19 is $1/3$. Despite exceeding the guarantee, the instance illustrates two peculiarities of the mechanism: The duplicate selection of agents 3 and 8 and an instance of tie-breaking as a result of all votes being omitted in the fourth partition.

For the performance guarantee, consider a single poll $A \in \mathcal{A}_n$. First, we observe that the modified scores for an agent sum up to its total score, that is

$$v_{\triangleleft(i)}(i) + v_{\triangleright(i)}(i) = \sigma_{S_1^{\triangleleft(i)}}(i) + \sigma_{S_1^{\triangleright(i)} \setminus S_1^{\triangleleft(i)}}(i) = \sigma(i) \quad (5.4)$$

for all $i \in [n]$, since property (ii) of Lemma 5.17 implies $S_1^{\triangleleft(i)} \cup S_1^{\triangleright(i)} = [n] \setminus \{i\}$. Furthermore, the definition of w_p ensures that

$$v_p(w_p) \geq v_p(i) \quad (5.5)$$

for every $p \in [k]$ and $i \in S_2^p$. Given these two facts, we claim that

$$v_{\triangleleft(i)}(w_{\triangleleft(i)}) + v_{\triangleright(i)}(w_{\triangleright(i)}) \geq \sigma(i) \quad (5.6)$$

for all $i \in [n]$. Informally, inequality (5.6) states that the agents selected in the two partitions that agent i competes in together receive as much weight in those two partitions alone as agent i receives in total. To see this, fix $i \in [n]$. If $w_{\triangleleft(i)} = w_{\triangleright(i)} = i$, then inequality (5.6) follows immediately

from equation (5.4). If $w_{\triangleleft(i)} = i$ and $w_{\triangleright(i)} = j \neq i$, then we have that

$$v_{\triangleright(i)}(j) \geq v_{\triangleright(i)}(i) = \sigma(i) - v_{\triangleleft(i)}(i),$$

where the inequality follows from inequality (5.5) and the equality from equation (5.4). In this case, inequality (5.6) follows from substituting $i = w_{\triangleleft(i)}$ and $j = w_{\triangleright(i)}$. The case where $w_{\triangleleft(i)} = j \neq i$ and $w_{\triangleright(i)} = i$ is analogous with $\triangleleft(i)$ and $\triangleright(i)$ exchanged. Finally, if both $w_{\triangleleft(i)} \neq i$ and $w_{\triangleright(i)} \neq i$, then we have by inequality (5.5) that

$$v_{\triangleleft(i)}(w_{\triangleleft(i)}) \geq v_{\triangleleft(i)}(i) \quad \text{and} \quad v_{\triangleright(i)}(w_{\triangleright(i)}) \geq v_{\triangleright(i)}(i),$$

and inequality (5.6) follows from summing up these two inequalities and applying equality (5.4). This concludes the proof of inequality (5.6).

Now, we can relate the total score of the agents selected by the mechanism to the modified scores of the winning agents in each partition,

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma(X) &= \sum_{i \in X} \sigma(i) \\ &= \sum_{i \in X} (v_{\triangleleft(i)}(i) + v_{\triangleright(i)}(i)) \\ &\geq \sum_{i \in X} (\mathbf{1}[i = w_{\triangleleft(i)}] v_{\triangleleft(i)}(i) + \mathbf{1}[i = w_{\triangleright(i)}] v_{\triangleright(i)}(i)) \\ &= \sum_{i \in X: i = w_{\triangleleft(i)}} v_{\triangleleft(i)}(w_{\triangleleft(i)}) + \sum_{i \in X: i = w_{\triangleright(i)}} v_{\triangleright(i)}(w_{\triangleright(i)}) \\ &= \sum_{p \in [k]} v_p(w_p). \end{aligned} \tag{5.7}$$

Recall that $X = \text{SELECT}_k(A)$ denotes the selected set. The second equality follows from equation (5.4) and the inequality simply from $\mathbf{1}[\cdot] \leq 1$. The last equality follows from the fact that we select exactly one winner in each partition, which by construction is an agent that makes its first or second appearance as a candidate in it.

We finally use inequalities (5.6) and (5.7) to obtain the performance guarantee. From property (iv) of Lemma 5.17, we know that there is a partition

$$\dot{\bigcup}_{t \in [b]} U_t = \text{OPT}_k(A)$$

such that for all $t \in [b]$ and all $i, j \in U_t$ with $i \neq j$, $i \in S_2^p$ implies $j \notin S_2^p$ for all $p \in [k]$. In other words, any size k subset of agents with maximum score can be partitioned into b many groups, each of which contains only agents that pairwise do not compete. From inequality (5.7) and this fact we obtain for every $t \in [b]$ that

$$\sigma(X) \geq \sum_{p \in [k]} v_p(w_p) \geq \sum_{i \in U_t} (v_{\triangleleft(i)}(w_{\triangleleft(i)}) + v_{\triangleright(i)}(w_{\triangleright(i)})) \geq \sigma(U_t), \tag{5.8}$$

where the second inequality follows from the fact that $\{\triangleleft(i), \triangleright(i)\} \cap \{\triangleleft(j), \triangleright(j)\} = \emptyset$ for every $t \in [b]$ and all $i, j \in U_t$ with $i \neq j$, and the last one from inequality (5.6). This yields

$$\sigma(X) \geq \max_{t \in [b]} \sigma(U_t) \geq \frac{1}{b} \sum_{t \in [b]} \sigma(U_t) = \frac{1}{b} \sigma(\text{OPT}_k(A)),$$

Algorithm 5: $\text{EXTEND}_{\text{ALG},k}(A)$

Parameter: An (\hat{n}, \hat{k}) -selection mechanism ALG and an integer $k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ with $\hat{k} \leq k$.
Input: A matrix $A \in \mathcal{A}_n$ with $k < n \leq \hat{n}$.
Output: A set $X \subseteq [n]$ with $|X| \leq k$.

```

1  $\hat{A} \leftarrow \{0\}^{\hat{n} \times \hat{n}}$ 
2 for  $i, j \in [n]$  do
3    $\hat{A}_{i,j} \leftarrow A_{i,j}$  // populate upper left square
4 return  $\text{ALG}(\hat{A}) \cap [n]$  // call sub-mechanism and deselect dummy agents
```

where the first inequality is a consequence of equation (5.8), the second relates the maximum and the mean value of a set, and the equality follows from the fact that $(U_t)_{t \in [b]}$ is a partition of $\text{OPT}_k(A)$. Now, substituting $X = \text{SELECT}_k(A)$ and rearranging yields, as required,

$$\frac{\sigma(\text{SELECT}_k(A))}{\sigma(\text{OPT}_k(A))} \geq \frac{1}{b} = \frac{k}{2n}. \quad \blacksquare$$

To prove our main result, it remains to translate the bound stated in Proposition 5.19 to a scenario where $2\sqrt{n} + (k \bmod 2) \leq k < n$ holds but where at least one of the additional conditions of $2n/k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ or $k/2 \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ is not satisfied. To this end, we utilize a straightforward (n, k) -selection mechanism that extends an (\hat{n}, \hat{k}) -selection mechanism, where $\hat{k} \leq k < n \leq \hat{n}$, while maintaining impartiality and incurring only a factor of \hat{k}/k in the performance guarantee. This mechanism is described by Algorithm 5: It simply adds dummy agents that cast and receive no votes, and invokes the proper mechanism, which may assume a reduced selection budget. If that mechanism selects a dummy agent, it is removed from the winning set. In the following, when \hat{n} is fixed in addition to A (or $B \in \mathcal{A}_n$), we write \hat{A} (or \hat{B}) to refer to the matrix defined in Algorithm 5 at the time when it returns.

Lemma 5.20. *Let $\hat{k}, k, n, \hat{n} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ with $\hat{k} \leq k < n \leq \hat{n}$ be such that there exists an impartial and $\hat{\alpha}$ -optimal (\hat{n}, \hat{k}) -selection mechanism. Then, Algorithm 5 can be parameterized as an impartial and α -optimal (n, k) -selection mechanism with $\alpha = (\hat{k}/k)\hat{\alpha}$.*

Proof. Let \hat{k}, k, n , and \hat{n} as in the statement. Let further ALG denote the impartial and $\hat{\alpha}$ -optimal (\hat{n}, \hat{k}) -selection mechanism. To see that $\text{EXTEND}_{\text{ALG},k}$ is impartial, let $A, B \in \mathcal{A}_n$ and $i \in [n]$ such that $A_{-i} = B_{-i}$. This implies $\hat{A}_{-i} = \hat{B}_{-i}$, and the impartiality of ALG paired with $[n] \cap \{i\} = \{i\}$ yields

$$\text{EXTEND}_{\text{ALG},k}(A) \cap \{i\} = \text{ALG}(\hat{A}) \cap [n] \cap \{i\} = \text{ALG}(\hat{B}) \cap [n] \cap \{i\} = \text{EXTEND}_{\text{ALG},k}(B) \cap \{i\}.$$

For the approximation guarantee, let again $A \in \mathcal{A}_n$ and observe that

$$\frac{\sigma(\text{EXTEND}_{\text{ALG},k}(A))}{\sigma(\text{OPT}_{\hat{k}}(\hat{A}))} = \frac{\sigma(\text{ALG}(\hat{A}) \cap [n])}{\sigma(\text{OPT}_{\hat{k}}(\hat{A}))} = \frac{\sigma(\text{ALG}(\hat{A}))}{\sigma(\text{OPT}_{\hat{k}}(\hat{A}))} \geq \hat{\alpha}, \quad (5.9)$$

where the first equality follows from the definition of $\text{EXTEND}_{\text{ALG},k}$, the second is due to the fact that $\sigma(i, \hat{A}) = 0$ for every $i \in [\hat{n}] \setminus [n]$, and the inequality follows from the $\hat{\alpha}$ -optimality of ALG . On

the other hand, since $\widehat{k} \leq k$ and as A is a submatrix of \widehat{A} , it is

$$\frac{1}{k} \sigma(\text{OPT}_k(A)) = \frac{1}{k} \max_{S \subseteq [n]: |S|=k} \sigma(S; A) \leq \frac{1}{\widehat{k}} \max_{S \subseteq [\widehat{n}]: |S|=\widehat{k}} \sigma(S; \widehat{A}) = \frac{1}{\widehat{k}} \sigma(\text{OPT}_{\widehat{k}}(\widehat{A})). \quad (5.10)$$

In other words, the average score of the k top-voted agents in A can be no larger than the average score of the \widehat{k} top-voted agents in \widehat{A} . Plugging inequality (5.10) into inequality (5.9) yields

$$\frac{\sigma(\text{EXTEND}_{\text{ALG},k}(A))}{\sigma(\text{OPT}_k(A))} \geq \frac{\widehat{k} \sigma(\text{EXTEND}_{\text{ALG},k}(A))}{k \sigma(\text{OPT}_{\widehat{k}}(\widehat{A}))} \geq \frac{\widehat{k}}{k} \widehat{\alpha}. \quad \blacksquare$$

We finally combine Proposition 5.19 and Lemma 5.20 to prove the main theorem.

Proof of Theorem 5.18. Let us first recall the theorem's statement: For $n, k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ with $k < n$ and $k - (k \bmod 2) \geq 2\sqrt{n}$, there exists an impartial (n, k) -selection mechanism that is α -optimal for

$$\alpha = \frac{k - (k \bmod 2)}{k \left\lceil \frac{2n}{k - (k \bmod 2)} \right\rceil}.$$

Let thus n and k be as in the statement. We derive

$$\widehat{k} := k - (k \bmod 2) \quad \text{and} \quad \widehat{n} := \frac{\widehat{k}}{2} \left\lceil \frac{2n}{\widehat{k}} \right\rceil.$$

As $\widehat{k} \geq 2\sqrt{n} \geq 2$, we have $\widehat{k} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$. Further, \widehat{k} is even and satisfies $\widehat{k} \leq k$ by construction. Concerning \widehat{n} , observe that without the ceiling operation it would equal n , so we have $\widehat{n} \geq n$. Since $k < n$, this implies $\widehat{k} < \widehat{n}$. As the ceiling is integral and \widehat{k} is even, we also have $\widehat{n} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$. Let now

$$\widehat{b} := \frac{2\widehat{n}}{\widehat{k}} = \left\lceil \frac{2n}{\widehat{k}} \right\rceil \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}.$$

We need to show that $\widehat{b} \leq \widehat{k}/2$. This is the case as

$$2\sqrt{n} \leq \widehat{k} \iff 4n \leq \widehat{k}^2 \iff \frac{2n}{\widehat{k}} \leq \frac{\widehat{k}}{2} \implies \left\lceil \frac{2n}{\widehat{k}} \right\rceil \leq \left\lceil \frac{\widehat{k}}{2} \right\rceil \iff \widehat{b} \leq \frac{\widehat{k}}{2}$$

due to $\widehat{n}, \widehat{k} > 0$ and $\widehat{k}/2 \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$.

To summarize, we defined $\widehat{k}, \widehat{n} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ with $\widehat{k} < \widehat{n}$ and such that $2\widehat{n}/\widehat{k} = \widehat{b} \leq \widehat{k}/2$, with both sides of the inequality integral. By Proposition 5.19, this implies that $\text{ALG} := \text{SELECT}_{\widehat{k}}$ is an impartial and $1/\widehat{b}$ -optimal $(\widehat{n}, \widehat{k})$ -selection mechanism. Further, we showed that $\widehat{k} \leq k < n \leq \widehat{n}$, and all are integral. Thus, by Lemma 5.20, we have that $\text{EXTEND}_{\text{ALG},k}$ is an impartial and α -optimal (n, k) -selection mechanism for

$$\alpha = \frac{\widehat{k}}{k\widehat{b}} = \frac{k - (k \bmod 2)}{k \left\lceil \frac{2n}{k - (k \bmod 2)} \right\rceil}. \quad \blacksquare$$

We note that within its applicable range of $k - (k \bmod 2) \geq 2\sqrt{n}$, we may further bound the performance guarantee of our mechanism from below by

$$\alpha = \frac{k - (k \bmod 2)}{k \left\lceil \frac{2n}{k - (k \bmod 2)} \right\rceil} \geq \frac{k - (k \bmod 2)}{k \left\lceil \frac{2(k - (k \bmod 2))^2}{4(k - (k \bmod 2))} \right\rceil} = \frac{2}{k}.$$

Thus, for such n and k , it improves upon the previous best performance guarantee of $1/k$ [13] in the restricted setting where every vote carries equal weight, formally $A \in \mathcal{A}_n \cap \{0, 1\}^{n \times n}$.

Figure 5.4: Partitions of a worst-case input $A \in \mathcal{A}_9$ for SELECT_6 that features just three votes of weight one that are cast for three distinct agents. All votes are processed in the first partition, and subsequent partitions break ties in favor of agents that receive no votes overall, according to the rule of preferring the agent with the higher index. This leads to a performance ratio of just $1/3$. See Figure 5.3 on page 132 for keys.

5.4.1 Tightness of the analysis

As illustrated by Figure 5.3, the outcome of the mechanism can be much better than the a priori performance guarantee suggests, even when some adverse events happen. However, we show in the following that the analysis of the mechanism is tight for any n and k satisfying Proposition 5.19, meaning that the worst-case guarantee is indeed attained for some poll $A \in \mathcal{A}_n$. Such a worst-case instance can be constructed as follows: Arrange a total of b uniformly weighted votes such that they are only seen in the first partition, with each of the candidates receiving exactly one vote. Then, ensure that none of the other $b - 1$ candidates of the first partition win a tie-breaker in any other partition. An example is given in Figure 5.4, which shows the same partition system as Figure 5.3 but a different set of votes. We formalize the construction in the following.

Proposition 5.21. *Algorithm 4 is not $(1/b + \varepsilon)$ -optimal for any $\varepsilon > 0$ and for any $n, b, k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ that together satisfy the conditions of Proposition 5.19.*

Proof. Let $n, k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ with $k < n$ be such that $b := 2n/k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ and $b \leq k/2 \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$, as in the statement of Proposition 5.19, and assume without loss of generality that the robust partition system

$$((S_1^p, S_2^p))_{p=1}^k = \mathcal{S}(n, k)$$

employed by Algorithm 4 satisfies $S_2^1 = [b]$. We construct an instance $A \in \mathcal{A}_n$ as follows. For each agent $j \in [b]$, implying $j \in S_2^1$, let $v(j)$ denote an arbitrary agent in $S_1^1 \cap S_2^{>(j)}$. Such an agent exists as $b < n$ ensures that there is a co-candidate $i \in S_2^{>(j)}$ with $i \neq j$, while property (ii) of Lemma 5.17 implies that $i \notin S_2^{<(j)} = S_2^1$, so that indeed $i \in S_1^1$. Let now

$$A_{i,j} := \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } j \in [b] \wedge i = v(j), \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

for all $i, j \in [n]$. By this construction, there are $b < k$ agents receiving any votes, and each of them receives one vote, so $\sigma(\text{OPT}_k(A)) = b$. Further, we have $\sigma(w_1) = 1$, as every agent in $S_2^1 = [b]$ receives precisely one vote, and $w_1 \in S_2^1$ by line 9 of Algorithm 4. It remains to show that $\sigma(w_p) = 0$ for all $p \in [k]$ with $p > 1$. Let thus $p \in [k] \setminus \{1\}$ be fixed.

Figure 5.5: Another worst-case input $A \in \mathcal{A}_9$ for SELECT_6 in which every agent casts exactly one vote and all votes have weight one. As in Figure 5.4, the performance ratio is just $1/3$.

First, assume towards a contradiction that some vote is processed by the mechanism in the p -th partition, formally $\sigma_{S_1^p}(S_2^p) \neq 0$. Then, by definition of A , there is an agent $j \in S_2^p$ such that $j \in [b]$ and $v(j) \in S_1^p$. Since $j \in [b]$, it is $j \in S_2^1$. As further $j \in S_2^p$ with $p > 1$, we have that $p = \triangleright(j)$. But then $v(j) \in S_1^{\triangleright(j)}$ and $v(j) \in S_2^{\triangleright(j)}$ together contradict $S_1^{\triangleright(j)} \cap S_2^{\triangleright(j)} = \emptyset$. Thus, $\sigma_{S_1^p}(S_2^p) = 0$, implying that also $v_p(i) = 0$ for all $i \in S_2^p$, and so $w_p = \max S_2^p$ is chosen by the tie-breaking rule.

Next, assume towards a contradiction that $w_p \in [b]$. Since $w_p = \max S_2^p$, we have $i \leq w_p$ for all $i \in S_2^p$. As property (i) of Lemma 5.17 states that $|S_2^p| = b$, it follows that $S_2^p = [b]$. But then $p \neq 1$ and $|S_2^1 \cap S_2^p| = |[b]| = b \geq 2$ contradicts property (ii). Thus, $w_p \notin [b]$, implying $\sigma(w_p) = 0$ by construction. It follows that $\sigma(\text{SELECT}_k(A)) = \sigma(w_1) = 1$ and therefore

$$\frac{\sigma(\text{SELECT}_k(A))}{\sigma(\text{OPT}_k(A))} = \frac{1}{b}. \quad \blacksquare$$

The adverse instance constructed in the proof of Proposition 5.21 is quite sparse: for $n = 9$ and $k = 6$ (Figure 5.4), only three out of 72 possible votes are cast. One may thus wonder whether the mechanism fares better in the no-abstentions or single-nomination settings, where agents are required to cast at least one vote or exactly one vote, respectively. Unfortunately, this is not the case. Figure 5.5 shows a single-nomination instance on which the performance ratio remains $1/b$. This answers a question we posed in the discussion section of [28] in the negative.

5.4.2 Instructions for use

We conclude with a brief non-technical summary of the mechanism proposed in this section to facilitate its implementation. The purpose of the mechanism is to select up to $k \geq 2$ out of $n > k$ agents who cast (nonnegatively weighted) votes for each other. This is done deterministically and in such a way that no agent can influence its own chance of being selected. These requirements imply that the mechanism will, in general, not be able to select k agents with maximum score. In particular, it will sometimes report fewer than k winners. The selection process is as follows.

1. If the maximum selection budget k is odd, decrement it.
2. Confirm that $k^2/4 \geq n$. Otherwise, resort to the mechanism of Bjelde et al. [13].
3. Increase the number of agents to

$$\frac{k}{2} \left\lceil \frac{2n}{k} \right\rceil$$

by adding dummy agents who cast and receive no votes.

4. Construct a $2n/k$ -regular bipartite graph with k vertices and n edges (see the discussion leading to Lemma 5.16, and Figure 5.2).
5. Identify the agents with the edges of the graph.
6. Iterate over the vertices of the graph to grow a winning set. For each vertex:
 - (a) Treat the incident edges as candidates and all remaining edges as voters.
 - (b) Consider all votes from voters to candidates that have not been counted in a previous iteration. Sum their weight to obtain a score for each candidate.
 - (c) Add the candidate with the highest score to the winning set; break ties arbitrarily.
7. Remove any dummy agents from the winning set.

In terms of the original values of n and k , the procedure guarantees that the winning set receives a total score that is at least α times the maximum achievable score by any subset of size k , for α as defined in Theorem 5.18. Note that all steps can be performed without resorting to random choice given that the agents are numbered in a way not influenced by them. To avoid picking dummy agents, one can disfavor them when breaking ties. This may increase the size of the reported set for some instances but does not yield a better performance guarantee.

5.5 Assignment mechanism

So far in this chapter, we studied the election of a size-restricted group of agents based on their peers' nominations. Moving forward, we will generalize this setting to the problem of assigning agents into at most one of *multiple* size-bounded groups, each associated with a separate poll on who should be included. These groups could still represent winning categories, although with the unusual restriction that no agent can win in more than one. More likely, one encounters such a setting in the context of a committee election or the formation of working groups: scenarios that involve distributing jobs to individuals best suited for them. The argument for impartiality is clear: Agents may have a substantial preference for the job that they are assigned to; or perhaps they would prefer not to be assigned at all. Fortunately, the strategy-proof mechanism of the last section can be adapted to this setting in a straightforward way, and forfeits only a constant factor in the suitably defined performance guarantee.

5.5.1 Preliminaries

We begin by extending the preliminaries from Section 5.2.1. Every agent now gets to cast weighted votes for each job separately.

Definition 5.22: Assignment poll. An *assignment poll* is given by a sequence of poll matrices

$$\mathfrak{A} = (A_\ell)_{\ell=1}^m \in \mathcal{A}_n^m,$$

one for each job $\ell \in [m]$.

While previously the desired outcome of a mechanism was just one size-bounded set, we now ask for a disjoint sequence of such sets.

Definition 5.23: Feasible assignments. We write

$$\mathcal{X}_{n,m,k} := \left\{ (X_\ell \subseteq [n] \mid |X_\ell| \leq k)_{\ell=1}^m \mid \forall \ell \neq h \in [m]: X_\ell \cap X_h = \emptyset \right\}$$

for the set of *feasible assignments* of n agents to m jobs with capacity at most k .

As a performance objective, we aim to maximize the sum of scores achieved for each job.

Definition 5.24: Total score. Let $\mathfrak{A} = (A_\ell)_{\ell=1}^m \in \mathcal{A}_n^m$ be an assignment poll and let additionally $\mathfrak{X} = (X_\ell)_{\ell=1}^m \in \mathcal{X}_{n,m,k}$ be a feasible assignment. In a slight overload of notation, we write

$$\sigma(\mathfrak{X}; \mathfrak{A}) := \sum_{\ell=1}^m \sigma(X_\ell; A_\ell)$$

for the *total score* of \mathfrak{X} with respect to \mathfrak{A} . We omit the sequence \mathfrak{A} when it is clear from the context.

As before, we will compare the total score achieved by a mechanism with the maximum achievable by any feasible assignment.

Definition 5.25: Optimal assignment. Let $n, m, k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ with $k < n$. For $\mathfrak{A} \in \mathcal{A}_n^m$, we write

$$\text{OPT}_k(\mathfrak{A}) := \operatorname{argmax}_{\mathfrak{X} \in \mathcal{X}_{n,m,k}} \sigma(\mathfrak{X}; \mathfrak{A})$$

for an arbitrary assignment with largest score.

Few surprises await the reader in the last definition.

Definition 5.26: Assignment mechanism. A (deterministic and inexact) (n, m, k) -assignment mechanism is a function $f: \mathcal{A}_n^m \rightarrow \mathcal{P}([n])^m$ such that $f(\mathfrak{A}) \in \mathcal{X}_{n,m,k}$ for all $\mathfrak{A} \in \mathcal{A}_n^m$. It is *impartial* if, for every pair of assignment polls $\mathfrak{A} = (A_\ell)_{\ell=1}^m \in \mathcal{A}_n^m$ and $\mathfrak{B} = (B_\ell)_{\ell=1}^m \in \mathcal{A}_n^m$ and for all agents $i \in [n]$, it obeys

$$\forall \ell \in [m]: (A_\ell)_{-i} = (B_\ell)_{-i} \implies \forall \ell \in [m]: f(\mathfrak{A})_\ell \cap \{i\} = f(\mathfrak{B})_\ell \cap \{i\}.$$

We further call the mechanism α -optimal for $\alpha \in [0, 1]$, if, for all $\mathfrak{A} \in \mathcal{A}_n^m$, it satisfies

$$\frac{\sigma(f(\mathfrak{A}))}{\sigma(\text{OPT}_k(\mathfrak{A}))} \geq \alpha.$$

5.5.2 Construction

We aim to prove the following analog to Theorem 5.18. Note that in comparison, we lose a factor of two in the performance guarantee, independently of the number of jobs m .

Theorem 5.27. Let $n, m, k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ with $k < n$, $k - (k \bmod 2) \geq 2\sqrt{n}$, and $m \leq 2n/k$. Then, there exists an (n, m, k) -assignment mechanism that is impartial and α -optimal for

$$\alpha = \frac{k - (k \bmod 2)}{2k \left\lceil \frac{2n}{k - (k \bmod 2)} \right\rceil}.$$

Algorithm 6: ASSIGN_k(\mathfrak{A})

Parameter: An even integer $k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$.
Input: An assignment poll $\mathfrak{A} = (A_\ell)_{\ell=1}^m \in \mathcal{A}_n^m$ with $m \leq 2n/k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ and $2\sqrt{n} \leq k < n$.
Output: An assignment $\mathfrak{X} \in \mathcal{X}_{n,m,k}$.

```

1  $((S_1^p, S_2^p))_{p=1}^k \leftarrow \mathcal{S}(n, k)$  // a robust partition system
2 for  $i \in [n]$  do
3    $\triangleleft(i) \leftarrow \min\{p \in [k] \mid i \in S_2^p\}$  // first partition agent  $i$  is candidate in
4    $\triangleright(i) \leftarrow \max\{p \in [k] \mid i \in S_2^p\}$  // second partition agent  $i$  is candidate in
5   for  $\ell \in [m]$  do
6      $v_\ell^{\triangleleft(i)}(i) \leftarrow \sigma_{S_1^{\triangleleft(i)}}(i; A_\ell)$  // consider full scores in first partition
7      $v_\ell^{\triangleright(i)}(i) \leftarrow \sigma_{S_1^{\triangleright(i)} \setminus S_1^{\triangleleft(i)}}(i; A_\ell)$  // omit duplicate votes in second partition
8    $\mathfrak{X} \leftarrow (\emptyset)_{\ell=1}^m$ 
9   for  $p \in [k]$  do // assign to each job in each partition
10     $w^p \leftarrow \operatorname{argmax}_{v \in (S_2^p)^m: |\cup_{\ell=1}^m \{v_\ell\}|=m} (\sum_{\ell=1}^m v_\ell^p(v_\ell), v_1, \dots, v_m)$  // select a vector
11    for  $\ell \in [m]$  do
12       $\mathfrak{X}_\ell \leftarrow \mathfrak{X}_\ell \cup \{w_\ell^p\}$ 
13   for  $i \in [n]$  do
14      $L(i) \leftarrow \{\ell \in [m] \mid i \in \mathfrak{X}_\ell\}$  // jobs assigned to agent  $i$ 
15     if  $|L(i)| = 2$  then // handle a double assignment
16        $\ell \leftarrow \operatorname{argmin}_{\ell \in L(i)} (\sigma(i; A_\ell), \ell)$  // unassign lower scored job
17        $\mathfrak{X}_\ell \leftarrow \mathfrak{X}_\ell \setminus \{i\}$ 
18 return  $\mathfrak{X}$ 

```

The result stems from adaptations of Proposition 5.19 and Lemma 5.20. In the mechanism, which is described by Algorithm 6, we select not one but m distinct agents in each partition, one for each job. The notation is a bit heavier than for Algorithm 4: For consistency with the input and output sequences, which are indexed by jobs, we put parameters specifying a job $\ell \in [m]$ into the subscript of any object concerned; parameters identifying a partition index $p \in [k]$ are now written in the superscript. Note further that we now select a vector of agents $w^p \in [n]^m$ for each partition p , which by definition does not contain any agent more than once.

For the remainder of this section, whenever $n, m, k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ and $\mathfrak{A} \in \mathcal{A}_n^m$ are fixed, we write

- $S_1^p, S_2^p, \triangleleft(i)$, and $\triangleright(i)$ for partitions and their indices as in Section 5.4,
- $v_\ell^p(i)$ for the modified score of agent i in partition $p \in \{\triangleleft(i), \triangleright(i)\}$ concerning job ℓ ,
- w^p for the m -vector of agents selected in the p -th partition,
- $L(i)$ for the jobs tentatively assigned to agent i , and
- ASSIGN_k(\mathfrak{A}) = \mathfrak{X} for the assignment returned,

all as defined when Algorithm 6 returns and for all agents $i \in [n]$, jobs $\ell \in [m]$, and partitions $p \in [k]$. We further write $v_\ell^p(i; \mathfrak{A})$, $L(i; \mathfrak{A})$, $w^p(\mathfrak{A})$, and $w_\ell^p(\mathfrak{A})$, when \mathfrak{A} is ambiguous in the context.

We first adapt Proposition 5.19 to the assignment setting.

Proposition 5.28. *Let $n, m, k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ with $k < n$ be such that $b := 2n/k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ and $m \leq b \leq k/2 \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$. Then, Algorithm 6 is an impartial and $1/(2b)$ -optimal (n, m, k) -assignment mechanism.*

The proof structure follows that of Proposition 5.19: We argue that the mechanism is well-defined, show that it is impartial, derive two key inequalities concerning agents' scores, and use them to conclude the performance guarantee. The high-level argument for impartiality also remains mostly the same: In each partition, only votes of agents who cannot be assigned are counted. But, we also need to account for the potential of unassignment in line 17. The analysis of the performance guarantee is slightly more intricate than that in Section 5.4. In particular, the factor-two loss in the performance guarantee is due to the possibility that an agent may be assigned to two different jobs as a result of its two candidacies. Then, we have to unassign it from one of the jobs to restore feasibility. The fact that we cancel the job for which the agent receives a lower score allows us to bound the loss in this situation.

Proof of Proposition 5.28. By analogy with the proof of Proposition 5.19, we have that the input conditions of Algorithm 6 are equivalent to the conditions on n, m , and k in the statement, and that lines 1, 3, 4, 6 and 7 of Algorithm 6 are well-defined. For line 10, the argument that $i \in S_2^p$ implies $p \in \{\triangleleft(i), \triangleright(i)\}$ now ensures that $\sum_{\ell=1}^m v_\ell^p(v_\ell)$ is well-defined for any $v \in (S_2^p)^m$. That the argmax in line 10 is non-empty follows from the fact that $|S_2^p| = b \geq m$ by property (i) of Lemma 5.17, so that there are sufficiently many agents in S_2^p to assign a distinct one to each job. Uniqueness of the chosen winner is again ensured by breaking ties lexicographically, now with respect to the entire agent vector v . Thus, line 10 is well-defined overall. Likewise, line 16 is well-defined by the condition in line 15 and the use of the job index ℓ to break ties.

To see that ASSIGN_k is impartial, consider two assignment polls

$$\mathfrak{A} = (A_\ell)_{\ell=1}^m \in \mathcal{A}_n^m \quad \text{and} \quad \mathfrak{B} = (B_\ell)_{\ell=1}^m \in \mathcal{A}_n^m,$$

and an agent $i \in [n]$ such that $(A_\ell)_{-i} = (B_\ell)_{-i}$ for all $\ell \in [m]$. Assume further that $i \in \text{ASSIGN}_k(\mathfrak{A})_\ell$ for some arbitrary but fixed job $\ell \in [m]$. Then, there is a partition $p \in [k]$ with $i = w_\ell^p(\mathfrak{A})$ and such that the existence of another partition $q \in \{\triangleleft(i), \triangleright(i)\} \setminus \{p\}$ and job $h \in [m]$ with $h \neq \ell$ and $i = w_h^q(\mathfrak{A})$ implies

$$(\sigma(i; A_\ell), \ell) > (\sigma(i; A_h), h). \quad (5.11)$$

Intuitively, we denote by p the partition in which agent i receives a lasting assignment to job ℓ , while partition q may have caused a duplicate assignment to another job h that was later canceled. As $i \in S_2^p$ implies $i \notin S_1^p$, and $(A_\ell)_{-i} = (B_\ell)_{-i}$ by assumption, we have that $v_\ell^p(j; \mathfrak{A}) = v_\ell^p(j; \mathfrak{B})$ for all $j \in S_2^p$. Thus, we also have that $i = w_\ell^p(\mathfrak{B})$. It remains to deduce that $i \in \text{ASSIGN}_k(\mathfrak{B})_\ell$. This only fails to hold if agent i is unassigned from job ℓ in line 17 of Algorithm 6, formally if $|L(i; \mathfrak{B})| = 2$ and

$$\ell = \operatorname{argmin}_{h \in L(i; \mathfrak{B})} (\sigma(i; B_h), h). \quad (5.12)$$

Let thus $|L(i; \mathfrak{B})| = 2$. Then, there is a unique other partition $q \in \{\triangleleft(i), \triangleright(i)\} \setminus \{p\}$ and another job $h \in [m]$ with $h \neq \ell$ and $i = w_h^q(\mathfrak{B})$. From an argument symmetric to the one that let us deduce

$i = w_\ell^p(\mathfrak{B})$ from $i = w_\ell^p(\mathfrak{A})$, it follows that $i = w_h^q(\mathfrak{A})$. Thus, inequality (5.11) holds for h as defined in the current scope. We invoke again $(A_\ell)_{-i} = (B_\ell)_{-i}$ to conclude that also

$$(\sigma(i; B_\ell), \ell) > (\sigma(i; B_h), h).$$

Therefore, ℓ does not attain the argmin in equation (5.12), which in turn does not hold. This proves that $i \in \text{ASSIGN}_k(\mathfrak{B})_\ell$. By symmetry, we conclude that $\text{SELECT}_k(\mathfrak{A})_\ell \cap \{i\} = \text{SELECT}_k(\mathfrak{B})_\ell \cap \{i\}$.

For the performance guarantee, consider a single assignment poll $\mathfrak{A} = (A_\ell)_{\ell=1}^m \in \mathcal{A}_n^m$. First, we note that the modified scores for an agent sum up to its total score for each job separately, that is

$$v_\ell^{\triangleleft(i)}(i) + v_\ell^{\triangleright(i)}(i) = \sigma_{S_1^{\triangleleft(i)}}(i; A_\ell) + \sigma_{S_1^{\triangleright(i)} \setminus S_1^{\triangleleft(i)}}(i; A_\ell) = \sigma(i; A_\ell) \quad (5.13)$$

for all agents $i \in [n]$ and jobs $\ell \in [m]$, as property (ii) of Lemma 5.17 implies $S_1^{\triangleleft(i)} \cup S_1^{\triangleright(i)} = [n] \setminus \{i\}$. This time, the definition of w^p ensures that

$$\sum_{\ell \in [m]} v_\ell^p(w_\ell^p) \geq v_h^p(i) \quad (5.14)$$

for every $p \in [k]$, $h \in [m]$, and $i \in S_2^p$. To see this, assume to the contrary that inequality (5.14) was not true for some such p , h , and i . Then, for an alternative vector $z \in (S_2^p)^m$ with $z_h = i$ and $|\bigcup_{\ell=1}^m \{z_\ell\}| = m$ we would obtain

$$\sum_{\ell \in [m]} v_\ell^p(z_\ell) \geq v_h^p(i) > \sum_{\ell \in [m]} v_\ell^p(w_\ell^p),$$

contradicting the definition of w^p . Given these two facts, we now claim that

$$\sum_{\ell=1}^m (v_\ell^{\triangleleft(i)}(w_\ell^{\triangleleft(i)}) + v_\ell^{\triangleright(i)}(w_\ell^{\triangleright(i)})) \geq \max_{\ell \in [m]} \sigma(i; A_\ell) \quad (5.15)$$

for all $i \in [n]$. In other words, all agents that are tentatively selected in the two partitions that agent i competes in together receive as much weight in those two partitions alone, summed over all jobs, as agent i receives in total for its “best” job. Note that, unlike in the proof of Proposition 5.19, the modified scores on the left-hand side of inequality (5.15) are preliminary contributions to the mechanism’s performance as agents might later be unassigned from one of two jobs that they can initially be assigned to. To show inequality (5.15), fix $i \in [n]$ and observe that the validity of inequality (5.14) for all $h \in [m]$ implies

$$\sum_{\ell \in [m]} v_\ell^p(w_\ell^p) \geq \max_{\ell \in [m]} v_\ell^p(i)$$

for all $p \in [k]$. In particular, substituting each of $\triangleleft(i)$ and $\triangleright(i)$ for p and summing the resulting inequalities gives us

$$\sum_{\ell \in [m]} v_\ell^{\triangleleft(i)}(w_\ell^{\triangleleft(i)}) + \sum_{\ell \in [m]} v_\ell^{\triangleright(i)}(w_\ell^{\triangleright(i)}) \geq \max_{\ell \in [m]} v_\ell^{\triangleleft(i)}(i) + \max_{\ell \in [m]} v_\ell^{\triangleright(i)}(i).$$

Pulling the maxima out of the sum only makes the right-hand side smaller, so it follows that

$$\sum_{\ell \in [m]} (v_{\ell}^{\triangleleft(i)}(w_{\ell}^{\triangleleft(i)}) + v_{\ell}^{\triangleright(i)}(w_{\ell}^{\triangleright(i)})) \geq \max_{\ell \in [m]} (v_{\ell}^{\triangleleft(i)}(i) + v_{\ell}^{\triangleright(i)}(i)) = \max_{\ell \in [m]} \sigma(i; A_{\ell}),$$

where the equality is due to equation (5.13). This proves inequality (5.15).

We next relate the total score of the assignment returned by the mechanism to the modified scores of the agents that receive a preliminary assignment in each partition. Here, we realize the relative loss in the performance guarantee due to the possibility of seeing duplicate jobs unassigned. Let thus

$$X := \bigcup_{\ell \in [m]} \mathfrak{X}_{\ell}$$

denote the set of all agents assigned to some job by the mechanism. Recall further that

$$L(i) = \{\ell \in [m] \mid i \in \{w_{\ell}^{\triangleleft(i)}, w_{\ell}^{\triangleright(i)}\}\}$$

denotes the jobs tentatively assigned to agent i . We thus have

$$\sigma(\mathfrak{X}) = \sum_{i \in X} \max_{\ell \in L(i)} \sigma(i; A_{\ell}) \geq \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i \in X} \sum_{\ell \in L(i)} \sigma(i; A_{\ell}), \quad (5.16)$$

where the equality holds as we break ties in favor of the higher score in line 16 of Algorithm 6 and the inequality follows from $|L(i)| \leq 2$ for all $i \in X$. A closer look at the right-hand side lets us reparameterize the sums as

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i \in X} \sum_{\ell \in L(i)} \sigma(i; A_{\ell}) &= \sum_{i \in X} \sum_{\ell \in [m]} (\mathbf{1}[i = w_{\ell}^{\triangleleft(i)}] \sigma(i; A_{\ell}) + \mathbf{1}[i = w_{\ell}^{\triangleright(i)}] \sigma(i; A_{\ell})) \\ &= \sum_{i \in X} \sum_{\ell \in [m]} \sum_{p \in [k]} \mathbf{1}[i = w_{\ell}^p] \sigma(i; A_{\ell}) \\ &= \sum_{\ell \in [m]} \sum_{p \in [k]} \sigma(w_{\ell}^p; A_{\ell}). \end{aligned} \quad (5.17)$$

Here, the first equality unravels the definition of $L(i)$, the second makes use of property (iii) of Lemma 5.17 and the definition of $\triangleleft(i)$ and $\triangleright(i)$, and the last follows simply from $w_{\ell}^p \in X$ for all $p \in [k]$ and $\ell \in [m]$. Plugging equation (5.17) into inequality (5.16), and utilizing the implication of equation (5.13) that the modified score never exceeds the original score yields

$$\sigma(\mathfrak{X}) \geq \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\ell \in [m]} \sum_{p \in [k]} \sigma(w_{\ell}^p; A_{\ell}) \geq \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\ell \in [m]} \sum_{p \in [k]} v_{\ell}^p(w_{\ell}^p). \quad (5.18)$$

We next use inequalities (5.15) and (5.18) to obtain the performance guarantee. For consistency with the shorthands \mathfrak{X} and X , which refer to the assignment produced by the mechanism and to the agents included in it, let

$$\mathfrak{O} := \text{OPT}_k(\mathfrak{A}) \quad \text{and} \quad O := \bigcup_{\ell \in [m]} \mathfrak{O}_{\ell}$$

denote an arbitrary optimum assignment and the set of agents included in it. For all $i \in O$, let further $\ell(i) \in [m]$ be the unique job such that $i \in \mathfrak{D}_{\ell(i)}$. Since $O \subseteq [n]$, we know from property (iv) of Lemma 5.17 that there is a partition

$$\dot{\bigcup}_{t \in [b]} U_t = O$$

such that for all $t \in [b]$ and all $i, j \in U_t$ with $i \neq j$, $i \in S_2^p$ implies $j \notin S_2^p$ for all $p \in [k]$. As in the proof of Proposition 5.19, this means that the agents assigned by an optimal assignment can be partitioned into b many groups, each of which contains only agents that pairwise do not compete. From inequality (5.18) and this fact we obtain for every $t \in [b]$ that

$$\sigma(\mathfrak{X}) \geq \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\ell \in [m]} \sum_{p \in [k]} v_\ell^p(w_\ell^p) \geq \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\ell \in [m]} \sum_{i \in U_t} (v_\ell^{\triangleleft(i)}(w_\ell^{\triangleleft(i)}) + v_\ell^{\triangleright(i)}(w_\ell^{\triangleleft(i)})) \geq \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i \in U_t} \sigma(i; A_{\ell(i)}), \quad (5.19)$$

where the second inequality follows again from the fact that $\{\triangleleft(i), \triangleright(i)\} \cap \{\triangleleft(j), \triangleright(j)\} = \emptyset$ for every $t \in [b]$ and all $i, j \in U_t$ with $i \neq j$, and the last one from inequality (5.15). This yields

$$\sigma(\mathfrak{X}) \geq \frac{1}{2} \max_{t \in [b]} \sum_{i \in U_t} \sigma(i; A_{\ell(i)}) \geq \frac{1}{2b} \sum_{t \in [b]} \sum_{i \in U_t} \sigma(i; A_{\ell(i)}) \quad (5.20)$$

where the first inequality is a consequence of equation (5.19) and the second relates the maximum and the mean value of a set. Furthermore, we have that

$$\sum_{t \in [b]} \sum_{i \in U_t} \sigma(i; A_{\ell(i)}) = \sum_{i \in O} \sigma(i; A_{\ell(i)}) = \sum_{\ell \in [m]} \sigma(\mathfrak{D}_\ell; A_\ell) = \sigma(\mathfrak{D}), \quad (5.21)$$

where the first equality holds as $(U_t)_{t \in [b]}$ is a partition of O , the second follows from the definitions of O and $\ell(i)$, and the third from that of the total score. Combining inequality (5.20) and equation (5.21) and substituting $\mathfrak{X} = \text{ASSIGN}_k(\mathfrak{A})$ and $\mathfrak{D} = \text{OPT}_k(\mathfrak{A})$ yields the claimed performance guarantee of

$$\frac{\sigma(\text{ASSIGN}_k(\mathfrak{A}))}{\sigma(\text{OPT}_k(\mathfrak{A}))} \geq \frac{1}{2b} = \frac{k}{4n}. \quad \blacksquare$$

As in Section 5.4, our next step is to extrapolate the bound of Proposition 5.28 to scenarios that satisfy the condition of $2\sqrt{n} + (k \bmod 2) \leq k < n$ but where either $2n/k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ or $k/2 \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ or both do not hold. The approach and proof are analogous up to quantification over $\ell \in [m]$, as any feasible number of jobs m is propagated through the extension procedure. The latter is formally described by Algorithm 7.

Lemma 5.29. *Let $m \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ and $\hat{k}, k, n, \hat{n} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ with $\hat{k} \leq k < n \leq \hat{n}$ be such that there exists an impartial and $\hat{\alpha}$ -optimal (\hat{n}, m, \hat{k}) -assignment mechanism. Then, Algorithm 7 can be parameterized as an impartial and α -optimal (n, m, k) -assignment mechanism with $\alpha = (\hat{k}/k)\hat{\alpha}$.*

Proof. Let \hat{k}, k, n, \hat{n} , and m as in the statement. Let further ALG denote the impartial and $\hat{\alpha}$ -optimal (\hat{n}, m, \hat{k}) -assignment mechanism. To see that $\text{EXTEND}_{\text{ALG}, k}^*$ is impartial, let $\mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{B} \in \mathcal{A}_n^m$ and $i \in [n]$ such that $(\mathfrak{A}_\ell)_{-i} = (\mathfrak{B}_\ell)_{-i}$ for all jobs $\ell \in [m]$. This implies $(\hat{\mathfrak{A}}_\ell)_{-i} = (\hat{\mathfrak{B}}_\ell)_{-i}$, and the impartiality of ALG paired with $[n] \cap \{i\} = \{i\}$ yields

$$(\text{EXTEND}_{\text{ALG}, k}^*(\mathfrak{A}))_\ell \cap \{i\} = (\text{ALG}(\hat{\mathfrak{A}}))_\ell \cap [n] \cap \{i\} = (\text{ALG}(\hat{\mathfrak{B}}))_\ell \cap [n] \cap \{i\} = (\text{EXTEND}_{\text{ALG}, k}^*(\mathfrak{B}))_\ell \cap \{i\}$$

Algorithm 7: $\text{EXTEND}_{\text{ALG},k}^*(\mathfrak{A})$

Parameter: An (\hat{n}, m, \hat{k}) -assignment mechanism ALG and an integer $k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ with $\hat{k} \leq k$.

Input: An assignment poll $\mathfrak{A} \in \mathcal{A}_n^m$ with $k < n \leq \hat{n}$.

Output: An assignment $\mathfrak{X} \in \mathcal{X}_{n,m,k}$.

```

1  $\hat{\mathfrak{A}} \leftarrow (\{0\}^{\hat{n} \times \hat{n}})_{\ell=1}^m$ 
2 for  $\ell \in [m]$  do
3   for  $i, j \in [n]$  do
4      $(\hat{\mathfrak{A}}_{\ell})_{i,j} \leftarrow (\mathfrak{A}_{\ell})_{i,j}$            // populate upper left square
5    $\hat{\mathfrak{X}} \leftarrow \text{ALG}(\hat{\mathfrak{A}})$                        // call sub-mechanism
6    $\mathfrak{X} \leftarrow (\hat{\mathfrak{X}}_{\ell} \cap [n])_{\ell=1}^m$        // unassign dummy agents
7 return  $\mathfrak{X}$ 

```

for all $\ell \in [m]$.

For the approximation guarantee, let again $\mathfrak{A} \in \mathcal{A}_n^m$ and observe that

$$\frac{\sigma(\text{EXTEND}_{\text{ALG},k}^*(\mathfrak{A}))}{\sigma(\text{OPT}_{\hat{k}}(\mathfrak{A}))} = \frac{\sigma\left((\text{ALG}(\hat{\mathfrak{A}})_{\ell} \cap [n])_{\ell=1}^m\right)}{\sigma(\text{OPT}_{\hat{k}}(\hat{\mathfrak{A}}))} = \frac{\sigma(\text{ALG}(\hat{\mathfrak{A}}))}{\sigma(\text{OPT}_{\hat{k}}(\hat{\mathfrak{A}}))} \geq \hat{\alpha}, \quad (5.22)$$

where the first equality follows from the definition of $\text{EXTEND}_{\text{ALG},k}^*$, the second is due to the fact that $\sigma(i, \hat{\mathfrak{A}}_{\ell}) = 0$ for every $i \in [\hat{n}] \setminus [n]$ and all $\ell \in [m]$, and the inequality follows from the $\hat{\alpha}$ -optimality of ALG . On the other hand, we have that

$$\frac{1}{k} \sigma(\text{OPT}_k(\mathfrak{A})) = \frac{1}{k} \max_{\mathfrak{X} \in \mathcal{X}_{n,m,k}} \sum_{\ell \in [m]} \sigma(\mathfrak{X}_{\ell}; \mathfrak{A}_{\ell}) \leq \frac{1}{k} \max_{\mathfrak{X} \in \mathcal{X}_{\hat{n},m,\hat{k}}} \sum_{\ell \in [m]} \sigma(\mathfrak{X}_{\ell}; \hat{\mathfrak{A}}_{\ell}) = \frac{1}{k} \sigma(\text{OPT}_{\hat{k}}(\hat{\mathfrak{A}})). \quad (5.23)$$

The inequality states that the average score of an assignment cannot decrease if the per-job agent limit is lowered while dummy agents are added. To see this, consider an optimum assignment $\mathfrak{X} \in \mathcal{X}_{n,m,k}$ and transform it into an assignment $\hat{\mathfrak{X}} \in \mathcal{X}_{\hat{n},m,\hat{k}}$ by simply ignoring the additional agents in $[\hat{n}] \setminus [n]$ while removing $k - \hat{k} \geq 0$ agents with the lowest per-job score $i \mapsto \sigma(i, \mathfrak{A}_{\ell})$ from \mathfrak{X}_{ℓ} for all $\ell \in [m]$. Plugging inequality (5.23) into inequality (5.22) concludes the proof as

$$\frac{\sigma(\text{EXTEND}_{\text{ALG},k}^*(\mathfrak{A}))}{\sigma(\text{OPT}_k(\mathfrak{A}))} \geq \frac{\hat{k}}{k} \frac{\sigma(\text{EXTEND}_{\text{ALG},k}^*(\mathfrak{A}))}{\sigma(\text{OPT}_{\hat{k}}(\hat{\mathfrak{A}}))} \geq \frac{\hat{k}}{k} \hat{\alpha}. \quad \blacksquare$$

It only remains to combine Proposition 5.28 and Lemma 5.29 to prove the assignment variant of the main theorem.

Proof of Theorem 5.27. Let us again recall the theorem's statement: For $n, m, k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ with $k < n$, $k - (k \bmod 2) \geq 2\sqrt{n}$, and $m \leq 2n/k$, there exists an impartial (n, m, k) -assignment mechanism that is α -optimal for

$$\alpha = \frac{k - (k \bmod 2)}{2k \left\lceil \frac{2n}{k - (k \bmod 2)} \right\rceil}.$$

Let thus n , m , and k be as in the statement. In the proof of Theorem 5.18, we showed that for

$$\widehat{k} := k - (k \bmod 2), \quad \widehat{n} := \frac{\widehat{k}}{2} \left\lceil \frac{2n}{\widehat{k}} \right\rceil \quad \text{and} \quad \widehat{b} := \frac{2\widehat{n}}{\widehat{k}},$$

it is $\widehat{k}, \widehat{n} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ with $\widehat{k} < \widehat{n}$ and $2\widehat{n}/\widehat{k} = \widehat{b} \leq \widehat{k}/2$, with both sides of the inequality integral. We also argued that $\widehat{n} \geq n$. From $\widehat{k} \leq k$ and $\widehat{n} \geq n$, it follows further that $m \leq 2n/k \leq \widehat{b}$. By Proposition 5.28, this implies that $\text{ALG} := \text{ASSIGN}_{\widehat{k}}$ is an impartial and $1/(2\widehat{b})$ -optimal $(\widehat{n}, m, \widehat{k})$ -selection mechanism. Further, as $\widehat{k} \leq k < n \leq \widehat{n}$ and all are integral, we have by Lemma 5.29 that $\text{EXTEND}_{\text{ALG}, k}^*$ is an impartial and α -optimal (n, m, k) -selection mechanism for $\alpha = \widehat{k}/(2k\widehat{b})$. Expanding the definitions of \widehat{k} and \widehat{b} yields the claim. ■

5.6 Conclusion

In an election among a group of peers, strategy-proofness is a desirable axiom that, so far, comes at a steep price. If multiple winners are sought and the selection process must be deterministic, then the impartial mechanism proposed in this chapter certainly signifies progress: For the first time, it allows the selection of more than two popular agents, and it can aggregate arbitrary ratings beyond the binary choice for or against approval. Yet, its improved performance guarantee remains at a level that could be difficult to sell to participants of the poll: In the best case, when up to two thirds of the agents may be declared winners, the subset selected by the mechanism is only guaranteed to be supported by one third of the score that the highest-rated subset receives. This minimum performance is indeed attained in adverse instances, and already for votes carrying unit weight. This raises the question if impartiality is just an inherently expensive property or whether one can build upon the ideas presented here, or tap the potential of new methods, to do much better. More than a decade after the observation that inexactness allows deterministic mechanisms to be α -optimal for $\alpha > 0$, that question is still remarkably wide open: The best known upper bound on the achievable performance ratio of $(k-1)/k$ remains unabatedly optimistic, suggesting that impartiality may come essentially for free if the selection budget k is just large enough. On the other end, we moved the lower bound from an antithetical $1/k$ to $k/(2n)$ for well-behaved combinations of k and n , and to a value in that order in the wider range of $k \geq 2\sqrt{n}$. In the limit of n , this guarantee ranges from a vanishing $2/k \rightarrow 0$ for $k = 2\sqrt{n}$ to the highlighted $1/3$ for $k \geq 2n/3$; both a notable improvement over $1/k$ but far from closing in on an answer. Narrowing the gap in the price of impartiality, both for deterministic and randomized mechanisms, thus remains a pivotal challenge for future research.

While the mechanism presented is tailored to the deterministic setting, it is conceivable that it also fares well in expectation when the agents' indices are permuted at random, thus turning it into an inexact and randomized procedure. Arguably, the property that it processes every vote exactly once may make it more attractive in practice than existing randomized mechanisms that fill the selection budget exactly but omit some votes. An analysis of this variant may thus be a promising starting point for further studies.

Bibliography

- [1] H. Ackermann, H. Röglin, and B. Vöcking. “On the impact of combinatorial structure on congestion games.” In: *Journal of the ACM* 55.6 (2008), pp. 1–22. DOI: [10.1145/1455248.1455249](https://doi.org/10.1145/1455248.1455249).
- [2] J. Aitchison, C. Barceló-Vidal, J. A. Martín-Fernández, and V. Pawłowsky-Glahn. “Logratio analysis and compositional distance.” In: *Mathematical Geology* 32.3 (2000), pp. 271–275. DOI: [10.1023/A:1007529726302](https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1007529726302).
- [3] J. Aitchison. “The statistical analysis of compositional data.” In: *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series B (Methodological)* 44.2 (1982), pp. 139–160. DOI: [10.1111/j.2517-6161.1982.tb01195.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2517-6161.1982.tb01195.x).
- [4] J. Aitchison. “On criteria for measures of compositional difference.” In: *Mathematical Geology* 24.4 (1992), pp. 365–379. DOI: [10.1007/BF00891269](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00891269).
- [5] N. Alon, F. Fischer, A. D. Procaccia, and M. Tennenholtz. “Sum of us: strategyproof selection from the selectors.” In: *Proceedings of the 13th Conference on Theoretical Aspects of Rationality and Knowledge*. Ed. by K. R. Apt. New York: Association for Computing Machinery, 2011, pp. 101–110. DOI: [10.1145/2000378.2000390](https://doi.org/10.1145/2000378.2000390).
- [6] V. Amati, T. Shafie, and U. Brandes. “Reconstructing archaeological networks with structural holes.” In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 25.1 (2018), pp. 226–253. DOI: [10.1007/s10816-017-9335-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-017-9335-1).
- [7] Ancient World Mapping Center. *Elevation, open water*. ACCESSED: 2021-07-21. URL: https://awmc.unc.edu/awmc/map_data/.
- [8] M. S. Andersen, J. Dahl, and L. Vandenberghe. *CVXOPT: Python software for convex optimization*. 2023. URL: <https://cvxopt.org>.
- [9] H. Aziz, O. Lev, N. Mattei, J. S. Rosenschein, and T. Walsh. “Strategyproof peer selection using randomization, partitioning, and apportionment.” In: *Artificial Intelligence* 275 (2019), pp. 295–309. DOI: [10.1016/j.artint.2019.06.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.artint.2019.06.004).
- [10] A. Banerjee, I. S. Dhillon, J. Ghosh, and S. Sra. “Clustering on the unit hypersphere using von Mises–Fisher distributions.” In: *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 6.46 (2005), pp. 1345–1382.
- [11] C. Berge. *Graphs and Hypergraphs*. Vol. 6. North-Holland Publishing Company, 1973.
- [12] M. C. Bishop. *The Secret History of the Roman Roads of Britain*. Yorkshire: Pen & Sword Military, 2021.
- [13] A. Bjelde, F. Fischer, and M. Klimm. “Impartial selection and the power of up to two choices.” In: *ACM Transactions on Economics and Computation* 5.4 (2017), 21:1–21:20. DOI: [10.1145/3107922](https://doi.org/10.1145/3107922).
- [14] L. Boncinelli and P. Pin. “Stochastic stability in best shot network games.” In: *Games and Economic Behavior* 75.2 (2012), pp. 538–554. DOI: [10.1016/j.geb.2012.03.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geb.2012.03.001).

- [15] N. Bousquet, S. Norin, and A. Vetta. “A near-optimal mechanism for impartial selection.” In: *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Web and Internet Economics*. Ed. by T.-Y. Liu, Q. Qi, and Y. Ye. Lecture Notes in Computer Science 8877. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2014, pp. 133–146. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-13129-0_10](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-13129-0_10).
- [16] S. Boyd and L. Vandenberghe. *Convex Optimization*. Cambridge University Press, 2004.
- [17] Y. Bramoullé and R. Kranton. “Public goods in networks.” In: *Journal of Economic Theory* 135.1 (2007), pp. 478–494. DOI: [10.1016/j.jet.2006.06.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jet.2006.06.006).
- [18] Y. Bramoullé, R. Kranton, and M. D’Amours. “Strategic interaction and networks.” In: *American Economic Review* 104.3 (2014), pp. 898–930. DOI: [10.1257/aer.104.3.898](https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.104.3.898).
- [19] S. Branting. “Seven solutions for seven problems with least cost pathways.” In: *Least cost analysis of social landscapes: Archaeological case studies*. Ed. by D. A. White and S. L. Surface-Evans. University of Utah Press, 2012. Chap. 12, pp. 209–224. DOI: [10.1353/book41407](https://doi.org/10.1353/book41407).
- [20] C. Broodbank. *An island archaeology of the early Cyclades*. Cambridge University Press, 2000.
- [21] I. Caragiannis, G. Christodoulou, and N. Protopapas. “Impartial selection with additive approximation guarantees.” In: *Theory of Computing Systems* 66.3 (2022), pp. 721–742. DOI: [10.1007/s00224-022-10081-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00224-022-10081-0).
- [22] I. Caragiannis, G. Christodoulou, and N. Protopapas. “Impartial selection with prior information.” In: *Proceedings of the ACM Web Conference*. Ed. by Y. Ding, J. Tang, J. Sequeda, L. Aroyo, C. Castillo, and G.-J. Houben. New York: Association for Computing Machinery, 2023, pp. 3614–3624. DOI: [10.1145/3543507.3583553](https://doi.org/10.1145/3543507.3583553).
- [23] M. Cavendish. *The Description of a New World, Called The Blazing-World*. London: Anne Maxwell, 1668.
- [24] J. Cembrano, F. Fischer, D. Hannon, and M. Klimm. “Impartial selection with additive guarantees via iterated deletion.” In: *Games and Economic Behavior* 144 (2024), pp. 203–224. DOI: [10.1016/j.geb.2024.01.008](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geb.2024.01.008).
- [25] J. Cembrano, F. Fischer, and M. Klimm. “Optimal impartial correspondences.” In: *Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Web and Internet Economics*. Ed. by K. A. Hansen, T. X. Liu, and A. Malekian. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2022, pp. 187–203. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-031-22832-2_11](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-22832-2_11).
- [26] J. Cembrano, F. Fischer, and M. Klimm. “Improved bounds for single-nomination impartial selection.” In: *Proceedings of the 24th ACM Conference on Economics and Computation*. Ed. by K. Leyton-Brown, J. D. Hartline, and L. Samuelson. New York: Association for Computing Machinery, 2023, p. 449. DOI: [10.1145/3580507.3597693](https://doi.org/10.1145/3580507.3597693).
- [27] J. Cembrano, S. M. Griesbach, and M. J. Stahlberg. “Deterministic impartial selection with weights.” In: *Proceedings of the 19th Conference on Web and Internet Economics*. 2023, pp. 151–168. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-031-48974-7_9](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-48974-7_9).
- [28] J. Cembrano, S. M. Griesbach, and M. J. Stahlberg. “Deterministic impartial selection with weights.” In: *ACM Transactions on Economics and Computation* 12.3 (2024), 10:1–10:22. DOI: [10.1145/3677177](https://doi.org/10.1145/3677177).
- [29] M. Chlebík and J. Chlebíková. “Approximation hardness of dominating set problems in bounded degree graphs.” In: *Information and Computation* 206 (2008), pp. 1264–1275. DOI: [10.1016/j.ic.2008.07.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ic.2008.07.003).

- [30] B. Cook. *John Carmack: making the magic happen*. ACCESSED: 2024-09-09. 2009. URL: <https://bradcook.net/games/articles/2009/02/johncarmack/>.
- [31] P. Crescenzi. "A short guide to approximation preserving reductions." In: *Proceedings of the 12th Annual IEEE Conference on Computational Complexity*. IEEE, 1997. DOI: 10.1109/CCC.1997.612321.
- [32] O. Cuntz, ed. *Itineraria Romana: Itineraria Antonini Augusti et Burdigalense*. Leipzig: Teubner, 1929.
- [33] L. Dall'Asta, P. Pin, and A. Ramezanzpour. "Optimal equilibria of the best shot game." In: *Journal of Public Economic Theory* 13.6 (2011), pp. 885–901. DOI: 10.1111/j.1467-9779.2011.01523.x.
- [34] H. E. H. Davies. "Designing Roman roads." In: *Britannia* 29 (1998), pp. 1–16. DOI: 10.2307/526811.
- [35] L. De Benedictis, V. Licio, and A. M. Pinna. "From the historical Roman road network to modern infrastructure in Italy." In: *Journal of Regional Science* 63.5 (2023), pp. 1162–1191. DOI: 10.1111/jors.12659.
- [36] G. De Clippel, H. Moulin, and N. Tideman. "Impartial division of a dollar." In: *Journal of Economic Theory* 139.1 (2008), pp. 176–191. DOI: 10.1016/j.jet.2007.06.005.
- [37] I. S. Dhillon and D. S. Modha. "Concept decompositions for large sparse text data using clustering." In: *Machine Learning* 42.1 (2001), pp. 143–175. DOI: 10.1023/A:1007612920971.
- [38] K. Dhull, S. Jecmen, P. Kothari, and N. B. Shah. "Strategyproofing peer assessment via partitioning: the price in terms of evaluators' expertise." In: *Proceedings of the 10th AAAI Conference on Human Computation and Crowdsourcing*. Ed. by J. Hsu and M. Yin. Palo Alto: AAAI Press, 2022, pp. 53–63. DOI: 10.1609/hcomp.v10i1.21987.
- [39] E. W. Dijkstra. "A note on two problems in connexion with graphs." In: *Numerische Mathematik* 1 (1959), pp. 269–271. DOI: 10.1007/BF01386390.
- [40] O. A. W. Dilke. "Itineraries and geographical maps in the early and late Roman empires." In: *Cartography in Prehistoric, Ancient, and Medieval Europe and the Mediterranean*. Ed. by J. B. Harley and D. Woodward. The History of Cartography 1. University of Chicago Press, 1987. Chap. 14, pp. 234–257.
- [41] O. A. W. Dilke. "Maps in the service of the state: Roman cartography to the end of the Augustan Era." In: *Cartography in Prehistoric, Ancient, and Medieval Europe and the Mediterranean*. Ed. by J. B. Harley and D. Woodward. The History of Cartography 1. University of Chicago Press, 1987. Chap. 12, pp. 212–233.
- [42] D. H. Douglas and T. K. Peucker. "Algorithms for the reduction of the number of points required to represent a digitized line or its caricature." In: *The Canadian Cartographer* 10.2 (1973), pp. 112–122. DOI: 10.3138/FM57-6770-U75U-7727.
- [43] B. Ducke and P. Suchowska. "Exploratory network reconstruction with sparse archaeological data and XTENT." in: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 29 (2022), pp. 508–539. DOI: 10.1007/s10816-021-09529-3.
- [44] P. H. Edelman and A. Por. "A new axiomatic approach to the impartial nomination problem." In: *Games and Economic Behavior* 130 (2021), pp. 443–451. DOI: 10.1016/j.geb.2021.08.014.
- [45] J. J. Egozcue, V. Pawłowsky-Glahn, G. Mateu-Figueras, and C. Barceló-Vidal. "Isometric logratio transformations for compositional data analysis." In: *Mathematical Geology* 35.3 (2003), pp. 279–300. DOI: 10.1023/A:1023818214614.

- [46] M. Erwig. “The graph Voronoi diagram with applications.” In: *Networks* 36.3 (2000), pp. 156–163. DOI: [10.1002/1097-0037\(200010\)36:3<156::AID-NET2>3.0.CO;2-L](https://doi.org/10.1002/1097-0037(200010)36:3<156::AID-NET2>3.0.CO;2-L).
- [47] T. G. Farr et al. “The shuttle radar topography mission.” In: *Reviews of Geophysics* 45.2 (2007). DOI: [10.1029/2005RG000183](https://doi.org/10.1029/2005RG000183).
- [48] F. Fischer and M. Klimm. “Optimal impartial selection.” In: *SIAM Journal on Computing* 44.5 (2015), pp. 1263–1285. DOI: [10.1137/140995775](https://doi.org/10.1137/140995775).
- [49] R. Fisher. “Dispersion on a sphere.” In: *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London A* 217.1130 (1953), pp. 295–305. DOI: [10.1098/rspa.1953.0064](https://doi.org/10.1098/rspa.1953.0064).
- [50] F. Fulminante, L. Prignano, I. Morer, and S. Lozano. “Coordinated decisions and unbalanced power. How Latin cities shaped their terrestrial transportation network.” In: *Frontiers in Digital Humanities* 4 (2017). DOI: [10.3389/fdigh.2017.00004](https://doi.org/10.3389/fdigh.2017.00004).
- [51] J. Gabarró, A. García, and M. Serna. “The complexity of game isomorphism.” In: *Theoretical Computer Science* 412.48 (2011), pp. 6675–6695. DOI: [10.1016/j.tcs.2011.07.022](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tcs.2011.07.022).
- [52] K. R. Gabriel and R. R. Sokal. “A new statistical approach to geographic variation analysis.” In: *Systematic Biology* 18.3 (1969), pp. 259–278. DOI: [10.2307/2412323](https://doi.org/10.2307/2412323).
- [53] A. Galeotti, S. Goyal, M. O. Jackson, F. Vega-Redondo, and L. Yariv. “Network games.” In: *The Review of Economic Studies* 77.1 (2010), pp. 218–244. DOI: [10.1111/j.1467-937X.2009.00570.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-937X.2009.00570.x).
- [54] M. R. Garey and D. S. Johnson. *Computers and intractability*. New York: W. H. Freeman, 1979.
- [55] J. D. Gergonne. “Solutions purement géométriques des problèmes de minimis proposés aux pages 196, 232 et 292 de ce volume, et de divers autres problèmes analogues.” In: *Annales de mathématiques pures et appliquées* 1 (1810). English: Purely geometric solutions to the minimization problems proposed on pages 196, 232, and 292 of this volume, and of various other analog problems, pp. 375–384.
- [56] M. Gilboa. “A characterization of complexity in public goods games.” In: *Proceedings of the 51st International Colloquium on Automata, Languages, and Programming*. Ed. by K. Bringmann, M. Grohe, G. Puppis, and O. Svensson. Leibniz International Proceedings in Informatics 297. Saarbrücken/Wadern: Dagstuhl Publishing, 2024, 73:1–73:19. DOI: [10.4230/LIPIcs.ICALP.2024.73](https://doi.org/10.4230/LIPIcs.ICALP.2024.73).
- [57] M. Gilboa and N. Nisan. “Complexity of public goods games on graphs.” In: *Algorithmic Game Theory*. Ed. by P. Kanellopoulos, M. Kyropoulou, and A. Voudouris. Lecture Notes in Computer Science 13584. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2022, pp. 151–168. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-031-15714-1_9](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-15714-1_9).
- [58] S. Gillies, C. van der Wel, J. Van den Bossche, M. W. Taves, J. Arnott, and B. C. Ward. *Shapely: manipulation and analysis of geometric objects*. 2024. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.5597138](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5597138).
- [59] L. J. Gorenflo and N. Gale. “Mapping regional settlement in information space.” In: *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 9.3 (1990), pp. 240–274. DOI: [10.1016/0278-4165\(90\)90008-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0278-4165(90)90008-2).
- [60] M. Grant. *History of Rome*. New York: History Book Club, 1997.
- [61] M. R. Groenhuijzen and P. Verhagen. “Comparing network construction techniques in the context of local transport networks in the Dutch part of the Roman limes.” In: *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports* 15 (2017), pp. 235–251. DOI: [10.1016/j.jasrep.2017.07.024](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2017.07.024).
- [62] A. A. Hagberg, D. A. Schult, and P. J. Swart. “Exploring network structure, dynamics, and function using NetworkX.” in: *Proceedings of the 7th Python in Science Conference*. Ed. by G. Varoquaux, T. Vaught, and J. Millman. 2008, pp. 11–15.

- [63] C. R. Harris et al. “Array programming with NumPy.” In: *Nature* 585 (2020), pp. 357–362. DOI: [10.1038/s41586-020-2649-2](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2649-2).
- [64] J. Hirshleifer. “From weakest-link to best-shot: the voluntary provision of public goods.” In: *Public Choice* 41 (1983), pp. 371–386. DOI: [10.1007/BF00141070](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00141070).
- [65] R. Holzman and H. Moulin. “Impartial nominations for a prize.” In: *Econometrica* 81.1 (2013), pp. 173–196. DOI: [10.3982/ECTA10523](https://doi.org/10.3982/ECTA10523).
- [66] B. K. P. Horn. “Hill shading and the reflectance map.” In: *Proceedings of the IEEE* 69.1 (1981), pp. 14–47. DOI: [10.1109/PROC.1981.11918](https://doi.org/10.1109/PROC.1981.11918).
- [67] C. F. Jekel, G. Venter, M. P. Venter, N. Stander, and R. T. Haftka. “Similarity measures for identifying material parameters from hysteresis loops using inverse analysis.” In: *International Journal of Material Forming* 12 (2019), pp. 355–378. DOI: [10.1007/s12289-018-1421-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12289-018-1421-8).
- [68] D. Jiménez-Badillo. “Relative neighbourhood networks for archaeological analysis.” In: *Proceedings of the 39th Conference of Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology*. Ed. by M. Zhou. Amsterdam University Press, 2012, pp. 370–380. DOI: [10.2307/j.ctt1zrvhmr](https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctt1zrvhmr).
- [69] D. S. Johnson. “How easy is local search?” In: *Journal of Computer and System Sciences* 37.1 (1988), pp. 79–100. DOI: [10.1016/0022-0000\(88\)90046-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-0000(88)90046-3).
- [70] R. M. Karp. “Reducibility among combinatorial problems.” In: *Complexity of Computer Computations*. Ed. by R. E. Miller, J. W. Thatcher, and J. D. Bohlinger. New York: Plenum, 1972, pp. 85–103. DOI: [10.1007/978-1-4684-2001-2_9](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4684-2001-2_9).
- [71] D. Kempe, S. Yu, and Y. Vorobeychik. “Inducing equilibria in networked public goods games through network structure modification.” In: *Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Autonomous Agents and Multiagent Systems*. Ed. by A. E. F. Seghrouchni, G. Sukthankar, B. An, and N. Yorke-Smith. Richland (SC): International Foundation for Autonomous Agents and Multiagent Systems, 2020, pp. 611–619.
- [72] M. Klimm and M. J. Stahlberg. “Complexity of equilibria in binary public goods games on undirected graphs.” In: *Proceedings of the 24th ACM Conference on Economics and Computation*. 2023, pp. 938–955. DOI: [10.1145/3580507.3597780](https://doi.org/10.1145/3580507.3597780).
- [73] C. Knappett, T. Evans, and R. Rivers. “Modelling maritime interaction in the Aegean Bronze Age.” In: *Antiquity* 82.318 (2008), pp. 1009–1024. DOI: [10.1017/s0003598x0009774x](https://doi.org/10.1017/s0003598x0009774x).
- [74] Z. Komarovskiy, V. Levit, T. Grinshpoun, and A. Meisels. “Efficient equilibria in a public goods game.” In: *Proceedings of the 2015 IEEE/WIC/ACM International Conference on Web Intelligence and Intelligent Agent Technology*. Ed. by E. Suzuki, B. K. H. Low, and J. Watson. IEEE, 2015, pp. 214–219. DOI: [10.1109/WI-IAT.2015.91](https://doi.org/10.1109/WI-IAT.2015.91).
- [75] D. König. “Gráfok és alkalmazásuk a determinánsok és a halmazok elméletére.” In: *Matematikai és Természettudományi Értesítő* 34 (1916). English: Graphs and their applications to the theory of determinants and sets, pp. 104–119.
- [76] A. J. M. Kropp. “The Roman road network of North Sardinia and other topographical puzzles.” In: *Orbis Terrarum* 19 (2021), pp. 115–142.
- [77] D. Kurokawa, O. Lev, J. Morgenstern, and A. D. Procaccia. “Impartial peer review.” In: *Proceedings of the 24th International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence*. Ed. by Q. Yang and M. Wooldridge. Palo Alto: AAAI Press, 2015, pp. 582–588. URL: <https://www.ijcai.org/Abstract/15/088>.

- [78] P. Larraañaga and J. A. Lozano, eds. *Estimation of distribution algorithms: a new tool for evolutionary computation*. New York: Springer Science+Business Media, 2002. DOI: [10.1007/978-1-4615-1539-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4615-1539-5).
- [79] O. Lev, N. Mattei, P. Turrini, and S. Zhydkov. "PeerNomination: a novel peer selection algorithm to handle strategic and noisy assessments." In: *Artificial Intelligence* 316 (2023), 103843:1–103843:23. DOI: [10.1016/j.artint.2022.103843](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.artint.2022.103843).
- [80] V. Levit, Z. Komarovskiy, T. Grinshpoun, and A. Meisels. "Incentive-based search for efficient equilibria of the public goods game." In: *Artificial Intelligence* 262 (2018), pp. 142–162. DOI: [10.1016/j.artint.2018.04.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.artint.2018.04.004).
- [81] D. López-Pintado. "Public goods in directed networks." In: *Economic Letters* 121 (2013), pp. 160–162. DOI: [10.1016/j.econlet.2013.08.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econlet.2013.08.003).
- [82] A. M. MacEachren. "Travel time as the basis of cognitive distance." In: *The Professional Geographer* 32.1 (1980), pp. 30–36. DOI: [10.1111/j.0033-0124.1980.00030.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0033-0124.1980.00030.x).
- [83] A. Mackenzie. "Symmetry and impartial lotteries." In: *Games and Economic Behavior* 94 (2015), pp. 15–28. DOI: [10.1016/j.geb.2015.08.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geb.2015.08.007).
- [84] A. Maiti and P. Dey. "On parameterized complexity of binary networked public goods game." In: *Algorithmica* 86 (2024), pp. 307–333. DOI: [10.1007/s00453-023-01174-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00453-023-01174-4).
- [85] D. F. Manlove. "On the algorithmic complexity of twelve covering and independence parameters of graphs." In: *Discrete Applied Mathematics* 91.1–3 (1999), pp. 155–175. DOI: [10.1016/S0166-218X\(98\)00147-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-218X(98)00147-4).
- [86] K. V. Mardia and P. E. Jupp. *Directional Statistics*. 2nd edition. Wiley Series in Probability and Statistics. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons, 2000. DOI: [10.1002/9780470316979](https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470316979).
- [87] A. Mastino, ed. *Storia della Sardegna antica*. La Sardegna e la sua storia 2. Nuoro: Edizioni Il Maestrale, 2005.
- [88] N. Mattei, P. Turrini, and S. Zhydkov. "PeerNomination: relaxing exactness for increased accuracy in peer selection." In: *Proceedings of the 29th International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence*. Ed. by C. Bessiere. International Joint Conferences on Artificial Intelligence Organization, 2021, pp. 393–399. DOI: [10.24963/ijcai.2020/55](https://doi.org/10.24963/ijcai.2020/55).
- [89] W. McKinney. "Data structures for statistical computing in Python." In: *Proceedings of the 9th Python in Science Conference*. Ed. by S. van der Walt and J. Millman. 2010, pp. 56–61. DOI: [10.25080/Majora-92bf1922-00a](https://doi.org/10.25080/Majora-92bf1922-00a).
- [90] N. Megiddo and C. H. Papadimitriou. "On total functions, existence theorems and computational complexity." In: *Theoretical Computer Science* 81.2 (1991), pp. 317–324. DOI: [10.1016/0304-3975\(91\)90200-L](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3975(91)90200-L).
- [91] P. Meloni. *La Sardegna romana*. Nuoro: Ilisso, 2013.
- [92] H. Melvill. *The Golden Lectures. Forty-Five Sermons Delivered at St. Margaret's Church, Lothbury, on Tuesday mornings, from January 2 to December 18, 1855*. The Preacher in Print. London: James Paul, 1855.
- [93] K. Miller. *Die Peutingerische Tafel*. Stuttgart: F. A. Brockhaus Komm.-Gesch. GmbH, 1962.
- [94] N. Miolane et al. "Geomstats: a Python package for Riemannian geometry in machine learning." In: *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 21 (2020), 223:1–223:9.

- [95] J. S. B. Mitchell. *Shortest paths among obstacles, zero-cost regions, and roads*. Tech. rep. 764. School of Operations Research and Industrial Engineering, Cornell University, 1987.
- [96] D. Monderer and L. S. Shapley. “Potential games.” In: *Games and Economic Behavior* 14.1 (1996), pp. 124–143. DOI: [10.1006/game.1996.0044](https://doi.org/10.1006/game.1996.0044).
- [97] J. F. Nash. “Equilibrium points in n -person games.” In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 36.1 (1950), pp. 48–49. DOI: [10.1073/pnas.36.1.48](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.36.1.48).
- [98] J. F. Nash. “Non-cooperative games.” In: *Annals of Mathematics* 54.2 (1951), pp. 286–295.
- [99] M. Neteler, M. H. Bowman, M. Landa, and M. Metz. “GRASS GIS: a multi-purpose open source GIS.” in: *Environmental Modelling & Software* 31 (2012), pp. 124–130. DOI: [10.1016/j.envsoft.2011.11.014](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2011.11.014).
- [100] E. Osaba, X.-S. Yang, and J. Del Ser. “Traveling salesman problem: a perspective review of recent research and new results with bio-inspired metaheuristics.” In: *Nature-Inspired Computation and Swarm Intelligence*. Ed. by X.-S. Yang. London, San Diego, Cambridge (MA), Oxford: Academic Press, 2020. Chap. 9, pp. 135–164. DOI: [10.1016/B978-0-12-819714-1.00020-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-819714-1.00020-8).
- [101] F. Pablo-Martí, Á. Alañón-Pardo, and A. Sánchez. “Complex networks to understand the past: the case of roads in Bourbon Spain.” In: *Cliometrica* 15 (2021), pp. 477–534. DOI: [10.1007/s11698-020-00218-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11698-020-00218-x).
- [102] E. Pais. *Ricerche storiche e geografiche sull’Italia antica*. Torino: Società Tipografico-Editrice Nazionale, 1908.
- [103] P. Pandit and A. A. Kulkarni. “Refinement of the equilibrium of public goods games over networks: efficiency and effort of specialized equilibria.” In: *Journal of Mathematical Economics* 79 (2018), pp. 125–139. DOI: [10.1016/j.jmateco.2018.04.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmateco.2018.04.002).
- [104] C. H. Papadimitriou and B. Peng. “Public goods games in directed networks.” In: *Games and Economic Behavior* 139 (2023), pp. 161–179. DOI: [10.1016/j.geb.2023.02.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geb.2023.02.002).
- [105] C. H. Papadimitriou and M. Yannakakis. “Optimization, approximation, and complexity classes.” In: *Journal of Computer and System Sciences* 43.3 (1991), pp. 425–440. DOI: [10.1016/0022-0000\(91\)90023-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-0000(91)90023-X).
- [106] Plotly Technologies Inc. *Plotly open source graphing library for Python*. 2024. URL: <https://plotly.com/python>.
- [107] L. Prignano, I. Morer, F. Fulminante, and S. Lozano. “Modelling terrestrial route networks to understand inter-polity interactions (southern Etruria, 950–500 BC).” in: *Journal of Archaeological Science* 105 (2019), pp. 46–58. DOI: [10.1016/j.jas.2019.02.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2019.02.007).
- [108] QGIS Development Team. *QGIS geographic information system*. Open Source Geospatial Foundation, 2022. URL: <https://qgis.org>.
- [109] U. Ramer. “An iterative procedure for the polygonal approximation of plane curves.” In: *Computer Graphics and Image Processing* 1.3 (1972), pp. 244–256. DOI: [10.1016/S0146-664X\(72\)80017-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0146-664X(72)80017-0).
- [110] C. Rego, D. Gamboa, F. Glover, and C. Osterman. “Traveling salesman problem heuristics: leading methods, implementations and latest advances.” In: *European Journal of Operational Research* 211.3 (2011), pp. 427–441. DOI: [10.1016/j.ejor.2010.09.010](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2010.09.010).
- [111] C. Renfrew and E. V. Level. “Exploring dominance: predicting polities from centers.” In: *Transformations: Mathematical Approaches to Culture Change*. Ed. by C. Renfrew and K. L. Cooke. New York, London: Academic Press, 1979. Chap. 6, pp. 145–167. DOI: [10.1016/B978-0-12-586050-5.50016-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-586050-5.50016-6).

- [112] R. Rivers, C. Knappett, and T. Evans. “What makes a site important? centrality, gateways, and gravity.” In: *Network Analysis in Archaeology: New Approaches to Regional Interaction*. Ed. by K. Knappett. Oxford Academic, 2013. Chap. 6, pp. 125–150. DOI: [10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199697090.003.0006](https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199697090.003.0006).
- [113] R. W. Rosenthal. “A class of games possessing pure-strategy Nash equilibria.” In: *International Journal of Game Theory* 2.1 (1973), pp. 65–67. DOI: [10.1007/BF01737559](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01737559).
- [114] G. Sagnol and M. J. Stahlberg. “PICOS: a Python interface to conic optimization solvers.” In: *Journal of Open Source Software* 7.70 (2022), 3915:1–3915:3. DOI: [10.21105/joss.03915](https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.03915).
- [115] A. A. Schäffer and M. Yannakakis. “Simple local search problems that are hard to solve.” In: *SIAM Journal on Computing* 20.1 (1991), pp. 56–87. DOI: [10.1137/0220004](https://doi.org/10.1137/0220004).
- [116] M. J. Stahlberg. *Sequential road network figure generators*. 2024. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10716369](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10716369).
- [117] M. J. Stahlberg. *Sequential road network toolbox*. 2024. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10715827](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10715827).
- [118] M. J. Stahlberg. *Sequential road network web dashboard*. 2024. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10716792](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10716792).
- [119] M. J. Stahlberg, G. Sagnol, B. Ducke, and M. Klimm. “Spatiotemporal reconstruction of ancient road networks through sequential cost–benefit analysis.” In: *PNAS Nexus* 2.2 (2023), pp. 1–10. DOI: [10.1093/pnasnexus/pgac313](https://doi.org/10.1093/pnasnexus/pgac313).
- [120] J. Q. Stewart. “Empirical mathematical rules concerning the distribution and equilibrium of population.” In: *Geographical Review* 37.3 (1947), pp. 461–485. DOI: [10.2307/211132](https://doi.org/10.2307/211132).
- [121] J. Q. Stewart and W. Warntz. “Physics of population distribution.” In: *Journal of Regional Science* 1.1 (1958), pp. 99–123. DOI: [10.1111/j.1467-9787.1958.tb01366.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9787.1958.tb01366.x).
- [122] R. J. A. Talbert, ed. *Barrington Atlas of the Greek and Roman World*. Princeton University Press, 2000.
- [123] S. Tamura. “Characterizing minimal impartial rules for awarding prizes.” In: *Games and Economic Behavior* 95 (2016), pp. 41–46. DOI: [10.1016/j.geb.2015.12.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geb.2015.12.005).
- [124] S. Tamura and S. Ohseto. “Impartial nomination correspondences.” In: *Social Choice and Welfare* 43.1 (2014), pp. 47–54. DOI: [10.1007/s00355-013-0772-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00355-013-0772-9).
- [125] J. Terrell. “Island biogeography and man in Melanesia.” In: *Archaeology & Physical Anthropology in Oceania* 11.1 (1976), pp. 1–17.
- [126] N. Tessore. *composition_stats: Python module for compositional data analysis*. 2021. URL: https://github.com/ntessore/composition_stats.
- [127] T. N. Tideman and F. Plassmann. “Paying the partners.” In: *Public Choice* 136 (2008), pp. 19–37. DOI: [10.1007/s11127-008-9276-z](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11127-008-9276-z).
- [128] W. R. Tobler. “Map transformations of geographic space.” PhD thesis. University of Washington, 1961.
- [129] W. R. Tobler. *Three Presentations on Geographical Analysis and Modeling: Non-Isotropic Geographic Modeling; Speculations on the Geometry of Geography; and Global Spatial Analysis*. Tech. rep. 93-1. Santa Barbara: University of California, 1993.
- [130] G. T. Toussaint. “The relative neighbourhood graph of a finite planar set.” In: *Pattern Recognition* 12.4 (1980), pp. 261–268. DOI: [10.1016/0031-3203\(80\)90066-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0031-3203(80)90066-7).
- [131] M. Treinish, I. Carvalho, G. Tsilimigkounakis, and N. Sá. “rustworkx: a high-performance graph library for Python.” In: *Journal of Open Source Software* 7.79 (2022), 3968:1–3968:5. DOI: [10.21105/joss.03968](https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.03968).

- [132] P. Verhagen, T. Brughmans, L. Nuninger, and F. Bertonecello. “The long and winding road: combining least cost paths and network analysis techniques for settlement location analysis and predictive modelling.” In: *Archaeology in the Digital Era*. Ed. by P. Verhagen and G. Earl. Amsterdam University Press, 2014, pp. 357–366. DOI: [10.1515/9789048519590-039](https://doi.org/10.1515/9789048519590-039).
- [133] P. Verhagen, L. Nuninger, and M. R. Groenhuijzen. “Modelling of pathways and movement networks in archaeology: an overview of current approaches.” In: *Finding the Limits of the Limes*. Ed. by P. Verhagen, J. Joyce, and M. R. Groenhuijzen. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2019. Chap. 11, pp. 217–249. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-030-04576-0_11](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-04576-0_11).
- [134] P. Virtanen et al. “SciPy 1.0: fundamental algorithms for scientific computing in Python.” In: *Nature Methods* 17 (2020), pp. 261–272. DOI: [10.1038/s41592-019-0686-2](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-019-0686-2).
- [135] V. G. Vizing. “Ob otsenke khromaticheskogo klassa p -grafa.” In: *Diskretnyy Analiz* 3 (1964). English: On an estimate of the chromatic class of a p -graph, pp. 25–30.
- [136] F. Wahl. “Does European development have Roman roots? Evidence from the German Limes.” In: *Journal of Economic Growth* 22 (2017), pp. 313–349. DOI: [10.1007/s10887-017-9144-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10887-017-9144-0).
- [137] S. Wasserman and P. Pattison. “Logit models and logistic regressions for social networks: I. an introduction to Markov graphs and p^* .” In: *Psychometrika* 61.3 (1996), pp. 401–425. DOI: [10.1007/BF02294547](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02294547).
- [138] G. S. Watson and E. J. Williams. “On the construction of significance tests on the circle and the sphere.” In: *Biometrika* 43.3–4 (1956), pp. 344–352. DOI: [10.1093/biomet/43.3-4.344](https://doi.org/10.1093/biomet/43.3-4.344).
- [139] D. A. White and S. B. Barber. “Geospatial modeling of pedestrian transportation networks: a case study from precolumbian Oaxaca, Mexico.” In: *Journal of Archaeological Science* 39.8 (2012), pp. 2684–2696. DOI: [10.1016/j.jas.2012.04.017](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2012.04.017).
- [140] D. A. White. “The basics of least cost analysis for archaeological applications.” In: *Advances in Archaeological Practice* 3.4 (2015), pp. 407–414. DOI: [10.7183/2326-3768.3.4.407](https://doi.org/10.7183/2326-3768.3.4.407).
- [141] F. Xie and D. Levinson. “Modeling the growth of transportation networks: a comprehensive review.” In: *Networks and Spatial Economics* 9.3 (2009), pp. 291–307. DOI: [10.1007/s11067-007-9037-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11067-007-9037-4).
- [142] Y. Yang and J. Wang. “A refined study of the complexity of binary networked public goods games.” In: *CoRR* (2020). arXiv: [2012.02916](https://arxiv.org/abs/2012.02916) [cs.GT].
- [143] D. Younger. “Minimum feedback arc sets for a directed graph.” In: *IEEE Transactions on Circuit Theory* 10.2 (1963), pp. 238–245. DOI: [10.1109/TCT.1963.1082116](https://doi.org/10.1109/TCT.1963.1082116).
- [144] S. Yu, K. Zhou, P. J. Brantingham, and Y. Vorobeychik. “Computing equilibria in binary networked public goods games.” In: *Proceedings of the 34th AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*. Palo Alto: AAAI Press, 2020, pp. 2310–2317. DOI: [10.1609/aaai.v34i02.5609](https://doi.org/10.1609/aaai.v34i02.5609).